

**Voices on inclusion: an IPA study of the
lived experiences of students with
disabilities and the perspectives of disability
support staff in one Algerian university.**

FATMA BOUABIDA

**Thesis submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements
of the University of the West of Scotland for the award of
Doctor of Philosophy**

November 2023

Student Declaration

I certify that this thesis is my original work, except where explicitly acknowledged. I further confirm that it has not been previously submitted for any other academic or professional qualification.

Name:

Date: 27-10-2023

Personal details withheld.

Abstract

With the increasing number of students with disabilities enrolling in higher education institutions, the need to embrace diversity and promote inclusiveness in these institutions has also increased. A growing body of international literature has explored the experiences of students with disabilities in higher education, revealing barriers that hinder their inclusion. The current study set out to explore the lived experiences of students with disabilities and the processes used by disability support staff to facilitate their inclusion in one Algerian university. The study sought to explore the support provided to students with disabilities in this university, identify available resources and strategies used to meet their needs, and consider the factors that influence the effectiveness of the provision. The study utilized interpretative phenomenological analysis with data collected through semi-structured interviews with nine students with disabilities and four disability support staff. This led to rich insights into the students' lived experiences of inclusion and the disability support staff's perspectives.

The study's findings reveal that the experiences of students with disabilities are affected by a range of factors. These factors encompass environmental, structural, and attitudinal aspects that facilitate or hinder the inclusion of students with disabilities at this university. The findings indicate that the experiences of students with disabilities are not influenced solely by their direct interactions within the university. They are also shaped by external factors that impact their educational journey positively or negatively. These external factors play a significant role in determining the overall educational experience of these students. Moreover, the findings highlight that, despite the efforts made by disability support staff, structural factors undermine their ability to provide effective and holistic support for students with disabilities at the

university. These findings align with Bronfenbrenner's ecological systems theory, bringing into focus the influence of direct and indirect internal and external factors on the experiences of students with disabilities. Considering the complex interplay between these factors contributes to a deeper understanding of the opportunities and challenges associated with inclusive education in this context. The study's findings highlight the multifaceted nature of the experiences of students with disabilities and underscore the importance of considering environmental, structural, and attitudinal factors as facilitators of or barriers to their inclusion in higher education. In addition, the findings focus attention on the proximal and distal forces that determine the availability and effectiveness of support and, ultimately, the experiences of university students with disabilities. This reinforces the significance of Bronfenbrenner's ecological systems theory in understanding the complexities of inclusive education.

The study concludes that inclusive education at this university is still in its early stages. Drawing on the perspectives of the participants, a number of recommendations are offered which could improve the experiences of students with disabilities. These include investments in accessible infrastructure, resources, equipment and staff training. The need for an inclusion policy for higher education has also been noted.

Overall, this study sheds light on the lived experiences of students with disabilities and on the perspectives of disability support staff in one Algerian university, uncovering the challenges faced by the students and potential areas for improvement. The study makes a significant contribution to the national and international literature on the experiences of university students with disabilities, and provides insights that could be useful to policymakers, academics, and support staff striving to develop inclusive higher education.

Acknowledgments

الحمد لله حمدا كثيرا طيبا مباركا, الحمد لله الذي بنعمته تتم الصالحات.

I would like to express my sincere gratitude to the Algerian Ministry of Higher Education and the Algerian Embassy for their sponsorship and funding, which made it possible for me to pursue my Ph.D. and conduct this research over the span of four years. Their support has been instrumental in making my academic journey a reality.

A heartfelt thank you goes to my lead supervisor, Lisa McAuliffe, for her invaluable guidance, constructive feedback, and unwavering support throughout the completion of this project. Her mentorship and encouragement have been vital in overcoming the challenges I encountered along the way, especially during the toughest times.

My heartfelt thanks go to my family members - my mom and dad (**Habiba and Mohamed**), who always believed in me and my inner strength, my dear sisters Asmaa, Warda and Sara, my three brothers Ahmed, Ibrahim, and Aymen, and my little nephews and niece: Mohammed, Bahaa, Ihabe and Alaa - for their unwavering emotional support during times of frustration and difficulty. Their love and encouragement have been my anchor throughout this endeavor.

I must acknowledge my husband, **Hamza**, with special thanks. His patience, and endless emotional, and moral support have been invaluable sources of strength during my Ph.D. Without him, I'm not sure where I would be.

I am extremely grateful to my best friends Zineb, Tiha, Rosa, and Omnia who have demonstrated incredible patience during my demanding PhD journey. They have kindly lent their ears to my academic conversations, even when the subject matter was not the most captivating for them.

I extend my appreciation to my wonderful colleagues in J202 – Marian, Meriem, Abir, Ichraf, and others - for the joy, insights, and diverse perspectives they brought to the research process. Their friendship has enriched this experience beyond measure.

I am deeply grateful to Mr. Hakim Oumokrane and Dr. Mohammed Amine Driss for their assistance during my Ph.D. journey. Their support and contributions have been instrumental in shaping the outcome of this research.

Last but not least, I extend my sincere gratitude to the 13 participants who wholeheartedly shared their experiences and insights, making this research possible. Their openness and enthusiasm have been instrumental in shaping the findings and enriching the overall study.

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Chapter 1: Background and Context

1.1 Introduction

The inclusion of students with disabilities in education is enshrined in international treaties and declarations such as the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (United Nations, 1948), the UNESCO Convention and Recommendation against Discrimination in Education (UNESCO, 1960), the Salamanca Statement on Special Needs Education (UNESCO, 1994), and the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD) (United Nations, 2006). Inclusive education is part of the UNESCO sustainable development goals and is defined as ‘a process that helps overcome barriers limiting the presence, participation, and achievement of learners’ (UNESCO, 2017, p. 13). According to UNESCO, when it comes to education, ‘the central message is simple: every learner matters and matters equally’ (UNESCO, 2017, p. 13).

In recent years, there has been a notable worldwide rise in the enrolment and engagement of students with disabilities in higher education (Lane, 2017; Karellou, 2019; Kimball and Thoma, 2019; Abrahams et al, 2023). Universities have been actively addressing crucial aspects such as physical accessibility, accessibility to academic resources, and assessment procedures to ensure that students with disabilities have equal opportunities for participation in university life. The implementation of anti-discrimination laws and policies has played a crucial role in driving these efforts. These developments aim to provide students with disabilities with the necessary accommodations and support to fully access and engage in higher education (Morina, 2017). However, despite efforts to enhance accessibility and support systems, there are still significant barriers that hinder the participation of students with disabilities in higher education (Morina, 2017; Fossey et al, 2017;

Osborne, 2019). Therefore, the goal of achieving full inclusion for students with disabilities in higher education remains an ongoing challenge in many countries.

An extensive literature search revealed dearth of research that investigates the experiences of students with disabilities at university in Algeria, which is my home country. As I intend to work in higher education in Algeria after completing my Ph.D., I decided to focus my doctoral research on inclusion in Algerian higher education. My goal is to contribute to the growing body of knowledge about inclusive higher education but also to generate insights that can help me, my colleagues, and other higher education staff become more inclusive in our thinking and practice. This chapter begins by presenting the justification for the research, and the research questions and aims that guided the study. Furthermore, it highlights the identified knowledge gap that the research seeks to fill and indicates the contribution it makes to the existing body of knowledge. Finally, it provides an outline of the education system in Algeria, and an overview of the evolution of higher education and inclusive education.

1.2 Rationale and motivation for conducting this study

The decision to pursue this study was driven by several factors and personal motives. As a former university student in Algeria, I witnessed first-hand the significant barriers that students with disabilities encountered in their journey through post-secondary education. These barriers, which impeded their participation and hindered their success, often went unaddressed and were not openly voiced and discussed. I noticed that the students with disabilities who attended university during the time I was a student did not receive sufficient support and assistance from the university. I did observe instances of support provided by teachers, peers, and administration staff but these seemed to be gestures of good will by individuals rather than practices guided

by university inclusion policy. In addition, my personal connections with students with disabilities, who were both my classmates and friends, offered valuable insights into their struggles and the limitations of the support they received. From witnessing my friends in wheelchairs unable to access lecture halls and observing their reliance on fellow students for assistance, I became acutely aware of the exclusionary practices and challenges faced by students with disabilities in their pursuit of higher education. This realization motivated me to explore the experiences of students with disabilities within the university setting, to understand why their needs are neglected and what can be done to address this and improve their experiences.

Furthermore, my experience studying at universities in the United Kingdom, specifically Canterbury Christ Church University and the University of the West of Scotland, deepened my interest in this topic. Witnessing the robust support systems and accommodations provided to students with disabilities in these universities, including accessible facilities and individualized support plans, inspired me to delve further into the principles and practices of inclusion within higher education. For instance, I recall a friend with visual impairment who approached the librarian at Canterbury Christ Church University to inquire about available support. The librarian responded that they were aware of her case and had already prepared an individual support plan tailored to her needs for the duration of her time at Canterbury Christ Church University and in the residency halls. This interaction left a lasting impression on me, highlighting the importance and impact of comprehensive support systems.

As an insider to the Algerian culture and having experienced university life at two different institutions in the United Kingdom (Canterbury Christ Church University and the University of the West of Scotland), I witnessed the stark contrast in support and inclusivity provided to students with disabilities in Algeria and in the United Kingdom.

This difference in support motivated me to conduct research on the experiences of students with disabilities in Algerian universities as a way to highlight the barriers they face and share their suggestions about what should be done to facilitate their inclusion in higher education. In addition, having gained some insight into the institutional policies and practices that are in place to provide support for students with disabilities in the United Kingdom, I was motivated to investigate what, if any, inclusion policies may be in place in Algerian Higher Education and what may hinder their effective implementation. Through this research endeavour, my aim is to contribute knowledge about the experiences of university students with disabilities in Algeria and measures that could be taken to improve them.

Adding to this motivation was the very limited literature and research about university students with disabilities in Algeria. An extensive search revealed only one relevant article written in English (Arib, 2020). This article reported a study of academic staff's experiences of including students with disabilities in the Department of English in one Algerian university. The findings suggest that academic staff understand the core principles of inclusive education but do not feel adequately prepared to meet the additional support needs of learners with disabilities in their classes. According to the author, improvements in university facilities and in teacher training are required to ensure that the additional support needs of students with disabilities are met more effectively. The author noted the importance of seeking the perspectives of students with disabilities, something that was not done in this study, and recommended that 'future research should focus on this neglected area of investigation' (Arib, 2020, p. 350).

In addition to the article outlined above, my search identified two relevant articles written in Arabic (Bouaicha, 2017; Djedidi and Djedidi, 2018). Bouaicha's (2017) article

reports a study investigating the experiences of 23 students with disabilities in one Algerian university. Data were collected through a questionnaire. The study revealed a number of barriers that hinder the inclusion and achievement of students with disabilities, including inaccessible learning resources and lack of consideration for these students' needs. Djedidi and Djedidi's (2018) article reports a similar study involving ten students with disabilities in a different Algerian university. The findings demonstrated a number of challenges faced by the students, including inaccessible university buildings and transportation, and limited opportunities for students with disabilities to participate in clubs and extracurricular activities. A further study on this topic but written in French was also identified (Zoreli, 2018). This was also a quantitative study, with data collected from another Algerian university via questionnaires completed by students with disabilities, academic staff, members of the university's senior management team, and disability support staff. The findings were similar to those of the studies mentioned above, revealing barriers to the inclusion of students with disabilities. Despite exhaustive efforts, only one further study was found (Nabti, 2018). This study is reported in an unpublished master's dissertation written in French. The study employed a qualitative approach, with data collected through interviews with ten students with physical disabilities and one disability support officer in the university where Zoreli (2018) also conducted his study. Similar to the findings from the other studies, this study revealed physical accessibility barriers, unadapted learning materials, and lack of assistive technology.

As can be seen from the very limited number of studies outlined above, there is a significant gap in our understanding of the experiences of students with disabilities in higher education in Algeria. Identifying this gap added to my motivation to pursue this topic.

1.3 Choosing the study context

While searching for relevant literature, I came across information about a project aiming to promote inclusion in Algerian higher education through the EU funded Trans-European Mobility Programme for University Studies (TEMPUS), which included collaborative projects aiming to promote inclusive education in Maghreb (North African countries) universities (Miłosz, Milosz and Grzegórski, 2016). The TEMPUS program, initially introduced in 1990, aimed to enhance higher education structures and support students from vulnerable groups, including those with disabilities. Three Algerian universities participated in this project in the early 2010s. However, upon reaching out to these institutions and other universities in Algeria, I was disappointed to discover that only one university continued the implementation of inclusive practices after the end of the project. This particular university has established a Disability Support Office aiming to provide support and assistance to students with disabilities throughout their academic journey. This information served as a catalyst for my research, motivating to seek the perspectives of disability support staff about the processes that facilitate the inclusion of students with disabilities at this university. This choice enabled me to explore the factors that influence the inclusion of students with disabilities from two perspectives: students with disabilities and disability support staff. This focused approach allowed me to gain valuable insights into the inclusion of students with disabilities in one Algerian university, and to give voice to the participants' recommendations for improvements. I hope that my research will be of value to stakeholders who can take action to improve inclusion not only in the university where the present study was conducted but in other Algerian higher education institutions as well. The findings and recommendations derived from the research can serve as a foundation and guide for future endeavours aimed at promoting inclusive education in

universities across the country. Through sharing the findings and recommendations with authorities and stakeholders who can act on them, this research has the potential to contribute to the enhancement of inclusive practices and the provision of adequate support for students with disabilities, ensuring their equal access and success in this university and other Algerian universities as well. In addition, the findings of this research make a contribution to the international body of knowledge about inclusive higher education.

In summary, the decision to select one Algerian university for my research is justified by the unique circumstances surrounding the context of the study, specifically, the existence of a Disability Support Office which allowed for the perspectives of disability support staff to be included in the study.

1.4 Terminology Considerations

There has been a long debate over the most appropriate language to use when referring to disability. Much of this debate is concerned with how language frames people, what assumptions it makes, and what messages it sends about them. An important question is whether to use the term 'people with disabilities' or 'disabled people'. The first is part of 'people first language' while the second is part of 'identity first language'. People first language came out of the American People First self-advocacy movement, which was launched in Oregon in 1974 (Armstrong, 2022). The name of the movement came from an individual with learning disabilities who, at one of the first meetings, said: "I want to be known as a person first" (Armstrong, 2022, p. 335). The aim of the People First movement was to highlight that people are not defined by their disabilities and should not be labelled with them. As Valerie Schaaf, first president of People First, remarked "label jars, label streets, but don't label persons' (Fisher, 2021, p. 72). By putting 'people' first the aim was to emphasise that

disability is one of many different aspects of a person's identity. Person-first language is rooted in the idea that each person is an individual who should not be predominantly identified by their disability and should be treated as a person above all (Gernsbacher, 2017). The People First movement influenced public discourse about disability in US and beyond. This is reflected in the use of people first language in the American Individuals with Disabilities Act and in the UN Convention on the Rights of People with Disabilities. People First influenced developments in the UK, with the British branch of People First being established in the early 1980s and still being active (People First, nd).

However, people first language is not unanimously adopted within the disability community. Several activists and scholars contend that disability is not a trait someone possesses; rather, it is a result of external forces that impose limitations on individuals with impairments (Barnes, 1994; Heaton, 2014). Therefore, they argue, referring to a person as disabled is more appropriate, because it highlights the existing social and environmental barriers that disable people with impairments (Heaton, 2014). Identity first language is advocated strongly by the neurodiversity movement, which advocates that disability and neurological conditions (such as autism, ADHD, and Dyslexia) are an integral part of human identity, like race and gender. The proponents of identity first language advocate embracing a person's disability as a vital aspect of their identity, fostering a sense of self-determination and pride rather than shame (Andrews, 2019; Botha et al., 2021).

A number of studies have sought to establish whether people first or identify first language is preferable. In a survey of 519 disabled people from 23 countries, Sharif, McCall, Bolante (2022) found that 49% of the participants preferred identity-first language, 33% preferred person-first language, and 18% had no preference. Of

particular interest is a study in UK universities (Lister, Coughlan, and Owen, 2020). Identity first language (disabled people) was found to be unpopular with the students who participated in this study (n=723). People first language (students with disabilities) was acceptable but other terms such as 'additional study needs' or 'conditions that affect your study' emerged as preferable. This indicates fluidity in language use and highlights that no single approach will suit all individuals in all situations.

In the absence of consensus, many organisations and professionals acknowledge the usefulness of both people first and identity first language and advocate the use of whichever seems to be suitable in the context and aligned with the preferences of the people present. Journals such as 'Disability & Society' publish articles using people first language as well as articles using identity first language, depending on the authors' preference. A recent search of the contents of this journal (Disability & Society) returned 3,289 results for the term 'people with disabilities' and 2,887 results for the term 'disabledpeople', suggesting a slight preference for people first language. When considering what terminology to use in this thesis, I was mindful that there is no consensus. Having noticed the prevalence of people first language in the literature reviewed for this study and that this is the preferred language in the UN CRPD, I chose to use people first language. However, on page 27, I used the term 'autistic' in adherence to identity-first language, respecting the preferences of the autistic community, who tend to favour the use of identity-first language (Botha, Hanlon, and Williams, 2021; Botha, Dibb, and Frost, 2020; Taboas, Zimmerman, Doepke, 2022). Furthermore, during the interviews I was prepared to align my language to the preferences of each participant. Consequently, when I noticed that a participant used identity first language, I did the same. This happened on a few occasions, but most participants used people first language most of the time.

1.5 Research Questions and Aims

The study set out to explore the following research questions:

1. What are the lived experiences of students with disabilities in Algerian higher education?
2. How do disability support staff facilitate the inclusion of students with disabilities in Algerian higher education?

The study had the following aims:

- To explore and understand the lived experiences of students with disabilities in Algerian higher education, including factors that facilitate and hinder their participation and achievement.
- To identify the needs of students with disabilities in Algerian higher education and convey their recommendations for improving their overall experience and academic success.
- To understand the processes used by disability support staff to facilitate the inclusion of students with disabilities in Algerian higher education, and the factors that affect their efforts.
- To investigate the effectiveness of existing support services and accommodations provided by Algerian higher education institutions and identify areas for improvement to better meet the needs of students with disabilities.

1.6 Contribution to knowledge

The study makes a contribution to knowledge about inclusive higher education, with a specific focus on the inclusion of students with disabilities. Disability issues and

inclusive education are topics of paramount importance that have been under-researched in the Algerian context. As already noted, there exists a scarcity of knowledge regarding the experiences of students with disabilities in Algerian universities and the support systems available to them. Consequently, by shedding light on this topic, the study has the potential to inform efforts to develop more inclusive practices for these students. Moreover, this study contributes to the disability studies literature, not only in Algeria, but also in the broader Arab world, where such research is limited. It also contributes to the international body of knowledge about inclusive higher education by sharing insights from the Algerian context. Additionally, the study can act as a research reference, encouraging future researchers to delve deeper into the areas of disability and inclusion in higher education, thereby advancing knowledge and facilitating progress in this area.

Methodologically, the study represents one of few research endeavours that employ interpretative phenomenological analysis (IPA) to examine the lived experiences of university students with disabilities and the processes used by disability support staff to facilitate their inclusion. This qualitative methodology transcends the realm of statistics and numbers, facilitating a deeper and more comprehensive exploration of the topic being studied. The choice of this methodology is particularly fitting for the study, given its novelty within the Algerian context. Furthermore, the study makes a contribution to the emerging literature on the inclusion of students with disabilities in Algerian Higher education, by complementing the findings of existing quantitative research (Bouaicha, 2017; Djedidi and Djedidi, 2018; Zoreli, 2018) with findings from a qualitative study.

Furthermore, to my knowledge, this is the first study to examine the lived experiences of students with disabilities in Algerian higher education and the process used by

disability support staff to facilitate their inclusion through the lens of Bronfenbrenner's (1989) ecological systems theory. Through mapping the factors that affect the students' university experiences onto the various systems that surround them, it was possible to locate positive as well as negative influences within specific contexts. This makes it easier to identify opportunities for change within each system and to target efforts for improvements more strategically.

The research has implications for various stakeholders. The findings can be of value to the Algerian Government, particularly the Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research, as they shed light into the experiences of university students with disabilities and highlight areas where more support is needed. They can stimulate the Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research to invest more resources to develop inclusive university environments where all students are able to participate and achieve. Additionally, the research can guide disability support staff, academic staff, families, and other stakeholders in their efforts to assist students with disabilities at the university level.

1.7 National context of the study

This section begins by providing a general introduction to the educational system in Algeria. It then focuses specifically on higher education, highlighting its significance and role in offering advanced academic opportunities. Following this, the section delves into the topic of inclusive education in Algeria.

1.7.1 Overview of the educational system

After gaining independence in 1962, the Algerian government placed significant emphasis on education, making it free and compulsory for children aged six and above (Rose, 2015; Abdeslam, 2020). The Algerian educational system is structured into various levels, including compulsory education that includes primary, middle, and secondary/high school education, as well as post-secondary education that includes vocational, and higher education. In order to pursue higher education in Algeria, students are required to have completed their basic education and to have obtained a baccalaureate or an equivalent recognized foreign qualification (Bouchikhi and Zine, 2017).

The Algerian Republic has been committed to a series of educational reforms in both the compulsory and higher education sectors (Rose, 2015; Lahlouhi, 2015). This commitment is driven by global developments in the field of education. The Ministry of National Education has adopted educational system reforms and established specialized committees at all levels of education, from preschool to primary, middle, secondary and higher education (Chachoua and Schoelen, 2019; Lahlouhi, 2015). These reforms reflect the government's aspiration to enhance the education system in Algeria and ensure quality education throughout all stages of learning. Aligned with these reforms, the primary aim of the Algerian educational system is to eliminate social and economic inequalities and to provide accessible learning opportunities for all Algerian citizens of different ages (Lahlouhi, 2015; Bouchikhi and Zine, 2017). This reflects the aspiration to promote equal opportunities and create welcoming learning environments that cater to the diverse requirements of students in Algeria (Lahlouhi, 2015; Bouchikhi and Zine, 2017).

1.7.2 Evolution of Algerian higher education

In Algeria, the university system plays a crucial role in providing high school graduates with free education and the chance to pursue further academic studies based on their achievements, interests, and aspirations (Chachoua and Schoelen, 2019). The responsibility for overseeing higher education in the country rests with the Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research, which is entrusted with the task of formulating and implementing governmental policies related to higher education and scientific research (Bouchikhi and Zine, 2017). Over the years, higher education in Algeria has witnessed significant transformations and reforms (Djaber and Ibrahimi, 2013; Bouchikhi and Zine, 2017; Chachoua and Schoelen, 2019), which can be categorized into three distinct periods:

1.7.2.1 First phase 1962-1969

During this particular phase, the Ministry of Education had authority over the university system in Algeria (Chachoua and Schoelen, 2019). Initially, Algiers University was the sole institution of higher education in the country. Subsequently, two additional universities, Oran University and Constantine University, were established with the aim of increasing access to higher education (Bouchikhi and Zine, 2017). Throughout this period, the universities in Algeria adopted a pedagogical system that closely mirrored the structure employed in French universities. The educational journey within the university system during this phase consisted of four distinct phases (Chachoua and Schoelen, 2019). First, students pursued a three-year bachelor's degree program, providing them with a solid foundation in their chosen field of study. Following the completion of the bachelor's degree, students had the opportunity to engage in further studies for a period of one year, enabling them to deepen their knowledge and specialization. For those seeking advanced qualifications, the university system offered a postgraduate degree, which required a minimum of two years of dedicated

study. This stage provided students with an opportunity to conduct in-depth research and contribute to their respective fields through original scholarly work. Finally, the pinnacle of academic achievement within this system was the Doctorate degree, which required a five-year commitment. Pursuing a Doctorate degree involved rigorous research, culminating in a dissertation that made a significant contribution to the chosen field of study. Overall, during this phase of development, higher education in Algeria experienced notable changes, including the expansion of universities beyond Algiers, the adoption of a pedagogical system akin to the French model, and the implementation of a structured academic progression encompassing Bachelor's, further studies, postgraduate degree, and Doctorate (Bouchikhi and Zine, 2017).

1.7.2.2 Second Phase 1970-1998

During this phase and following the establishment of the Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research in the 1970s, Algerian universities underwent significant transformations. They transitioned into public institutions with corporate status and financial autonomy, encompassing scientific, cultural, and professional bodies. The universities were governed by bodies such as the board of directors and scientific council while comprising faculties, institutes, annexes, administrative and technical departments. Moreover, a reform was implemented in the higher education system during this period. A new structure was introduced, which involved a four-year bachelor's degree, followed by a two-year Magister degree, and finally a Doctorate degree (Bouchikhi and Zine, 2017).

As part of these changes, numerous courses were introduced, broadening the range of study options available to students. Additionally, the number of universities in Algeria increased, allowing for greater accessibility to higher education across the

country. Furthermore, scholarship opportunities were introduced during this phase, providing financial support to students who might not have been able to attend university without them. These changes aimed to promote equal opportunities and facilitate access to higher education for students from diverse socio-economic backgrounds (Bouchikhi and Zine, 2017). Overall, this phase marked a period of significant progress and expansion in the Algerian higher education system. The introduction of new specializations, increased university numbers, and scholarship opportunities were all instrumental in enriching the higher education landscape and fostering a more welcoming higher education environment in Algeria (Djaber. and Ibrahimi, 2013).

1.7.2.3 From 1998 onwards

In response to the globalization of the university education system, Algerian universities adopted the Licence/Bachelor, Master, and Doctorate system (LMD) (Chachoua and Schoelen, 2019; Abdeselam, 2020). This reform resulted in significant curriculum changes and the adoption of new pedagogical practices (Bouchikhi and Zine, 2017). The main objective behind adopting the LMD system was to enhance international cooperation (Djaber and Ibrahimi, 2013; Bouchikhi and Zine, 2017).

Algeria transitioned from the previous system (4-year Bachelor's degree, 2-year Magister, 3-4-year Doctorate) to the LMD system (3-year Bachelor's degree, 2-year Master's degree, and 3/5-year Doctorate) in 2004. Starting from the 2004-2005 academic year, the Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research has undertaken reforms focusing on improving three key areas: educational curricula, teaching methodologies, and pedagogical systems (Bouchikhi and Zine, 2017).

1.7.3 Access to higher education

Admission to higher education in Algeria is open to students who have successfully completed their Baccalaureate exam or possess an equivalent recognized foreign qualification (Bouchikhi and Zine, 2017). The process of university admission is organized through a pre-registration and orientation circular that is issued annually. This circular outlines the requirements for admission to faculties and institutions of higher education and training. The allocation of students to different programmes is determined by a classification system that considers the student's preferences, their specialisation and results in the Baccalaureate examination, the available capacity of educational institutions, and the geographical district where the student resides. Additionally, specific fields of study may have additional requirements, such as presenting a medical certificate or participating in an interview with a panel (MERIC-net, 2019).

Access to higher education in Algeria appears to be structured and considerate of various factors such as previous academic performance, student preferences, and institutional capacity. However, one could question whether other criteria used for admission truly promote equal opportunities and inclusivity. Additional conditions, such as medical certificates or interviews, may introduce subjectivity which could undermine fair and transparent access to certain courses. It may be time to revise these admission procedures to ensure that they align with the principles of equal opportunity and provide a level playing field for all students.

1.7.4 The evolution of inclusive education in Algeria

Algeria is among the Arab and North African countries that have demonstrated a commitment to guarantee the rights of individuals with disabilities (Khochen-Bagshaw, 2020; Saidi and Bouizem, 2020; Bennoui, 2021). During the last three decades,

support provision for students with disabilities in Algerian education has known many developments (Boutebal and Yahy, 2018; Saidi and Bouizem, 2020). These include a series of changes in the Algerian policy and constitution demonstrating a growing awareness of the additional support needs of students with disabilities (Boutebal and Yahy, 2018; Saidi and Bouizem, 2020). Yet, the inclusion of students with disabilities in different educational settings in Algeria remains under-researched and at a stage of early development (Bouaicha, 2017; Zoreli, 2019).

In 1980, the Algerian government implemented the first policy to support children with disabilities. This support was through the establishment of Medical and Psycho-pedagogical centres (MPC), and institutions specialized to teach individuals with intellectual disabilities. In addition, this period witnessed the creation of specialized institutes for people with visual and hearing impairments (Boutebal and Yahy, 2018).

According to Bouzid-Baa and Mekhoukh (2016), two years later, in 1982, the authorities introduced the notion of including children and adolescents with disabilities in schools. However, this was not done until 1992, when Algeria ratified the convention on the rights of children, adopted from the general assembly of the United Nations on the 20th of November 1989 (ref Presidential decree No92 / 461 of December 19, 1992).

The Algerian Ministry of Solidarity then set up and equipped special classes in primary schools with specialized and trained teachers for children with disabilities. However, this initiative failed to scale across all mainstream schools, as the majority of primary school headmasters were reluctant to host such classes in their schools due to perceived difficulties associated with them. According to the headteachers, one such difficulty was that these special classes did not help the learners who attended them to mix socially with their peers who attended the general classes. Related to this was

the headteachers' observation that students without disabilities who were enrolled in the same schools held negative attitudes toward the students who attended the special classes. Furthermore, these classes did not have much in common with the general classes as they used different curriculum and resources (Bouزيد-Baa and Mekhoukh, 2016).

In 2002, Algeria took a significant step forward by enacting dedicated legislation aimed at addressing the needs of individuals with disabilities. This approach reflected Algeria's aspiration to support and include individuals with disabilities (Bennoui, 2021). Accordingly, a new definition of disability was adopted. Law No. 85, which pertains to the protection and promotion of health, provides a definition of persons with disabilities in Article 89. The article states the following:

'A person with a disability is defined as any child, adolescent, adult, or elderly individual who experiences either a mental or physiological impairment that limits their ability to perform activities within the normal range for a human being, or who has a disability that hinders their social life or prevents it altogether.'

However, it is important to note that this legislation, which seems to favor the use of the medical model over the social model of disability, failed to define disability in accordance with the principles of the CRPD as it only focused on impairment and limitations of the person, without addressing social and environmental barriers (Degener, 2018).

From 2002 onwards, new laws were introduced obliging the sector of education, in collaboration with parents' associations, the Ministry of Solidarity, and health institutions, to promote the inclusion of students with disabilities in educational settings. Article 14 from the 2008 legislation on protecting the rights of people with disabilities stated that:

'The government guarantees the right to education for children with special needs. In addition to that, the educational sector with the help of the other concerned sectors should ensure and provide appropriate teaching environment and school integration for students with disabilities and those with chronic diseases.'

During that time, several charity associations, such as EL Baraka association in Algiers, ANIS in Boumerdes, Tedj in El oued, and NOUR in Oran, were created with the aim of assisting not only people with disabilities but their families as well. A key goal of these associations was to bring to Algeria the principle of inclusion and to create "schools for all" [...] which include everybody, celebrate differences, support learning, and respond to individual needs' as envisioned by the Salamanca statement (UNESCO, 1994, p. iii). The adoption of the Salamanca framework into the Algerian context was an important step towards inclusive education in the compulsory sectors (primary, middle and secondary schools). A number of projects from 2010 to 2017 were instrumental to this (Bouzid-Baa and Mekhoukh, 2016). Their aim was to improve the quality of access and support provided to students with disabilities in educational settings, through the following objectives:

- Spreading awareness among families and relatives of people with disabilities, and the media about the potential of students with disabilities and their right to education.
- Providing professional training and development in order to enhance inclusion in education.
- Providing necessary resources and equipment for students with disabilities.
- Raising awareness and lobbying local and national authorities to develop policies that can improve the experiences and outcomes of students with disabilities.

However, despite these projects and relevant legislation, there remains a gap in achieving inclusive higher education (Zoreli, 2019). The Algerian Constitution and Law 02-09 provide a strong foundation for safeguarding the rights of persons with disabilities, including access to education and vocational training. However, progress in the higher education sector with regards to accommodations for students with disabilities has been limited (Bouaicha, 2017; Djedidi and Djedidi, 2018). Furthermore, there is insufficient information and understanding about the experiences of disabled students within Algerian higher education institutions (Guersas and Ouadah, 2018). The current provisions in Law 02-09 and other regulations primarily address social inclusion and access to specialized education and vocational training. However, they do not adequately address the specific challenges faced by students with disabilities in pursuing higher education (Guersas and Ouadah, 2018). As noted above, some efforts to create a more inclusive environment for university students with disabilities were made through projects under the auspices of the EU funded programme TEMPUS (Miłosz, Milosz and Grzegórski, 2016). However, only three Algerian universities participated in these projects and the information available at the time of writing indicates that limited progress has been made towards including students with disabilities in Algerian higher education.

Despite the pronouncements made by the Algerian authorities about supporting students with disabilities and protecting them against discrimination and exclusion, it seems that there is still a significant disparity between legislation and practice (Bouzid-Baa and Mekhoukh, 2016; Zoreli, 2018). For this reason, it can be concluded that there is a need for research in this area to provide insights into the experiences of students with disabilities in Algerian higher education and how they can be enhanced. The current research aims to provide such insights. The focus and design of the research

will be explained later in the methodology chapter, after a literature review of relevant research from other parts of the world is presented in the following chapter.

1.8 Thesis structure

The following sections offer a concise summary of the chapters in this thesis:

Chapter 1: Background and Context

This chapter acts as an introduction, aiming to familiarize the reader with the research topic. It serves as a foundation for the subsequent chapters, establishing the context of the research. The chapter begins by outlining the rationale for the study and the reason for selecting a specific university as the context of the research. After presenting the research questions and aims, the chapter outlines the significance of the study and its contribution to knowledge. This is followed by a brief overview of the education system in Algeria, a section on the evolution of the higher education system, and a section on inclusive education.

Chapter 2: Literature Review

This chapter commences by delving into the background of the research, shedding light on the concepts of disability and inclusive education, and on their evolution over the years. It examines the historical context and the development of conventions, policies, and practices aimed at promoting inclusivity and support for students with disabilities. This is followed by an overview of the development of inclusive education and the Arab region, and a section on inclusive higher education. Finally, the chapter considers previous international research on the inclusion of university students with disabilities.

Chapter 3: Methodology and Research Design

The methodology chapter outlines the research approach, design, and methods employed in the study. It describes the data collection procedures, sample selection, and data analysis techniques. The chapter also addresses any limitations or challenges encountered during the research process.

Chapter 4: Findings

This chapter presents the findings of the study in three sections. The findings from the interviews with the students with disabilities are presented in the first section. The findings from the interviews with the disability support staff are presented in the second section. A comparison between the findings from the two groups is presented in the third section.

Chapter 5: Discussion

The discussion chapter focuses on the interpretation and synthesis of the findings, linking them to existing literature and Bronfenbrenner's ecological systems theory.

Chapter 6: Conclusions and Recommendations

In the final chapter, the research findings are summarized. This chapter draws conclusions based on the findings and discussion, and makes recommendations for practice and for future research. The contribution of the study and its limitations are also considered.

Chapter 2: Literature Review

2.1 Introduction

This chapter aims to establish a foundation for the study by discussing the concepts of disability and inclusive education. It will trace the evolution of these concepts over time at both the international level and within the context of the Arab world. Furthermore, this chapter will explore the development of inclusive higher education, and share insights into the experiences of university students with disabilities drawing on international research on this topic.

2.2 The evolution of the concept of disability

The concept of disability has evolved over the years and is still defined variously in the literature (Shakespeare, 2018; Shanimon and Rateesh, 2014). Conceptualisations of disability tend to be aligned with sets of assumptions and attitudes referred to as 'models of disability' (Finkelstein, 1996; Shanimon and Rateesh, 2014). Some of the most influential models of disability are outlined below.

2.2.1 The Moral/Religious and Charity Models

The moral/religious model represents an ancient understanding of disability, rooted in theological contexts such as Judeo-Christianity (Rieser, 2017). According to this model, disability was perceived as a shameful condition and a divine revenge for sin, leading families to hide their children with disabilities and feel a sense of disgrace (Otieno, 2009; Retief and Letšosa, 2017; Wilson and Martin, 2018). This model viewed people with disabilities as burden to society due to them being dependent on others (Shanimon and Rateesh, 2014).

In this model, physical disabilities were often associated with the belief that those affected were cursed, and their conditions were seen as a consequence of their or their parents' alleged disobedience to God. As a result, they were deemed as lacking worth, productivity, and the ability to contribute to society (Otieno, 2009). Consequently, specialized institutions were established to provide skills training to people with disabilities and alleviate the challenges faced by them and their families (Rieser, 2017). As a result, this model is also referred to as the charity model (Shanimon and Rateesh, 2014; Jackson, 2018). It should be noted that, despite its intentions of assistance, the charity model perpetuated a significant divide between people with disabilities and those without disabilities, and failed to promote justice and inclusion (Rieser, 2017). It constructed people with disabilities as passive victims and undermined their value and agency by portraying them as dependent and weak, reliant on others for support (Retief and Letšosa, 2017).

2.2.2 The Medical Model

The emergence of the medical model, as a response to the limitations of the moral/religious and charity model, was driven by advancements in medical sciences during the mid-1800s (Graham *et al.*, 2020). According to Henderson and Bryan (2012), the medical model perceives disability as a medical problem to be rehabilitated and cured (Shanimon and Rateesh, 2014; Jackson, 2018; Graham *et al.*, 2020). It views people with disabilities as imperfect bodies that require treatment to conform to the norms of an ableist society. Also referred to as the personal tragedy model, individual model, or rehabilitation model, the medical model is based on a comparison between people with disabilities and those without disabilities (Croft, 2010; Henderson and Bryan, 2012; Oliver, 2013; Jackson, 2018). It characterizes disability as a limitation or inability of individuals to perform tasks in the same manner as non-

disabled people (Morley and Croft, 2011). It perceives disability as an inherent characteristic, and focuses solely on the perceived limitations and weaknesses of people with disabilities, disregarding their strengths and needs (Oliver, 1999; Croft, 2010; Morley and Croft, 2011; Rieser, 2017; Wilson and Martin, 2018). Graham *et al.*, (2020) and Rieser (2017) argued that the medical model focuses excessively on the individual's disability, neglecting the disabling factors within the environment and the surrounding context. Goering (2015) points out that this model negatively impacts how people with disabilities perceive themselves, as it can lead them to internalize blame for being born with a disability and to perceive it as a personal fault.

2.2.3 The Social Model

The social model of disability emerged in the 1970s as a response to the prevailing medical model that viewed disability as a medical deficit. The Union of Physically Impaired Against Segregation (UPIAS), a British disability rights organisation established in 1972, played a significant role in shaping this model (Shakespeare, 2010; Oliver, 2013). Unlike its predecessors, the social model distinguishes between impairment and disability. Impairment is seen as a health condition, while disability is understood as the result of the interaction between an individual's health condition and features in the environment that act as challenges for the individual with this health condition, e.g. stairs that present a challenge to people with mobility constraints (Oliver, 2013; Graham *et al.*, 2020). According to the social model, the barriers and restrictions faced by people with disabilities are not a consequence of their impairments, but rather the outcome of cultural, social, and economic factors that have created a society which excludes them (Croft, 2010; Rieser, 2017; Graham *et al.*, 2020). In order to address this, the social model advocates for adjustments in the physical and social environment to meet the needs of people with disabilities. This

entails reconsidering policies, legislation, attitudes, architectural design, and service accessibility, as well as eliminating social and economic barriers that hinder equal participation and engagement for people with disabilities (Rieser, 2017).

The social model places responsibility on society for failing to accommodate the needs of people with disabilities. While acknowledging the impact of impairment on the individual, the social model directs attention to the environment as the primary source of disability and calls for societal changes to enable equal opportunities for all (Oliver and Barnes, 2012; Pitman, Brett and Ellis, 2023). The social model has been highly influential by rejecting the conceptualisation of disability as personal tragedy and redefining it as a social construct that encapsulates the ways in which an ableist society marginalises and oppresses individuals with impairments by creating barriers that restrict their access and participation (Owens, 2015). However, the social model's distinction between impairment (defined as a bodily or mental condition that is a variation within the spectrum of human differences) and disability (defined as disadvantage caused by society's failure to accommodate people with these impairments) has been criticised as artificial and simplistic by scholars who argue that disability should not be exclusively attributed to social barriers, even though the significance of these barriers in individuals' lives cannot be understated (Shakespeare and Watson, 2002; Degener, 2014; Owens, 2015).

The premise of this argument is that impairment has an impact on the individual's quality of life and this should not be overlooked as doing so can be perceived as dismissive of the lived experiences of the individual. While the environment can be disabling by being inaccessible, the impairment itself creates challenges for the body or mind, such as pain, fatigue, low mood, trouble focusing, etc., and these should not be overlooked. While these challenges are exacerbated by societal barriers, attributing

all challenges to society cannot be justified. In an attempt to address the limitations of the social model, Shakespeare and Watson (2002) advocated for an embodied ontology that recognises the body as a fundamental aspect of the disability experience, acknowledging that it is not a neutral entity but actively shapes how individuals engage with the world.

A related criticism of the social model of disability is that, by focusing exclusively on disabling societal barriers, the advocates of this model have raised awareness about necessary societal changes but have overlooked the need for policies that can help alleviate the challenges experienced by individuals as a result of their impairment (Degener, 2014). In addition, the social model's exclusive focus on disability as a social construct overshadows individual needs and the complexity of human beings. Because of this, the social model tends to refer to 'the disabled' as a homogeneous group and fails to consider how characteristics such as race, gender, social and cultural background interact with impairment to create individual experiences that cannot be subsumed under one broad umbrella, that of disability (Degener, 2014). The scholars who have critiqued the social model of disability, argue that a more holistic model can help address societal barriers while also ensuring that individualised support is provided to address the effects of impairment on the body and mind (Shakespeare and Watson, 2002; Degener, 2014). Such arguments have helped the conceptualisation of disability to evolve towards more nuanced and integrative approaches.

2.2.4 The Biopsychosocial Model

The biopsychosocial model, introduced in 1977 by George Engle, an American physician and psychiatrist, seeks to integrate aspects of both the medical and social models of disability (Petasis, 2019). The biopsychosocial model defines disability as

the interaction of biological and psychological factors that reside within the individual and social factors that reside within the environment (Graham *et al.*, 2020; Shakespeare, Watson, and Alghaib, 2017; Petasis, 2019). By considering the interactions between an individual's biological and psychological health on the one hand and societal factors on the other, this model aimed to provide a comprehensive understanding of disability and emphasized the need for both medical treatment and social adjustments to ensure equal opportunities for people with disabilities (Petasis, 2019). The biopsychosocial model questions the simplicity of the medical model, which focuses on impairment, and of the social model, which focuses on the environment, emphasizing the need for a more balanced approach that acknowledges the impact of both (Petasis, 2019). As such, this model has been influential in driving policy improvements and infrastructure changes to address the challenges faced by people with disabilities, particularly in terms of access and employment (Van Oudenhove and Cuypers, 2014). While acknowledging that the severity of impairment can impact full participation and employment opportunities for people with disabilities, the biopsychosocial model has been instrumental in guiding efforts to overcome segregation, stigmatization, and social exclusion, and to provide adequate support for people with disabilities (Petasis, 2019).

2.2.5 The Neurodiversity model

The origins of the neurodiversity model can be traced back to autism activist Jim Sinclair's essay 'Don't Mourn Us', published in 1993. A few years later, the term 'neurodiversity' was coined, encapsulating the concept of celebrating and embracing the diverse neurological characteristics and experiences that enrich our world (Armstrong, 2012). In 1998, Judy Singer, an Australian sociologist, introduced the term 'neurodiversity' as a unifying concept for emerging social movements advocating for

the civil rights of individuals with diverse neurological profiles, including those that were often stigmatized and medically labelled, such as autism (Milton, 2020). As the movement gained momentum, it encompassed a broader range of neurodivergent profiles. This expansion includes embracing learning and intellectual difficulties, such as dyslexia, dyspraxia, ADHD. The model advocates that these should be recognised as natural variations within human neurocognitive diversity (Armstrong, 2012; Hughes, 2021). The principles of the neurodiversity model align with those of the social model, by arguing that disability emerges from the interaction between the person and an environment that cannot accommodate their needs. The neurodiversity model advocates the creation of an environment that accepts and respects the diversity of minds (Dwyer, 2022).

Throughout its history, the neurodiversity movement has been primarily driven and shaped by autistic and other neurodivergent individuals who actively advocate for the rights of neurodivergent individuals (Den Houting, 2019; Ne'eman and Pellicano, 2022). However, as the movement gained momentum, an increasing number of neurotypical scholars and practitioners have aligned their work with the principles of neurodiversity, advocating for strengths-based support and emphasising the importance of ensuring that the voices of neurodivergent people are central in discussions about practices aiming to enhance their experiences (Den Houting, 2019).

The neurodiversity paradigm emphasizes the importance of acknowledging and celebrating the richness and diversity inherent in human nature and the human brain (Armstrong, 2012). This perspective carries significant implications for education and educational environments, encouraging educators to embrace the diversity of human experiences. Rather than attempting to adjust, cure, ameliorate, or alter an individual's disability, educators should strive to comprehend these differences and to work with

neurodivergent students to develop support plans that can meet their needs. Support plans that demonstrate respect for the unique perspectives and abilities of neurodivergent students are more likely to help them achieve their objectives (Armstrong, 2012; Hamilton and Petty, 2023).

While the neurodiversity movement focuses on cognitive diversity, arguably, its principles are also applicable to physical diversity. As such, physical impairment should be considered a human variation and the voices of people with physical impairments should be central in discussions and decisions about appropriate support.

2.2.6 The Human Rights Model

The human rights model of disability views disability as an inherent aspect of human diversity and emphasizes that human dignity, which is at the core of human rights, is not diminished by disability (Graham *et al.*, 2020). It highlights that people with disabilities have the same rights as everyone else and should not be excluded or discriminated against based on their disability. As noted by Degener (2017), this model takes a comprehensive approach by encompassing both civil and political rights, as well as economic, social, and cultural rights.

Unlike the medical, social, and biopsychosocial models, which appear to only define, classify or explain disability, this model is founded on the notion that disabled people possess inherent human dignity, and should be legally recognized as people before the law (Degener, 2017). It emphasizes the vital right of people with disabilities to fully and equally enjoy human rights within a culture of respect for their individual worth, and advocates that disability policy should be rooted in human rights. This model opposes the medical model, as it rejects the notion that impairment obstructs a person's ability to exercise their human rights, emphasizing that human rights are

applicable from birth, regardless of impairment (Degener, 2017). Furthermore, Degener (2017) argues, the absence of impairment should not serve as a prerequisite for being entitled to human rights. This model underscores the importance of considering human rights when formulating policies to promote equity and respect for individual dignity (Graham *et al.*, 2020).

2.3 Contemporary conceptualisations of disability

In recent years, one of the most commonly cited definitions of disability is the definition included in the preamble to the United Nations CRPD:

“Disability is an evolving concept and ... results from the interaction between persons with impairments and attitudinal and environmental barriers that hinders their full and effective participation in society on an equal basis with others.”

(United Nations, 2006, p. 3).

Article 1 of the CRPD states that ‘[p]ersons with disabilities include those who have long-term physical, mental, intellectual or sensory impairments which in interaction with various barriers may hinder their full and effective participation in society on an equal basis with others’ (United Nations, 2006, nonpaginated). Taken together, these definitions suggest that disability can be understood as the consequence of the interaction between individual characteristics and environmental factors, both physical and social. Kazou (2017) has argued that the definition of disability provided by CRPD is aligned with the definition of disability in the International Classification of Functioning (ICF), introduced by the World Health Organisation (WHO) in 2001. Under ICF disability is defined as:

“An umbrella term for impairments, activity limitations and participation restrictions. It denotes the negative aspects of the interaction between an individual (with a health condition) and that individual’s contextual factors (environmental and personal factors).”

(WHO, 2001, p. 221)

ICF's conceptualisation of disability is illustrated by the following figure:

Figure 1. The International Classification of Functioning, Disability and Health (ICF) Model.

(Adapted from WHO, 2001.)

In defining disability as an interaction of personal and environmental factors, both the ICF and the CRPD attempted to combine and integrate the medical model, which, as noted above, views disability as a medical issue (Rieser, 2017) with the social model, which views disability as the outcome of societal barriers which prevent those who are differently abled from benefiting from experiences and opportunities that are available to those who fit the conventional notion of ability (Rieser, 2017). In doing so, the ICF and CRPD are aligned with what has been referred to above as the biopsychosocial model, which perceives disability as an interaction of individual (biological and psychological), and social factors. In addition, according to Theresia Degener, a member of the CRPD committee between 2011 and 2018, the CRPD offers a human rights model of disability (Degener, 2017).

Degener (2017) argues that, although powerful in highlighting the environmental barriers faced by people with disabilities, the social model focuses on explaining

disability from an environmental perspective and on highlighting the discrimination experienced by people with disabilities. On the other hand, the CRPD focuses on the human rights and dignity of people with disability, and states that ‘human rights do not require absence of impairment’ (Degener, 2017, p. 34). In other words, the CRPD provides a framework that can be used “to promote, protect and ensure the full and equal enjoyment of all human rights and fundamental freedoms by all persons with disabilities, and to promote respect for their inherent dignity” (UNESCO, 2006).

With the conceptualisations of disability outlined above in mind, in the current study, disability is conceptualised as an interaction of personal, social and environmental factors which can limit an individual’s experiences and opportunities, and can restrict their human rights. In order to uphold the human rights of people with disabilities, appropriate support should be provided to address restrictions and limitations and ensure that people with disabilities are not disadvantaged in relation to those who do not have a disability. As advocated by the neurodiversity movement, the voices of people with disabilities should be central in any discussions about the type and amount of support required to meet their needs and enhance their experiences.

Having considered how the concept of disability has evolved over the years, and having outlined the definition of disability that has been used in the current study, this chapter will now turn to the education of people with disabilities, with particular focus on inclusive education.

2.4 Inclusive education

Inclusive education for people with disabilities emerged relatively recently but can be traced back to the civil rights movement in the 1960s (Thomas, Walker and Webb, 2005; Winter and O’Raw, 2010, Graham, 2020). An exploration of the development of

education for people with disabilities over the years reveals that it went through a long journey (Graham, 2020), and that it encompasses different stages (Dray, 2008). This section aims to provide a brief overview of this journey.

2.4.1 From exclusion to inclusion

As noted in the section on the religious/charity model of disability above, in the past, people with disabilities were stigmatized and seen as a burden to society (Dray, 2008; Rieser, 2017). They were excluded from various spaces, such as education, work, and health, and were considered passive and unproductive members of society (UNESCO, 2009). Many were even murdered at birth, while others were subjected to marginalization and mistreatment (Davis et al, 2020). The establishment of organized religion marked a slight shift in the attitudes towards people with disabilities. Islam, for instance, deemed maltreatment of people with disabilities to be against the principles of the religion (Al Thani, 2006). Similarly, Christianity advocated care for people with disabilities, including financial and emotional support (Winzer, 1993). In this context, institutions and asylums were established for people with disabilities. However, although their aim was to provide care for people with disabilities and to teach them basic skills, in practice, they ended up isolating them from their families and society (Colker, 2006; Dray, 2008; Shakespeare, 2018; Graham, 2020). Furthermore, while initially meaning to provide care and support, these institutions became tools for social control and oppression (Rieser, 2017).

Attitudes towards disability began to change in the modern era, as people started recognizing the rights and value of people with disabilities (Jackson, 2018). The Universal Declaration of Human Rights in 1948 emphasized the right to education for all, including people with disabilities (United Nations, 1948). The civil rights movements of the 1960s, which focused on racial and gender equality, also influenced

the inclusion of people with disabilities (Colker, 2006). For example, in the USA, disability rights groups started advocating for the rights of people with disabilities (Blanchett, Brantlinger and Shealey, 2005). The decision reached in the Brown vs. Board of Education case in the United States brought an end to the practice of excluding and segregating people based on their race, leading to the integration of all students in regular schools (Dray, 2008; Friend and Bursuk, 2012). This landmark ruling also had implications for disability (Dray, 2008). According to Blanchett, Brantlinger, and Shealey (2005), this shift towards desegregation prompted a more serious approach to addressing the dilemma of marginalized groups, including people with disabilities, with an increasing number of people resorting to legal action to protect the rights of their disabled children (National Council on Disability, 2018). Yet, although civil law stressed the importance of desegregation and widening access, those with disabilities who attended mainstream educational institutions were often regarded as guests and were provided with limited support and guidance (Artiles, Harris-Murri, and Rostenberg, 2006).

As Ainscow, Dyson, and Weiner (2013) have noted, although the process of including people with disabilities in education settings has varied across countries, it has commonly undergone three stages: segregation, during which students with disabilities were placed in different settings; integration, during which students with disabilities were placed in the same settings as students without disabilities but these settings were not adjusted to accommodate the needs of students with disabilities; and inclusion, during which education settings were transformed to become suitable for all students regardless of ability, background, characteristics or support needs. While the 1960s civil rights movement in USA led to integration, in Europe, in the early 1970s, much effort focused on closing institutions and establishing special schools,

which could be seen as replacing one form of segregation with another (Panzavolta and Lotti, 2012).

In Europe, efforts to integrate students with disabilities into mainstream education settings began to emerge in the late 1970s, within the context of mainstreaming, the process of opening mainstream schools to students with disabilities (Danforth and Jones, 2015). However, early attempts to include learners with disabilities in mainstream schools often resulted in neglect and isolation (Rieser, 2017). Parents and advocates had to fight for better conditions and support, leading to progress in the educational experiences for students with disabilities (Dray, 2008).

Efforts to ensure that people with disabilities access education with dignity and without discrimination led to the development of inclusive education. Although the roots of inclusion can be traced back to the civil rights movements of the 1960s (Thomas, Walker, and Webb, 2005; Graham, 2020), this approach gained notable attention and momentum in the 1990s, particularly following the influential UNESCO Salamanca statement in 1994, which sparked various international initiatives towards providing full inclusion for students with disabilities (Evans and Lunt, 2002). The Salamanca statement conceptualized inclusive education as not simply a set of rules and practices but rather a philosophy that embraces diversity and transforms learning and teaching to ensure that it is inclusive for all regardless of abilities, backgrounds, characteristics and needs (UNESCO, 1994). The Salamanca statement successfully transformed the perception of disability, previously associated with limited potential, by shifting the responsibility from the student to stakeholders and educational institutions to eliminate educational barriers and facilitate access and participation for all (Ainscow, Slee and Best, 2019; Hernández-Torrano, Somerton, and Helmer 2020; Graham *et al.*, 2020).

The UNESCO definition of inclusive education that was put forward with the Salamanca statement has since been broadened to include references to access and participation to quality education for all learners, regardless of background or characteristics (UNESCO, 2005, 2017). Alongside this, in 2016, the United Nations Committee on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities, commenting on Article 24 (right to inclusive education) of the Convention of the Rights of People with Disabilities (CRPD) defined inclusive education as

“a process of systemic reform embodying changes and modifications in content, teaching methods, approaches, structures and strategies in education to overcome barriers with a vision serving to provide all students of the relevant age range with an equitable and participatory learning experience and environment that best corresponds to their requirement and preferences.”

As part of efforts focusing on Sustainable Development Goal 4, a guide was produced aiming to support educators and other stakeholders in ensuring inclusion and equity in education (UNESCO, 2017). This guide makes specific reference to the importance of an inclusive education environment, which is described as a non-discriminatory setting that adjusts its architectural structures, teaching approaches and programmes, policies and practices, in order to promote accessibility and meet the requirements of all students without exception. The guide states that mainstream settings that do not make these adjustments are not considered inclusive. An inclusive environment, as defined in this guide, is aligned with the ‘presence, participation, achievement’ framework for inclusive education developed by one of the key scholars in the area, Mel Ainscow (2016).

Ainscow (2016) argues that inclusion is underpinned by the idea that the world is full of differences, which should be recognised, valued and respected. In this sense, diversity should be perceived in a positive sense. In order for education to be inclusive,

all barriers to access and participation must be removed. All students should enjoy the right to education, and should be enabled to participate in all educational activities, and to accomplish their goals.

The definition of inclusive education that is adopted in this study encompasses key elements of the definitions outlined above and can be summed up by the following statement from UNESCO's 'guide for ensuring inclusion and equity in education':

“Inclusion is a process that helps overcome barriers limiting the presence, participation and achievement of learners. Equity is about ensuring that there is a concern with fairness, such that the education of all learners is seen as having equal importance.

The central message is simple: every learner matters and matters equally”.

(UNESCO, 2017, p. 13)

This definition is well aligned with the rights-based conceptualisation of disability mentioned in the previous section, as it highlights the importance of fairness and the requirement to see all learners as having equal importance and, by extension, equal rights, and entitlement to support so that they can enjoy these rights.

2.4.2 Inclusive education in the Arab region

Historically, in the Arab world, disability has been a neglected topic of study with limited research and exploration of disability related issues (Saad and Borowska-Beszta, 2019; Balogova and Szot, 2020). In the past, as other countries throughout the world, Arab countries subjected people with disabilities to pity, marginalization, neglect, and even mistreatment (Saad and Borowska-Beszta, 2019; Al Thani, 2006). Balogova and Szot (2020) argue that people with disabilities were seen as 'symbols of *sins*', and continued to face widespread prejudice and discrimination in the Arab region until the 1960s. In general, assistance and support for people with disabilities were predominantly driven by feelings of pity and charitable intentions, and were primarily

offered by Islamic-affiliated institutions (Al Thani, 2006; Al-Hendawi, Keller and Khair, 2023). It was not until 1965, with the establishment of the Arab Labor organization, a body focusing on employment issues, including those affecting people with disabilities, that the Arab world started to gradually shift their perspective on people with disabilities and acknowledge their rights in different aspects of life (Alkhateeb, Hadidi and Alkhateeb, 2016; Saad and Borowska-Beszta, 2019; Balogova and Szot, 2020). At the same time, disability started becoming the topic of study and research to gain a deeper understanding of its nature, related issues, and effective approaches to support people with disabilities (Alkhateeb, Hadidi and Alkhateeb, 2016; Saad and Borowska-Beszta, 2019; Balogova and Szot, 2020; UNESCO, 2020).

In recent years, Arab countries have made progress in formulating legislation and policies that recognise the rights of people with disabilities in various domains of life (Bennoui, 2021). Notably, specific countries within the Middle East and North African region (MENA) have implemented national strategies to promote the rights of individuals with disabilities, particularly in the field of education. These advancements have been guided by the endorsement of guidelines and principles outlined in the CRPD, (Weber, 2012). The Arab region has pledged to uphold the fundamental right of all people with disabilities to access education at all levels (Alkhateeb, Hadidi and Alkhateeb, 2016; UNESCO, 2022). However, there is still much to be done to fully include people with disabilities in the education. According to a recent report on the experiences of people with disabilities in North Africa (Rohwerder, 2018) educational policies are not fully aligned with the principle of ensuring access to education for all children while there is often ambiguity surrounding the implementation of the commitment to inclusive education. Specifically in relation to Algeria, this report noted that most children with disabilities only attend primary school and are educated in

segregated settings. The report also revealed that, although Algeria has made discrimination against people with disabilities unlawful, the law is not effectively enforced thus making discrimination against people with disabilities, including students, a common occurrence. More recently, a UNESCO report on developments in relation to inclusion in education for children and young people with disabilities in the Arab region (UNESCO, 2022) noted that progress towards inclusive education has been slow due to limited resources and underdeveloped plans to end segregation.

It should be noted that in the Arab region, the term inclusive education is not used widely and the terms '*integration*,' '*mainstreaming*,' '*least restrictive environment*,' and '*inclusion*' are often used interchangeably (Al-Khateeb, Hadidi and Al- Khateeb, 2016). For instance, in Algeria the governmental policies to support people with disabilities use the term integration instead of inclusion (Degener, 2018; Hasroumi and Haffad, 2021). Aligned with the medical model of disability, integration means that people with disabilities are expected to fit in an environment that is not adjusted to meet their needs, in other words, the focus is on presence in a mainstream setting (UNESCO, 2020). On the other hand, in line with the social model, inclusion means that the environment welcomes and values diversity, and is designed to facilitate the access, participation and achievement of all, regardless of background, ability or other characteristic (UNESCO, 2020).

Students with disabilities in most educational settings in the Arab countries are still facing different barriers and are integrated rather than included (Al-Khateeb, Hadidi and Al-Khateeb; Al-A'dra, 2016; Bessai, 2018; Boutebal and Yahi, 2018; Zoreli, 2019). Barriers include insufficient support services, limited financial resources to support inclusive programmes, lack of physical accessibility, as well as negative societal attitudes stemming from a lack of understanding about the needs and capabilities of

people with disabilities (Alkhateeb, Hadidi and Alkhateeb, 2016; Khazaleh *et al.*, 2022; Al-A'dra, 2016; Bessai, 2018; Zoreli, 2019). These barriers will be discussed in some detail later on in this chapter, in the context of higher education. Before turning to them, the concept of inclusive higher education will be considered below.

2.5 Inclusive higher education

According to Peterson (2020), the origins of inclusive higher education can be traced back to the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR) (1948). Article 26 of the UDHR specifically recognizes the right to education for all, stating that ‘everyone has the right to education, [...] and higher education should be equally accessible on the basis of merit’ (UN, 1948). The right to education and specifically higher education, established through UDHR, was reiterated and reinforced through subsequent international conventions, treaties, and declarations, including UNESCO’s Convention against Discrimination in Education (1960), the Declaration on the Rights of Disabled Persons (1975), the World Declaration on Education for All (EFA) (UNESCO, 1990), and Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) (United Nations General Assembly, 2015).

The right to access higher education was also included in the UN convention on the rights of the child (1990), in Article 28 (1), which urges states to “make higher education accessible to all on the basis of capacity by every appropriate means”. The 1994 Salamanca statement also placed significant emphasis on ensuring equitable support and accessibility in post-secondary educational settings. Specifically, Article 19 advocates that ‘[n]ecessary provision should [...] be made for ensuring inclusion of youth and adults with special needs in secondary and higher education’ while Article 58 urges states to ensure that ‘curricula for students with special educational needs in senior classes [...] include specific transitional programmes [and] support to enter

higher education whenever possible' (p. 34). Through this emphasis on the need for transitional programs to assist students with disabilities in their transition to university, the Salamanca statement acknowledges the entitlement of people with disabilities to university life (Pavone, Bellacico, Cinotti, 2019).

Furthermore, the Salamanca statement not only emphasized the importance of ensuring access to higher education but also highlighted the need for active engagement of people with disabilities in this process, as a way to facilitate the exchange of valuable insights on inclusion and bridge the gap between research in inclusive education and practical implementation through the development of training and evaluation programs (Pavone, Bellacico, Cinotti, 2019). The statement recognized the significance of involving people with disabilities in research and training to ensure their voices are heard and their perspectives are taken into account, as stated in article 47:

'It is [...] important to actively involve people with disabilities in research and training roles in order to ensure that their perspectives are taken fully into account.'

Further reinforcing the need for inclusive higher education was the World Declaration on Higher Education (1998), which sought to improve accessibility of tertiary institutions for all people, including those with disabilities. This declaration reiterated the provisions set forth in the UDHR, reaffirming the commitment to ensuring equitable access to higher education for all people:

"[A]dmission to higher education should be based on the merit, capacity, efforts, perseverance and devotion, showed by those seeking access to it, and can take place in a lifelong scheme, at any time, with due recognition of previously acquired skills. As a consequence, no discrimination can be accepted in granting access to higher education on grounds of race, gender, language or religion, or economic, cultural or social distinctions, or physical disabilities."

(UNESCO 1998)

The importance of inclusive higher education was also emphasised in the Convention on the Rights of People with Disabilities (CRPD) (2006) which reiterated the rights of people with disabilities in all levels of education and lifelong learning (UN, 2006). The CRPD is considered a significant achievement that upholds the principles set forth in other documents such as the Salamanca statement (Pavone, Bellacico, Cinotti, 2019). Of particular note is Article 24 which recognizes inclusive education as a fundamental right and advocates the provision of reasonable accommodations to enable people with disabilities to access free education at all levels (primary, secondary, and tertiary) and engage in lifelong learning. The convention also highlights the need to protect people with disabilities from discrimination and exclusion based on their disabilities:

“States parties recognize the right of persons with disabilities to education. With a view to realizing this right without discrimination and on the basis of equal opportunity, States parties shall ensure an *inclusive education* at all levels.”

(UN, 2006; original Italics)

The CRPD places a significant emphasis on the right to post-secondary inclusive education, encompassing higher education, vocational training, adult education, and lifelong learning (United Nations, 2006). The convention also highlights the need to address accessibility issues by taking

“appropriate measures to ensure to persons with disabilities access, on an equal basis with others, to the physical environment, to transportation, to information and communications, including information and communications technologies and systems, and to other facilities and services [...]”

(United Nation, 2006)

In this context, the CRPD emphasizes the importance of employing qualified teachers with disabilities who are proficient in sign language and/or Braille, and of providing

appropriate training and disability awareness to staff at all levels to ensure that they are well equipped to support students with disabilities (UN, 2006).

The more recent international initiative to promote inclusive higher education is Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) (United Nations General Assembly, 2015). The explicit inclusion of tertiary education in the SDGs indicates a recognition of the increasing significance of access to this level (McCowan, 2019). The 2030 Agenda directly referred to higher education and recognized it as an objective, highlighting the significance of expanding access at this level, ensuring equitable opportunities free from discrimination, and fostering the active participation of marginalized groups, including those with disabilities (McCowan, 2019).

This brief outline of key international treaties and conventions promoting inclusive higher education for people with disabilities indicates that the rationale for inclusive higher education is well established and that detailed guidance is available to help states in their efforts. However, a growing body of literature exploring the development of inclusive higher education in various countries around the world indicates that the reality of inclusive higher education does not quite match the aspirations of the international conventions, declarations and treaties outlined above. An overview of some of this literature is provided below.

2.6 Research insights into inclusive higher education

Recently, the area of inclusion and participation of students with disabilities in higher education has gained much interest. A growing body of research has focused on examining the experiences of these students (eg. Garison-Wade, 2012; Kendall, 2016; Moriña, 2017; Mutanga, 2017; Martins, Borges and Gonçalves, 2018; Karellou, 2019; Mustaffa *et al.*, 2019; Lourens and Swartz, 2020; García-González *et al.*, 2021;

McKinney and Swartz, 2022). This literature suggests that, despite the aspirations of international treaties and conventions, and the efforts of states to implement these aspirations, many students with disabilities are still facing barriers in relation to access and participation in higher education. The proponents of the social model of disability have written extensively about the barriers that disable people with impairments (Finkelstein, 1993, 1996, 2001; Oliver, 1990, 1999, 2013; Oliver and Barnes, 2012). They classify these into three broad and interconnected groups: environmental, structural and attitudinal. Environmental barriers include inaccessible spaces, buildings and transportation. Structural barriers include policies, practices, procedures and communication systems that have been developed from an ableist perspective and do not accommodate the needs of individuals with impairments (Finkelstein, 1993, 1996, 2001; Oliver, 1990, 1999, 2013; Oliver and Barnes, 2012). Attitudinal barriers include misconceptions, prejudices and stereotypes about people with disabilities held by people without disabilities (Finkelstein, 1993, 1996, 2001; Oliver, 1990, 1999, 2013; Oliver and Barnes, 2012). Writing from a social model of disability theoretical perspective, Allan (2008; 2013) used this classification to refer to the barriers experienced by children with disabilities in education. When I reviewed the topics covered in the literature that I consulted for this study, it became clear that this classification would be a helpful framework for my thesis. In the following sections, the classification has been used to present the barriers experienced by the university students with disabilities as identified in previous research.

2.6.1 Environmental factors

After reviewing international literature on factors that affect the experiences of students with disabilities in higher education, it was clear that students with disabilities are still facing a series of obstacles, and they are not yet enjoying their full right to participation

in universities as their peers without disabilities. In line with the accounts and arguments of the proponents of the social model of disability (Finkelstein, 1993, 1996, 2001; Oliver, 1990, 1999, 2013; Oliver and Barnes, 2012) and with the observations of Allan (2008, 2013) in relation to the inclusion of children with disabilities in mainstream schools, the reviewed literature revealed that university students with disabilities face several environmental barriers, including lack of appropriate physical facilities and physical accessibility.

2.6.1.1 Physical environment

Accessibility to the physical environment appears to be among the problems that limit the full engagement of students with disabilities at university. Examples of such barriers include buildings, stairs, doorways, passages, and walkways that are not easily accessible.

A number of studies have reported barriers arising from inaccessible physical environment. Perspectives from Europe include a study conducted by Kendall (2016) on the views and experiences of students with disabilities in UK universities. The study showed that students with disabilities encountered various barriers that inhibited their full participation, including environmental barriers that hindered their access to different campus settings. Students with disabilities in Greek universities have also reported being unable to access different buildings and settings within their campus. Many of the participants in recent studies conducted in Greece mentioned inaccessible physical facilities, such as unsuitable lifts, absence of ramps and inaccessible toilets (Vlachou and Papananou, 2018; Karellou, 2019). Students with disabilities in Spanish universities have also reported accessibility challenges (Moriña and Perera, 2020; García-González *et al.*, 2021). They have described the rooms and buildings of their

universities as out-dated, because it is difficult for them to access classrooms. Furthermore, they have reported that the class equipment was not adapted to their needs. The findings of this research highlight that Spanish universities have still not adapted most of their basic facilities to meet the requirements of students with disabilities, including furniture, doors, parking facilities and lifts. Participants suggested that old universities need to make more effort to accommodate students with disabilities, both inside the classrooms and outside, as they are not yet ready to welcome them. On a slightly different but related issue, participants in a study by Moriña and Morgado (2018) brought up the problem of transportation to the university, highlighting that public transportation in Spain was still inaccessible at the time the study was conducted.

Perspectives from Asia include a study in Thailand, which examined the barriers that hinder the participation of 12 blind students in higher education (Bualar, 2018). The participants in this study outlined several barriers including uneven walkways, last minute classroom relocations that cause students with disabilities to arrive late to classes, and desks that are not designed to be disability-friendly.

Similarly, Mustaffa *et al.*, (2019) who investigated the perceptions of students with disabilities towards the services and support offered by Malaysian higher education institutions reported that students faced difficulties in relation to physical access to university buildings and infrastructures. The students were dissatisfied with the quality of the existing equipment and facilities at their universities because they were not 'disability-friendly'. Another study conducted in 2019 by Yusof *et al.*, which also examined the experiences of students with disabilities in Malaysian universities, corroborated the findings of the previous study, as the participants stated that the architectural infrastructure of most universities was still a barrier to their access and

participation. Students with disabilities in this study (Yusof *et al.*, 2019) further voiced their concern about the lack of transportation and mobility services, and argued that universities in Malaysia were still not well prepared to provide support for them.

Perspectives from Africa include the findings of Tudzi, Bugri and Danso (2020) who examined the experiences of one female student facing mobility challenges, and investigated how the Ghanaian university she attended addressed her specific needs. The student reported that navigating the university's physical environment posed significant challenges and hindered her ability to move independently at university. Reported challenges included long distance between buildings, and inability to use libraries, classrooms and examination halls that had not been adapted to become accessible.

Students with disabilities in the Arab world appear to face similar environmental barriers including inaccessible and outdated buildings, lack of ramps, absence of elevators, lack of signposting, uneven walkways (Khayat-zadeh-Mahani *et al.*, 2020). In a major study aiming to understand the challenges faced by university students with disabilities in Egypt, Fathi-Ahmed (2020) reported that the 140 students with disabilities who participated face various environmental problems both within and outside the university campus. These problems include inaccessible restrooms, canteen services, elevators, and transportation. More than half of the participants stated that the university buildings do not meet their needs. Other challenges reported included difficulties in attending lectures due to transportation issues, narrow elevators which cannot accommodate a wheelchair, obstacles in corridors and doors that hindered their access to desired locations, and lack of signs to facilitate moving between university buildings. Similar findings arose from a study examining the experiences of undergraduate and postgraduate students with disabilities at Shaqra

University in Saudi Arabia (Madhesh, 2023), The participants reported dissatisfaction with their university experience due to various reasons. Among the primary concerns were inaccessibility of the university environment and disregard of their additional support needs.

Another study conducted in the Arab world, specifically in Jordan (Alhusban and Almshaqbeh; 2023), sought to examine the impact of design factors on students with disabilities and to evaluate how the built environment of Jordanian universities aligns with international standards. The study found that Jordanian public universities lack certain design features necessary for achieving an accessible built environment comparable to international universities. Additionally, although the participants in this study expressed satisfaction with some aspects such as pathways, ramps, and elevators, they showed dissatisfaction with parking, bathrooms, and signage systems (Alhusban and Almshaqbeh; 2023). These findings indicate that some progress has occurred since an earlier study that was conducted in Jordan, which reported inaccessible buildings and libraries (Al-A'dra, 2016), but suggest that further improvements are needed.

In Algeria, it seems that the situation of students with disabilities is not different from the situation of students with disabilities in other Arab and international universities. Although research on the experiences of students with disabilities in Algerian higher education institutions is very limited, the few existing studies report barriers and challenges faced by students with disabilities and highlight the need to improve the accessibility of the environment.

Zoreli (2019) reported that the Algerian university where he conducted his study had limited accessibility features, particularly in transportation, canteen services, libraries,

classrooms, and residency halls, mainly due to the presence of stairs and steps. While new residency halls had some adaptations, older residences lacked accessibility features. In line with these findings, Nabti (2018) who conducted a study in the same Algerian university, concluded that environmental barriers were the most encountered challenges for students with disabilities. Despite efforts by the university to improve accessibility by refurbishing buildings and classrooms, overall accessibility remained an issue. Similarly, a study of the experiences of students with disabilities in another Algerian university revealed that inaccessible buildings as well as unavailability of suitable transportation presented significant challenges to the participants (Djedidi and Djedidi, 2018). The authors concluded that, with only a few students with disabilities at this university, their additional support needs were overlooked, resulting in limited accessibility and reduced participation.

Taken together these studies provide insights into the environmental factors that affect the experiences of students with disabilities in higher education institutions, revealing the need to improve accessibility. The findings underscore the importance of addressing environmental obstacles, providing necessary adaptations, and promoting a supportive and inclusive environment for students with disabilities in universities.

A growing body of literature has also investigated the perceptions of academic and support staff in relation to the accessibility of physical facilities in universities. Academic and support staff tend to share the same views as students with disabilities and have the same perceptions as students with disabilities of the physical/environmental barriers to inclusion in higher education (Morina and Morgado, 2018; Yusof et al, 2019; Morina and Perera, 2020)

A qualitative study which investigated the perceptions of academic and non-academic staff towards barriers to inclusion in Portuguese universities (Martins, Borges and Gonçalves, 2018) highlighted that despite the efforts made by universities to renovate and adapt the architecture to accommodate the additional support needs of students with disabilities, physical infrastructure was still impeding students' access and mobility. Similarly, Kendall (2018) and Carballo, Morgado, and Cortés-Vega (2021), through their investigations in the UK and Spain respectively, reported that staff believed that the university environment was still unaccommodating for students with disabilities. Participants from both studies reinforced results of other research from different parts of the world, as they reported that students with disabilities faced many infrastructural obstacles and barriers including inaccessible lecture rooms, and inappropriate seating.

In another major study, Moriña and Orozco (2021) sought academic staff's perceptions of barriers and aids to inclusion in Spanish universities. Interviews were conducted with 119 academics from 10 Spanish universities. The participants mentioned that some of the most significant obstacles faced by students with disabilities at universities were physical obstacles. They indicated that many university buildings were not adapted and were inaccessible for students, particularly doors, desks, offices, and toilets. In addition, they stated that it is very challenging for students with disabilities to be attending universities where the basic conditions such as accessible physical facilities are not met. For example, they referred to desks being fixed to the floor, which prevents students with disabilities from moving freely and joining their peers in different activities inside the classroom, making them feel marginalised.

Inaccessibility of university buildings was not the only environmental factors reported as barriers in the literature. Unavailability of accessible academic materials and

resources within universities was another environmental factor affecting the experiences of students with disabilities in higher education institutions. As highlighted in the findings outlined below, this exposed students with disabilities to different types of discrimination and marginalisation, and made them feel under-valued.

2.6.2 Structural Factors

Finkelstein(1993, 1996, 2001) Oliver (1990, 1999, 2013) and Allan (2008, 2013) have argued that structures such as policies, procedures, regulations and routines tend to be informed by an ableist mindset and as such they are not accommodating the needs of individuals with disabilities. The experiences of students with disabilities at university level, as reported in the reviewed research, highlight the presence of multiple structures that affect their full participation. These disabling structures are discussed below.

2.6.2.1 Access

Research on the experiences of students with disabilities has shown that these students can experience challenges in accessing their preferred higher education courses. For instance, a study exploring the experiences of students with disabilities in South African universities (McKinney and Swartz, 2022) revealed that disclosure of disability prior to enrolment can result in students not being accepted in the courses they wish to study. Participants shared their frustration, recounting how their applications were overlooked after they had disclosed their disabilities. This relates to a finding from an earlier study (Yusof *et al.*, 2019), in Malaysian universities, in which administrative staff reported that students with disabilities who were interested in pursuing science courses were not given the opportunity to do this due to concerns that their disabilities would make it difficult to participate fully in these types of courses.

Rather, these students were directed towards social sciences courses, which university staff considered easier for students with disabilities to navigate. One of the administrators who participated in this study reported that a student with visual impairment managed to get a place in a science course due to his disability being very mild and almost unnoticeable (Yusof *et al.*, 2019).

Similarly, in a study exploring the university experiences of students with visual impairments in Ghana (Odame *et al.*, 2021), the participants reported that they experienced restrictions in the type of courses they could choose to study. They said that university staff steered them towards courses in education, social sciences and languages. According to the participants, this was because other programmes did not have any resources that could accommodate their needs. The participants highlighted the long term implications of this practice, such as narrowing down the employment opportunities and career prospects these students could have as graduates if they were only allowed to study specific subjects at university (Odame *et al.*, 2021).

These findings suggest that, in some cases, disability disclosure can limit the course options for prospective students with disability and, in order to avoid this, students whose disabilities are not visible prefer not to disclose them. However, when the disability is visible, as in the case of the participants in the study by Odame *et al.* (2021) mentioned above, this can restrict their access to the courses and subjects they wish to study at university.

2.6.2.2 Participation and achievement

2.6.2.2.1 Transition to higher education

As noted above, inclusive higher education is founded on the idea that all people, regardless of ability, background, characteristics and needs should be able to access

higher education, participate fully, and complete their studies successfully (UN, 1948; UNESCO 1998; UN, 2006). In order to participate fully in their higher education studies, students with disabilities require accommodations and adjustments to ensure that their experiences are equitable to those of students without disabilities. However, many studies report that such accommodations and adjustments are not always available. Early challenges include the transition to higher education. A number of studies have identified this as a critical period for students with disabilities. For instance, Lane's (2017) review of 41 different research studies investigating the experiences of students with disabilities across various higher education establishments globally, revealed that the transition experiences of these students tend to be challenging due to multiple factors, including the need to get used to a new environment and ways of learning often without sufficient information and support. Similarly, in another qualitative study investigating transition issues from the perspectives of students with visual impairment transitioning to a university in New Zealand (Pacheco, Yoong and Lips, 2021) the participants reported that university was different from high school, and that they were worried about the high educational demands of university. The participants found it difficult and stressful to handle their academic responsibilities at university, as they felt that they were not prepared to meet such demands, and some of them even thought of dropping out. The authors concluded that universities must offer students with disabilities effective induction to university life, and must ensure that appropriate services are available to support them as they make the move to higher education. Similarly, a study into the experiences of students with disabilities in German universities (Bartz, 2020) revealed that one of the greatest structural barriers experienced by the participants was lack of preparedness

to manage the academic workload, which they found to be much heavier than in high school.

Lengthy and complicated registration processes and difficulty changing groups or courses have been reported as challenges that affect negatively the university experiences of students with disabilities, especially those who are starting university (Al-A'dra, 2016). Similarly, students with disabilities have raised concerns about the bureaucracy and long waits in order to request and obtain accessible materials, resources and other types of support (Strnadová, Hájková and Květoňová, 2015; Lane, 2017; Moriña, 2017; Hector, 2020; Moriña, and Orozco, 2021; Abrahams *et al.*, 2023). Reporting on their experiences studying in UK universities and on the factors that affect them, students with disabilities who participated in Hector's (2020) study indicated that they face extra burdens compared to their peers without disabilities, particularly when it comes to dealing with the administrative procedures of accessing support. Students in this study identified significant issues with applying for the Disabled Students' Allowance, which was described as a complex and lengthy process.

2.6.2.2.2 Learning resources, teaching methods, and assessment

Concerns about the availability and accessibility of learning materials have been expressed in various studies. For example, academic staff in a study conducted by Moriña and Orozco (2021) stated that curriculum and learning materials can act as obstacles for students with disabilities since they are not designed with them in mind. Similarly, in the study by Nabti (2018), which, as mentioned above, was conducted in an Algerian university, the participating students with disabilities reported absence of pedagogical materials tailored to their additional support needs. They mentioned

inadequately adapted learning materials, ineffective teaching methods, a scarcity of accessible learning resources, and a lack of access to necessary technological devices. Similar findings were reported in a study focusing on the experiences of students with visual impairment in higher education in Lagos, Nigeria (Okiki and Okonji, 2019). The students who participated in this study reported that they encountered a number of barriers that affected their learning, including lack of appropriate resources such as audiobooks and braille materials. The participants said that they experienced a sense of exclusion because they did not have equal chances as their sighted peers, since universities and libraries in Nigeria lacked adequate supplies to enable them to participate fully in the learning process. Students with visual impairment in another study also reported experiencing a sense of exclusion and stated that they had to take responsibility for sourcing accessible resources in order to achieve academic success (McKinney and Swartz, 2022). Mustaffa *et al.*, (2019) reported similar findings in their study of the experiences of students with disabilities in a Malaysian university. Some students with hearing impairment who participated in this study mentioned that it was hard for them to listen to the lecturers, as lecture rooms were not equipped with microphones.

The theme of unavailability of accessible learning materials, such as Braille and equipment with talkback features has been mentioned by many other researchers (Al-A'dra, 2016; Hewett et al, 2017; Kendall, 2016; Mustaffa *et al.*, 2019; McKinney and Swartz, 2022; Moriña and Orozco 2021; Lourens and Swarts, 2020; Beyene, Mekonnen and Giannoumis, 2023; Cihan, 2021). For example, drawing on interviews with students with disabilities in Ethiopian higher education, Beyene, Mekonnen and Giannoumis (2023) revealed limited supply of educational resources in alternative format. This made these students reliant on recording some lectures, which did not

always work due to lecturers' low tone or background noise, especially when teachers walked inside the class. This is congruent with the findings of another study that investigated the experiences of students with visual impairments in six Turkish universities (Cihan, 2021). These students reported that they depended heavily on recording classes. This reliance stemmed from the fact that course materials, including notes, presentations, and textbooks, were not typically made available to them in alternative formats such as digital files, braille, or voice recordings.

The theme of technology and its role in facilitating the academic engagement of students with disabilities in higher education has also appeared in many studies (Garrison-Wade, 2012; Mullins and Preyde, 2013; Asselin, 2014; Seale *et al.*, 2015; Strnadová, Hájková, and Květoňová, 2015; Khumalo, 2019; Olatokunbo, and Patrick, 2019; García-González *et al.*, 2021; Lourens and Swartz, 2020; Pacheco, Yoong and Lips, 2021). Students with disabilities from different parts of the world who participated in these studies have argued that higher education institutions should invest in assistive technology (e.g. magnification software, adapted keyboards, word processing aids) in order to make it easier for students with disabilities to access their learning and participate effectively in higher education. It has also been argued that adjustments should be automatically incorporated in higher education to fulfil the potential of all students without exception, and students should not have to reiterate their needs to each new member of staff (Osborne, 2019).

In their study of access to higher education for people with disabilities in Spain, García-González *et al.* (2021) reported that students with disabilities also experienced difficulties with the virtual elements of their programmes because the platforms used were outdated in terms of organisation of information and content and lacked accessibility features that could enable students with disabilities to adjust the settings

to suit their needs. Students with disabilities in this study also reported that lack of staff training to use software and technological resources effectively made it even more difficult for them to use those tools. In line with participants in other studies (Seale *et al.*, 2015; Lopez-Gavira, Moriña and Morgado, 2021), the participants in this study suggested that staff should be trained on how to use technology in order to assist those students.

Other research has revealed that faculty members themselves can sometimes act as a barrier, when they do not have enough awareness and information on how to support students with disabilities and accommodate their additional support needs (Black, Weinberg, and Brodwin, 2015; Moriña, 2017; Bartz, 2020). Students with disabilities have also reported that the teaching methods and techniques adopted by some academic staff are ineffective, for example some academic staff do not explain concepts clearly, or simply read from their slides or notes (Moriña Díez, López, and Molina, 2015). Students with disabilities but also academic staff themselves have attributed these challenges to academic staff's lack of awareness of the needs of students with disabilities and to lack of training in strategies that they can use to support them (Kendall, 2016; Yusof *et al.*, 2019; Collins, Azmat, and Rentschler, 2018; Zhanget *al.*, 2018; Moriña, Sandoval and Carnerero, 2020; Firat, 2021).

Assessment has also been identified as a structural factor affecting the experiences of university students with disabilities. The reviewed literature shows that when assessment has not been adjusted in line with the additional support needs of students with disabilities, it can affect negatively their academic achievements. Kendall (2016) has reported that students with disabilities appreciate alternative methods of assessment and reasonable adjustments that accommodate their needs. However, not all universities offer this. In a study focusing on the experiences of students with

disabilities (Osborne, 2019), the participants, most of whom had been studying in English universities, argued that some types of assessment were unfair, including grading by attendance, presentations, and activities that require mobility. According to the participants, these assessments can be challenging for students who may have unstable health conditions or mobility constraints or find it difficult to present in front of a large audience due to anxiety or other mental health issues. The timetabling and duration of exams have also been raised by students with disabilities as issues that can affect their academic performance, with opportunities for extra time and extensions proposed as helpful accommodations (Yssel *et al.*, 2016; Collins, Azmat and Rentschler, 2018; Yusof *et al.*, 2019; García-González *et al.*, 2021; Moriña and Orozco, 2021).

Moreover, unavailability of scribes/readers and assistants during exams was another problem highlighted by students with disabilities. In studies conducted in various countries, including Jordan (Al-A'dra, 2016), Ethiopia (Beyene *et al.*, 2023), as well as Algeria (Bouaicha, 2017), students with disabilities spoke of the challenges they face in finding someone to read or write for them during exams. They spoke of instances when the administration and support office promised to allocate assistants who could provide the necessary support on the day of the examination, however, these promises were not fulfilled, and the necessary assistance was not provided. This lack of support from the administration and support office added to the difficulties faced by these students during their exams, further highlighting the barriers that affect their participation and progress in university.

On the back of international treaties and conventions urging states to widen access to higher education for students with disabilities, many countries have extended the scope of their inclusive education policies to include higher education. Such policies

tend to include statements about accommodations and reasonable adjustments. However, research findings indicate that there is often a gap between policy and practice. For example, reporting on the experiences of students with visual impairment in Thailand, Bualar (2018) concluded that barriers that impede students with visual impairment from experiencing inclusive higher education are due to limitations in policies and in the implementation of available guidelines. Kendall (2016) and Yusof *et al.* (2019) have also concluded that, although UK and Malaysian universities respectively are making efforts to support students with disabilities, there is scope for improvements, including greater consistency across all departments and universities. Similarly, focusing on Algeria, Arroudj (2019) has stressed the need to develop a comprehensive inclusive policy and implementation strategy to accommodate the additional support needs of higher education students with disabilities.

2.6.2.3 Social and emotional support

Different studies have documented the importance of emotional and mental health support for university students with disabilities, as it can have a positive impact on their academic experiences and achievements. The existence of a counselling service within universities is regarded by many as a crucial necessity in order to assist all students, including students with disabilities, in overcoming the challenges they may encounter throughout their university journey (Al-A'dra, 2016; Bartz, 2020; Khazaleh *et al.*, 2022). The study of challenges facing students with disabilities at the University of Jordan mentioned above (Al-A'dra, 2016) emphasized the need to increase the number of psychologists and counsellors within the university to help the growing number of students with disabilities. Similarly, through a quantitative study that aimed to evaluate the counselling services offered to 244 students with disabilities in Jordanian universities, Khazaleh *et al.*, (2022) revealed the importance of university

counselling services in helping these students develop coping strategies for exams, as well as personal and interpersonal skills.

Peer interactions can be another source of social and emotional support for students with disabilities. Recent studies have shown positive relationships between students with disabilities and their peers without disabilities. Bouaicha (2017), who conducted a quantitative study at Biskra University in Algeria, reported that peers without disabilities played a crucial role in supporting students with disabilities, including help with exam preparation and provision of lesson summaries. Additionally, in a study which explored the experiences of students with visual impairments in Ghana, Odame *et al.* (2021) referred to the importance of peer support, as students with disabilities highlighted that due to the absence of institutional support, they relied on sighted peers for assistance, including exam preparation and help with daily activities. However, as will be seen in the section entitled 'attitudinal factors' below, research has shown that relationships between students with disabilities and peers without disabilities are not always positive due to some peers' negative attitudes towards disability.

Structural factors that are external to the university environment but can help or impede the academic experiences of university students with disabilities have also been identified. Among these external factors is family support. Different studies have shown that family support can be instrumental in creating a positive university experience for students with disabilities (Mutanga, 2017; Abrahams *et al.*, 2023). In a qualitative systematic review that sought to explore the implementation of inclusive higher education policy based on the lived experiences of students with learning disabilities in South African universities, Gow, Mostert and Dreyer (2020) pointed out that in most of the reviewed studies, students expressed gratitude about support coming from their families. The majority of the students who participated in the studies

reviewed by the authors revealed that they preferred relying on family and friends rather than waiting for institutional support which they described as inadequate and inconsistent. Similarly, in a study that explored the psychosocial support for students with disabilities enrolled in Ghanaian universities (Akoto et al, 2022), family support featured highly. The findings from this study emphasized the importance of family support in encouraging students with disabilities to pursue their higher education studies, and persevere in them. The eleven students with disabilities who participated in this study expressed gratitude towards the motivational, emotional but also financial support provided from their families, which enabled them to overcome different challenges and barriers at university. However, as noted in a study investigating factors that affect the transition of youth with disabilities to higher education (Lindsay et al., 2018) family support should not be taken for granted. The findings of this study showed that not all students with disabilities have supportive families or receive assistance from their families, which highlights the importance of effective institutional support to enable students with disabilities to pursue university studies.

2.6.2.4 Financial Matters

According to the literature, another structural challenge which affects the university experiences of students with disabilities is the financial burden of university related costs. The study by Hector (2020), mentioned above, revealed that financial burden is among the most influential factors affecting the experiences of students with disabilities in UK universities. This burden is exacerbated by the limited opportunities students with disabilities have to get a part time job during their studies. The students who participated in this study also mentioned challenges in applying for financial support, which they found to be a complex and time consuming process.

Likewise, in the study exploring the experiences of students with visual impairment in Ghana (Odame *et al.*, 2021), the participants stated that although the government provides financial support for people with disabilities, these funds are insufficient compared to the cost of living and their needs for accessible learning materials (e.g. braille sheets and equipment) for which they have to pay themselves. Some participants mentioned that they could not always afford the necessary resources to study, which hindered their academic progress (Odame *et al.*, 2021).

Abrahams *et al.*, (2023) also reported interesting findings in relation to financial support, in their study on the experiences of students with disabilities in three African countries (Ghana, Ethiopia, and South Africa). Although participating students revealed high satisfaction with the financial support provided from their government in the form of scholarships and university stipends, they stated that they are still in need of additional financial support that goes beyond tuition fees, for example, financial resources to cover the costs of extra-curricular activities that can enable them to participate more fully in university life (Abrahams *et al.*, 2023).

2.6.3 Attitudinal Factors

Finkelstein (1993, 1996, 2001) Oliver (1990, 1999, 2013) and Allan (2008, 2013) have argued that misconceptions and stereotypes about people with disabilities lead to prejudice and discrimination. They consider negative attitudes to be one of the most significant and persistent barriers to the inclusion of people with disabilities. The literature reviewed for this study concurs with this. Previous research indicates that the experiences of students with disabilities in university are not only affected by the quality of physical and academic resources. They are also influenced by attitudes that university staff and their peer group have towards people with disabilities. Positive attitudes have been found to be one of the most significant factors in promoting

inclusion in universities (eg Edna, 2016; McKinney and Swartz, 2022; Hector, 2020; Abrahams *et al.*, 2023). For example, positive attitudes can motivate staff to be supportive and diligent in adapting strategies and methods to meet the needs of students with disabilities (Moriña, Sandoval and Carnerero, 2020). On the other hand, negative attitudes can be detrimental to the students' wellbeing and academic success (Moriña and Orozco, 2021). Arguably, the quality of interactions between students with disabilities and their peers and staff is at least as important for the inclusion of students with disabilities in higher education as architecture or accessibility of resources.

Many students with disabilities who have participated in research on inclusion in higher education have reported that they have experienced prejudice, stereotyping and negative attitudes because of their disability so much so that they prefer not to disclose it, if possible, for fear that they will be stigmatised and discriminated (McKinney and Swartz, 2022; Anderson, Stephenson, and Carter, 2017; Moriña, 2017).

In a study of the experiences of students with disabilities in an American university (Yssel, Pack and Beilke, 2016), the participants reported that although some academic staff were supportive and had positive attitudes towards students with disabilities, others were distant or acted in ways that suggested doubt about these students' capacity for study at this level, for example they seemed to have lower expectations of them. This finding was corroborated in a later study in Spain (Moriña and Orozco, 2021). Some of the academic staff who participated in this study confessed that sometimes they do not believe in the abilities of students with disabilities, and admitted that this can create an unpleasant situation inside the class.

Negative attitudes were also reported in a study conducted in an American university (Francis *et al.*, 2019). Some of the students with disabilities who participated in this

study reported that they felt disempowered as a result of being doubted by academic staff who did not believe they had disabilities and attributed their challenges to not trying hard enough or not paying attention in class. Similar experiences were reported by students with disabilities in the study by Osborne (2019). The participants mentioned that teachers did not always believe what students with disabilities said. According to these students, some staff seemed to think that students with disabilities were being lazy or faking it (especially those with invisible disabilities) or wanted to take advantage of their circumstances to gain empathy.

Some of the academic staff who participated in the study by Moriña and Orozko (2021) argued that the source of negative attitudes towards students with disabilities is the medical view of disability which is still held by many. Some of the students with disabilities, who participated in this study (Moriña and Orozko, 2021), seemed to be aware of this and expressed their frustration with societal stereotypes and the perception that their disabilities were merely a medical issue that needed to be cured and fixed. This was a particular area of concern for the future, as students with disabilities were apprehensive regarding any future similar challenges that would limit their occupational opportunities and their chances in the workplace. Research findings about the attitudes of students without disabilities are mixed. A number of studies have shown that students without disabilities hold positive attitudes toward their peers with disabilities and offer them their support. For example, in a study examining the attitudes of different higher education stakeholders towards students with disabilities in Spain (Polo Sánchez, Fernández-Jiménez, and Cabezas, 2018) it was found that university students without disabilities held positive attitudes towards their peers with disabilities, considering them intelligent and capable people, and acknowledging their right to education and full participation in society. In contrast, students with visual

impairment who participated in a study about their experiences in Turkish universities reported that some of their peers appeared biased towards them and seemed reluctant to involve them in group work, possibly because they were unsure of how to communicate with them (Firat, 2021).

Studies have shown that, sometimes, students with disabilities are apprehensive of their peers. For example, Kendall (2016) has found that students with disabilities are often reluctant to disclose their disabilities due to fear of being treated differently or stigmatized by their peers. Similarly, Majoko (2018) reported that some students with disabilities feel that their peers perceive them as '*deviating from the norm*'. Research indicates that these concerns are not unsubstantiated. According to the academic staff who participated in Moraña and Orozco's (2021) study in the Spanish context, peers' reluctance to collaborate can be a major challenge for the students with disabilities. The participants reported that they have noticed peers exhibiting lack of empathy and refusing to work with students with disabilities, leading the students with disabilities to feel marginalised. However, the same study also revealed that positive relationships existed between students with disabilities and some of their peers without disabilities. The solidarity and empathy shown by these peers contributed to the resilience and academic achievement of the students with disabilities.

2.7 Chapter Summary

This chapter discussed the concept of disability, through a consideration of the various models that have been used over the years to map its evolution. It traced the evolution of conceptualisations of disability back to the religious/moral model, which viewed disability as divine punishment inflicted on the individual and their family as retribution for sin. It noted the emergence of the medical model, which viewed disability as a

defect within the individual rendering them as inferior and in need of fixing by medical professionals. It reviewed the social model, which rejected the conceptualisation of disability as deficiency and redefined it as something that is caused by barriers in society that prevent people with impairments from social participation and living independently. While acknowledging the significance of the social model in highlighting the consequences of an ableist society, it was also noted that this model has been critiqued for downplaying the impact of impairment on individuals and for treating the 'disabled' as a homogenous group, and for ignoring individual differences and the role of intersectionality in the experience of disability. The chapter then considered efforts to move beyond the rather simplistic account of disability provided by the social model. Such efforts include: the biopsychosocial model, which defined disability as an interaction between biological, psychological, and socio-environmental factors; the human rights model which emphasises that people with disabilities have the same rights as people without disabilities; and the neurodiversity model, which sees disability as variation in human functioning.

The chapter then moved on to discuss inclusive education, tracing its development from integration, which opened mainstream schools to children with disabilities but expected them to fit in the existing structures, to inclusion, which highlighted the importance of restructuring the physical and social environment to ensure their presence, acceptance participation and achievement. The chapter then considered the development of inclusive education in the Arab region, concluding that it is still in the integration stage as, despite governmental endorsement of the Salamanca statement, the opening of mainstream schools to children with disabilities has not been accompanied by restructuring of these schools to accommodate their needs.

When moving the focus to higher education, it was noted that, while the right of people with disabilities to participate in post-secondary education has been recognised and affirmed through a raft of international treaties and conventions, a large body of research from around the world has identified persistent barriers that limit the opportunities of university students with disabilities and stifle their right to higher education. Drawing on Oliver's (1990, 1999, 2013), Finkelstein's (1993, 1996, 2001) and Allen's (2008, 2013) classification of barriers to inclusion, the barriers to full participation in higher education identified in the international literature have been grouped as environmental, structural and attitudinal and have been discussed along these lines.

Chapter 3: Methodology and Research Design

3.1 Introduction

As noted in chapter 1, this study sought to understand the lived experiences of students with disabilities and the processes used by disability support staff to facilitate their inclusion in one Algerian university. Chapter 1 also indicated that research in the area of inclusive higher education in Algeria and the support provided for students with disabilities is scarce. Thus, this research presents a unique and valuable opportunity to contribute to the Algerian context by examining the lived experiences of students with disabilities and the processes used by disability support staff to facilitate their inclusion in one Algerian university. This research distinguishes itself from the very small number of relevant studies conducted in Algeria, by taking a comprehensive approach that includes the perspectives of both students and disability support staff. It is also important to highlight that this research goes beyond the scope and depth of those studies. By employing an Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA) approach and drawing on Bronfenbrenner's (1989) ecological systems theory, this research aimed to delve deeper into the experiences, challenges, and support systems surrounding the inclusion of students with disabilities in the Algerian higher education context. This chapter offers a comprehensive overview of the study's approach, encompassing the philosophical underpinnings that shaped the research, the chosen methodology, the sample, the tools employed for data collection, and the method utilized for data analysis. All of these elements worked together to address the research questions and aims.

3.2 Philosophical Assumptions and research paradigm

Research is a systematic way through which researchers can gather and analyse data in order to understand a specific phenomenon (Bryman and Bell, 2016). In addition, through research, researchers can contribute to the development of knowledge about a particular field (Merriam and Tisdell, 2016). Researchers work within a process that is guided by a structure that includes a set of principles and procedures to be followed, which are the philosophical framework, paradigms, methods, and research tools (Bryman and Bell, 2016). In this section, I will talk about and justify the philosophical assumptions and the paradigm underpinning the current research. In addition, I will outline the research design and methodology that I used to conduct this study.

Creswell and Creswell (2018) argue that, whether intentionally or unintentionally, researchers always incorporate some philosophical dimensions and assumptions into their research. These assumptions, which are informed by the researcher's worldview, values and beliefs about what reality is and how it can be understood, inform the framing of the phenomenon being investigated, the questions being asked, the way data are collected and analysed, and the conclusions drawn. These assumptions can be summarised under a set of paradigms that researchers use to frame their investigation (Creswell and Creswell, 2018). All paradigms are known to have their unique ontology and epistemology. According to Creswell and Poth (2018) and Leavy (2017), ontology refers to the nature of reality and its characteristics, whereas epistemology refers to the relation between the researcher and reality, what can be known about reality and how such knowledge can be obtained. To put it simply, ontology refers to what reality is and epistemology refers to how this reality can be explored and understood.

A research paradigm consists of all the principles and values that guide researchers in their understanding and perception of the world and reality (Cohen, Manion, and Morrison, 2018). Therefore, a paradigm is considered as an abstract through which researchers examine sampling, data collection and analysis methods to identify those that are aligned with their worldview, values and beliefs.

There are different types of paradigms that social science researchers can adopt in their studies (Leavy, 2017). In the current study, I aimed to explore the lived experiences of students with disabilities and the processes used by disability support staff to facilitate their inclusion in one Algerian university in order to understand inclusion for students with disabilities in Algerian higher education. Since my intention was to focus on the subjective realities of the participants, and to understand how these realities are shaped by interactions within the contexts they find themselves, I adopted a constructivist-interpretative paradigm (Creswell and Poth, 2018). This research paradigm has been deemed to be the most suitable paradigm for the current study because I intended to understand the phenomenon through the eyes of participants who have first-hand experience of it, and to give the participants voice to explain how they make sense of this phenomenon (Cohen, Manion, Morrison, 2018). Given this focus, the constructivist- interpretative paradigm seemed an appropriate and well-suited approach to use. The research is aligned with the constructivist-interpretative paradigm (Cohen, Manion, and Morrison, 2018; Merriam and Tisdell, 2016), since it focuses on subjective and socially constructed realities and interactions (constructivist ontology) and assumes that individuals can experience the same phenomenon differently. Therefore, for a better understanding of the phenomenon, I had to draw on the multiple interpretations of it from different participants (interpretative epistemology).

Researchers using a constructivist-interpretative paradigm tend to construct knowledge based on participants' experiences and perceptions of a certain phenomenon (in this case inclusion for students with disabilities in Algerian higher education). As I was interested in investigating the experiences and perceptions of students with disabilities and disability support staff in relation to inclusion for students with disabilities in one Algerian university, and in understanding how these experiences and perceptions have been formed, the constructivist-interpretative paradigm approach fits well with my own worldview and with what I intended to do. I aimed to understand the different realities that exist in the world of the participants and how these realities have been shaped by different context- and time- specific experiences. Through my interpretation of what the participants shared with me, I aimed to construct knowledge about the phenomenon that is the focus of my study (Creswell and Poth, 2018). In line with the constructivist- interpretative paradigm, I believe that participants' interactions with the same context (in this case the university they attend or work for) are likely to be different because contexts have many features which are combined in unique ways to shape individual experiences. The constructivist-interpretative paradigm allowed me to recognize multiple realities, meanings and interpretations of the same phenomenon (Cohen, Manion, and Morrison, 2018; Merriam and Tisdell, 2016).

3.3 Research Design

3.3.1 Research Questions and Aims

As noted in Chapter 1, the research questions and aims that guided the study were shaped by my personal interest in the topic and by the realisation that the topic has received scant attention in the Algerian context.

The study set out to address the following research questions:

1. What are the lived experiences of students with disabilities in Algerian higher education?
2. How do disability support staff facilitate the inclusion of students with disabilities in Algerian higher education?

The study had the following aims:

- To explore and understand the lived experiences of students with disabilities in Algerian higher education, including factors that facilitate and hinder their participation and achievement.
- To identify the needs of students with disabilities in Algerian higher education and convey their recommendations for improving their overall experience and academic success.
- To understand the processes used by disability support staff to facilitate the inclusion of students with disabilities in Algerian higher education, and the factors that affect their efforts.
- To investigate the effectiveness of existing support services and accommodations provided by Algerian higher education institutions and identify areas for improvement to better meet the needs of students with disabilities.

The study adopted a qualitative research approach, and specifically employed IPA. This design was chosen as it fits with the nature of the research, which is the lived experiences of students with disabilities and the processes used by disability support staff to facilitate their inclusion in an Algerian university. The following sections will discuss the rationale behind selecting IPA as a suitable methodology for this study and will outline the implementation of my research plan.

3.3.2 Qualitative Approach

Qualitative studies are often conducted by researchers who want to know about the experiences of certain individuals or groups (Creswell and Poth, 2018). Qualitative inquiries tend to focus on the narratives of participants, and are interested in identifying interactions, beliefs, understandings, and perceptions in relation to a social phenomenon. Cohen, Manion, and Morrison (2018) argue that qualitative research draws attention to the different meanings and understandings generated by and gathered from different participants. It is frequently used to gain in-depth knowledge about a phenomenon or an issue from a small sample (Creswell and Poth, 2018; Leavy, 2017). Researchers conduct a qualitative study when the objective is to explore, describe, and explain (Leavy, 2017). Creswell and Poth (2018) add that qualitative design prioritizes experiences and perceptions that participants have in relation to the issue being investigated, and focuses on how the context and its features influence and shape those experiences and perceptions.

Adopting a qualitative approach seemed appropriate since the study's aim was not to understand the phenomenon in terms of numbers, for example how many students with disabilities are registered in Algerian universities, how many staff are employed in each university to support these students, or how much each university spends on resources that aim to facilitate the participation of students with disabilities in their studies. Given my constructivist ontology and interpretative epistemology, my aim was to understand how the phenomenon is experienced by those who live it. Through this investigation, I intended to go beyond what is quantifiable and measurable, for example how many different resources might be available to students with disabilities in different universities, to understand what cannot be quantified but, in line with my

worldview, I believe to be valuable, for example how these resources are perceived and experienced by the participants. Additionally, a qualitative study would allow the participants to share their realities, stories, and experiences in depth and detail, therefore, it was considered to be a good fit for the study, and a close match to my worldview and the aims I had set for my study.

3.3.3 Phenomenological approach

In the present study, I chose to employ a phenomenological approach. According to Vagle (2018), phenomenological research aims to understand individuals' or groups' lived experiences of a phenomenon through listening and analysing their accounts of these experiences. In this study, I aimed to understand the lived experiences of the participants from their perspective. Consequently, a qualitative phenomenological approach has been deemed to be suitable, because it enables the researcher to understand the phenomenon being studied through the eyes of those who experience it (Creswell and Poth, 2018; Denscombe, 2021; Smith, Flowers and Larkin, 2009).

I aimed to provide descriptions and interpretations of how students with disabilities experience university life, and how disability support staff assist them to achieve their goal. The study was interested in how these experiences are constructed by the participants through their interactions with multiple layers of their shared environment (Creswell and Poth, 2018). I regard my participants as agents, who construct understandings about the world they live in through their daily interactions and engagements (Denscombe, 2021).

Denscombe (2021) argues that phenomenology has many advantages, including:

- It is a way to gain in-depth and detailed accounts and data.

- It goes beyond the surface and allows researchers to deal with phenomena that are more complex.
- It is a “humanistic approach”, since it builds connections between the researcher and the participants and focuses on unquantifiable aspects of human experience such as perceptions, feelings and emotions.
- It allows researchers to gather stories and experiences as they are lived by the participants and permits them to present those stories in accessible and interesting ways to different readers.

3.3.4 Interpretative stance

There are two main types of phenomenology; the first is descriptive phenomenology and the other is interpretative/hermeneutic phenomenology (Vagle, 2018; Creswell and Poth, 2018).

Descriptive phenomenology was developed and introduced by Edmund Husserl (1859-1939), who is considered as the founding father of descriptive phenomenological philosophy (Vagle, 2018, Creswell and Poth, 2018; Smith, Flowers and Larkin, 2009; Wojnar and Swanson, 2007). This phenomenological approach is interested in describing how a phenomenon is perceived from the inside by those who experience it, through the identification of commonalities across the accounts of the participants. These commonalities point to the general features of the phenomenon and, ultimately, to its essence (Vagle, 2018; Smith, Flowers and Larkin, 2009). In order to ensure that the description of the phenomenon is based exclusively on the participants' accounts, researchers who employ the descriptive phenomenological approach engage in bracketing (Creswell and Poth, 2018; Vagle, 2018; Smith, Flowers and Larkin, 2009). That is, researchers suspend and put aside their pre-conceptions

and pre-knowledge about the phenomenon so that they can be fully open to it and approach it with fresh eyes (Vagle, 2018).

Interpretative phenomenology, led by Heidegger, Merleau-Ponty and Sartre, was first introduced as a reaction against some of Husserl's principles of descriptive phenomenology (Vagle, 2018; Smith, Flowers and Larkin, 2009). While the aim of descriptive phenomenology is to get to the essence of a phenomenon by describing its general features as revealed by those who have experienced it, in interpretative phenomenology the researcher focuses on the lived experiences of those who are directly involved in the phenomenon and on their interpretations of these experiences. Interpretative phenomenologists acknowledge that each participant's lived experience will be unique and their main focus is on "how a particular phenomenon has been understood from the perspective of particular people, in a particular context" (Creswell, 2014, p. 82). That is, interpretative phenomenology is a move from the description of a phenomenon based on commonalities identified through the participants' accounts of it, to deriving understanding through analysis, explanation and interpretation of the participants' accounts treating each one as unique (Vagle, 2018; Smith, Flowers and Larkin, 2009). As Vagle (2018, p. 17) argues, 'understanding the phenomenon is an act of ongoing interpretation'.

IPA was developed by Jonathan Smith in the mid 1990s as a distinct approach to qualitative research in the context of health psychology (Smith, 1996). Since then, it has been developed further and has been used in various fields. IPA has been defined as "a qualitative research approach committed to the examination of how people make sense of their major life experiences" (Smith, Flowers and Larkin., 2009, p.1). In recent years, IPA has been used frequently to good effect by researchers in the social sciences. IPA is committed to recognizing the uniqueness of individuals' lived

experiences of the same phenomenon rather than seeking the essence of the phenomenon through the identification of common features from across the participants' accounts as is the case in descriptive phenomenology. Findings in an IPA study are co-created from participants' interpretations of their experiences and researchers' interpretation of the participants' interpretations of their experiences (Vagle, 2018; Smith, Flowers and Larkin, 2009). It is through analysing their interpretation of the participants' interpretation of their experiences, that IPA researchers come to an understanding of the phenomenon being studied. This is known as the double hermeneutic approach, which means that "the participant is trying to make sense of their personal and social world; the researcher is trying to make sense of the participant trying to make sense of their personal and social world" (Smith, 2004, p. 40).

As suggested above, IPA is 'hermeneutic' in that it involves the researcher in creating meanings and understandings from the participants' accounts of the phenomenon being studied, in the way biblical scholars interpret biblical manuscripts or scholars of literature interpret poems or works of fiction (Vagle, 2018; Smith, Flowers and Larkin, 2009). Hermeneutics, which comes from the Greek word "ἑρμηνεία", meaning "interpretation", focuses on how meaning can be created across different levels, suggesting that in order to interpret and understand certain parts or aspects of a phenomenon, one needs to pay attention to the whole and vice versa (Smith, Flowers and Larkin, 2009). This creates what is known as the hermeneutic circle, which was developed by Heidegger and Gadamer (Vagle, 2018). In the hermeneutic circle, interpretation is a continuing process, which functions across several levels within the part-whole relationship (Vagle, 2018; Smith, Flowers and Larkin, 2009). As Hansen (2011, p. 44) has explained 'the hermeneutic circle means that we do not simply

acquire knowledge, but rather that knowledge is always a process of looking at concrete details in light of larger ideas, and then re-contextualizing those larger ideas based upon an understanding of those details. In other words, knowledge is never complete: it is a constant process of re-interpretation'.

As noted above, the active involvement of IPA researchers in meaning making is known as "double hermeneutics" (Smith, Flowers and Larkin, 2009). When employing double hermeneutics, meaning is co-constructed between the participant and the researcher as the participant creates meaning through reflecting on and interpreting experiences of relevance to the phenomenon being studied while the researcher actively develops this meaning through interpreting the participants' interpretation. In other words, as an IPA researcher, I interpret what has already been interpreted by my participants. The understanding of the phenomenon reported at the end of the study is an integration of the participants' meaning and the researcher's meaning; this integrated meaning is the outcome of double interpretation or double hermeneutics.

The above suggests that two conceptual systems are in operation in IPA: the researcher's conceptual system, which includes the pre-knowledge, and pre-conceptions with which they approach the phenomenon being studied, and the participants' system of concepts that they use to make sense of the phenomenon as they experience it (Chirkov, 2016). In descriptive phenomenological research, I am expected to put aside (bracket) my pre-knowledge and pre-conceptions so that I can be fully open to the phenomenon and the participants' accounts of it. IPA researchers have moved away from the idea of bracketing. This is because, according to Dahlberg (2006), researchers cannot fully exclude former experiences and the pre-understandings they already have about a specific phenomenon; they instead need to

acknowledge their pre-existing knowledge, assumptions and biases and keep them in check. According to Vagle (2018) and Dahlberg (2006), this is referred to as “bridling”.

Bridling, Dahlberg (2006) argues, involves me, the researcher, acknowledging my assumptions and recognizing that it is not possible to suspend all my prior knowledge and beliefs. This recognition helps me engage in ongoing reflection about the potential influence my pre-understandings may have on my interpretations of the phenomenon I am studying. Bridling then can be understood as the effort to keep the researcher’s assumptions and preconceptions in check (the way the bridle keeps a horse in check) by continuously reflecting on them throughout the research process (Dahlberg, 2006). According to Dahlberg (2006), bridling also has another role: it helps the researcher not only to keep their pre-understandings in check but also to refrain (during the research process) from arriving at an understanding of the phenomenon being studied too quickly, without having given the interpretations of the phenomenon provided by the participants sufficient attention and consideration (Dahlberg and Dahlberg, 2003).

IPA researchers are interested in the unique, subjective accounts and perceptions of individuals experiencing a certain phenomenon (Smith, Flowers and Larkin, 2009). This is referred to as “idiographic sensibility” (Smith, Flowers and Larkin, 2009). Idiography comes from the Greek words “ιδιος” and “γραφη”, which, taken together, mean the study of the particular. IPA focuses more on individual cases and aims to go deeper and gather thorough details and understandings from a single case, before moving to another (Smith, Flowers and Larkin, 2009). In other words, in an IPA study each participant and their experiences are represented and analysed in an idiographic manner, prior to any steps towards comparing participants’ accounts (Smith, Flowers and Larkin, 2009). The adoption of an idiographic stance seemed appropriate in this

study, as it would help to appreciate the uniqueness of the experiences of each participant.

Based on the above arguments, I concluded that IPA was a suitable approach to use in my research. This is because descriptive phenomenology is interested in investigating general attributes and common points of people's experiences in relation to a certain problem or phenomenon, while IPA is more concerned with in depth interpretations of individual experiences (Smith, Flowers and Larkin, 2009; Vagle, 2018). I adopted IPA because I was seeking rich interpretations of the lived experiences of students with disabilities in higher education in Algeria and of the perspectives of disability support staff, to understand their unique experiences before comparing, contrasting and synthesising insights across all cases. Incorporating the voices of disability support staff in addition to those of students with disabilities was important as it allowed me to consider the phenomenon being studied from different angles and this helped me to identify complementary and contrasting themes, thus understanding the phenomenon more fully.

3.3.5 Limitations of IPA methodology

While, as outlined above, IPA has been shown to be a particularly useful methodology for understanding subjective experiences, it does have limitations and weaknesses which should be acknowledged. The following section outlines the main critiques that have been directed towards this methodology.

According to Tuffour (2017), it is questionable whether lived experiences and their meanings can be captured fully by IPA. IPA seeks to understand experiences from the viewpoint of those who have lived them (Smith, Flowers and Larkin, 2009). Language is central in IPA because it is the means through which experiences are

communicated. Critics have argued that the extent to which IPA can capture the richness and depth of experience depends on the capacity of the participant to effectively communicate intricate thoughts and feelings, and on the capacity of the interviewer to understand what the participants are communicating (Tuffour, 2017; Noon, 2018). There can be situations where it is not possible to express fully the complex aspects of an experience, especially when participants are not used to talking in such a manner about themselves and their lived experiences, or in cases where they do not have the fluency to do so (Willig, 2013; Tuffour, 2017; Noon, 2018). Consequently, interview transcripts may contain fewer details, which can make it difficult for researchers to gain rich and deep insights into the experiential worlds of the participants (Noon, 2018). It is important that IPA researchers are mindful of this and attempt to mitigate this limitation by paying attention to non verbal cues and by rephrasing and asking follow up questions to facilitate fuller responses (Tuffour, 2017). IPA studies tend to use small, and purposefully selected samples (Smith, Flowers and Larkin, 2009). This is perceived as another limitations of IPA because it means that findings cannot be applied to other contexts (Charlick *et al*, 2016). According to Smith, Flowers and Larkin (2009), the objective of IPA researchers is to explore the perceptions and understandings of a specific group within their particular setting, rather than seeking to generalise across different groups and settings. Having a small sample size allows for a more thorough and deeper analysis that might be compromised with a larger sample. Therefore, IPA researchers opt for depth and detail rather than generalisability of findings. One way to address this limitation is by conducting further research which can provide additional insights into the topic (Noon, 2018).

Another criticism of IPA is that it is descriptive rather than explanatory because it captures participants' perceptions of a phenomenon but cannot explain why the phenomenon is as it is (Willig, 2013; Tuffour, 2017). Arguably, an element of explanation can be achieved towards the end of the analysis process, when researchers look for convergences and divergences across cases. However, for fuller explanations, IPA researchers need to refer to the literature. This was the case in my research, where, after conducting an inductive analysis of participants' data across cases, I turned to the literature for explanatory insights. This is discussed later in this chapter, in the section entitled 'Theoretical Framework'.

A final criticism is that, as IPA studies frequently engage with personal experiences, IPA has the potential to evoke intense emotions in the participants and this can pose ethical challenges (Noon, 2018). However, a robust ethics protocol can help address these challenges. Later in this chapter, in the ethics section I will discuss how I addressed ethical challenges in my study.

3.3.6 Sampling

Sampling in qualitative research is defined as the process of selection of specific participants from whom the researcher can collect data that is relevant to the topic being investigated (Creswell and Poth, 2018). Researchers conducting qualitative research tend to use non-probability sampling in order to choose purposefully individuals who have particular characteristics and are in a position to give information about an event, situation or issue they have experienced (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018).

Data in this IPA study were collected from a purposefully selected sample who study or work at one university in Algeria. Cohen, Manion and Morrison (2018) argue that purposeful sampling is one of the characteristics of a qualitative inquiry; researchers

select a sample of participants who have experience of the phenomenon being investigated. Although purposeful sampling cannot provide breadth of information about a certain phenomenon, it can provide in depth, rich knowledge (Creswell and Poth, 2018). Findings arising from data collected from a purposefully selected sample are not representative of a wide population and cannot be generalised (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018). However, this is not considered an issue for qualitative researchers, as they are more interested in digging deep and gathering detailed information from individuals who have an experience of a certain phenomenon and as such are in a position to provide the needed information (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018).

In this study, I recruited students with disabilities and disability support staff from one Algerian university. As noted in Chapter 1, I chose this university because it had been involved in the TEMPUS programme (Miłosz, Milosz and Grzegórski, 2016), which aimed to promote inclusive education in North African universities. The decision to recruit participants from two groups was made in order to understand the phenomenon from different angles (Smith, Flowers and Larkin, 2009). I utilized a combination of purposive sampling and snowball sampling. While I acknowledge that snowball sampling may introduce bias as initial participants may refer their friends, potentially influencing the study's findings, the benefit of having more participants seemed to outweigh this risk. The process I followed to recruit my participants is outlined below. After obtaining ethical approval from the Ethics Committee of the School of Education and Social Sciences at UWS (see appendix 2), I emailed the Foreign Affairs Office of the Rectorate in the university where I intended to recruit participants providing them with detailed information about my study, including invitation letters, participant information sheets and consent forms (see appendices 4 to 8). The Foreign Affairs

Office gave me permission and forwarded my email to the Disability Support Office coordinator to negotiate access (see appendix 1). The Disability Support Office responded favourably to my request and facilitated the recruitment process by forwarding the invitations and participant information sheets to the disability support staff and registered students with disabilities. This resulted in four disability support staff expressing interest in participating in my study. However, only two students who received the email invitation via the Disability Support Office got in touch with me. When no further responses were received from students four weeks after the email invitation had been sent out, I asked the two students who had agreed to participate in the study to share my invitation with students with disabilities known to them. When participants in a study identify other potential participants, this is known as snowball sampling (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018). Snowball sampling resulted in the recruitment of ten more students. However, two students withdrew before the interview, and one participant withdrew after the interview, reducing the final sample size to nine students with disabilities and four disability support staff. Despite the small sample size, the data collected were rich and insightful. As Reid, Flowers and Larkin (2005, p. 22) report: 'IPA challenges the traditional linear relationship between number of participants and value of research'. Small sample size is one of the main features of an IPA guided study. Since IPA takes an idiographic stance, IPA researchers focus on each case separately and seek to elicit rich data from each participant's account before comparing and contrasting across accounts; consequently, it is better to choose a small sample. Although larger samples can be recruited, this can be more demanding during the analysis phase (Smith, Flowers and Larkin, 2009).

3.3.6.1 Participants

In this study, my intention was to give voice to students with disabilities and disability support staff to share their experiences in relation to inclusion for students with disabilities in their university. I interviewed nine students with disabilities and four disability support officers. This number allowed me to remain faithful to the ideographic feature of IPA, which requires analysing each case on its own in order to elicit particular and unique perceptions and viewpoints from the participants. The use of a small sample size allowed me to analyse each case in depth to understand the experiences of each participant, rather than relying on aggregated data. This ensured that the unique viewpoints of each participant received the attention and analysis they deserved (Smith, Flowers and Larkin, 2009).

The students with disabilities who participated in this study were from different levels and departments in the university. Additionally, the study included disability support officers, who work in the same university, and, in addition to their role as disability support officers, have experience in teaching students with disabilities. Participants in this study share a number of characteristics including nationality, and experience as students with disabilities or disability support officers in the same university. However, this does not mean that they share the same experience in relation to support provision and inclusive education. The students with disabilities who participated in this study differ in type of disability, additional support requirements, as well as educational experiences. Similarly, the disability support staff differ in terms of subject expertise and length of service.

3.3.7 Data Collection

Data collection is considered one of the most important phases in any investigation (Bryman and Bell, 2016). Therefore, deciding upon suitable research instruments and

methods to collect data for a research project is as important as choosing the right methodology that fits well with the study's aims (Cohen, Manion, and Morrison, 2018). Additionally, Cohen, Manion and Morrison (2018, p. 469) argue that choosing a research instrument 'is not a matter of preference, arbitrary or automatic decision making'. Rather, it is a matter of justification, relevance, and consideration of the extent to which this instrument can enable the researcher to achieve the aims of the study. The current study used interviews to collect qualitative data.

My aim was to collect in-depth data about the lived experiences of students with disabilities and the processes used by disability support staff to facilitate their inclusion in one Algerian university. Given my focus on the individual experiences of the participants (idiographic stance), I considered that the best way to collect data was through listening to individual students with disabilities and disability support staff talk about, reflect on and interpret their lived experiences of inclusion (students) and the processes they use to facilitate inclusion for these students (staff).

Eliciting rich accounts of experiences in relation to a certain phenomenon through individual interviews is one of the main features of IPA (Creswell and Poth, 2018; Smith, Flowers and Larkin, 2009). As Reid, Flowers and Larkin (2005, p.22) point out: 'One-to-one interviews [...] are easily managed; allow rapport to be developed; allow participants to think, speak and be heard; and are well suited to in-depth and personal discussion.'

Generally speaking, interviews are seen as a conversation between two or more persons, through which they actively interact with each other, and exchange opinions and insights related to a specific topic or issue (Cohen, Manion, and Morrison, 2018). The main objective of the interview is to achieve 'special kind of information' (Merriam

and Tisdell, 2016). That is, researchers use interviews when they seek to gather data that cannot be collected through observation or other methods (Merriam and Tisdell, 2016).

There are different types of interviews: structured, semi-structured, and unstructured (Cohen, Manion, and Morrison, 2018; Merriam and Tisdell, 2016). In this study, I used semi-structured interviews. The interview schedules for students with disabilities and disability support staff included similar questions, with slight differences according to the role of the interviewees (see Appendix 6 and 7). This allowed me to have a list of questions for each group of participants but be flexible and follow each participant's lead in terms of pursuing topics that may be particular to their experience. In other words, semi-structured interviews helped me to add, re-order, and omit questions during the interview in response to each interviewee's answers (Merriam and Tisdell, 2016). Noon (2018) also confirms that semi-structured interviews offer flexibility for the researcher to amend questions according to the participants' answers, and this can shift attention towards other interesting questions and points that might have been missed.

Regarding the nature of interviews, my plan was to conduct face-to-face interviews with my participants. However, it was not possible to do this due to factors beyond my control such as my inability to get back to Algeria due to the COVID 19 pandemic which took place during my doctoral studies. However, it is possible that, even if I was able to travel to Algeria, some participants may not have been able to meet me for face-to-face interviews potentially due to logistical issues such as lack of transportation or time constraints, or for personal reasons.

I started my data collection in the summer of 2020. I utilized online platforms such as Streamyard, Teams, and Zoom to conduct interviews with my participants (students with disabilities and disability support staff) who were in Algeria. Despite the challenges posed by the pandemic, conducting interviews online proved to be a feasible and convenient means of collecting data. Interestingly, some participants expressed a preference for online interviews over face-to-face interactions, highlighting their comfort with the virtual setting. Two students with disabilities specifically requested audio-only calls, as they believed that this would create a more comfortable environment for them. Respecting their preferences, I ensured that their comfort was prioritized during the interviews by providing the necessary support and accommodations. All other interviews were conducted via video calls.

3.3.8 Ethical consideration

Every research project should be guided by ethical principles (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018; Merriam and Tisdell, 2016). According to Denscombe (2021), social science research should:

‘protect the interests of the participants; ensure that participation is voluntary and based on informed consent; avoid deception and operate with scientific integrity; comply with the laws of the land’

(Denscombe, 2021. p. 33).

The British Educational Research Association (BERA) advises researchers to adhere to the association’s ethical guidelines to effectively address ethical considerations and concerns. These guidelines emphasize the importance of respecting ‘the privacy, autonomy, diversity, values, and dignity of individuals, groups, and communities’ (BERA, 2018, p. 4), when conducting social and educational research. The UWS guidelines for ethical research outline a number of principles that must be followed by UWS staff and students conducting research. These are:

“Honesty in the intentions of the work; in acknowledging the work of others; reporting all the findings; and in making valid interpretations and claims. Rigour in choosing and adhering to appropriate methods; in drawing conclusions; and in communicating the results. Transparency in declaring conflicts of interest; in reporting data collection methods; in the analysis and interpretation of data; and in making findings widely available, including to the general public. Respect and care for all participants in research and for the environment”

(UWS Ethics Committee, 2021, p. 3).

In the current study I took several steps to address ethical considerations and ensure that my research was informed by these principles. These steps are outlined below.

3.3.8.1 Prior to data collection

As part of ethical considerations, I took the necessary steps to obtain approval from the Ethics Committee of the School of Education and Social Sciences at UWS before contacting potential participants or initiating any data collection. I submitted a comprehensive application that included all relevant documents such as the participation information sheet, consent forms, interview schedules, and an official letter to the university where I intended to recruit participants (see appendices 1-8). Once I received permission from the Ethics Committee to begin my data collection, I sent the necessary documents to the Foreign Affairs Office of the Rectorate in the university where I intended to conduct my study, specifying that my research would involve students with disabilities and disability support officers. The Foreign Affairs Office gave me permission and then forwarded my request to the Disability Support Office. The Disability Support Office coordinator forwarded my invitation to the disability support staff and to the students with disabilities who were registered with the Disability Support Office at the time. As noted above, four disability support staff contacted me to express interest and eventually participated in the study. Although

only two students with disabilities got in touch with me after they had received my invitation through the Disability Support Office, these two students shared my invitation with other students with disabilities known to them and eventually, I was able to interview nine students.

3.3.8.2 Informed consent

During the data collection process, an important step was to provide information about myself, and an explanation of the study to potential participants. This was done through the participant information sheet, with follow up clarifications as needed. Before each interview, the participant was asked for informed consent. Informed consent is defined in the literature as the process of ensuring that the participants have made an informed decision whether to participate in a study or not, after knowing the aims and expected outcomes of the study (Cohen, Manion, and Morrison, 2018). As the researcher, it was my responsibility to ensure that participants had a comprehensive understanding of what their participation would involve, their rights, and the measures in place to maintain confidentiality. This was accomplished through transparent communication. By engaging in open and honest discussions, I aimed to provide participants with the necessary information to make informed decisions about their involvement in the study.

In terms of obtaining consent, it is important to note that all the participants in this study were adults who had the capacity to make their own decisions. Their involvement in the research was entirely voluntary and they had the right to withdraw from the study at any point until the analysis of the data commenced. As noted earlier, two student participants withdrew before an interview had been arranged and another student participant withdrew after the interview had been conducted. Both the recording and transcript of this interview were destroyed in accordance with the wishes of this

participant. It is worth mentioning that most participants displayed a strong willingness and intention to share their experiences with me. In fact, some of them went the extra mile by reaching out to me after the interviews to inquire if I needed any further assistance or additional information. This high level of engagement and collaboration from the participants resulted in the emergence of rich data. Their active participation greatly enriched the study and contributed valuable insights.

3.3.8.3 Confidentiality and anonymity

One of the key ethical considerations in this study pertained to ensuring anonymity, privacy, and confidentiality for the participants involved. I informed potential participants that their data would be treated with strict confidentiality. I explained that their identities would remain protected, and no details that could lead to their identification would appear in the transcripts of the interviews, in my thesis and in any other outputs arising from the research. I also assured them that their data would be used exclusively for the purpose of this research and would not be utilized for any other purposes.

During the interview process, I ensured that I clearly re-explained the aims and purpose of the study to the participants, what their participation would involve and their right to withdraw at any point until the analysis of the data commenced. Additionally, I emphasized that all data shared with me will be anonymized and kept confidential. To protect their identities, I replaced the participants' real names with Student A, Student B, Student C...etc for students with disabilities, and Disability Support Officer A, Disability Support Officer B....etc for disability support officers. While I have referred to participants as 'she' or 'he' in the findings chapter, thus revealing their gender, I have not provided any other details such as type of disability or level and programme of study for students and length of service or specialism for the disability support staff,

out of concern that such details could jeopardise the confidentiality I promised to the participants. My intention was to make my findings available to the university in the hope that they will stimulate reflection and action leading to improvements in the inclusion of students with disabilities. It was therefore particularly important to ensure that the participants could not be identified by anyone within the university who knows them.

To maintain privacy, several measures were implemented during the transcription and data handling process. The recorded interviews were transcribed, and the transcripts were anonymised. The only characteristic that could distinguish each transcript from the others was the code Student A, Student B, Student C...etc or Disability Support Officer A, Disability Support Officer B....etc that was added to each transcript. This ensured that any specific details that could potentially lead to the identification of the participants were deliberately omitted from the dataset (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018). By taking these precautions, I aimed to guarantee the privacy and confidentiality of each participant, safeguarding their sensitive information from any unintended disclosure.

Like any other cross-cultural research, it is important to note that the interviews were conducted in multiple languages, namely English, French, and Arabic, in accordance with the preferences expressed by the participants themselves. I am proficient in all three languages so after the transcription and anonymization, I translated the French and Arabic transcripts into English. As a way to check for accuracy, a few days after each translation, I translated the transcript back into the original language, French or Arabic, and compared the two versions for discrepancies. This process is known as back translation and is common in cross-cultural research (Brislin, 1970). A few minor

corrections were made as a result of this. Once all transcripts had been checked, I used them for the analysis.

3.3.9 Data Analysis

Researchers conducting qualitative inquiries tend to use different approaches to analyse their data (Sparkes and Smith, 2014). According to Merriam and Tisdell (2016), the process of data analysis can be the most daunting task in research. It is an operation through which investigators try to extract meanings and understandings from the gathered data. While analyzing the data, researchers need to describe, combine, compare, and interpret what participants have shared with them and reflect upon it. Analysis is the act of creating meaning from the data (Merriam and Tisdell, 2016). Flick (2014, p. 5) further defines the process of data analysis in qualitative research as 'the classification and interpretation of linguistic (or visual) material to make statements about implicit and explicit dimensions and structures of meaning-making in the material and what is represented in it'.

Generally, IPA investigations encompass two main connected features. The first one is referred to as 'the phenomenological requirement', that is giving voice to those experiencing a specific phenomenon and trying to understand it from their perspective. The second feature is 'the interpretative requirement', that is to reflect upon the experiences shared by the participants and draw new meanings from them (Sparkes and Smith, 2014). Researchers conducting IPA research follow certain steps in order to analyse the perceptions and attitudes of their participants towards the phenomenon they experience (Creswell and Poth, 2018; Sparkes and Smith, 2014; Smith, Flowers and Larkin, 2009). Following these steps can help researchers achieve their research goals (Pietkiewicz and Smith, 2012). IPA offers an iterative, recursive approach to data

analysis, as it helps researchers to go back and forth during the analysis process instead of following a linear pattern (Noon, 2018).

It should be noted that in 2022, Smith, Flowers and Larkin published the second edition of their book “Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis: Theory, Method and Research”. This book introduced novel terminology for the data analysis phase. As a member of the online IPA qualitative group (ipaqualitative) led by Jonathan Smith and Michael Larkin, I was keen to find out whether researchers who had already begun their analysis using the first edition should switch to the second. During the group discussions, Jonathan Smith advised that researchers who have already made substantial progress with their analysis could stick with the terminology used in the first edition. I also consulted with my supervisor, who recommended that I continue using the terminology of the first edition, as I had completed most of the analysis by that point.

Following the manual transcription of the recordings and translation from Arabic/French to English, I initially considered employing NVivo software for coding and analysis. However, I rejected this and opted for manual analysis using traditional tools such as pen, paper, and highlighters (Wagstaff et al, 2014). This enabled me to stay close to the data throughout the analysis process. Additionally, this approach provided me with greater flexibility while navigating each transcript, and later when I worked across transcripts to identify patterns. The following table outlines the steps that I followed to analyze my data according to Smith, Flowers and Larkin (2009).

Step	Process
Reading and Re-Reading	After a careful transcription of the interview recordings, I anonymized and organized each separately. I then used the back

	<p>translation method (Brislin, 1970) to check each transcript for accuracy. Once the necessary corrections were made, I listened to the recordings as I read and re-read carefully each transcript (Noon, 2018). This way I was able to grasp primary ideas and understandings about each case and to be as close as I could to the data. This helped me ensure that I did not miss any important information shared by my participants (Noon, 2018; Sparkes and Smith, 2014).</p>
Initial noting	<p>While reading the transcripts, I added comments and made notes at the margin of each transcript. Following Smith, Flowers and Larkin's (2009) recommendation, I made three types of comments: descriptive, which focused on what the participants said, linguistic, which focused on the participants' use of language and word choice, and conceptual, which captured ideas. I used different colors to highlight each type of comment. This step helped me reflect upon what I was reading, what the text was telling me about the participants' experiences and the meaning they gave to these experiences, and what my own thoughts were in response. Being reflective enabled me to move beyond mere description (Smith, Flowers and Larkin, 2009; Sparkes and Smith, 2014; Noon, 2018). This step was crucial, since it helped me to understand and interpret what my participants said, and it allowed concepts to emerge from their accounts (Noon, 2018).</p>

<p>Developing emergent themes</p>	<p>After thoroughly reading and annotating each transcript, I shifted my focus to the comments I had made rather than the transcript itself. I aimed to condense the data by identifying relationships and patterns within the notes and by transforming them into statements, known as emergent themes (Smith, Flowers and Larkin, 2009).</p>
<p>Searching for connections across emergent themes</p>	<p>In this stage, I arranged the themes in the order they emerged and analyzed their interconnections, grouping them into clusters and categories based on their relationships (Noon, 2018). It is important to note that while the wording of the themes was different from the participants' own expressions, I strived to ensure that, conceptually, the extracted themes were faithful to the original material (Noon, 2018; Smith, Flowers and Larkin, 2009).</p>
<p>Moving to the next case</p>	<p>During this step, I proceeded to work on the next transcript, applying the same procedures as before. To uphold the idiographic approach of the study and respect the uniqueness of each case, I analysed each transcript separately and independently, aiming 'to do justice to its own individuality' (Smith, Flowers and Larkin, 2009, p. 94). To ensure the integrity of the analysis for each new transcript and allow the emergence of fresh themes, I made a conscious effort to set aside any preconceived ideas or understandings from previous transcripts (Noon, 2018). This approach aimed to avoid influencing the</p>

	analysis process and allowed for the exploration of new and distinct themes in each case.
Looking for patterns across cases	During this stage, I engaged in a process of looking across all transcripts simultaneously, searching for connections and patterns. Themes across cases were identified and grouped under broader themes, referred to as super-ordinate themes by Smith, Flowers and Larkin (2009), while sub-themes were organized into what Smith, Flowers and Larkin (2009) call subordinate themes and placed under a conceptually related super-ordinate theme (Noon, 2018; Smith, Flowers and Larkin, 2009).

Table 1. Data Analysis steps in accordance with Smith, Flowers, and Larkin (2009)

The qualitative and interpretative nature of my research required deriving themes as suggested by the data shared by the participants, which is referred to as inductive process, rather than following a top down deductive approach (Pietkiewicz and Smith, 2012). This means that the analysis was guided by the data itself (Smith, Flowers and Larkin, 2009). I paid close attention to the raw data provided by my participants, and tried to immerse myself in their authentic experiences to understand their unique perspectives and views. This approach allows for a more nuanced and detailed understanding of the phenomenon being studied and brings to the surface insights that may not be possible to uncover otherwise (Smith and Osborn, 2007).

After a continuous inductive process of analysing the transcripts and identifying patterns following the hermeneutic circle from the part (individual cases) to the whole (all cases) and vice versa (Smith, Flowers and Larkin, 2009), I was able to arrive at a

set of super-ordinate and sub-ordinate themes that captured the lived experiences of the participants. As indicated by Smith, Flowers and Larkin (2009), at this point the researcher can draw on their own interpretative framework to illuminate what they have found. While keeping the insider perspectives that emerged from the data in mind, I allowed my focus to shift to the insights I had gained from the literature review but also to knowledge I have accumulated through my studies in the field of education. This led to the realisation that, similar to findings from previous studies focusing on university students with disabilities, the experiences of the participants in my study seemed to be influenced by forces that operate in their immediate environment but also by forces operating in more distant contexts. This suggested that Bronfenbrenner's ecological systems theory (1979, 1989) could be a useful framework to contextualise my findings. In the following section, I provide a brief overview of this theory and explain how it was used in my study.

3.4 Theoretical framework

Bronfenbrenner's ecological systems theory (1979) explains how individuals' development and experiences are influenced by factors operating in multiple contexts, some immediate and others distant. Factors operating at the individual's immediate context include interactions with others who are also present in this context, while factors operating at distant contexts include the influences of political, economic and educational systems, cultural values and attitudes, historical events and changes. Bronfenbrenner initially developed this theory in his book 'The Ecology of Human Development' which was published in 1979, but he continued refining and adding to the theory until his death in 2005 (Bronfenbrenner and Morris, 2006; Rosa and Tudge, 2013). This section provides a brief overview of the development trajectory of the

ecological systems theory, and a justification for the use of this theory in the current research.

3.4.1 Evolution of the ecological systems theory

According to Rosa and Tudge (2013), Bronfenbrenner's theory is developed over three distinct phases:

3.4.1.1 The first phase (1973–1979)

During this phase, Bronfenbrenner (1979) proposed the central tenet of his theory which is that human development occurs in an environment that is multilayered and could be perceived as a set of concentric circles. The individual is at the centre of these circles and is affected directly by interactions within the inner circle, which includes the individual, and indirectly by forces operating within the outer circles where the individual does not participate actively. According to the theory, as articulated in 'The Ecology of Human Development' (Bronfenbrenner, 1979), these circles represent four interconnected systems and are organized in a nested pattern, from the inner and closest to the individual to the outer and most distant. These interrelated systems are as follows:

Microsystem, which is concerned with the direct interactions between the individual and their immediate surroundings, and how these interactions influence the individual's development and experiences (Bronfenbrenner, 1979). Individuals are present in more than one microsystem, including family, education settings, and local community.

Mesosystem, which refers to the interactions between the various microsystems in which the individual is present (Bronfenbrenner, 1979). For a university student, this

would involve the interactions between home and university and would capture the influence of these interactions on the student's experiences. For example, if the family is supportive of the student's university studies, this would create a positive interaction between home and university and, ultimately, it will have a positive influence on the student.

Exosystem, which encompasses contexts, structures and settings that do not involve the individual directly but exert indirect influence on them. For university students, these would include government departments and policies that dictate how educational institutions should operate and what resources should be allocated to them.

Macrosystem, which captures the cultural context that surrounds and permeates the other systems (microsystem, mesosystem, exosystem). It refers to the attitudes, customs, traditions, values and beliefs that prevail in a society.

3.4.1.2 The second phase (1980–1993)

During this phase, Bronfenbrenner developed his theory in response to the criticism his first version received (Bronfenbrenner, 1989). The main criticism was that the theory focused only on the influences of the environment, suggesting that the individual is passive (Rosa and Tudge, 2013). In the updated version, Bronfenbrenner highlighted the role of individual characteristics in the interactions between individuals and people, objects and symbols within the microsystems in which they participate (Bronfenbrenner, 1989). He argued that development does not depend merely on environmental factors, but it is also affected by interactions between an individual's characteristics and the contexts in which they are situated (Bronfenbrenner, 1989).

Thus, individuals should not be regarded as passive agents, but as active agents who participate in their own development (Bronfenbrenner, 1989).

Additionally, during this phase Bronfenbrenner paid greater attention to the role of time and its importance in the process of development. As a result, a new system, the chronosystem, was added outside the macrosystem. The chronosystem captures events and shifts that occur over time and have an influence on the individual's experiences and development. It emphasizes the role of continuity and change in shaping development and experience (Bronfenbrenner, 1989).

3.4.1.3 The third phase (1993–2006)

During this phase, the theory was renamed the biological/bio-ecological/Process-Person-Context-time (PPCT) model of human development (Bronfenbrenner and Morris, 2006). Additionally, there was a shift of emphasis from the environmental effects on the development and experiences of an individual, to the biological characteristics of the individual and the role these characteristics play in the interactions the individual has with the environment (Bronfenbrenner and Morris, 2006). These interactions, which involve ongoing and sustained engagement with other individuals, objects, and symbols in the environment were referred to as proximal processes by Bronfenbrenner and were given central place in this version of his theory (Bronfenbrenner and Morris, 2006). As indicated by its updated name, the Process-Person-Context-time (PPCT) model of human development focuses more on the processes that connect a person with others in their immediate context over time (proximal processes), than on the influences the outer layers of the environment such as the exo- and macrosystem exert on the person.

While this shift in emphasis can be useful for researchers who are interested in studying these proximal processes, those who are interested in the bigger picture may find the earlier versions of the ecological systems theory more suitable for their purposes. In their discussion of the evolution of Bronfenbrenner's theory, Rosa and Tudge (2013) indicate that it is acceptable for researchers to use an earlier version of the theory as long as they state this explicitly. In the next section, I will explain why I used the second version of Bronfenbrenner's theory in my study.

3.4.2 Justification for using the second version of the ecological systems theory

When, as suggested by Smith, Flowers and Larkin (2009), I considered the findings from my study in the context of relevant literature, Bronfenbrenner's theory stood out as an appropriate theoretical framework because of its acknowledgement of the impact of multi-level environmental factors on the individual. My data analysis had indicated that the experiences of students with disabilities and the capacity of disability support officers to support them were affected by a range of factors operating at different levels. Some of these factors were present in the university microsystem but others were located in outer systems (mesosystem, ecosystem, macrosystem). While the final version of Bronfenbrenner's theory recognizes the influence of wider forces, its main focus is on proximal processes within the microsystem (Rosa and Tudge, 2013). Furthermore, the biological characteristics of the individual have been given much prominence in this version (Rosa and Tudge, 2013). However, the participants in my study did not refer to their biological characteristics during the interviews. Their focus was exclusively on environmental factors and on the impact of these on their experiences. This suggested that an earlier version would be a better fit with my findings. As will be seen in the next chapter, one of the findings was that there has not

been much progress in the development of inclusive education in Algeria, given that the challenges students with disabilities encounter at university are similar to those they experience in school. This suggested that time was an important feature. Consequently, the second version of Bronfenbrenner's theory, which includes the chronosystem, seemed an appropriate choice.

A further reason for choosing the ecological systems theory as updated during the second phase (from this point onwards simply referred to as 'ecological systems theory') is that the literature on inclusive education places considerable emphasis on the role of the environment in facilitating students' inclusion (Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler, 2014). While students' personal characteristics should be taken into consideration when accommodations and support are planned to ensure their full participation in education, in line with the social model of disability, the onus is on the educational environment to be proactively accessible to all students (Rieser, 2017). A focus on the environment highlights the need to consider factors that could create barriers for students with disabilities and actions that could be taken to address these factors. This can ensure that interactions between individual students and the environment are positive and that all students have equal chances to learn and succeed, regardless of their individual characteristics (Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler, 2014). With its main focus on the environment as a multilayered system that can exert direct but also indirect influence on an individual's development and experiences, the ecological systems theory seems to be a good fit for the study of inclusive education and, as such, an appropriate theoretical framework for this research.

3.4.3 Previous research employing the ecological systems theory as theoretical framework

The aim of the ecological systems theory is to determine the impact of the multilayered environment on individuals' development and experiences, and to understand the forces that are responsible for this impact within immediate and more distant contexts. According to Mahlo (2013) the ecological systems theory is widely used in inclusive education, because it highlights that students are part of a multifaceted ecological framework, which includes a wide range of factors and systems that impact their experiences and development. The ecological systems theory can be used as a useful device for identifying where the various forces that influence students' development and experiences are located, enabling researchers to make context specific recommendations for improvements (Mahlo, 2013).

Many researchers have used the ecological systems theory to understand better the experiences of students with disabilities and the concept of inclusion in higher education settings (Kitchen et al. 2019). In a longitudinal study, Hewett et al. (2017) investigated the experiences of 32 students with visual impairment in higher education in the UK using the ecological systems theory to frame their findings. Hewett et.al (2017) stated that this theory helped them to identify factors within these students' immediate and wider environment that affected their experiences, and to understand the layered impact of these factors. In another study that sought to understand the transition process of young people with disabilities to post-secondary institutions, Lindsay et.al (2018) also used the ecological systems theory to contextualise their findings. The authors found that the theory enabled them to develop a more comprehensive understanding of the various obstacles faced by these young people when transitioning to higher education, and the specific contexts where these

obstacles were situated. According to Lindsay et.al (2018), this approach facilitated their understanding of the numerous challenges that exist not only at the microsystem but also in broader societal and cultural contexts. It also enabled them to propose specific recommendations for each of these contexts, arguing that improvements at the microsystem must be complemented by changes at the wider contexts that exert an indirect but significant influence on the experiences of these young people. Similarly, in their synthesis of literature on the experiences of university students with disabilities, Kimball and Thoma (2019) highlighted the significance of the use of the ecological systems theory in providing a comprehensive understanding of the experiences of university students with disabilities, and in offering context specific implications and recommendations for research and practice.

To sum up, a number of previous studies have indicated that Bronfenbrenner's (1979, 1989) ecological systems theory is an appropriate framework for studying the experiences of university students with disabilities. Such studies have highlighted the value of this theory in illuminating the multilayered environmental influences that shape the university experiences of these students. This confirmed the suitability of the theory for use in my study as a lens through which to discuss my findings.

3.4.4 Application of the ecological systems theory in this study

Since my study employed an IPA design, which is regarded as a typical inductive approach (Smith, Flowers and Larkin, 2009), my aim was not to test a hypothesis based on a theory, but to generate direct insights from the participants' experiences. However, as noted by Smith, Flowers and Larkin (2009), this should not prevent researchers from incorporating a theory to contextualise their findings, and to link the study to the broader existing literature. The findings that emerged from this study

indicated that ecological systems theory could be useful in this respect. Despite the fact that participants did not use similar terminology and concepts to those of Bronfenbrenner, they were able to communicate how immediate and distal factors within the university environment and other broader contexts influenced their experiences and participation at university. To remain faithful to the IPA approach, in the following chapter I have presented the findings as they emerged from the data, using quotes from the participants to illustrate the various themes. In Chapter 5, I have used the ecological systems theory to contextualise the discussion of the findings, while in Chapter 6 the ecological systems theory has been used to frame the recommendations that have been made based on the findings.

3.5 Establishing Validity and Quality

To ensure validity and quality in qualitative research, researchers must adopt appropriate guidelines that align with their chosen research methodology. In this particular study, following the recommendation of Smith, Flowers and Larkin (2009) the guidelines outlined by Yardley (2000) were used. These guidelines are informed by four principles: sensitivity to context, commitment and rigor, transparency and coherence, impact and importance (Yardley, 2000). Below, I outline the measures that I took to ensure that my study abides by each principle.

3.5.1 Sensitivity to context

Yardley (2000) states that sensitivity to context can be shown through an extensive review of the existing research literature in the area being investigated. Doing this enabled me to familiarise myself with the factors that affect the experiences of university students with disabilities across different countries. It also helped me to identify Bronfenbrenner's (1989) ecological systems theory as a framework that could

be used to contextualise my findings by illuminating the proximal and distal forces that exert direct and indirect influence on the participants.

According to Yardley (2000) sensitivity to the context of the study should also be demonstrated through the choice of methodology, which should convey respect for the participants and their perspectives. In this study, the adoption of IPA as methodology enabled me to develop strong and meaningful engagement with the participants during the interviews, and through the idiographic nature of the analysis process, which allowed me to be sensitive to each individual case (Smith, Flowers and Larkin, 2009). In addition, as recommended by Smith, Flowers and Larkin (2009), I have included several quotes from the participants' interviews in the findings chapter, to give them voice and to enable the reader to check my interpretations and conclusions.

Yardley (2000) advocates sensitivity to the sociocultural setting where the research is conducted. My familiarity with the cultural, social, and institutional aspects of the Algerian context, where my study took place, enabled me to build trust and rapport with the participants, and to create a comfortable environment during the interviews, which encouraged openness and led to rich and insightful data.

3.5.2 Commitment and rigor

Commitment and rigor refer to attentiveness and care towards each participant, particularly during the interviews and the data analysis phase (Smith, Flowers and Larkin, 2009). Throughout the analysis process, I immersed myself in each individual account, prioritizing their unique perspectives before deriving broader themes across cases. I strived to remain faithful to the data shared by my participants. However, member checking, which involves participants confirming that the interpretations of the researcher are an accurate reflection of their responses (Birt et al, 2016), was

intentionally not used in this study, as the implementation of the double hermeneutic process in IPA means that the research findings reflect the researcher's interpretation of the participants' subjective accounts (Smith, Flowers and Larkin, 2009).

Triangulation was another method used to ensure validity and rigor in this IPA study (Pringle, Hendry and McLafferty, 2011). By including two groups of participants, namely students with disabilities and disability support staff, the study allowed me to consider the phenomenon from two different angles. This allowed for a deeper understanding of the support provided to students with disabilities by considering the perspectives of both students and staff. By employing triangulation, a more comprehensive and nuanced picture of the phenomenon has emerged.

According to Yardley (2000), rigor also refers to the competence of researchers in using their chosen methodology. As a novice IPA researcher, I developed competence by immersing myself in the IPA literature, by attending IPA seminars, including a masterclass offered by Jonathan Smith, and by becoming a member of the online IPA qualitative group (ipaqualitative) led by Jonathan Smith and Michael Larkin. Inspired by Vicary, Young and Hicks (2017), who discuss the benefits of a reflective journal as a learning process for the novice IPA researcher, I used a journal throughout my PhD journey. The journal served as a space to keep track of plans, progress, reflections, questions, and links to literature. It documented my learning and helped me maintain rigor and criticality. Furthermore, my supervisor supported me as I developed my competence as a researcher by discussing every stage of the study with me and by offering advice and suggestions throughout.

3.5.3 Transparency and Coherence

In this study, I strived to ensure transparency and clarity in my writing for the benefit of the readers. In order to achieve this, I have provided a detailed account of the design of my study, including how participants were recruited, how the interviews were conducted, how the data were analysed, and how the themes were developed. In the appendices, I have included the documents that I submitted to gain ethical approval, and examples of the analysis process. This information gives readers a clear picture of the research process and enables them to check how accurately I have used the IPA methodology.

To maintain coherence in this study, I considered carefully what methodology would be suitable for my research questions. I chose IPA because it seemed to be a good match. I applied the IPA principles faithfully and strived to present the findings in a logical and clear manner. However, I recognise that judgment regarding coherence rests with the readers. It is their task to assess whether the thesis has a cohesive structure and if the arguments and themes are presented in a coherent and comprehensible manner (Smith, Flowers and Larkin, 2009).

3.5.4 Impact and importance

The final criterion proposed by Yardley (2000) is impact and importance. This refers to the contribution the research makes to knowledge and to practice, According to Smith, Flowers and Larkin (2009), the key question here is what value the research has and to whom. This study was undertaken to address a significant gap in the existing literature regarding the experiences of students with disabilities and the support available to them in Algerian higher education (discussed in Chapter 1). Through an extensive review of relevant literature, it became evident that there is very limited research specifically focusing on this topic within the Algerian context. By

conducting this study, I aimed to contribute insights that have the potential to bring about practical changes and improvements in the area of inclusive higher education for students with disabilities in Algeria. The findings presented in the next chapter shed light on the current state of inclusion and support for students with disabilities in Algerian higher education and highlight areas for enhancement. These findings have led to a number of recommendations which, if implemented, can lead to a more inclusive environment and culture, not only in the university where this study was conducted but in other universities as well.

3.6 Positionality and reflexivity

Positionality refers to the researcher's standpoint in relation to the participants and the context of the research (Jones, Torres and Arminio, 2022). The researcher's positionality is influenced by their personal characteristics, experiences, values and beliefs. In turn, this constellation of characteristics, experiences, values and beliefs, influences the researcher's choice of topic, research design, interaction with the participants, and interpretation of the data.

According to Cohen, Manion and Morrison (2018), reflexivity is a process which involves researchers acknowledging and reflecting critically on their positionality and its influence on their research. Cohen, Manion and Morrison (2018) argue that it is not possible for researchers to eliminate the impact they have on their research. Instead, they should 'hold themselves up to the light' (p. 303) by being open and transparent about their position in relation to the topic, the participants and the research context (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018).

Researchers are required to reflect on and question the knowledge, experiences, biases, and assumptions they have in relation to the topic under investigation (Merriam

and Tisdell, 2016). Reflexivity is considered an important step in research, particularly while conducting a qualitative inquiry, as it enables researchers to recognise and acknowledge how their positionality influences the research process. According to Tracy (2010), when researchers are open about their positionality this can increase the trustworthiness of the study.

In chapter 1, I noted that, as a former student in one of the Algerian universities, I already had an idea about the situation of students with disabilities in Algeria before I embarked on this research. Although I do not have a disability, I am aware of the challenges that students with disabilities encounter in Algerian universities. However, I do not have insider understanding of what it is like to be a student with a disability or a member of a Disability Support Office. Being a peer of students with disabilities in my university, and noticing the lack of support for them, motivated me to conduct the current study. What interests me more than the policies that may be available to accommodate students with disabilities in university or the number of students with disability who complete their programme of study is how each student with disability experiences university life. My ontological position is constructivist, in that I do not believe that there is one objective reality but rather reality is constructed through the interactions of individuals with the physical and social environment. I consider these interactions to shape an individual's experiences in unique ways. I believe this to mean that not two students with disability studying in the same university will have the same experiences because their interactions are shaped by who they are and are unique to them. This ontological position has led me to interpretative epistemology, which is based on the assumption that a phenomenon can be best understood through listening to how individuals with direct experience of the phenomenon make sense of it. The assumption that recounting experiences provides individuals with the opportunity to

reflect on, analyse and interpret them, led me to the IPA methodology and double hermeneutics, as I am interested in how the participants interpret their experiences but, through my analysis, I am attempting to interpret their interpretations individually and collectively. This is in line with the hermeneutic circle (Vagle, 2018) which sees interpretation as an ongoing process moving from the parts (the individual accounts) to the whole (the phenomenon being studied) (Vagle, 2018; Smith, Flowers and Larkin, 2009).

In IPA research, the researcher's active engagement in the hermeneutic circle, a continuous process of meaning making and interpretation, necessitates a deep understanding of participants' subjective realities (Smith, Flowers and Larkin, 2009). However, this immersion requires reflexivity to account for the researcher's own biases and positionality. In this research and through extensive readings on IPA, I have been able to gain the competence to understand the data shared by my participants and to articulate findings (Smith, Flowers and Larkin, 2009). I strived to maintain a balanced approach in order to avoid imposing my own understandings on the data (Smith and Osborn, 2007). By engaging in reflexive practice, I maintained awareness of my biases and subjectivities, which facilitated a nuanced understanding of the participants' experiences.

Using Dahlberg's (2006) suggestion, I strived to bridle my pre-knowledge and preconceptions. Through continuous reflection, documented in the journal I kept throughout the study, I made a conscious effort to keep my pre-knowledge and preconceptions in check and minimise their impact on the study. I attempted to conduct this study with the optimism that I would be able to amplify the voices and experiences of students with disabilities and disability support staff, and provide insights into the current situation of inclusive practices and support in Algerian higher

education, hoping that this will generate new knowledge that will be of value and use to the higher education community in Algeria and beyond. At a personal level, this study enhanced my inclusive thinking and provided me with ideas on how to be more inclusive and supportive for my students and colleagues.

3.7 Study contributions and limitations

Studies on the experiences of students with disabilities in Algerian universities, and disability in general are scarce. This study sought the voices of students with disabilities and disability support staff in one Algerian university. Although this study revealed positive aspects in the experiences of students with disabilities, it also brought to the fore the challenges that students with disabilities encounter at university, and the barriers that hinder the efforts of disability support staff to promote inclusion. This study makes a contribution to the limited existing knowledge about the inclusion of students with disabilities in Algerian higher education. It also contributes to the international literature about the experiences of university students with disabilities by adding perspectives from the Algerian context. In addition, the study makes a practical contribution by offering recommendations for policy makers, disability support staff, academics, and the wider university community. If followed up, these recommendations could lead to the improvement of the experiences of university students with disabilities in the university where the study was conducted and in Algerian higher education more broadly.

Although this study provides valuable insights, several limitations need to be acknowledged.

- The study sample is small, consisting of nine students with disabilities and four disability support officers. Findings based on data from one university

may be influenced by features that are specific to this university. Consequently, the findings of this research cannot be generalised to other Algerian universities

- Some of the student participants were recruited via snowballing. I acknowledge this as a limitation as it might have introduced bias in the study. This could be because the participants who were recruited this way were friends of the two students who expressed interest in the research in response to the email invitation they received from the Disability Support Office. Being friends could mean that they had similar views on the topic and this may have limited the diversity of student perspectives in the data. Equally, the participants who expressed interest in my study after having received the invitation via the Disability Support Office, may have done so because of the involvement of the Disability Support Office in the recruitment process. In other words, they may have thought that this was an opportunity to present the Disability Support Office in a positive light, if they were students who had positive dealings with it or staff who are working under its auspices. Although I made it clear in the participant information sheet that all data will be kept confidential, it should be acknowledged that bias may have entered the findings as a result of the strategy used to recruit participants.
- Data was collected online, via Streamyard, Teams, and Zoom, due to inability to travel to Algeria to collect data during COVID19. However, not all participants were comfortable to be interviewed via video call. Consequently, some of the interviews were conducted over the phone, and via email. Conducting the interviews in this way, via video calls, audio

calls and email may have resulted in loss of some of the nuance and richness that face to face interviews can offer.

- The findings presented in the next chapter have arisen from an IPA study. Had I used a different methodology or analysis approach, different findings may have emerged. This may also have been the case if I had interviewed participants from other groups, such as students without disabilities, or members of the university leadership team.
- Finally, as already noted, this research has been informed by my positionality, including being Algerian and able-bodied. Being Algerian could have made it easier for me to build rapport with the participants, who are also Algerians, but, at the same time, it may have resulted in the participants omitting important information because they thought that I would be aware of it due to our shared culture. Being able-bodied, I do not have insider understanding of disability and as such I may have missed data that a researcher with insider knowledge of disability would have noticed.

3.8 Chapter summary

This chapter provided a discussion of the methodology used in this research. It illuminated the philosophical lens, ontology, and epistemology guiding the study and explained the use of IPA methodology. The chapter also provided details about the research design such as sampling technique, sample size, data collection tool (semi-structured interviews), ethical considerations, and measures taken to ensure validity and quality in this research. This methodological chapter sets the stage for the following two chapters, where the findings are presented and discussed.

Chapter 4: Findings

4.1 Introduction

This chapter presents the findings of the study. It has been organised in three sections. The first section presents the findings from the interviews with the nine students with disabilities who participated in the study. The second section presents the findings from the interviews with the four disability support staff who participated in the study. In the third section a comparison of the findings from the two groups of participants is presented.

4.2 Section one: findings from the interviews with students with disabilities

This section presents findings following IPA analysis of the interviews with nine students with disabilities. These interviews were conducted to answer the first research question:

- What are the lived experiences of students with disabilities in Algerian Higher Education?

The themes that emerged across the nine cases are presented under two superordinate themes: Facilitators of inclusion and barriers to inclusion.

4.2.1 Facilitators of inclusion

During the interviews, the participating students revealed some positive aspects that facilitate their inclusion in the university. According to the participants, these facilitators help to support their learning and participation, although there is still much to be done to alleviate the existing barriers and to enhance the quality of these provisions (see section 'barriers to inclusion'). During the analysis, under the superordinate theme of

'facilitators of inclusion', two subordinate themes were identified: structural facilitators, and self-reliance.

Figure 2. Facilitators of inclusion

4.2.1.1 Structural facilitators

The data gathered from the interviews with students with disabilities provided insights into structural facilitators both within and outside the university, which support the participation and engagement of these students. This subordinate theme was further explored through the sub-themes of academic support, emotional support, family support, and self-reliance.

4.2.1.1.1 Academic support

Those who received academic support reported that it had a significant impact on their involvement in the learning process, and their academic achievement at this university. Academic support practices in this institution entailed the provision of adapted learning materials, extension for the submission of assignments, extra time during exams, extended library loans from librarians, and timetabling classes in the ground floor. This type of support was regarded by the students as crucial to their learning experiences and progress at university.

Although there was considerable variation in the students' responses of how much academic support they received from the university, several spoke positively about the support they have received from academic staff and reported that they felt supported and accommodated in their classroom environment:

“in class, everything is easier and better, my lecturers are very understanding and they offer me help whenever it's needed [...], some lecturers dictate slowly for me, others offer to write for me, while some lecturers allow me to enter class no matter how late I am.” (Student E)

“[...] some lecturers try their best to offer help and provide me with efficient support [...] listening to my concerns in relation to studies, dictating slowly in class... etc.” (Student D)

Furthermore, some students shared positive experiences related to assessment such as extra time allocation for assignments and during exams:

“[...] I do not know about others, but my lecturers always inform invigilators about my case, so I always receive 30 minutes extra during exams.” (Student C)

“ regarding lecturers, [...] they even ask me if I revised or not, so that they can give me extra time to get myself ready for exams and presentations [...].” (Student D)

“[...] my XX lecturer for example, always offers us additional time to submit homework and assignments, in case we failed to submit on time.” (Student G)

One of the students referred to extended loan periods from librarians:

“Extended loans for library books is what I prefer the most, once they know about your case, they will try to help you as much as they can [...]” (Student B)

Some students who are registered with the Disability Support Office reported positive attitudes and willingness from the disability support staff to accommodate them:

“By registering with the Disability Support Office, lecturers have to know my case now, they are more open to help me, and I have all my classes timetabled downstairs.” (Student F)

“Sometimes, the office is able to help me, as they provide me with a scribe during exams and mediate with teachers whenever I have a problem.” (Student D)

It was encouraging to hear about the efforts university staff make to ensure equal accessibility to academic content and resources for students with disabilities. However, it is worth noting that there seems to be inconsistency in the support provided across the university, as, according to some participants, some lecturers fail to offer such type of academic support: “[...] unfortunately, not all of them do this [...]” (Student G). Similarly, although the Disability Support Office can arrange for classes for groups that include students with disabilities to be timetabled downstairs, this is not done consistently:

“ [...] I had all my classes timetabled downstairs when I was in my bachelor degree, but now it is quite different and difficult [...]” (Student I)

This highlights the need for a more robust approach to accommodate students with disabilities, and to ensure that they receive consistent support.

Students with disabilities in this study also reported positive experiences with their peers inside and outside the classroom. They highlighted the importance of formal and informal peer support, and the role their classmates play in supporting their learning:

“ [...] regarding my peers, I don’t know what to say, but without them, I would have been lost. They helped me many times, they bought a Dictaphone for me, and even when it was damaged, they bought me another one. They helped me a lot and I will never forget that” (Student D)

“[...] I usually get summaries and lessons from my friends. We also used to gather at the library in order to revise together and to explain for me the lectures I missed [...]”(Student A)

“[...] I have a friend of mine and she is my classmate at the same time, she always comes to my house and write for me the lessons I record in class, and when I am absent she also records lessons for me [...] she even brings her sister to read and write for me in exams” (Student F)

Participants also mentioned that their classmates help them to access buildings and classes:

“[...] my peers are very supportive, they help me use the stairs to get to upper classes, and they are very open to aid me whenever it is needed.” (Student H)

“[...] I have some friends who always try to arrive early and help me get up to classes, or use the ramp to go to different places at university (cafeteria, toilets...etc), and even outside university.” (Student B)

The above testimonies from students with disabilities underscore the importance of peer support, highlighting the various forms of assistance peers can provide, whether it is formal academic help with note-taking, providing summaries, or replacing damaged equipment, motivational and emotional help, or practical support, e.g. helping them access classrooms. This shows that nurturing positive relationships with fellow students and the culture of peer support can help students with disabilities to overcome challenges and achieve success.

Aside from the academic support that students with disabilities receive from their lecturers and peers, which has enabled them to participate in their studies, the students also highlighted the importance of emotional support received from their lecturers.

4.2.1.1.2 Emotional support

Some of the participating students reported positive emotional support and supportive attitudes that they received from their lecturers and peers:

“some lecturers are just great; they always care, and ask about you even outside class, and they believe that you can do it” (Student F)

“some lecturers are nice, and try to support you with everything they can, they encourage you and do not see your disability as a problem [...]” (Student H)

The emotional support provided by lecturers seems to have a significant impact on students' motivation and academic performance. The participating students who reported that they receive emotional support from their lecturers felt that they are not only valued for their abilities, but also cared about and encouraged as individuals. This emotional support and encouragement appear to fuel their motivation and boost their sense of worth. Additionally, the fact that some lecturers were reported to be supportive even outside the university indicates that a supportive environment beyond the university is important to students with disabilities. It suggests that the establishment of a supportive environment can be crucial in facilitating the participation and academic achievements of students with disabilities, even when it transcends university boundaries.

Some of the participating students also reported positive attitudes from peers without disabilities:

“[...] I don't know what to say, without them (classmates), I would have been lost. [...] I love how they believe in my abilities and do not judge me because of my disability” (Student D)

“[...] they believe in my abilities and capacities [...] that's what I like about them, because this boosts my self-

confidence and makes me feel like I am like others [...]"
(Student A)

"[...] they are very helpful and kind to me, and they always try to support me with what they can, which means a lot to me." (Student F)

It seems that students with disabilities appreciate the support received from their peers. This does not only encourage students with disabilities, but it also creates a sense of belonging and acceptance of diversity in university. Arguably, the supportive mind-set of peers without disabilities and lecturers towards students with disabilities helps minimise barriers and create a culture inclusion.

4.2.1.1.3 Family Support

Although not within university support mechanisms, students with disabilities in this study pointed out that external support coming from their families is crucial. Most of the interviewed students reported that family support maximizes their chances to study at university and contributes to their success. They described the way their families helped them achieve their goals and validated their choices (university choice and course choice):

"My family are very supportive [...] especially my father. Above all he supported me to go to university, as he believes in my abilities, and this matters a lot [...]"
(Student F)

Another student stated how grateful he feels towards the support he receives from his sister:

" I am grateful for my big sister, without her I would have never entered school, she was the one who encouraged me to go to school, and she always accompanied me wherever I went, and without her support I would have never reached university level [...]" (Student B)

In addition to emotional support and encouragement provided from families, students with disabilities referred to other types of family support, such as academic or financial:

“my father bought me an electric chair from his own pocket, so that I can rely on myself and not ask others to help push my chair [...]” (Student E)

“ I can never describe the support I receive from my family, they do anything to help [...] for example, whenever I am home my father always listens to how I spent my day, and also helps me write my recorded lessons [...]” (Student D)

“ [...] he [the interviewee’s father] also bought me the necessary technological tools to study with [...]”. (Student F)

As these quotes show, family support plays a crucial role in encouraging students with disabilities during their university studies, and in helping them to progress, by providing emotional, financial, and sometimes academic support. The importance of family support was also implied by students who reported that they chose to study in this particular university because of its proximity to their families and homes. This suggests that the students rely on the support provided by their families, and wish to avoid the hassle of adapting to a new environment away from home and the challenges it may entail:

“I have chosen this university because it is the closest to my home.” (Student C)

“I opted for XX Course in an another university, but it was far away from where I lived, so I chose this university, as it was the closest to my home’ (Student E)

“ [...] I found it better to drop out of my course and change to another university that is closer to my hometown,” (Student F)

4.2.1.1.4 Self-determination

It was apparent through their responses that the students who participated in this study have developed a range of self-support strategies which help them navigate their university life. Additionally, they revealed that they have developed new personal skills such as self-determination, independence and self-confidence. They emphasised the importance of such strategies and skills for their progress and for overcoming the existing barriers at university. They mentioned that they have developed abilities to find solutions for themselves, and reported the strategies they use in order to support and accommodate themselves academically:

“ [...] everything is available on the internet; I do not wait for lecturers to upload lectures or provide me with notes. If I wanted anything I would simply get it from google scholar or other databases.” (Student A)

“I get notes from my peers then I try to elaborate and develop these notes, I use resources from the internet and public library, to revise for exams and prepare for assignments [...].”(Student B)

“[...] I have a type of camera that magnifies texts and a laptop that reads documents at home [...] I use them to read documents or to hear audio books and articles [...].” (Student F)

Additionally, these students revealed that they are thankful for who they are. For them, accepting themselves and their disabilities enabled them to develop high levels of self-confidence and self-determination, which helped them to succeed. Understanding their abilities and disabilities enabled them to adapt to the environment and overcome difficulties and barriers. These students identified themselves as strong and independent individuals, and as survivors and warriors.

“[...] among the good side of disability and all the barriers I faced is experience, I mean, you will gain experience and you will learn how to be responsible. You will build a strong character, and you will gain social immunity to overcome all types of barriers and contempt. [...] you gain self-confidence too. [...] whatever the barriers, social, physical,

emotional...etc. I managed to overcome all of them. Where there is a will there is always a way. I am a true survivor' (Student C)

"[...] a person with a disability, who does not have a strong desire to succeed and a strong will can do nothing. You have to be a warrior in the face of the environment and its barriers. [...] I have a goal in my mind; I will study hard and succeed. I know that I can do it." (Student B)

"At university, you should attract the attention of lecturers and fellow students by different means. [...] Studying hard, and doing your best to succeed, is your only weapon at university." (Student A)

"[...] despite all the barriers I am facing, I am proud of myself, and I am now more confident, you just have to accept yourself, that is how you overcome your fears and all other barriers [...]" (Student D)

These quotes demonstrate the personal development that students with disabilities have gone through. It was apparent that these students had developed self-reliance through their experiences of overcoming barriers. Furthermore, they emphasize their conviction that, through self-acceptance and determination, they can overcome different barriers, prove their abilities, and succeed.

4.2.2 Barriers to inclusion

While the previous section reported factors which the participating students saw as facilitators of their inclusion in the university, it also alluded to barriers. During the analysis, these barriers were grouped into the superordinate theme of 'barriers to inclusion' with three subordinate themes named environmental barriers, structural

barriers, and attitudinal barriers, in line with the classification developed by Finkelstein (1993, 1996, 2001) Oliver (1990, 1999, 2013) and Allan (2008, 2013).

Figure 3. Barriers to inclusion

4.2.2.1 Environmental barriers

Drawing on Finkelstein (1993, 1996, 2001) Oliver (1990, 1999, 2013) and Allan (2008, 2013), environmental barriers in this section refer to all the concrete and physical aspects that tend to restrict or prevent students with disabilities from full participation in learning and social activities, e.g. stairs, inaccessible doorways, inaccessible built environment.

University architecture that is supposed to facilitate accessibility to the different university buildings seems to exclude students with disabilities and those with physical disabilities in particular. Students with disabilities in this study referred to different obstacles that hinder their experience inside this institution, such as the poor quality of ramps and corridors, the existence of stairs, the absence of lifts, long distance between buildings, lack of signposting, risky sidewalks and paths, inaccessible dormitories, inaccessible libraries, and inaccessible transportation.

4.2.2.1.1 Inaccessible university buildings

Most of the student participants revealed that they are facing difficulties reaching different buildings, and that physical accessibility in their university is still an issue for them. It was apparent through the participants' accounts that this university is not built to welcome everyone, as participants made negative comments about inaccessible infrastructure; one participant, for example, described the university's physical accessibility as "[...] Catastrophic" (student E). Similarly, another agreed saying "[...] I always feel like I am in need of others' help, this is all because of the university stupid architecture" (Student B).

Most participants reported that they have never used the university library, and that the library is not a friendly place for them. Four of them said it is because libraries are very far, inaccessible and not stocked with sufficient resources. For example, Student C stated:

"I am in my final year, and I have never gone to the library, it is so far and not accessible at all."

Student I also stated:

"[...] I cannot make it to the library alone, it is inaccessible".

Similarly, student E commented:

"[...] I have to go to the library, to get resources, but you know I always need someone to accompany me there otherwise I will get lost [...]" (Student E).

Another student reported the following in a sarcastic way:

"even the library has stairs [laughs] [...] actually the librarians were so helpful, I have had no other issues except for stairs." (Student B).

Participants revealed that the inaccessibility of university buildings and classrooms is demonstrated by the absence of lifts and the existence of stairs to reach upper

classrooms, which prevent them from joining when their classes are upstairs. In the previous section, it was mentioned that the Disability Support Office can arrange that classes for groups including students with disabilities are timetabled downstairs, but it appears that this is not done consistently because several of the students mentioned that they have classes upstairs, and this presents challenges for them:

“university is full of stairs; there are no lifts, I am always obliged to get upstairs with the help of my friends, when I have classes in the upper floors” (Student B).

“[...] there is also the problem of stairs and upstairs classes, I get so tired trying to reach upper classes, and sometimes I am not even permitted to join the class because of coming late [Laughs] like it is my fault.”(Student C)

According to these students, it seems that the university physical infrastructure favours those without disabilities. This was highlighted by a student, who observed that, unlike her, peers without disabilities have benefited a lot from going to the library and studying there.

“[...] for me it was hard to go to the libraries, I would love to, but all libraries are inaccessible and very far, and I might get lost because of my disability [...] however, those without disabilities are lucky because they can go and study there [...]” (Student D)

Participants also reported inaccessible dormitory facilities and infrastructures. According to some participants, this obliged them to travel every day from home to university, because they found residence halls uncomfortable and not equipped to receive students with disabilities. For example, Student E reported that she prefers to travel from home to university on a daily basis, rather than live on campus:

“ [...] I don't live there because the conditions there are very poor for someone with a disability, I went once and it was terrible, I was given a room in a place that wasn't comfortable or appropriate at all. This includes the room and the bathrooms. They were aware of my disability [...]. I'm not talking about the room because I can get used to it, but the bathroom had stairs leading up to it, which meant I couldn't get there on my own [...].” (Student E)

Another participant reiterated this point:

“Student dormitories were uncomfortable and not adequate at all [...] it feels like a prison, this is why I do not stay there I prefer to travel daily from my home to the university.’ (Student A)

One student mentioned that although the accommodation team managed to allocate a ground floor room for her, it is still hard to reach other services in the students' residence:

“ [...] they always give me a room in ground floor buildings, yet I am unable to make it to other places like the dining hall, the cafeteria [...] and sometimes I like to go to the study space inside the residence, but I cannot make it there either, unless other people help me [...].” (Student C)

Inaccessibility of university buildings, such as classrooms, libraries and dormitories, was not the only physical barrier reported by the students with disabilities who participated in this study. Participants also pointed out the poor quality of the existing physical facilities that prevented them from accessing different university buildings. These include inaccessible ramps and corridors, long distance between buildings, risky pathways, and lack of signposting.

One of the participating students expressed dissatisfaction about the available facilities (ramps), using a strong tone:

“-[...] there are facilities that exist, but you can tell that these facilities were not made well [...]. If you enter the university, you will be able to see them on the surface, but once you get closer you will realize the opposite, and you will see the ugly picture.” (Student E)

The same participant continued to express disappointment about the existing facilities, as she stated that corridors and ramps, for instance, are not built well at all:

“I had no idea about how horrible these facilities were [...] I study in a building that has a ramp. When I used my electric wheelchair to get to the building, I was not aware of the terrible quality of the corridor; it seemed as if I was climbing a mountain. I tried to go up until I saw my wheelchair falling backwards. I screamed, and thank goodness there were two guys there that rushed to my aid and got hold of my chair, had they not come in that instance, I would've fallen [...] from that moment I never use that corridor on my own again, I have to be accompanied by another person, who can help me climb that mountain.” (Student E)

Students with disabilities also referred to additional accessibility problems, such as long distance between buildings, and insufficient time allocation between sessions to change classrooms:

“[...] there is a huge distance between them (buildings and classrooms) [...] imagine yourself studying in a class for 1 hour and a half, and then moving to another class in a different building, which is situated in a very far place, and vice versa. [Pause] long, very long distance. This makes me miss or skip classes, because it is very tiring to get there. Especially when it is raining, it is even more difficult.” (Student C)

The same sentiments were expressed by students D and F, who reported how lack of signposts on campus affected their ability to make it to certain places while at university.

“Last year, it was very difficult for me to find buildings, and to reach lecture halls. Our university is so big, and I get lost easily. I feel shy to ask people to guide me to certain places [...] sometimes I struggle to reach the university bus station, and I even take the wrong bus to get me to university or to the accommodation [...] It is still so hard for me to make it on time to certain places at university.” (Student D)

“[...] although they have managed to number classrooms after I raised my concerns, I still get lost if teachers change classes, I always need someone to guide me to get to classes and rooms, [...] in order to avoid being late, I always come earlier to find the classrooms [...]” (Student F)

In addition to the inaccessibility problems in this university, Student F added that walking in the university is not always safe, as she recalled a situation that put her safety at risk:

“ [...] I remember once on a rainy day, a sewage pipe was left open, I didn't pay attention, and I fell into it [...] thank goodness I was not alone, and people hurried to help me [...]” (Student F)

The above quotes offer valuable insights into the experiences of students with disabilities navigating the university physical environment. It is apparent that these students face multiple challenges on a daily basis as they experience difficulties finding, reaching, and accessing buildings including classrooms, libraries and dormitories. This is due to different factors, including absence of lifts, lack of signposting, long distances between buildings, risky walkways, inadequate maintenance procedures. The responses of these students highlight serious challenges that require urgent attention to ensure an accessible and safe environment that meets disability requirements and welcomes diversity.

4.2.2.1.2 Inaccessible Transportation

Most participants reported limited and inaccessible transportation inside and outside the university as a barrier that affects their university experience. It seems that it is still difficult for students with disabilities to travel to the university in the same way as their peers without disabilities because university and public transportation is not constructed to accommodate individuals with disabilities. For example, student B made the following comment in a sarcastic tone:

“[...] university buses are not accessible at all, imagine a bus with steps, this makes you always feel helpless, and wait for others to get you on the bus.” (Student B).

Equally, student E reported how hard it is for her to use buses, because they are not disability-friendly: “[...] I always need the help of the driver or my friends to get on the bus.” (Student E).

Student D shared different challenges associated with university transportation:

“[...] bus stops are not accessible, all buses are alike and I cannot read which one is going to the residence hall, I used to miss my buses because of that, but after a while at university, bus drivers remembered me, and used to stop for me once they saw me in the bus stop. [...]” (Student D)

Lack of public transportation was another issue that one of the interviewed students spoke about:

“[...] Not only me, my friends in other universities suffer from lack of transportation [...] the first bus leaves at 7 a.m. and classes start at 8 a.m. I often miss the bus because there are a lot of people there [...]. Sometimes, I miss exams [sighs] or I cannot make it on time to class, I arrive late and tired, especially if I have something to present in front of my peers [...] lecturers grade your work based on

your answers, and the way you presented, and do not care about your situation. [Low tone] it is complicated.” (Student G)

Unfortunately, inaccessibility and unavailability of public transportation was not the only problem reported by the students who participated in the study. Sometimes the attitudes of bus-drivers towards individuals with disabilities are also a problem. One of the participants recalled when public bus drivers would not let him or others in wheelchairs to get on the bus, because there was not enough space to get their wheelchairs on the bus, unless he paid for both urban transportation, until I bought a car. Sometimes, I had to pay for two seats just to bring my wheelchair with me on the bus.” (Student B)

Lack of accessible transportation in addition to the architectural barriers outlined in the previous section appear to be major concerns for students with disabilities because they hinder their access and participation in this university. As the participating students recounted their experiences of environmental barriers, they highlighted the effect these barriers have on their academic journeys. According to the students, these environmental barriers affect their university experience, academic performance and achievement. In this sense, Student E said:

“Sometimes I make it late to class because of the inability to find someone that can help me get to classrooms. Sometimes I am forced to wait in the winter where it can get very cold, and when I enter class, I have to get into the class mood and follow along with the teacher, but it can be very difficult. Sometimes we are tasked to write and I wouldn’t be able to, because I would be very exhausted and feeling cold from all the waiting.” (Student E)

Student C and Student F reported similar issues that stem from the unaccommodating and exclusive environment:

"This [...] affected my educational achievement and my exam marks, since I was obliged to miss some classes."
(Student C)

" [...] I often miss classes and miss important lessons that might come in the exam [...]" (Student F).

The students suggested that further adjustments should be made in order to improve physical accessibility and to reduce the physical barriers in this institution. The following statements indicate what the university experiences of students with disabilities might be like if quality physical accessibility existed:

" [...] if actual facilities that could help me access classrooms and other places existed, I would not struggle or need the help of others [...]. The only thing that bothers me is the access to these buildings and places in college, because if they were built well, it would have been much easier."(Student C)

"[...] I would suggest [...] building accessible ramps and lifts, so that I can make it on my own and not feel that I am always at others' mercy."(Student B).

Other suggestions for changes to enhance the university's physical accessibility and to make the infrastructure more accessible and accommodating for all students with disabilities included:

" [...] mmm, allocating classes in the ground floor, this might be a solution, but it doesn't always work, because I am always in need of someone to help me reach lecture halls. I don't know if that's possible or not, but providing someone who's capable of helping me instead of my friends, someone whose job is to help people like me. I wish they can provide that in a professional manner so that you won't feel that you're always in need of others."
(Student F)

" [...] we do need parking spaces for those with physical disabilities in our university [...]" (Student I)

Thus far, findings from the students' interviews in relation to the university architecture, do not only reflect the struggle of the majority of participants with physical accessibility, but they also reveal the influence of the principles of the medical model on the experiences of students with disabilities inside and outside the university context. The participants explained how environmental barriers affect their higher education experience and highlighted the importance of reasonable physical accommodations in their university. Nonetheless, it could be seen through the participants' responses that the university environment with its accessibility barriers and flaws obliges students to adapt to it, as students' responses revealed alternative ways to navigate the university. This adaptation could be perceived as imposed limitation of the environmental barriers that align with the medical model, which compels individuals with disabilities to adapt into inaccessible environments.

4.2.2.2 Structural Barriers

As noted in Chapter 2, Finkelstein (1993, 1996, 2001) Oliver (1990, 1999, 2013) and Allan (2008, 2013) have been very vocal about the role of structures in the experiences of people with disabilities. They have argued that most structures are ableist because they have been established to accommodate the needs of people without disabilities and, as such, they act as barriers for people without disabilities. The findings from the interviews with the students who participated in this study reflect these sentiments. The students reported a number of structural barriers within the university context which affect their ability to fully participate at university, and affect negatively their learning and progress. These barriers include: the challenge of transition to higher education, lack of institutional support, lack of academic support, lack of financial

support, limited job opportunities, lack of sense of belonging, and absence of inclusive policy.

4.2.2.2.1 The challenge of transition

During the interviews, the students indicated that there is a lack of systemic preparedness for the transition of individuals with disabilities between different educational levels. This creates challenges for students with disabilities:

“[...] I always find it hard in my first year of each level, I mean when I move from one educational level to another (from primary to middle school, to high school, to university), but then I get used to it [...] it is always the first year that is the most difficult [...]” (Student D)

This student further explained why she found it hard to adjust to university life:

“[...] I feel overwhelmed by the modules that I have to re-write and summarize at home, by the presentations I have to deliver, and the deadlines I have to meet as well. I wish they prepared us for such challenges before going to university [...] also, I need someone to accompany me, and teachers to understand my situation, I need someone to write for me during exams [...] all of that is not easily provided at the start of each new level [...]” (Student D)

Student D was not the only interviewee who noted the lack of preparation for university transition. Student F stated:

“[...] it was so hard to rapidly adapt to the workload in the first year [...] I mean university is more autonomous [...]. [...] and since I can't write in class I have to postpone this until I am home to listen and re-write all the recorded lessons of the day, which is so challenging and tiring in addition to my health condition [...]” (Student F)

Arguably, this lack of preparedness for the transition to university can affect the academic progress of students with disabilities as it creates additional challenges for

them. Two respondents raised the problem of workload, as one of the challenges of being unprepared for the transition to university study. Student G expressed his concerns, in a low tone:

“[...] university became very hard [...], lots of pressure, lots of research and work to do, due dates, submissions...etc., which means if you want to proceed, you'd have to put a lot of effort in, which is really hard and stressful for me to deal with, in addition to what I am going through.” (Student G)

Student H's experience seems to resonate with the experience of student G. She perceived workload as an extra burden in addition to her disability, and mentioned that it has a huge impact on her experience and on the experiences of others like her, stating that the burden is so immense that she sometimes felt hopeless and unable to continue.

“[...] lecturers give many tasks, which is sometimes unbearable, especially because I suffer from XX, I feel so stressed about it, I couldn't make it this term, and I am afraid I won't make it next term either [...]” (Student H)

These responses reveal the challenges the students who participated in this study encounter trying to adapt to a new academic environment, including adapting to high academic demands and academic expectations. They indicate how difficult and overwhelming this could be for their wellbeing, and highlight the pressure it adds to their experience at university. This suggests that there is a need to bridge the gap between different educational levels to avoid the burden of stressful transition experiences for these students.

4.2.2.2.2 Lack of institutional support

Lack of institutional support at this university was another structural barrier that students with disabilities face. This includes lack of academic support (e.g. exclusionary assessment system), and administrative barriers (e.g. long and slow process of receiving support and information).

Few of the participating students referred to the Disability Support Office or disability support staff when talking about support provision (some examples can be seen in the section entitled 'Facilitators of inclusion'). Most participants referred to administrative staff, as they seemed to be unfamiliar with the Disability Support Office. From this, it is possible to conclude that the support provided by disability support staff is insufficient, or not reaching all students equally and equitably.

In order to understand further how the Disability Support Office works, from the perspective of students with disabilities, I asked the participating students about their relationship with it, the quality of support provided to them by disability support staff, and the role that disability support staff play in their university experience. Participants' responses in relation to the Disability Support Office varied. Some of them appeared not to be aware that their university has a Disability Support Office:

“[...] I believe there is no disability support office, or an office that can provide help and support to us, and I can tell you this according to my experiences in different universities in Algeria, and not only in this university. And it would be great if there was one” (Student A)

“Well, I really do not think that such an office exists. If it does exist, I would definitely register with it.” (Student B)

“I am not sure about that, well, I do not know if there is a disability support office or not, but I do not think so, and no one told me that such an office exists.”(Student G)

Other students reported that registering with Disability Support Office was a waste of time, as they tried to seek help several times from disability support staff, but nothing has changed:

“In actuality, I had no idea that such an office exists until this year. I coincidentally met up with a college professor, and after he saw me, he told me about an office that offers support and told me to register with it. I registered but I honestly do not think that they can do much, as I have spoken to them many times about many problems, but nothing happened so far.”(Student E)

“I once heard that there is an office, which provides support for students with disabilities [...]. It was in my first year, I went there once to raise my concern about the long distance between buildings, hoping that they may find a solution for me. They registered me and noted my issue, but I have never been contacted by any of them. I think this office is only ink on paper.” (Student C)

“[...] I have repeatedly tried to raise with the office the problem related to bus accessibility, but in vain [...]” (Student B)

These responses suggest that the Disability Support office is limited in its reach and perhaps in the scope of the support they can provide. The findings from the interviews with the disability support staff, which are presented in the next session, throw some light on issues that may be responsible for these students' experiences.

Lack of institutional support was also mentioned in relation to the university's administration systems. Some students expressed concerns about the way these systems operate and the impact they have on their overall university experience.

“[...] even with my condition, they made me sign papers in several offices, and each office is very far from the other. They sent me to several places to sign a document. [...] Everything was delayed; I had missed many classes and sessions because of my illness and the delay in receiving my certificate of registration [...] This prevented me from joining my studies on time” (Student C)

“[...] even with my condition I suffer from bureaucracy, for instance, I was prevented from getting a room in the residence halls because I am older than the specified age, this is unfair [...] they should consider this point [...]” (Student G)

“ [...] the university is very big, I find it difficult to request support from administration, especially if you have to submit something or sign documents, you will go through a lot even with your disability there is no support provided in terms of that [...]” (Student D)

“[...] there should be a dedicated number or email that students with disabilities can use to ask for support [...] to avoid moving from one office to another in vain.” (Student A)

“ [...] each year, I need to go again and talk to them about XX issue, so that they can accommodate me [...]” (Student I)

“I usually contact administration staff, they make it harder for me, because I have to remind them each year of the adjustments I need.” (Student B)

These quotes indicate that students with disabilities face bureaucratic challenges when seeking support or information. These administrative barriers include the tiresome and lengthy tasks of signing multiple documents in various offices, often located far apart, which not only cause delays in getting necessary support, but also lead to missed classes, and can restrict students' access to accommodations and facilities. This emphasizes the need to establish more efficient communication channels and processes such as dedicated phone numbers, emails, or online platforms, to ensure that students do not have to go through so many burdensome steps.

The students also reported implicitly lack of emotional support through their suggestions and recommendations for mental health support and psychological counselling:

“I wish they could provide us with psychological support. It is great to have someone who listens to your concerns and defends your rights.” (Student C)

“[...] University should provide a good atmosphere for students with disabilities, and they should start with offering emotional support and therapy sessions for us, I hope that other students with disabilities will not go through the same thing that I went through.” (Student A)

“[...] university should make it easier for students with disabilities so that they do not feel discouraged and undermined [...] I suggest they provide us with mental health support, in order to boost our determination and not the opposite.”(Student E)

The barriers that students with disabilities encounter in this university can have a detrimental effect on their wellbeing and sense of belonging, as they can make them feel excluded and marginalised. This highlights the importance of creating support systems that transcend the scope of environmental and academic accommodations. The students with disabilities who participated in this study emphasized the need for emotional support, and the creation of counselling services, where their concerns can be heard and their rights can be advocated for.

4.2.2.2.3 Lack of academic support

Among the structural factors that influence the learning experiences of students with disabilities is the teaching methodology and pedagogy that most lecturers follow. Some participating students spoke of lack of provision of accessible lectures and notes before or even after class. Some of them highlighted the need to upload learning materials on the e-learning platform dedicated to students, and recommended that lecturers should start doing this.

“ [...] I asked a lecturer about the lectures, she didn't send me all of them, I tried again and told her that I didn't receive all the lectures, but she didn't care at all.” (Student D)

“None of my lecturers provide lectures or notes before the session, so if I am absent, I have to contact my friends to provide me with lectures [...] But during the period of Covid19, teachers started uploading lectures on the e-learning platform [...] I found that amazing and really helpful. I think I am the only person on earth who is grateful for COVID19.” (Student C)

“I usually get lesson summaries and questions for assignments from my classmates. If lecturers could upload lectures on the e-learning platform, and guarantee us access to it, it would have been much easier [...]” (Student A)

Other students also highlighted issues with lecturers’ inaccessible resources and teaching methodology, like delivering lectures in the form of PowerPoint presentations, without taking the additional support needs of students with disabilities in mind. For example, student D said:

“I use a Dictaphone to record lectures, because most lectures are PPT based. Once I get home, I try to listen to the whole recording, I have to skip forwards and backwards to reach the points I need, and this is daunting. If only they could provide me with copies of the lectures after the class, but I usually get lectures a week before my exams [laughs] could you imagine that.” (Student D)

Student F also shared challenges she experienced in class:

“[...] I find it difficult to follow the pace of some lecturers, it is difficult for me to absorb what they say; I mean listening and trying to jot down some notes. My peers would not find it hard because they can follow the slides. I keep asking lecturers to provide me with lecture notes or slides but not all of them do that.” (Student F)

The students also reported lack of assistive technology and computers to assist their learning. It appears that this university is ill equipped with such tools, as many of the students pointed out the need to incorporate assistive technology in libraries and to

replace the outdated, one-size-fits all materials with accessible books and e-resources.

“I am very good at using the computer and searching for electronic resources; it would have been much easier if they could afford computers at the library, and newer e-resources [...]” (Student B)

“[...] if an audio library existed it would have been great, and I would not seek for others’ help.” (Student F)

“[...] sometimes I like to stay in the library, but it does not contain new resources, nor does it contain adapted computers to use.” (Student E)

“[...] I never used the library because it has one-size-fits-all resources [...] there are no audio resources, no magnifiers, no zoom tools and no assistive tools there [...]” (Student D)

The reported lack of accessible learning materials and assistive technology in this university highlights a significant gap in support for these students, and places a significant burden on them, as it makes them always dependent on their peers to help them access lectures and module information. It is interesting that one of the participants remarked that the COVID-19 pandemic led to positive changes such as uploading lectures and lecture notes to the e-learning platform. However, this raises questions regarding the lack of implementation of such accommodations earlier, emphasizing the lack of a proactive approach. This was also highlighted through the responses of students who mentioned that their request for accessible materials was often overlooked, which indicates lack of responsiveness to the requirements of students with disabilities in this university, and failure of the university system to support these students.

Even though students with disabilities mentioned that some academic and support staff showed willingness to support them during the assessment and examination

process (as can be seen in 'academic support' above), according to the participants, not all lecturers provide such support, and not all students benefit from the provided support in the same way. As shown by the quotes below, it seems that there is still work to be done to enhance the amount and quality of support provided during the assessment and examination process:

"[...] you know 30 minutes of extra time is not always enough for me. I get really tired, because of the uncomfortable seating situation, I feel so tired and it is painful sitting for two hours in a row, in the same position, without taking rest breaks, and I receive no support concerning that." (Student C)

"I find it difficult to find someone who would write for me during exams, [...]. Sometimes, I cannot afford to find someone who can write and read for me, I cannot bring someone from outside the university, nor can I bring someone from the same speciality, they don't trust them – they say- [laughs]. This is inconvenient, because if I bring someone I know this will get me into trouble with my lecturers, and it happened many times to me [...], lecturers and administration would not allow you to bring someone you know, and at the same time, they do not put effort to provide a reader or a scribe for me." (Student D)

The above quotes reflect lack of inclusive assessment accommodations for students with disabilities. Although this institution offers extra time during exams of 30 minutes duration, it appears that this type of accommodation is not adequate for all students with disabilities, and may not necessarily suit all of them. Students with disabilities differ in the type and severity of disability they experience, therefore, they differ in terms of support they require. Student C's quote above indicates that more time than is typically provided is needed to accommodate her needs. It also indicates that allowing extra time for students with disabilities during exams may not fully meet their additional support needs, as they might require other types of support during exams. Student D's quote suggests reluctance of university staff to provide assistance during

exams (scribes/ readers), which creates additional burdens for students like him as they need to take responsibility for finding someone to assist. This raises questions about the duty of the university to support all learners and create equal opportunities during exams.

4.2.2.2.4 Lack of financial support

Funding and financial issues were repeatedly reported by students with disabilities during this study. All participants noted the lack of financial aid from the government. According to students' responses and the Algerian law, the Algerian government provides financial allowance for all students, in order to encourage equal access to higher education. The funds are allocated directly to students once they pass the baccalaureate exam and transition to higher education. However, if you are a student with disability, you cannot benefit from this financial allowance, as the Algerian government provides a monthly stipend for individuals with disabilities (Moktari and Zerguine, 2021). As a consequence, some students with disabilities feel obliged to work in order to be able to support themselves financially while studying, which is considered as an additional burden that can distract them from their primary goal (concentrating on their studies and academic achievement). For them, financial support is as essential as any other type of support, and it is important because it can influence their success and achievement in higher education. This is illustrated in the following quote:

“[...] there is a grant for people with disabilities. The joke is that, if you get that grant, you will not get the student grant. I find that unfair [sighs]. Well, both grants are insufficient to cover the needs of a student with a disability at university [...] Not all individuals with disabilities are able to work alongside their studies as many of their peers without disabilities do.” (Student E)

Equally, participant B explained how financial concerns affected his university choice,

“[...] I have chosen this university because it is closer to my home, so that I can work and study at the same time, in order to support myself financially” (Student B).

Other students also stressed the importance of financial support, and its effect on their progress and experience at university:

“[...] I see myself in need of financial support to afford transportation, food and even medications, I would not be able to continue my studies without financial support from my parents [...]” (Student D)

“[...] what matters the most to a university student and especially to a student with a disability is financial support [pause], [...] it is hard to study, deal with all the barriers, your condition, and at the same time think about how you are going to afford food, clothes, transportation.” (Student C)

“[...] I am a good student, and if I had enough financial support at university, I would have been among the valedictorians [...]” (Student A)

The students with disabilities who participated in this study were vocal about their financial concerns and their impact on their experience at university. The quotes above reflect different issues faced by students with disabilities due to limited financial support, which create additional burdens on them. The governmental grant offered to individuals with disabilities is deemed insufficient, and being ineligible for the university grant seems unfair. This underscores the need for implementing supportive measures that can minimise the challenges that result from financial instability for university students with disabilities.

4.2.2.2.5 Limited employment opportunities

During the interviews, all students talked about transitioning from higher education to work life. They argued that employment after university is the only way to secure a stable life and become independent. The participants raised concerns in relation to low levels of recruiting individuals with disabilities in the job market, and pointed out that the government should reconsider recruitment conditions and create more job opportunities for them. They stated:

“[...] we are not in need of a grant; we need a job after university. I know many people with disabilities, who graduated and are still without a job. They applied for many jobs and they were refused because of their disabilities.”
(Student A)

“[...] the government recruits around 1% of individuals with disabilities, which means out of 100 workers we have only 1 individual with disability, and this applies to different sectors [...] I suggest they raise the percentage of recruitment, so that people with disabilities will have more chances to work.” (Student B)

“[...] not many individuals with disabilities are recruited in the workforce, the government should consider this, where are the disabled in the workplace?” (Student C)

Participants perceived work and employment as a way to prove themselves and to show their abilities to others. One participant stated:

“[...] I got my bachelor degree 3 years ago, and I couldn't find a job. Having a job after graduation is an opportunity that enables you to be in touch with other people, and to prove yourself and show normal people that you are the same as them, and you are capable to work.” (Student A)

Concerns about negative perceptions and attitudes in the workplace were also reported in this study. Participating students highlighted that they are concerned about

the way they are going to be perceived by their work-peers, in addition to being concerned about making it out there in the workplace:

“[...] well you know, I am talking about recruiting people with disabilities and affording employment to them, but I am not sure after all about being able to work [...] you know with all the barriers to accessibility and integration, I am not sure I can do it.” (Student C)

“[...] it is hard, if you know what I mean, I am afraid of being marginalised or underestimated because of my disability, by my co-workers.” (Student B)

“[...] I am afraid that I may not be accepted [as a teacher] because of XX disability, I mean even if I am accepted, I am afraid that I will face difficulties with my students inside the class.” (Student H)

“I would love to work as a teacher after graduation, but I am not sure that I will be accommodated as a teacher. I use braille to write, I am not sure I can make it inside the classroom with my students, and I don't think that parents would accept me to teach their children.”(Student D)

The above statements reflect the concerns and apprehensions that students with disabilities in this study are having in relation to the transition from university to the workplace. These statements reveal worries related to finding employment after university, and their inclusion in the job market. Limited job opportunities for people with disabilities lead to under-representation of these individuals in the workforce, which is another issue that needs to be addressed. Furthermore, it appears that these students also have concerns in relation to exclusion, marginalisation and lack of appreciation they could face at work by co-workers and others.

4.2.2.2.6 Lack of Sense of Belonging

Lack of sense of belonging was identified as an important structural barrier for students with disabilities. The findings suggest that the majority of students with disabilities in this study are not included in the social life of the university:

“I do not participate in social events, and I would not do that [...] actually I was never invited to participate.”
(Student C)

“I hear about social events, clubs and organizations but I was never part of them. They do not bother to invite me, and I do not try to join them [...] I think they do not need me there, I do not want to be a burden.” (Student A)

One of the participants stated that he is active in many clubs and organizations outside the university rather than inside university. He said:

“I have never been part of any club inside university, but I am very active outside the university, and I am a president of a sport club, I train children [...] Inside the university, I do not think that they need me, because they have never approached me or invited me to join them.” (Student B)

If we are to approach this lack of sense of belonging from the Dasein lens (being-in-the-world as introduced by Heidegger), which emphasizes the idea that human beings exist in a particular context and are constantly engaged in ongoing interactions with their environment, it can be understood that the lack of a sense of belonging experienced by students with disabilities at university is not simply a personal issue, but rather a complex interplay between the experiences of students with disabilities and their university environment. The Dasein lens provides a useful perspective in understanding this interplay, as it highlights the inseparability of students with disabilities from their environment: the university. Due to this inseparability, lack of involvement in social events and programmes is experienced as rejection and

marginalisation. The students are part of the university environment but feel that they do not belong. The quotes below demonstrate their desire to be part of the social life of the university and the benefits they believe they will gain from this:

“Although I have never participated in social events, I see them as a chance to show yourself to others. It is a chance for others to get to know you and be familiar with you [pause] it is also a way to voice your concerns and the concerns of other students with disabilities [sighs] I believe that social activities are an occasion for other people to see diversity at university.” (Student C)

“[...] these social events are a chance to stand in front of others and show ourselves. Moreover, it is a chance for others as well to see your situation and hear about the problems you are facing [...].” (Student D)

“I think it is better to let students with disabilities organize workshops and events, and invite lecturers and other students, this would be a way to get in touch with others [...].” (Student E)

These quotes show that students with disabilities see these social events as a bridge between them and other people, and an opportunity to socialize and connect with them.

4.2.2.2.7 Absence of inclusive policy

When asked about international and national policies that promote the inclusion of university students with disabilities and preserve their rights, only two participants mentioned that they are aware of some international conventions on the rights of people with disabilities, and of inclusive policies inside and outside universities. They reported:

“I know about disability welfare in Saudi Arabia (KSA), Equality Act in the UK, disability welfare law in KSA, CRPD, UNESCO, and other internal laws in a few

European universities, which promote inclusiveness and support for students with disabilities [...] and I got this information from searching in foreign universities and governmental websites [...].” (Student A)

“I know about the UNICEF and UNESCO as international organizations [...].” (Student B)

Most of the interviewed participants had no or only basic awareness about the existence of inclusive legislation and policies:

“[...] in Algeria, I am not sure [...] there are some clubs and associations, but I don’t think there is policy in relation to individuals or students with disabilities [...].” (Student A)

“I only hear about them (policies), but I have never seen a real application of any policy.” (Student B)

“I don’t see any application of any of the policies that preserve the rights of individuals with disabilities in Algeria. And I have no idea about the international level.” (Student E)

“I don’t think that such policies exist. Even if you do a search on governmental websites, you will find nothing [...].” (Student C)

“I have no idea [...].” (Student G)

“[...] if I had an idea about that (existence of policy), I would claim for my rights, I would not let anyone make me feel that they are doing me a favour when helping me out.” (Student C)

“ [...] these policies will make us feel included and safe at university [...] also it would be so great to have such policies, you will not have to keep reminding administration or support staff to accommodate your needs, because there is policy that defends people like us, and your rights would not be lost” (Student E)

“[...] I do not think that this exists, [...] I have never heard of that [...] [...] I wish such policies existed, lots of our problems would have been solved [...] but I think it needs lots of efforts such as funds and trained people in order to provide these policies first and apply them in reality second [...]” (Student D)

These quotes suggest that the existence of inclusive higher education policy could make a difference in the experiences of these students as it could make them feel supported and empowered to advocate for their rights. An inclusive higher education policy would place responsibility on the university to identify and eliminate the barriers that students with disabilities encounter at university, and to create a welcoming and supportive learning environment for all.

4.2.2.3 Attitudinal Barriers

According to Finkelstein (1993, 1996, 2001) Oliver (1990, 1999, 2013) and Allan (2008, 2013) attitudinal barriers to inclusion are assumptions, stereotype and misconceptions that discriminate against people with disabilities. In this study, participating students with disabilities reported that they have experienced negative attitudes and misconceptions from people outside the university but also from people at the university.

4.2.2.3.1 Negative attitudes inside the university

Participants described and interpreted experiences in relation to the way they are perceived, and treated by academics and administrative staff, even before their enrolment. For example, Student A reported encountering negative attitudes from a member of the admissions team who prevented him from enrolling in his desired course. He felt that his disability was viewed negatively, and as a result, he was unable to pursue his chosen course. He stated “[...] they did not accept me because of my disability, [I have a disability], but I have a mind [...]”. This student also shared another experience with one of his teachers:

“ [...] my XX teacher did not believe I got the best mark. Once she saw who I was, she was surprised and thought I cheated to pass her module with an excellent grade, and this is all because of my disability [...]” Student A

Other participants also shared experiences about the way academics and administrative staff perceive them. Participant G, for instance, stated that concerns about negative perceptions prevented him from disclosing his disability to staff and his lecturers prior to entry in higher education. He thought that this would affect the way they would treat him, and that he would be seen as 'a special case':

“ [...] you know, if I tell them, they won't be treating me the same after that, I mean they will treat me with pity, and I do not want that [...].” (Student G)

Student C stated that lecturers' negative perceptions and attitudes hurt her feelings and affected her educational achievement. She mentioned:

“I had no other barriers at university except for long distance, and mistreatment from lecturers. I mean, some lecturers destroy the student and make them hate university, especially the way they look at you [...] in fact, I feel that my level at university is lower compared to when I was at secondary school, and the whole university environment is responsible for that.” (Student C)

This student continued:

“ [...] some lecturers [...] do not bother to communicate with you [...] some of them provoke you, try to belittle you or underestimate you through their looks and offensive comments [...] I remember once a lecturer stood in the class and said to me in front of all my peers: do you think you can manage to teach like that? I do not know how I felt exactly, but I was so down, I said I am sure I can, but I was so hurt.” (Student C)

Students D and A also spoke of negative attitudes in class that might be shaped by the medical model:

“ [...] lecturers ask weird questions, such as how can I help you now? What can I do for you now? This is so annoying,

as if they are telling you indirectly that your place is not at university and that you cannot make it [...]" (Student D)

"[...] some lecturers are kind, but others think you are pretending or faking your disability, they do not believe in your capacities and abilities, so you have to work hard to prove yourself. [...]" (Student A)

According to some students, the way they are perceived by their lecturers is due to reasons related to experience, age, lack of training, and lack of empathy. They remarked:

"[...] you know it might be related to age, years of experience, maybe, as I find some elderly lecturers more supportive than others... Well, even some new lecturers are supportive...Umm... I think those who treat us well are taught how to deal with students with disabilities." (Student C)

"[...] I think that there is no training in relation to the way students with disabilities should be supported and treated. In addition, they cannot empathise with you because they are not in your shoes, they do not have a disability." (Student B)

"[...] you know what, the support we get from teachers is only a gesture of good will [...]." (Student A)

"Well, I really do not blame lecturers for that [lack of understanding and support], because they are very limited in terms of knowledge on disability and how to accommodate those with disabilities. Most of them say that they don't know how to help us, I believe they are not trained for that [...] teachers should be aware of how to treat people with disabilities, they should learn this [...]" (Student D)

In relation to negative attitudes from peers, only one participant commented on this, as he recounted some instances when his peers ignored his existence:

“Some students totally forget that you exist. The support office timetabled classes downstairs, but whenever there is an additional session, they (his peers) agree with the lecturer to schedule it upstairs. My classmates do not bother to remind the teacher of my case. And sometimes I keep waiting for them downstairs [...] this frustrates me a lot.” (Student B)

Arguably negative attitudes lead to the creation of many barriers for students with disabilities, including limited accessibility and support.

4.2.2.3.2 Negative attitudes outside the university context

The students' responses also revealed negative attitudes encountered outside the university context. They shared incidents which showed how these attitudes affect their experience. One of the participants stated that those who do not know him might undervalue his abilities, only because of his disability. He angrily expressed his annoyance about the way people within and outside the university perceive him:

“[...] at university or outside university, people who do not know me well make different scenarios in their heads about me. [...] some of them think that my parents provide me with financial support, but this is wrong and it annoys me a lot. They think that a person with a disability cannot do things on his own [...] they call me handicapped, but I just want to tell them, I do have a brain and I built myself up.” (Student A)

Interestingly, as Student A continued to talk about his experience regarding the way people around him in the Algerian context perceive his disability, he compared this to his experience in other western countries he visited. It can be interpreted, through the analogy he made, that disability is context dependent, and that other Western contexts are more developed in the area of inclusion than Algeria, as he mentioned that people with disabilities are treated with more respect in a European country that he visited. He said:

“ [...] I can tell you from my visit to XX (European country) that people with disabilities are treated in a different way from how they are treated in Algeria. Here in Algeria, they see you as a handicapped person, no matter how sporty you are. In Europe this does not exist [...] here, they see you as someone without a brain [...], but I do have a brain.” (Student A)

Another participant reported the same issue and expressed, in a low tone, his sadness about how people around him pity him, and how seeing him as a charitable case is something annoying to him:

“Sometimes it is about how people look at you, they see you as abnormal. I hear the word “poor” daily, from my home until I reach the university, which is something I strongly hate, and this has affected me a lot [...] even at university, people who do not know me have the same view towards me.” (Student B)

Similarly, a student expressed his concerns towards being labelled by the outside society, once they know about his hidden disability:

“[...] you know if someone, for instance, breaks something, they'll say he has temper or anger issues, but if someone with a mental disability does, they'll say that he is crazy [...].” (Student G)

Although the majority of participating students reported that they received positive support from their families (see section ‘family support’ above), two participants reported that this is not the case. These two students found it very difficult to cope with university life in the absence of university support and family support. For instance, student A noted:

“ [...] the first two years were very hard for me, as I enrolled in two different universities before coming to this institution, I had no financial support from my family back

then, and I haven't even received emotional support from them [...] I think they do not even know where I study or what course I am doing currently [...].” (Student A)

Student H expressed slightly different concerns:

“ [...] I am afraid to fail, I fear my parents' reaction to this, they do not know what I am going through, and even if I tell them I am sure they will not be understanding and supportive [...].” (Student H)

The students' experiences of negative attitudes reflect the impact of the medical model of disability, which perceives disability as deficiency that needs to be fixed and people with disabilities as incapable and inept (Lourens and Swartz, 2020). They also reflect the charity model, which is illustrated by the people who pity students with disabilities, and perceive them as 'special cases' that need help and sympathy (Amponsah-Bediako, 2013). This was apparent from the students' remarks and frustration towards being labelled and facing societal misconceptions and stereotypes that disregard their abilities. It can be deduced that negative attitudes in society that stem from the medical and charity model can create significant barriers for individuals with disabilities, which can limit their opportunity to fully participate and engage in different settings. These negative attitudes could be attributed to lack of knowledge and awareness about disability (Carballo et al, 2022). Moreover, the participants' responses suggest that people with disabilities receiving negative attitudes in the form of labelling and stereotypes are likely to feel excluded and marginalised, and this can limit their chances to access essential services like education, social activities, and employment.

4.3 Section two: Findings from interviews with disability support staff

This section presents findings that emerged from interviews with four disability support staff, which were conducted to answer the second research question:

- How do disability support staff facilitate the inclusion of students with disabilities in Algerian higher education?

After analysing the data from the interviews with the disability support staff, I was able to identify two superordinate themes: 'facilitators of inclusion' and 'barriers to inclusion'.

4.3.1 Facilitators of Inclusion

Disability support staff shared their perspectives and experiences regarding practices and accommodations they undertake to facilitate the inclusion of students with disabilities at their university. Under the superordinate theme of 'facilitators of inclusion', two subordinate themes were identified: 'environmental facilitators' and 'structural facilitators'.

Figure 4. Facilitators of inclusion

4.3.1.1 Environmental facilitators

Disability support staff referred to different environmental accommodations which were implemented since the establishment of the Disability Support Office to ensure that students with disability have access to different university buildings, and to support

their participation in university activities. This subordinate theme covers endeavors to enhance the physical accessibility of different buildings and university infrastructure.

Physical accessibility was the most frequently mentioned type of accommodation that disability support officers said they are providing for students with disabilities. According to them, it was only after the establishment of the Disability Support Office that students with disabilities could benefit from physical accessibility in the university. Physical accessibility includes building ramps, opening side doors, allocation of classes in ground floors, and adapting toilets and restrooms. Although, according to the disability support officers, much work is still needed to ensure physical accessibility and inclusivity for all students with disabilities, they are trying their best to enhance the physical accessibility in the university's infrastructure:

“ [...] the first thing we did, after the establishment of the Disability Support Office, was to facilitate students' access to campus buildings [...] we built ramps, and we asked the administration to open all side doors to facilitate moving between buildings and classes.” (Disability Support Officer A)

“[...] I am happy to tell you that the office contributed a lot in improving some aspects of accessibility. In the past, we had no access to restrooms, and there were stairs everywhere, even in ground floor buildings there were steps [...] The Disability Support Office is now accessible to everyone at the uni [sic], and it is at the main entrance of the university, in the ground floor with ramps.” (Disability Support Officer B)

“[...] through our meetings we suggested building ramps, and timetabling classes in ground floors [...]” (Disability Support Officer C)

“Indeed, our university did not adapt to the requirements of good physical accessibility until the increase in the number of students with disabilities enrolling in our university, especially those in wheelchairs [...]. The establishment of the Disability Support Office has contributed to the construction of corridors and ramps, in addition to the construction of adapted toilets [...]” (Disability Support Officer D)

The establishment of the Disability Support Office appears to have contributed to the improvement of environmental accessibility in the university. This reflects the good intentions and commitment of disability support officers to create an accessible environment for students with disabilities. While the participating disability support staff noted that there is still much work to be done in this area (see section 'environmental barriers' below), they do not seem to be aware of the extent of accessibility challenges students with disability experience, as reported by the students in section 'environmental barriers' above. This suggests a disconnect between the experiences of students with disabilities and the experiences of disability support staff, which will be discussed in the comparison section.

4.3.1.2 Structural facilitators

Through their responses, disability support staff referred to structural facilitators, highlighting the institutional support provided to students with disabilities by academics and disability support staff.

4.3.1.2.1 Academic support

The disability support staff spoke of the different academic accommodations they provide for students with disabilities, including extended due dates, extra time during exams, provision of readers and scribes during exams, rescheduling exam times and venues:

“In case we need to schedule remote exam sessions, or arrange separate classes for students with disabilities, we try to contact the department and try to find a solution. We also try to talk to lecturers to re-arrange exams for students with disabilities, who could not attend exams. We allow students with disabilities to have exams in separate classes, as we offer them extra time [...] We offer exam

papers in large print for those with visual impairments. For those who need assistance during exams, we try to allocate a reader or a scribe. Those with visual impairments, and those who have severe anxiety problems or those who use Braille often prefer to have exams in separate classrooms, so that they do not disturb their classmates [...] We help students to prepare for exams, some of the students come to the office to prepare for exams, and it is done with the provision of accessible resources and materials [...]" (Disability Support Officer A)

" [...] we do offer some academic facilities and resources in order to help students with disabilities, such as extra time during exams, access to exams with a companion (reader or scribe)...etc. [...]" (Disability Support Officer B)

"[...] we do provide extra time during exams [...] disabled students are allowed to have exams in a separate class if they want to, and we try to offer them breaks during exams. We try to offer a scribe for them as well." (Disability Support Officer C)

Assessment accommodations (such as extra time during exam, and provision of scribes or readers) reflect the positive intentions of the Disability Support Office to assist students with disabilities. However, these accommodations may not be adequate for all students with disabilities or consistent and available to all students with disabilities. This issue was raised in the section reporting findings from the interviews with students and will be discussed in the comparison section. Furthermore, when providing accommodations for students with disabilities, careful consideration should be given to the manner in which these accommodations are presented to ensure that they do not trigger, inadvertently, feelings of isolation and stigmatization for these students. Disability Support Officer A acknowledged this by stating that, sometimes, he feels hesitant to offer extensions for assignment submissions, to avoid misunderstandings:

"[...] extra time to send assignments is offered for students with disabilities in a way that does not make them

feel pitied... Sometimes students hesitate to ask for support and help, so we refrain from providing support, only because we do not want them to misunderstand our intention.” (Disability Support Officer A)

When it comes to the provision of educational materials and resources, the disability support staff referred to specific types of accommodations they provide for students with disabilities, such as uploading lectures and learning materials in the e-learning platform, and providing Dictaphones and large print materials.

“[...] as disability support officers, we try to be in touch with lecturers, and ask them to upload lectures, assignments, and resources on the e-learning platform. ” (Disability Support Officer A)

“[...] we also offer Dictaphones, large print materials, and we ask lecturers to upload lectures on the e-learning platform.” (Disability Support Officer B)

Disability support officers A and C, who are also lecturers, referred to accommodations they provide to students with disabilities who attend their classes:

As a lecturer I follow the instructions of the Disability Support Office to support my students, I even allocate additional sessions for students with disabilities who were absent, to explain lessons or assignments, and offer them resources that could help them.” (Disability Support Officer A)

“I personally provide my students with lectures and necessary learning materials” (Disability Support Officer C)

The disability support staff who participated in this study did not only speak of the accommodations they provide for students with disabilities. Some of them also referred to instances when they had to intervene to negotiate solutions for issues that affect the learning and progress of students with disabilities:

“[...] there was a disabled student who could not make it and submit her thesis by the due deadline, so we mediated

to ask the submission team to give her extra time. They refused at the beginning, but we managed to convince them providing enough proof of her condition and the difficulties she faced.” (Disability Support Officer A)

“[...] for example, I have a student who has psychological problems. I always try to negotiate possible support solutions with the department, other lecturers, and my other colleagues at the Disability Support Office. Especially when it comes to extra time to submit work or the dissertation...etc. [...]” (Disability Support Officer B)

“ [...] I belong to the department of XX, they often call me to say there is a student, for example with visual impairment, could you help her to connect with the department, or the Disability Support Office in order to see whether they can manage rescheduling exams for her, this is an example of us trying to facilitate the academic life of disabled students [...].” (Disability Support Officer C)

It appears that the responsibility to request accommodations from lecturers lies with disability support officers, which might indicate a potential issue with the university system to support students with disabilities. This could possibly relate to inability of the university to build an inclusive approach to accommodate these students. This may result in inconsistencies in accommodations across different lecturers, which can lead to lack of provision of accessible learning materials to some students with disabilities, unless they seek them out in person, through the Disability Support Office or lecturers.

The commitment to accommodate the needs of students with visual impairments or those with hearing impairments is evident through the provision of large print materials and recorders, for instance. However, it is important to mention that these are only a few accessibility measures, which do not address possible barriers that students with other types of disabilities (e.g. learning disabilities) might encounter. Furthermore, the use of the word “try” from disability support officers might indicate inconsistency in the provision of learning materials for students with disabilities in this university. Additionally, the statement “I personally provide my students with lectures and

necessary learning materials” (Disability Support Officer C), may denote that not all lecturers are aware of the need to support students with disabilities, and not all of them prioritize accommodating students with disabilities in their classes. Similarly, the fact that the submission team refused to give the student extra time shows the lack of understanding and empathy towards the challenges faced by students with disabilities. This situation underscores the importance of the Disability Support Office’s role in advocating for the requirements of students with disabilities and working to create a more inclusive academic environment. However, it is not enough for disability support officers to advocate for support each time, or provide accommodations on an ad-hoc basis. Rather, all parties (administrative team, academics, and disability support staff) should collaborate to create an inclusive academic environment. The need for collaboration between different departments and services at the university will come up in the ‘structural barriers’ section and later on in the comparison section.

4.3.1.2.2 Psychological support

Two of the four disability support officers who participated in the study mentioned psychological support:

“ [...] Disability Support Office works with psychologists to support those students and prepare them for exams at any time, mental health support and counselling services are available for all students in our office, especially during exam periods.” (Disability Support Officer A)

“ [...] the academic facilities offered by our university to allow students with disabilities to engage in the learning process as their peers are diverse, including counselling service that provides psychological support for students with disabilities... we have a full time psychologist who schedules meetings with students and organizes counselling sessions with them [...]” (Disability Support Officer B)

The provision of counselling services demonstrates awareness of the need to make emotional and psychological support available to students with disabilities at this university. It indicates that staff members are aware of the possible challenges that students with disabilities may face and the need for mental health support. However, as indicated in the section reporting findings from the interviews with students, this psychological support does not seem to reach all students with disabilities. This suggests issues with communication, which will be discussed in the comparison section.

4.3.1.2.3 Social engagement support

During the interviews, the disability support staff also spoke of efforts to facilitate the participation of students with disabilities in decision-making, extra-curricular activities, workshops and events at university. According to the disability support, this can foster a sense of belonging as it encourages students with disabilities to socialize with others and make new networks:

“ [...] we try to organize events and workshops through our office, and we invite those registered with the office to join us [...] the invite is for everyone [...] the aim behind those meetings is to enable students with disabilities to maintain contact and build relations with others at university, in order to socialize and mix with others.” (Disability Support Officer A)

“[...] students with disabilities are involved in social activities; [...] they are invited to Disability Support Office meetings, so they are involved in the decision-making process with the Disability Support Office. They are involved whenever there is a ceremony [...] what I suggest is to create activities for them. Why not give them the chance to lead conferences and organize events. Why not give them leadership. This way they will feel more valued, they will feel that they can be leaders within their community” (Disability Support Officer B)

“ [...] students with disabilities are generally supported by our office to join clubs and associations inside and outside the university, but not all of them are keen to join these

clubs, for fear of being excluded or feeling discriminated.”(Disability Support Officer C)

It is apparent from the responses of the disability support staff that they endeavour to engage students with disabilities in the decision making process, and in extra-curricular activities, clubs and associations. These quotes indicate the conviction of the disability support staff that social interactions at university are important and can provide students with disabilities with opportunities to meet other people, build new relationships, spread awareness about disability and inclusion, and raise their concerns in relation to the barriers they encounter at university. However, as indicated in the section reporting findings from the interviews with students with disabilities, encouraging students to become involved in decision-making and to join events, clubs and associations may not be enough to address the barriers that prevent them from participating in these activities. The Disability Support Office should actively remove any barriers that may prevent students with disabilities from participating, and ensure the creation of a welcoming and supportive environment within these clubs and associations.

To sum up, based on their responses in the interviews, it appears that the disability support officers are keen to provide support for students with disabilities and have a number of processes in place to achieve this. They seem to strive to find ways to accommodate and assist these students in order to help them succeed. They described the role of the Disability Support Office as a resource that aims to assist students with disabilities with accommodations, facilitate accessibility to buildings, offer academic and psychological support, and encourage the engagement of these students in university events, and in the decision-making process. However, as suggested in the section reporting findings from the interviews with students with

disabilities, the efforts made by the Disability Support Office may not be sufficient to adequately support students with disabilities, and to realize inclusion at this university. It would appear that a more proactive approach with more inclusive resources and strategies is needed in order to effectively support these students.

The next section addresses the obstacles and difficulties encountered by members of the Disability Support Office as they work to support students with disabilities.

4.3.2 Barriers to Inclusion

Disability support staff in this study did not only share the helpful strategies they use to help students with disabilities. They also identified several obstacles that hinder the access and participation of students with disabilities at this university, as well as barriers that impede their own ability to create an inclusive environment and effectively support these students. The superordinate theme 'barriers to inclusion' comprises the subordinate themes of 'environmental barriers' and 'structural barriers'. This is in line with disability advocates such as Finkelstein (1993, 1996, 2001) Oliver (1990, 1999, 2013) and Allan (2008, 2013) who used this classification to refer to the disabling conditions that limit the opportunities and participation of people with disabilities.

Figure 5. Barriers to inclusion

4.3.2.1 Environmental barriers

As discussed in Chapter 2, disability advocates have long pointed out that features of the physical environment can be disabling by restricting the free movement and full functioning of people with impairments (Finkelstein, 1993, 1996, 2001; Oliver, 1990, 1999, 2013; Allan, 2008, 2013). Their calls for the removal of these barriers have led to positive changes, however, much work is still required to ensure that the physical environment is accessible to all (Oliver, 2013). The current study confirms this. In spite of the attempts of the Disability Support Office to address environmental accessibility issues, and to remove architectural barriers, accessibility in the university infrastructure was the most challenging aspect reported by disability support staff:

“[...] I don’t think that there is another barrier at university that could have a strong impact on students’ experiences more than physical accessibility [...] Students with disabilities are more likely to drop out due to the physical barriers and lack of physical accessibility [...]” (Disability Support Officer A)

“[...] in some places, such as the old buildings, there is no accessibility [...] there are no elevators in the whole university. Even buses are not accessible [...]” (Disability Support Officer A)

“[...] buses are not accessible for students with disabilities. I think we also need to allocate buses that can help students to move between university buildings, because as I told you our uni [sic] is so big and it sometimes takes a long time to reach some buildings especially between sessions [...] it would have been easier if there were shortcuts, or buses inside the university.” (Disability Support Officer B)

“ [...] another thing I would like to mention is the library; none of the existing libraries is accessible [...]. They do not afford accessibility for disabled students, mainly those in wheelchairs [...] also, we need parking spaces that are specific for disabled students, we need signs to show

whether the space is accessible or not for those students
...etc.” (Disability Support Officer D)

Additionally, the disability support officers remarked that due to inaccessible infrastructure, students with disabilities might feel dependent on others to help them access university buildings:

“[...] one of the rights of students is to access the library, and access to the library is done through the help of other students or members of the Disability Support Office.”
(Disability Support Officer D)

This issue could be related to inadequate consideration of the rights and requirements of students with disabilities, as another interviewee highlighted that sometimes heads of departments do not take into consideration students with disabilities when scheduling classes.

“ [...] sometimes heads of departments do not take students with disabilities into account when scheduling classes so not all classes for groups that include students with disabilities are scheduled in ground floors [...] fellow-students are obliged to give a hand to their disabled classmates and help them get to upper floor classes.”(Disability Support Officer C)

Allocation of classes in inaccessible settings makes students with disabilities obliged to seek help from their peers to access classes. Although, as noted in the section presenting the findings from the interviews with students, peer support is appreciated by students with disabilities and is considered a positive aspect of their university experience, having to rely on peers to access classes can affect their sense of independence and may trigger feelings of resentment and exclusion. The disability support officers' responses suggest that more effort is needed to ensure accessibility for all students on an independent and equal basis.

The participating disability support staff made some suggestions to enhance the quality of the physical environment. For them a good physical environment should be disability friendly, and should take into consideration the difficulties that students with disabilities may encounter inside and outside the university. They advocated for practical solutions such as installing elevators, escalators, accessible restrooms, signposting and automatic doors, which, they believe, are essential to address accessibility issues:

“ [...] according to my experience, the first thing to do is renovate old and inaccessible buildings [...] a practical and good physical environment for disabled students must start from the student’s home, from transportation, to passages, to university campus, to the university hall. Students with disabilities should benefit from quality physical accessibility in all areas of the university, including passages, adapted buses, sidewalks and elevators, corridors and signposts... etc. (Disability Support Officer A)

“ I suggest installing elevators, cuz [sic] we have none. I also suggest having escalators, accessible restrooms, and automatic doors [...].” (Disability Support Officer C)

Implementation of the above suggestions could result in an accessible physical environment that is disability friendly and takes into consideration the difficulties that students with disabilities may encounter inside and outside the university. However, as will be seen in the next session, the implementation of these suggestions is hindered by structural barriers.

4.3.2.2 Structural barriers

As noted in Chapter 2, structural barriers include restrictive policies, procedures, regulations and practices (Finkelstein, 1993, 1996, 2001; Oliver, 1990, 1999, 2013). Structural barriers can also limit the capacity of relevant professionals, such as educators or support staff, to facilitate inclusion and participation (Allan 2008,

2013). Through the interviews, the disability support staff revealed that they are facing several structural barriers that significantly hinder their ability to create an inclusive environment and provide effective support to students with disabilities. These barriers are organised into five sub-themes, which are summed up in the figure below:

Figure 6. Structural barriers to inclusion

4.3.2.2.1 Lack of Financial support for the Disability Support Office

The participating disability support officers revealed that they do not receive any funds from the Algerian ministry of higher education or the university because the Disability Support Office is not yet an official support mechanism at this university – it has voluntary status. According to the disability support staff, lack of funding undermines their efforts to facilitate inclusion at their university and makes them feel helpless as they cannot afford reasonable accommodations and adequate support for students with disabilities:

“ [...] there is a lack of learning resources [...] This is due to insufficient budget [...] due to national authorities' reluctance to make the Disability Support Office official.” (Disability Support Officer A)

“[...] we do not have enough budget to afford new technological materials [...]” (Disability Support Officer B)

“[...] sometimes disability support officers pay from their own money to provide equipment and facilities to those students. When we ask administration for budget, they say

we have no budget for these things, since it is still not recognized as an official office [...]” (Disability Support Officer C)

“[...] we asked the ministry to make the Disability Support Office an official entity, and to provide us with budget to accommodate the students’ needs, but no response was received.” (Disability Support Officer D)

These quotes indicate that insufficient budget is a major challenge faced by the Disability Support Office. The lack of financial support acts as a hurdle for them and prevents them from providing necessary accommodations to students with disabilities. This indicates that addressing the issue of disability inclusion in this university requires not only efforts from the disability support staff, but also policy changes at the wider national level to accommodate these students. The responses of the disability support staff indicate that they have been trying to raise awareness about the area of disability and inclusion and to obtain funds, but their efforts have been unsuccessful. This emphasizes the need for the MESERS to recognize this particular office as an official support mechanism within the university and to allocate adequate funds to enable disability support staff to provide inclusive support consistently to all students with disabilities.

4.3.2.2.2 Lack of training

Participants also reported lack of training for staff as a structural barrier. They consider training in relation to inclusive education an important step towards supporting students with disabilities effectively. The participants remarked that lack of training can result in lack of understanding of the requirements of students with disabilities, and difficulty in providing appropriate and inclusive support. They emphasized the need for training and its importance in building the skills and knowledge required to accommodate students with disabilities appropriately and adequately:

“[...] disability support staff and lecturers should receive training on inclusive education and types of support and reasonable accommodations they should provide to students with disabilities.” (Disability Support Officer A)

“[...] we need experts [...] in inclusive education, in order to learn about techniques and methodologies we should use. We need to have training about the tools and instruments that each category of disabled learners need [...] we need to be trained in order to know how to help. It happened to me once, I had a student with vision problems [...] she could not read easily what lecturers wrote on the board, and even when writing during the exams she had difficulties, so she needs somebody to help her.” (Disability Support Officer B)

Disability Support Officer C (who is also a lecturer) mentioned that she has developed the strategies she is using to support her students with disabilities through personal efforts:

“[...] it is only some personal strategies that I have adopted from watching videos or reading about inclusion, and on how to support learners with different disabilities. We have never received such training. I think that the type of training we should receive as disability support staff and lecturers should be about how to deal with students with disabilities, because some of them (lecturers) perceive it as doing the job for students with disabilities, but [...] they should let them work by themselves, in order to offer them a sense of autonomy.” (Disability Support Officer C)

Moreover, it seems that lack of training can result in misunderstanding of disability related issues and of the challenges that students with disability may experience. Lack of training may lead academics or support staff to think that some students are exaggerating, lying or faking their disabilities in order to get access to support:

“The problem we encounter with such category of students is sometimes they use disability as a way to gain compassion from others [...] we need to be trained to be able to differentiate between the real need of students from students who just want a good mark. (Disability Support Officer B)

“ [...] the problem with disabled students sometimes, they exaggerate the severity of their disability [...] if we are trained adequately, we can know how to handle and accommodate each student, and we will be able to figure out who is faking it and who is not. We had some cases when students tried to fake their disabilities, and use their disabilities for their advantage [...]” (Disability Support Officer C)

Gaps in understanding of disability coupled with societal misconceptions can influence the way different people interact with individuals with disabilities. For example, in this study, this can affect the way academic and support staff perceive and interact with students with disabilities, which can lead to difficulty in understanding fully the challenges that students with disabilities face. This can lead them (academics and support staff) sometimes to suspect and question the severity of the disability of their students. This indicates that it is important for academic and support staff to be aware of their own biases and to seek out training and resources that can help them better understand and support students with disabilities. It also highlights how crucial it is to understand that disability is an intricate experience that differs from one person to another, and it can be challenging to determine the impact of a disability on an individual. The suggestion of disability support staff that some students may be exaggerating or faking their disabilities, in order to take advantage of support, implies lack of specialized training about disability and inclusion. This can lead to assumptions and stereotypes about the severity or authenticity of a student's disability, which can result in lack of support and in discrimination. Training for disability support staff is particularly important because it can help dispel misconceptions and promote essential understanding about the additional support needs and experiences of individuals with disabilities.

4.3.2.2.3 Lack of collaboration

Collaboration has been identified as a crucial aspect for providing inclusive education (Florian, 2017; Hedegaard-Soerensen et al, 2017). Participants in this study highlighted lack of teamwork within the university and lack of collaboration between Algerian universities in raising awareness in relation to the obstacles that students with disabilities encounter in higher education. They referred to the importance of collaboration between higher authorities, academics, administration staff, and disability support staff on different levels such as promoting inclusion, spreading awareness on disability-related issues, making the Disability Support Office an official entity, and sharing these ideas with all Algerian universities:

“[...] collaboration between different systems and offices at university is necessary, to exchange expertise and strategies that may help in supporting students with disabilities. Also, collaborations at the national level between different universities, in order to spread awareness in relation to the area of inclusion and support for students with disabilities.” (Disability Support Officer A)

“I think we are far away from having an inclusive university. [...] there is no collaboration [...] teachers do not collaborate with us, they take what the Disability Support Office says, sometimes they apply it and sometimes not. There is no teamwork [...] teamwork is in the Disability Support Office only, apart from that, there is no collaboration.” (Disability Support Officer B)

“[...] we tried to contact other universities to join this program, to open disability support offices, and to spread inclusive thinking. Unfortunately, no response was received. Through our office, we are trying to spread the idea of having an office that supports university students with disabilities, because many students with disabilities

drop out just because they are not supported [...]"
(Disability Support Officer C)

These quotes suggest that lack of collaboration is an additional reason behind accessibility issues and inconsistency in support provision for students with disabilities. Lack of collaboration between the Disability Support Office at this university and other support mechanisms, such as academic staff, administrative staff, and the ministry of higher education, can negatively influence the effectiveness of support for students with disabilities. Furthermore, lack of collaboration can lead to lack of awareness of the additional support needs of these students among other staff and departments. This can make it more difficult for students to fully participate in campus life. This highlights the need for a culture of collaboration and teamwork within the university to ensure that students with disabilities are supported and included in the learning environment.

4.3.2.2.4 Students' reluctance to disclose disability

Reluctance of students with disabilities to disclose their disability to the Disability Support Office was another structural barrier highlighted by the disability support staff. According to the disability support staff, when students disclose their disability, the disability support staff can work with them to identify their support needs and provide the necessary accommodations. However, disability support staff revealed that not all students with disabilities show a willingness to disclose their disability to the Disability Support Office. According to them, this is related to many reasons such as shyness, fear of being marginalized, fear of being labeled and stigmatised, and thinking that disclosing would change nothing for them. For disability support staff, unwillingness to disclose makes their job in reaching all students even more complicated, since the number of students with disabilities remains ambiguous. They reported different

experiences, where students refuse to reveal their disabilities, especially those with hidden disabilities:

“Well there are surely people with disability that we do not know, because [...] disability is not only what we see. Sometimes it is psychological problems, depression, chronic diseases...etc., [...] such students do not like to be labeled as having a disability, and are not registered with the Disability Support Office [...] Almost 90% of the registered students have visible disabilities [...] students with hidden disabilities do not like to disclose having a disability [...] because they fear not being accepted by others. Students also feel ashamed or refrain from speaking out for fear of being rejected or negatively treated by administrative staff and academics. I know many students with hidden disabilities who did not declare to me, until the day of the exam, or a week before the exam, students with hearing impairments, students with severe anxiety and others with chronic illnesses...etc. This puts me in a difficult situation with regards to providing support for those students [...]” (Disability Support Officer A)

“[...] sometimes we discover that a person has a disability only when he is in class.” (Disability Support Officer C)

“Of course there are students who don’t want to reveal their disability or illness, because they feel they don’t need to, or think that nobody can do much for them, so they do not seek support. However, others register with the office, because they need help and support, and without support, they will feel lost. Registering with the office helps us know which type of support students need.” (Disability Support Officer B)

Disability Support Officer A shared a broader perspective:

“[...] Another thing is that the culture of inclusive education requires the university to provide the necessary support, not because I am disabled, because I am a student. Some students refrain from asking for support because they do not want to feel that they are treated in a special way or as charitable cases [...] this will make them feel inept and at the mercy of others. Whereas inclusion requires creating equal opportunities for all students, and here lies the difference between integration and inclusion.” (Disability Support Officer A)

As indicated by the disability support staff but also by the students (see section 'attitudinal barriers' above) students with disabilities may be reluctant to disclose their disabilities for a variety of reasons. Some students with hidden disabilities may fear discrimination and stigmatization. This highlights the negative attitudes that still exist towards individuals with disabilities in the Algerian society. However, the fear of being rejected or negatively treated by staff can prevent students with disabilities from receiving the support they need to succeed at university. Another reason for lack of disclosure may be that some students with disabilities are unaware of their rights, or may not know how to advocate for their rights at university. Therefore, it is important for the university and Disability Support Office to create a welcoming and inclusive environment that encourages individuals to disclose their disabilities.

Moreover, reluctance to disclose a disability can also have a negative impact on the effectiveness of the Disability Support Office. If students with disabilities do not disclose their disabilities, they may not receive the accommodations and support they need to progress and succeed at university. Additionally, reluctance of disclosure may prevent the Disability Support Office from getting accurate information about the number of students with disabilities and types of disabilities and this may hinder the disability support staff from providing effective support for these students.

4.3.2.2.5 Absence of inclusive policy

When asked about awareness of inclusive legislation and policies, participants showed awareness of the national legislation and policies that promote inclusion and aim to protect the rights of people with disabilities in the Algerian society and of students with disabilities in schools but they said that they are not aware of any inclusive policy about students with disabilities in the university context. For example,

Disability Support Officer C stated: “we have no inclusive policy for disabled people in higher education [...] but for other levels yes.” (Disability Support Officer C).

Others referred to international conventions and treaties, which indicated their awareness of the existence of inclusion policies not only at the national level but at the international level as well:

“There are different laws that seek to protect the rights of people with disabilities in the Algerian society [...] there is only one law that talks about supporting students with disabilities and protecting the right to education for all students which is adopted from UNICEF [...] and this is a general one that applies to all levels and is not specific to higher education [...]” (Disability Support Officer A)

“ [...] I do not know much about international legislation, but I know UNICEF and UNESCO conventions that were introduced to help students with disabilities. [...] I know about the national legislation in relation to preserving the rights of people with disabilities in society and in primary, middle and secondary schools, but not at university.” (Disability Support Officer B)

These responses highlight the lack of specific legislation and policies that are tailored to support students with disabilities in higher education in Algeria. While there are existing laws that aim to protect the rights of people with disabilities in the Algerian society, there seems to be a gap when it comes to ensuring that these individuals are able to fully access and participate in higher education:

“[...] none of these policies or laws is available at university. [...] we try to take some policies from other international contexts, and try to adapt them or make them fit with the Algerian context. We also take tips and strategies from universities abroad and apply them to our university in order to adapt the environment for our students with disabilities and to accommodate them.” (Disability Support Officer A)

Moreover, there appears to be lack of concrete implementation and application of the wider policies that promote inclusion for individuals with disabilities in society. While laws and policies may exist on paper, according to the participants, they are not effectively enforced or implemented in practice.

“ [...] the rules and laws are there, they are very well written, but their application is almost not found in our education system, in our society, and even in our everyday life. We need to have things implemented specifically for students with disabilities.” (Disability Support Officer B)

This quote suggests that the rights of individuals with disabilities in the Algerian society are still not fully recognized and prioritized. It highlights that it is not enough to introduce policies and laws to protect the rights of people with disabilities; it is important to ensure that these policies are effectively enforced and implemented.

The disability support officers highlighted the need for a comprehensive approach to promote inclusion at this university. This included both introduction of inclusive policies, and implementation of practical changes such as making the Disability Support Office official, allocating funding to it, providing training opportunities for academic and support staff, and spreading awareness on disability issues through conferences and events. Disability support staff further emphasized that inclusive education should start from primary school and should be promoted at all levels to ensure good learning experience and smooth transitions.

“Government and establishments should start considering students with disabilities in their policies, planning and training [...] training opportunities should be open to all lecturers and university staff. Additionally, promoting inclusive education at all levels should start from primary schools in order to ensure quality transitions for students with disabilities, and to help them overcome the different barriers they may encounter.” (Disability Support Officer A)

“ [...] I suggest that our public policies should start working with the concept of inclusion, and raise awareness about it.” (Disability Support Officer B)

“ [...] there is still a lot to be done, for example making the Disability Support Office an official entity, having financial support, recruiting trainers, having training sessions for all staff [...] we cannot achieve all of that without legislation that supports inclusion in higher education.” (Disability Support Officer C)

“ [...] We need more collaborations, and more conferences and seminars, in order to raise awareness about vulnerable groups at universities.” (Disability Support Officer D)

These quotes suggest that the lack of inclusive policy to support students with disabilities at university can make it difficult for the Disability Support Office to ensure that students are protected from discrimination, marginalization and negative attitudes. Without policy in place, it can be challenging for disability support officers to create a safe and inclusive environment for all students with disabilities. Moreover, disability support staff may struggle to effectively advocate for the rights of students with disabilities, due to lack of necessary training and guidance on how to provide effective support for students with disabilities, and how to ensure their full participation and inclusion. Furthermore, the absence of a policy can also result in lack of understanding among staff and students without disabilities about the nature of disability and how to support students with disabilities.

4.4 Section three: Comparing the experiences of students with disabilities with the experiences of the disability support staff

Both groups of respondents revealed some positive practices and accommodations that promote the inclusion of students with disabilities, but also barriers that affect their participation and progress. Accordingly, this section presents a synthesis of the most

prevalent themes that appeared in the findings of both groups of participants. It was apparent while analysing both data sets that there were some similarities between student and staff experiences, however, there were a few differences as well. Therefore, findings from both data sets were compared and are presented in this section.

The comparison between the findings from the interviews with students and the findings from the interviews with the disability support staff led to the development of themes that vary somewhat from those that appear in the previous findings sections. These themes emerged from the comparison step, highlighting similarities and differences between the experiences and viewpoints of students with disabilities and disability support staff: These themes are presented in the following table.

Superordinate themes	Subordinate themes
Environmental factors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Infrastructure accessibility • Transportation
Structural factors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Academic support • Social engagement support • Peer support • Emotional support • Family involvement • Reluctance to disclose • Training • Collaboration • Financial support • Inclusive policy

Attitudinal factors

- Attitudes towards disability

Table 2. Themes emerging from the comparison of the findings from the interviews with students with disabilities and the interviews with disability support staff.

4.4.1 Environmental factors

As noted in Chapter 2, disability advocates have long argued that the environment privileges ability and disregards the needs of people of disabilities thus restricting their opportunities (Finkelstein, 1993, 1996, 2001; Oliver, 1990, 1999, 2013; Allan, 2008, 2013). A comparison of the data from the interviews with the two groups of participants (students with disabilities and disability support staff), revealed similar and dissimilar views regarding environmental factors that affect the inclusion of students with disability in this university. The findings indicated a diverse range of opinions regarding the efficacy of existing infrastructural accommodations. Notably, disability support staff spoke of a set of constructive measures implemented by the Disability Support Office to promote physical accessibility, which have been assumed to be effective. However, students with disabilities highlighted enduring obstacles that undermine the accessibility of the university infrastructure.

4.4.1.1 Infrastructure accessibility

Both students and staff agreed upon the existence of ramps, and the allocation of classes in ground floors, however, there was variation in the views about the quality, effectiveness and consistency of these accommodations. In relation to the existence of ramps, students confirmed that they exist, for example:

“[...] I study in a building that has a ramp [...]” (Student B)

“[...] there are facilities that exist like corridors and ramps for those with mobility disabilities and those in wheelchairs [...]” (Student F)

However, the quality of the ramps was an issue raised by some students, who stated that the ramps in the main entrances of buildings and lecture halls were not accessible. One student described them as : “[...] climbing a mountain [...]” adding “[...] ‘you can tell that these facilities were not made well [...]’ (Student E). Therefore, it seems that existing accessibility features such as ramps may not be as effective as disability support staff believe them to be, and may not meet the requirements of all students with mobility constraints.

Allocation of classes in ground floors was another aspect that staff mentioned as part of their efforts to ensure accessibility to buildings and classes. For example one disability support officer stated:“ [...] we always suggest to the administration to timetable classes in ground floors [...]” (Disability Support Officer C). However, one of the students indicated that she had to raise the issue herself:

“[...] in my first year, I tried to raise this issue to the administration, and they managed to timetable all my classes in the ground floor [...]” (Student E)

Although, it appears that the administration was responsive to this student’s needs, it seems that they are not following a proactive approach to ensure infrastructure accessibility for all students with disabilities. This was apparent in the response of student B, who highlighted that the allocation of classes on the ground floor is not done routinely for groups that include students with disabilities. Rather, they have to raise this issue repeatedly:

“[...] you know they cannot do it each year, and you have to remind them every time, [...]” (Student B)

This puts an additional burden on students and can make them feel marginalised.

Despite the efforts the Disability Support Office makes to address accessibility issues, inaccessible infrastructure appears to remain among the major challenges at this university as reported by both students and disability support staff, who highlighted several aspects of inaccessible infrastructure, including stairs. For example, student B noted: “[...] even the library has stairs [Laughs] [...], I have had no other issues except for stairs.” The inaccessibility of the library was also highlighted by Disability Support Officer D, who mentioned:

“[...] all of them (libraries) are situated in upper floors. They do not afford accessibility for disabled students, mainly those in wheelchairs [...].” (Disability Support Officer D).

Accessibility of toilets and bathrooms was also reported by students with disabilities to be limited, and sanitary facilities were described as not disability-friendly. For instance, students E and F said:

“[...] bathrooms have steps leading up to it, which meant I could not get there on my own [...].” (Student E).

“[...] bathrooms are inaccessible for students with disabilities, especially those with mobility disabilities and those with visual impairments [...].” (Student F)

However, the disability support staff said that renovations to make washrooms and toilets accessible for all students started as soon as the Disability Support Office was established: “the establishment of the Disability Support Office has contributed to [...] the construction of adapted toilets [...].” (Disability Support Officer D).

It remains unclear whether these adapted toilets are fully accessible for all students with disabilities, or whether they only address the additional support needs of students with specific disabilities. Therefore, while the construction of adapted toilets is a positive step towards accessibility, it appears that there are still gaps in addressing specific accessibility issues.

These discrepancies suggest a clear gap between the perceptions of disability support staff about the facilities they provide, and the experiences of students with disabilities. This highlights the need for the university to undertake significant improvements in its physical infrastructure to ensure that it is accessible and inclusive for all students, without discrimination. Both groups of participants made suggestions for making the university physical environment more accessible and more welcoming for students with disabilities. For example, student A and Disability Support Officer C proposed renovating buildings and installing elevators as a way to ensure accessibility to all students without exception.

“[...] old buildings should be renovated and lifts should be built to help those with physical disabilities to move freely [...]” (Student A)

“I suggest the use of elevators, cuz [sic] we have none. I also suggest having escalators, accessible restrooms, and automatic doors [...]” (Disability Support Officer C)

Despite the differences in staff perceptions and student experiences highlighted above, it seems that disability support staff and students with disabilities are raising similar concerns regarding the inaccessibility of buildings and both are advocating for solutions to enhance the university infrastructure.

4.4.1.2 Transportation

Both students with disabilities and disability support staff highlighted the issue of university transportation and agreed upon the inaccessibility of buses and its effects on students with disabilities. From the perspective of both groups, this issue is not only limited to the university environment; public transportation is also an issue for these students. Inaccessible transportation is one of the challenges that students with disabilities face outside the university and inside the university. According to staff and

students, this hinders the true inclusion of individuals with disabilities in Algerian society, and can make them feel marginalised. In this regard, some students said:

“[...] I was suffering with urban transportation [...] sometimes, I had to pay for two seats just to bring my wheelchair with me on the bus.” (Student B)

Staff have also highlighted the issue of inaccessible transportation and the need to resolve it:

“[...] even buses are not accessible; some parents are obliged to travel daily to get their sons and daughters with disabilities to university.” (Disability Support Officer A)

“a practical and good physical environment for disabled students must start [...] from transportation [...] students with disabilities should benefit from quality physical accessibility [...] including [...] adapted buses [...].” (Disability Support Officer D)

Inaccessible transportation has a direct impact on students with disabilities, as it restricts their access to the university. Inaccessible transportation outside the university reveals a problem that is situated outside the university environment. This reflects a societal issue that challenges students with disabilities, and highlights their marginalisation within the Algerian society at the macro level.

4.4.2 Structural factors

The impact of structural factors on the experiences of people with disabilities are well documented in the literature (Finkelstein, 1993, 1996, 2001; Oliver, 1990, 1999, 2013; Allan, 2008, 2013). In this study, comparison of findings from students with disabilities and disability support staff shed light on nuanced perceptions about the quality of support provided within the university context. It was apparent that structural factors play a significant role in shaping the challenges faced by students with disabilities and the effectiveness of support provided by disability support staff. These structural

factors influence the immediate environment of students with disabilities and the ability of disability support officers to fully support them. On one hand, the findings highlighted factors that contribute to the positive experiences of students with disabilities, such as institutional support in the form of academic assistance from disability support staff, academic staff, and peers, as well as family support. These factors were seen as instrumental in facilitating positive experiences for students with disabilities within the university environment. On the other hand, the findings also revealed structural barriers that hinder the participation and progress of students with disabilities. These barriers include issues related to lack of emotional support, students' reluctance to disclose their disability, lack of financial support for both students with disabilities and disability support staff, insufficient training and knowledge among disability support staff, limited collaboration between disability support staff and other university staff, and the absence of clear policies and guidelines for inclusive practice in higher education.

4.4.2.1 Academic support

Positive relationships between students with disabilities, academic staff and disability support staff can create an inclusive and supportive environment that fosters academic engagement for students with disabilities. In this study, students with disabilities reported having positive relationships with academic staff and disability support staff who showed interest in their progress and provided individualized support. They also reported positive experiences with peers, who helped students with disabilities during their university journey. These positive experiences not only benefit the students with disabilities academically but also enhance their sense of belonging.

Some students with disabilities reported positive relationships with academic staff that promoted academic engagement:

“some lecturers [...] try to support you with everything they can [...]” (Student D)

“[...] my XX course teacher always offers to write for me in class [...]” Student E

The disability support staff also highlighted the help provided from lecturers to students with disabilities. Three of the disability support officers are also lecturers, and already had the chance to teach students with disabilities. Their position at Disability Support Office provides them with the opportunity to apply the knowledge they have on inclusive education, accommodating students with disabilities, and adjusting teaching and assessment methods in their classes. For example, Disability Support Officer A and Disability Support Officer B stated:

“[...] I teach students with dyslexia in my class [...] I always provide them with alternative exam methods, [...] I avoid asking them to do an oral presentation, so that they do not feel embarrassed [...]” Disability Support Officer A

“[...] I am supervising one of the students with disabilities, she suffers from[XX, and she is late for her submission, I mentioned her case to the faculty and requested from them to extend the due date of her submission, so that she can have a chance to submit [...] you know this is part of inclusion [...]” (Disability Support Officer B)

Students with disabilities and disability support staff also commented on academic support provisions, including the provision of learning materials and resources, as well as assessment accommodations. However, comparison of the responses revealed differences between staff’s perceptions and students’ experiences.

Disability support staff spoke about a range of educational adjustments they offer in order to support the learning experience of students with disabilities. This includes making available a variety of aids for these students, such as accessible learning

materials, including large print lecture notes and exam sheets, and encouraging academic staff to upload lectures and lecture notes to the online learning platform.

“[...] we [...] ask them (academics) to upload lectures, assignments, and resources on the E-learning platform.”
(Disability Support Officer B)

“[...] we make sure to print lectures in large prints for students with visual impairment [...]” (Disability Support Officer A)

However, the responses of the majority of students with disabilities tell a different story about availability of academic resources and learning materials. Only one student reported a positive experience, in relation to library resources, as he mentioned “Extended loans for library books is what I prefer the most [...]”. Other students reported challenges due to lack of accessible learning materials, and unadjusted teaching methods and resources.

“None of my teachers provides lectures or notes before the session, [...]” (Student C)

“[...] I find it difficult to follow some teachers’ pace [...]”
(Student F)

“ [...] if the reference list was in large print, or maybe an audio library existed it would have been great.” (Student B)

Disability support staff also noted that despite the efforts they are making, the academic environment is still challenging for students with disabilities, as there is a remarkable shortage of academic tools and materials to facilitate the academic inclusion and learning progress of these students. Their responses indicate that this shortage of accessible learning materials and resources is largely related to lack of financial support from higher authorities. This, as staff highlighted, leads to limited availability of resources and, ultimately, to insufficient support:

“[...] I can tell that there is a lack of learning resources and tools to realize academic inclusion [...] affording learning materials and resources is not always possible [...] sometimes we cannot afford them.” (Disability Support Officer A)

“[...] we do not have enough and appropriate materials to help disabled students [...].We have few audiobooks, computers, and encyclopedias, and few online resources. [...] [...]” (Disability Support Officer C)

Both students and staff referred to assessment accommodations and provisions, which included breaks and extra time during exams, extra time to submit homework, provision of scribes, readers, and the reallocation and rescheduling of exam times and settings:

“ [...] we allow students with disabilities to have exams in separate classes, as we offer them extra time [...], and I also [...] allow students with disabilities in my class to have extra time to deliver assignments [...]” (Disability Support Officer A)

“ [...] my [...] lecturer [...] always offers me and some of my classmates additional time to submit homework and assignments [...]” (Student E)

However, not all students with disabilities agreed on the efficacy of assessment accommodations. Comparing the responses of students and disability support staff indicated that while disability support staff make efforts to support students with disabilities and to provide them with accommodations, these accommodations may not always be successful or sufficient to address the requirements of the students with disabilities. For example, not all students shared positive views regarding assessment accommodations. Student D pointed out that it is not always possible to find someone who would read or write for them during exams, as staff are not always able to suggest

someone who could help, and the university regulations will not allow students to bring someone they know (e.g. one of their friends or siblings):

“ I find it difficult to find someone who would write for me during exams [...] teachers and administration would not allow you to bring someone you know, and at the same time, they do not put efforts to afford a reader or a scribe for me.’ (Student D)

Another student mentioned that extra time allocation during exams is not always sufficient for her.

“[...] 30 minutes of extra time is not always enough for me it is painful sitting for two hours [...], in the same position, without taking rest breaks, and I receive no support concerning that.” (Student C)

This divergence in views highlights how important it is that Disability Support Office seek feedback from students with disabilities in relation to the effectiveness and quality of the provided accommodations. Ongoing communication and collaboration with the students will give the Disability Support Office the opportunity to develop better understanding of how to tailor support to individual students’ requirements, and make necessary adjustments accordingly, since every student with disability may have unique additional support needs so a one-size-fits-all type of support is not appropriate.

4.4.2.2 Social engagement support

As part of their efforts, disability support officers also mentioned planning and organizing social activities for students with disabilities to help them feel part of the university culture, and to allow them to integrate with others and to have opportunities to voice their concerns.

“ [...] we [...] organize events and workshops through our office [...] the invite is for everyone [...] the aim behind those meetings is to enable students with disabilities to maintain contact and build relations with others at university[...].” (Disability Support Officer A)

However, participating students had a significantly different perspective in terms of participation in extracurricular events and activities, which highlighted their sense of isolation on campus:

“I do not participate in social events [...] I was never invited to participate.” (Student C)

“[...] they do not bother to invite me [...] I think they do not need me there, I do not want to be a burden.” (Student A)

“[...] I do not think that they need me, because they had never approached me or offered me to join them.” (Student B)

“[...] lack of participation in social activities and lack of integration would worsen the psychological state of students with disabilities, they will make them feel unworthy.” (Student B)

Staff efforts to include students with disabilities in events and decision-making processes are important steps towards creating a more inclusive learning environment. However, the discrepancies between students' and staff's responses indicate a potential breakdown in communication between staff and students. This suggests that more careful planning is required to ensure that invites to events and opportunities to become involved in the decision-making processes reach all students with disabilities. More effective communication and collaboration between students and disability support staff can help with this.

4.4.2.3 Peer Support

Students with disabilities in this study reported positive experiences with their peers inside and outside the classroom. They highlighted the importance of peer support, and the role their classmates played in supporting them:

“[...]because I stay upstairs all the time, they buy me food, and bring me the things I need, I really appreciate that in them.” (Student C)

“[...] they bought a Dictaphone for me, [...] and when it was damaged, they bought me another one.” (Student D)

“[...] my classmate used to explain and revise for me the lessons I missed, and even write lessons for me [...]” (Student F)

In addition to support received from peers inside the classroom, peer support outside the class environment was also mentioned. This included helping students with disabilities access classes:

“[...] I have some friends who always try to arrive early and help me get up to classes [...]” (Student B)

It was apparent that peer support was highly appreciated by students with disabilities, as they valued the support received from their peers and described it as significantly encouraging. For instance, student A stated: “this boosts my self-confidence [...]”. Findings from the students’ interviews seem to concur with those of some disability support staff, who spoke of positive relationships between students with disabilities and their peers inside and outside the university:

“[...] other students are very supportive to their friends with disabilities, they accompany them, write for them, revise with them [...]” Disability Support Officer A

“[...] students without disabilities sometimes intervene and ask us as academics to take into consideration the needs of their peers with disabilities, when it comes to teaching and provision of learning materials [...]” Disability Support Officer B

The value of peer support was apparent through the responses of staff and students with disabilities. This suggests that encouraging peer interactions can be a positive influence on the university experience of students with disabilities.

4.4.2.4 Emotional support

Students with disabilities highlighted that the barriers they face affect their emotional wellbeing as well as their academic experience. Disability support staff mentioned that registered students with disabilities receive emotional support, however, the students with disabilities who participated in the study reported lack of such support.

According to the disability support staff, the Disability Support Office has a full-time psychologist to provide mental health support and counselling sessions for students with disabilities in this university. As Disability Support Officer A stated: “[...] counselling services are available for all students [...] especially during exam periods.” However, students with disabilities reported lack of psychological support, while highlighting the importance of such support and the benefits it can have on students’ well-being and achievement:

“[...] University should start [...] providing emotional support and therapy sessions for us [...]” (Student A)

“[...] I suggest they provide us with mental health support, [...]” (Student E)

Lack of emotional support may lead to feelings of isolation and anxiety for students with disabilities, which can negatively affect their academic progress. It is encouraging that this university has a system in place to offer emotional support to students with disabilities. The fact that the students who participated in the study seemed to be unaware of this support system indicates that more effort should be focused on

ensuring that all students with disabilities are informed of this support and can benefit from it.

4.4.2.5 Family involvement

Both staff and students mentioned the importance of family support in shaping the educational experiences of students with disabilities, and the way this can influence their engagement at university. All but two students, reported how much they appreciated family support. For example, Student F stated: “[...] my father [...] supported me to go to university, as he believes in my abilities [...] he also bought me the necessary technological tools to study with.”. Student B praised the efforts of his sister to support him: “I am grateful for my big sister, without her I would have never entered school [...]”. Student D also stated: “[...] whenever I am home my father always [...] helps me write my recorded lessons [...]” (Student D)

Disability support staff also commented on the significant role of family support for students with disabilities:

“ [...] there are some students who withdraw from their studies because they have no one to accompany them at university, I had a student in my class who dropped out of her studies just because her brother graduated, and she doesn't have support anymore [...]” (Disability Support Officer A)

“I always see the father of one of the students with disabilities bringing him to university on a daily basis, this is the best picture of support I have ever seen in my life [...]” (Disability Support Officer B)

Findings from the interviews with both students and staff indicate that family support is an important pillar in helping students with disability navigate university life; therefore, the quality of this support (existence or lack of it) affects their experiences accordingly.

4.4.2.6 Reluctance to disclose

Reluctance to disclose disability to the Disability Support Office was another issue identified from the interviews with both students with disabilities and disability support staff. It was apparent through students' testimonies that there is a breakdown in communication between disability support staff and students with disabilities. This may have affected students' willingness to disclose having a disability, as some of them stated that they believe that doing so would not benefit them in any way.

“[...] they (disability support staff) registered me and wrote my issue, but I have never been contacted by any of them. I think this office is only ink on paper.”(Student C)

On the other hand, disability support staff highlighted that reluctance of students with disabilities to register with the office and to declare their disabilities is a barrier to accommodating them and identifying alternative and viable methods to assist them. This may explain why the available support is not reaching all students with disabilities at this institution:

“[...] I had many students with hidden disabilities that did not declare to me, until the day of the exam, or a week before the exam, students with hearing impairments, students with severe anxiety and others with chronic illnesses...etc. This puts me in a difficult situation regarding providing support for those students [...]”
(Disability Support Officer C)

These findings suggest that the efforts of the disability support staff do not reach all students with disabilities in this university. One reason for this seems to be that not all students disclose their disabilities and register with the Disability Support Office. The findings indicate that reluctance to disclose stems from students' concerns about being stigmatized and distrust that disclosure will have any benefits for them. This would

suggest that, in collaboration with students with disabilities, the Disability Support Office should review the disclosure process and the way disclosure information is shared and used to address students' concerns and distrust. More effective communication about the benefits of disclosure can also be helpful in convincing students to disclose their disabilities.

4.4.2.7 Lack of financial support

Financial support is as crucial as any other type of support to ensure a fair university experience for students with disabilities. The findings of this study suggest that limited financial support is a challenging factor for both students with disabilities and the Disability Support Office at this university.

Although university students with disabilities receive monthly financial support as part of the governmental disability support scheme, the students with disability who participated in this study indicated that this allowance is insufficient to cover their needs. This puts students with disabilities in a difficult situation, and creates an additional burden for them:

“[...] disability stipends are insufficient to fulfil the needs of a student with a disability at university [...] Not all individuals with disabilities are able to work alongside their studies as normal people do [...]” (Student E)

Equally, disability support officers reported that lack of funds for the office is a significant barrier to affording accommodations for students with disabilities and realizing full inclusion in the university. The responses of the disability support staff indicated that inaccessibility of the physical environment and lack of accessible academic resources is mainly due to limited funding for the office. One of the staff mentioned that lack of funding obliged them to pay for some services from their own

money: “[...] we have gathered money to build some ramps at the university [...]” (Disability Support Officer A).

According to the disability support staff, the lack of financial support stems from the reluctance of higher authorities, including the Ministry of higher education and scientific research (MESRS), to make the Disability Support Office official:

“[...] lack of learning resources and tools to realize academic inclusion [...] is due to insufficient budget, and [...] national authorities’ (MESRS) reluctance to make the Disability Support Office official.” (Disability Support Officer A)

Financial support is important for both students with disabilities and the Disability Support Office. For students with disabilities, financial support can help cover the costs related to their university life, studies, transportation, food, specialized equipment, medication and anything else they need. This can help alleviate their financial burden and allow them to focus on their studies, instead of worrying about how to fund themselves. For the Disability Support Office, financial support can help cover the costs of proposed renovations and learning resources which can help promote inclusion and equality for students with disabilities at this university. Overall, financial support for both staff and students can play a crucial role in increasing students’ chances to access an inclusive university environment, and can help them have the necessary resources and support to progress and succeed.

4.4.2.8 Lack of training for disability support staff

Lack of relevant training seems to affect the availability and effectiveness of the accommodations for students with disabilities at this university. Without relevant training, academic staff and disability support staff may not have sufficient knowledge to understand the additional support needs of students with disabilities and to support

them effectively. Therefore, lack of accommodations to meet the needs of different students can be related to lack of relevant training and professional development:

“[...] we need training about the tools and instruments that each category of disabled learners need [...] we need to be trained in order to know how to help [...]” (Disability Support Officer B)

Students with disabilities seem to agree with staff on the issue of training, as they think that lack of accommodations is due to lack of training:

“Well, I really do not blame teachers for that, because they are very limited in terms of knowledge on disability and how to accommodate those with disabilities. [...] I believe they are not trained for that [...] [...]” (Student D)

The lack of proper inclusive training for disability support staff and academic staff means that staff have limited or even no understanding of how to create an inclusive classroom environment that meets the requirements of all students. Moreover, insufficient knowledge and training can lead to inconsistency in providing appropriate accommodations. These findings highlight the need to provide academics and disability support staff with comprehensive and ongoing training on inclusive education. This training must go beyond a simple understanding of disability and inclusion related laws and policies to focus on practical strategies that can facilitate inclusion for students with disabilities.

4.4.2.9 Lack of collaboration

Responses from the disability support staff indicate that barriers faced by students with disabilities also stem from lack of collaboration between university systems. For example, Disability Support Officer A stated:

“ [...] we cannot do much, we are only volunteers, sometimes we inform lecturers of the things they should be doing and strategies they should incorporate to

accommodate their students, but not all of them adopt these strategies or work with our instructions [...]"
Disability Support Officer A

Similarly, one of the students with disabilities highlighted lack of collaboration as a barrier that affects the quality of learning support:

"[...] sometimes they just cannot, and I do not blame them at all [sighs] it is beyond their abilities. [...] I guess they lack collective capabilities. [...] I feel that the office is not supported by university, [...] few people work there, and few people cannot do a lot on their own." (Student D)

From the above quotes, it could be concluded that the obstacles encountered by the Disability Support Office in their efforts to support students with disabilities extend beyond financial constraints or insufficient training. The lack of collaboration between university systems is a significant barrier that undermines the intentions and efforts of the disability support staff to promote inclusion and support students with disabilities. This highlights a failure within the university system that affects the experience of students with disabilities.

4.4.2.10 Absence of policy

Concerning familiarity with inclusive education policies and laws, both staff and students spoke of lack of inclusion related policy at university level.

Disability support staff seem to have an understanding of the national and some of the international policies that promote inclusiveness and preserve the right of students with disabilities in educational settings. However, they mentioned that the existing body of legislation and policies in relation to disability are not specific to the university context:

“[...] only one policy [...] talks about supporting students with disabilities and the right to education for all students which is adopted from UNICEF [...] and this is a general one that applies to all levels and not specific to higher education [...]” (Disability Support Officer A)

Students with disabilities shared similar perceptions on the availability and implementation of disability related policies in their university:

“[...] in Algeria, [...] I do not think there is policy in relation to individuals or students with disabilities in university [...].” (Student A)

“I do not see any application of any of the policies that preserve the rights of individuals with disabilities in Algeria.” (Student E)

In some instances during the interviews, students with disabilities recounted earlier experiences at middle, primary and secondary schools. They remarked that some of the barriers they experienced then are similar to the barriers they are experiencing now at university, suggesting that not much has changed:

“[...] when I was in middle school. There was a lab to conduct experiments, the teacher [...] never registered me for these classes, because I was disabled, and labs were not accessible and equipped to receive people in wheelchairs. [...] I never had the chance to attend any of those sessions [Cries] [...] and at university, I miss some classes because the building is inaccessible [...]” (Student B)

“ [...] I have had a friend who used to accompany me to school every day, we studied together for more than ten years, he was always helping me to get upstairs [...] even at university [...] he was always there to help me until he got a job [...]” (Student B)

“ [...] my sister used to help me when I was at primary and middle schools, now at university nothing has really changed, but I am more dependent on myself rather than requesting from others to help me [...]” (Student A)

Comments from disability support officers also suggest that the development of inclusive education policy and practice is slow in Algeria:

“ I joined this office because my little niece has a disability,[...] she is in primary school and there is no support provided to her [...] I always write papers and present in conferences to raise awareness about students with disabilities.”. (Disability Support Officer B)

The challenges reported by both students with disabilities and disability support staff in this study indicate the limited progress in the area of inclusive education in the Algerian context, and failure of the educational system, especially the higher education system, to adapt to diversity and promote equity and accessibility for all. However, it is encouraging to hear from disability support staff about their efforts to raise awareness and bring about change:

“[...] I share my experience and disseminate the Disability Support Office work to encourage high schools to have the same office, and for the sake of raising awareness on support for students with disabilities [...]”

“[...] I remember in the 90s when I was a university student [...] I was almost the only student with a visible disability in my cohort at least, and not much was done to support others with disabilities or me with my disability. [...] now it is different as the number of students with disabilities enrolling in universities is growing, and we need to do something about it [...]” (Disability Support Officer A)

Arguably, the lack of an inclusive higher education policy is a structural barrier that prevents the disability support staff from providing effective support to students with disability in this university. This policy gap could explain the reluctance of government and higher authorities to make the Disability Support Office official, which prevents staff from benefiting from funds and training that would help them provide effective support for students with disabilities. An inclusive higher education policy could help

ensure that students with disabilities receive the support they need to fully participate at university, and can provide staff with the guidance and resources they need to provide an inclusive university experience for these students.

4.4.3 Attitudinal factors

It has been argued that attitudinal barriers to inclusion can be particularly difficult to remove given how deeply rooted they are in society (Finkelstein, 1993, 1996, 2001; Oliver, 1990, 1999, 2013; Allan, 2008, 2013). Misinformation, misconceptions, assumptions, and stereotypes encourage negative attitudes towards disability and lead to actions that hinder the full participation of people with disabilities. The university experiences of the students with disabilities who participated in this study were significantly affected by attitudinal factors. These include negative attitudes, stigma and discrimination from academics and peers that are shaped by the cultural and societal values and ideologies in the Algerian context. Some students reported positive attitudes from academics and other university staff, for example, student D stated: "my XX course teacher, believes in my abilities and he is so supportive, I like the way he doesn't judge me because of my disability [...]". However, a number of students reported negative attitudes, including stereotypes, stigma, discrimination, and marginalization, which are related to lack of awareness about disability, and seemed to have a significant influence on the experiences of these students. For instance, Student C shared two different experiences and compared how educators' attitudes influenced her self-confidence and motivation. She noted that her experience with her teachers at secondary and middle school was very positive, and this boosted her motivation:

"[...] at secondary and middle school, my teachers were very nice and supportive, they make you feel proud of

yourself and make you feel worthy [...] this motivates you and pushes you to work harder.” (Student C)

However, she stated that she does not feel the same at university, and that her academic achievement is lower in comparison to previous learning experiences, as university teachers hold negative attitudes towards her disability:

“ [...] some lecturers [...] do not bother to communicate with you [...] some of them provoke you, try to belittle you or underestimate you through their looks and offensive comments [...] I remember once a lecturer stood in the class and said to me in front of all my peers: do you think you can manage to teach like that? I do not know how I felt exactly, but I was so down, I said I am sure I can, but I was so hurt.” (Student C)

Disability support staff also shared experiences showing that negative attitudes towards disability are still prevalent in Algerian society:

“ [...] you know the society is so judgmental when it comes to disability. Especially if it is a woman with a disability [...] and this is the case for one of my students who has an invisible disability [...] she never declared that to anyone for the fear of being discriminated inside and outside the university especially when it comes to the topic of marriage [...] “ (Disability Support Officer A)

“ [...] I have a student with disability in my class, and I noticed that she is isolated. [...] when I asked her about the reason behind having no friends, she said that she cannot trust anyone at this university, because she got disappointed, as she always discovers that she is not accepted [...] especially when they refuse to work with her or be friends with her [...]” (Disability Support Officer B)

These findings reveal that the attitudes, perceptions, and level of awareness of society towards people with disabilities has a significant impact on their experiences. They also indicate that reluctance to disclose disability or advocate for support are influenced by societal attitudes, which highlights the need for increased awareness

about disability, in order to promote inclusion in the Algerian society and higher education.

4.5 Chapter summary

The comparison section and integration of both sets of findings provides a comprehensive understanding on the facilitators and barriers in the university experience of students with disabilities, as well as the challenges faced by the disability support officers in providing necessary support services and accommodations. The findings from the experiences of the staff go some way towards explaining some of the challenges faced by students with disabilities. They provide insights into the barriers encountered by the Disability Support Office that affect the effectiveness of support services and accommodations for students with disabilities, and how these barriers contribute to the challenges faced by students with disabilities. The findings reveal that environmental and structural factors significantly shape the learning experiences of students with disabilities. Infrastructure accessibility, academic support received from staff, lecturers and peers, and family involvement are recognized as facilitators that positively influence the experience of students with disabilities. However, various environmental, structural and attitudinal barriers, including inaccessible buildings and transportation, lack of funding, absence of inclusive policies and practical guidelines, and negative attitudes towards disability restrict their access and engagement. The experiences of disability support staff shed light on the challenges faced by the Disability Support Office in providing effective support services and accommodations to students with disabilities. These findings indicate an inconsistent and reactive approach by the Disability Support Office to provide support for these students. However, it was apparent that the ability of the Disability Support Office to realize inclusion in this university is hindered by factors

such as the authorities' reluctance to give this office official status, limited financial resources, lack of training, and the reluctance of some students to disclose their disabilities.

It appears that the university is a multi-faceted entity, which is composed of various interconnected systems that work together to shape the overall educational experience of students with disabilities. These intricacies can be seen through participants' responses that revealed the contribution of different university layers to the current situation. This complexity emphasizes that experiences and development of individuals are affected by multiple systems within the university environment and even outside of it. The experiences of both students with disabilities and disability support officers highlight the need for an inclusive approach, collaboration between different departments, ongoing training opportunities, and investment in infrastructure and resources to address the challenges and promote inclusiveness at this university.

Chapter 5: Discussion

5.1 Introduction

The previous chapter reported findings from interviews with students with disabilities and disability support staff in one Algerian university. These findings highlighted factors that facilitate or hinder the inclusion of students with disabilities in this university. This chapter will discuss the findings in relation to the theoretical framework and previous literature. Conclusions, implications and recommendations arising from the study will be discussed in the next chapter.

5.2 Considering the findings through the lens of Bronfenbrenner's ecological systems theory

The findings of the present study showed similarities as well as divergences in the lived experiences of students with disabilities and the perspectives of disability support staff in this university. Approaching this phenomenon from a dual perspective, i.e., investigating the experiences of students with disabilities as well as the experiences of disability support staff, allowed multiple realities to appear. Additionally, it facilitated the exploration of available support and inclusive practices from two different angles, and helped bring to the fore factors that prevent disability support staff from realizing full inclusion for students with disabilities.

Both groups of respondents revealed some positive practices and accommodations that promote the inclusion of students with disabilities, such as timetabling classes on the ground floor, and providing extra time for exams. Several barriers were also identified, including inaccessible buildings and transportation, inaccessible learning materials, negative attitudes and marginalisation. This chapter presents a synthesis of the most prevalent themes that appeared in the findings from both groups of

participants. Bronfenbrenner's (1989) ecological systems theory is used as framework to help situate the factors that affect the inclusion of students with disabilities in the university microsystem but also in other systems that may not be part of the students' immediate environment but influence them nonetheless. As noted in Chapter 3, Bronfenbrenner (1979, 1989) places the individual at the center of concentric circles that represent contexts that affect this individual's development and experiences. The individual has direct contact with some of these contexts, which are referred to as microsystems. Contexts outside the individual's immediate environment include: the mesosystem, which captures interactions between the different microsystems the individual inhabits; the exosystem, which encompasses structures and policies that shape the practices that take place in the microsystems; the macrosystem, which encompasses societal values, attitudes and norms; and the chronosystem, which captures changes over time in the individual and in the systems, and considers how these changes affect the individual directly (in the microsystem) or indirectly (through the mesosystem, exosystem, and macrosystem).

As discussed in Chapter 2, while impairment is part of human diversity, disability is a social construct created by an ableist society that does not accommodate the needs of people with impairments (Finkelstein, 1993, 1996, 2001; Oliver, 1990, 1999, 2013). This means that disability identity is socially constructed and shaped by the contexts people with disabilities inhabit. University students with disabilities may experience a range of challenges that can have an impact on their participation and progress. The ecological systems theory can help explain how the different levels of the environment interact to influence the students' experiences. In the present study, findings from the interviews with both groups of participants revealed that the experiences of students

with disabilities are influenced by a range of factors. Some of these factors are situated within the university microsystem but others are external, operating within outer systems (mesosystem, exosystem, macrosystem, chronosystem) but influencing the university microsystem and, ultimately, the students. Mapping these factors onto the different systems can help identify the proximal and distal, positive and negative influences of the different systems, and show how these influences shape the experiences of students with disabilities in this university. This can lead to a better understanding of what could be done at each system to enhance the experiences of university students with disabilities, and what policies and practices may be necessary to promote their inclusion and progress.

Before discussing the findings in relation to the ecological systems theory and previous studies of relevance to the topic, a summary table of how the identified factors relate to each system is provided below:

Bronfenbrenner's systems	Factors identified by the students with disabilities	Factors identified by the disability support officers
Microsystem	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Environmental factors (infrastructural facilitators and barriers) • Academic support and constraints • Emotional support • Sense of belonging • Self-determination 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Environmental factors (infrastructural facilitators and barriers) • Academic support and constraints • Emotional support • Sense of belonging • Disclosure
Mesosystem	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Family support • Transportation • Transition 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Family support • Transportation
Exosystem	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inclusive policy • Training for staff • Financial support 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inclusive policy • Training for staff • Financial support for the Disability Support Office

Macrosystem	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Negative attitudes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Negative attitudes
Chronosystem	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Evolution of inclusive education in Algeria 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Evolution of inclusive education in Algeria

Table 3. Mapping the factors that affect the inclusion of university students with disabilities, as identified by each group of participants, on Bronfenbrenner's systems.

5.2.1 Microsystem

5.2.1.1 Environmental factors (infrastructural facilitators and barriers)

When talking about factors that have a direct influence on the experiences of students with disabilities in this university, students with disabilities and disability support staff referred to facilitators and barriers within the university environment which enable or prevent students with disabilities from participating fully in learning and social activities within this university. The immediate experiences of students with disabilities included direct interactions with the physical university environment. These are referred to as environmental factors (infrastructural facilitators and barriers).

Disability support officers reported their efforts to improve the accessibility of the physical environment and to remove architectural barriers. They stated that since the establishment of the Disability Support Office, they have contributed to the building of ramps, allocating classes in ground floors, opening side doors, and renovating university toilets. Students with disabilities in the present study also referred to positive practices in relation to the physical environment, including the allocation of classes on the ground floor, and opening side doors to facilitate access to classrooms for those with physical disabilities. This is congruent with findings from international studies that revealed similar practices aiming to help students with disabilities access classrooms and buildings (Lane, 2017; Mustaffa et al, 2019; Morina and Parera, 2020; Tudzi, Bugri and Danso, 2020). For instance, in a study focusing on the experiences of university

students with disabilities in Spain, Morina and Parera (2020) reported that considerable refurbishments and adaptations had been made in lecture halls and classrooms in order to facilitate accessibility. A more inclusive and disability friendly infrastructure that enables students with disabilities to move freely can facilitate their learning at university and helps them feel included (Majoko, 2018; Bialka et al, 2017).

However, students with disabilities in the current study also revealed that they are still facing barriers that affect their ability to access the different university buildings and facilities. While they acknowledged efforts to make the environment more accessible, including the building of ramps, they remarked that some of these facilities are not of a good quality and do not meet their additional support needs. Poor quality ramps and inaccessible toilets were among the accessibility problems highlighted by the students, particularly those using wheelchairs. These findings concur with findings from the studies of Hadjidakou et al (2010), Engelbrecht and de Beer (2014), Spassiani et al (2017) and Mustaffa et al (2019) and Kabtyimer (2020), which revealed that poor quality ramps and inaccessible toilets are among the most challenging physical constraints identified by university students with disabilities. For instance, in a study of the experiences of university students with disabilities in Ireland (Spassiani et al, 2017), ramps were found to be dangerous and challenging to use, especially for students in wheelchairs.

Other environmental barriers reported by the students who participated in the present study include outdated buildings, absence of lifts, inaccessible libraries and classrooms. These findings concur with findings from previous studies in many countries. They echo the findings of Mutanga (2017), which revealed that the physical environment in South African universities, is among the most prevalent barriers for students with disabilities, especially those using wheelchairs and those with visual

impairments. Similarly, they are aligned with the findings of Abrahams et al (2023) who have extensively documented the negative consequences of inaccessibility of the university infrastructure on the inclusion of students with disabilities in universities in Ghana, Ethiopia and South Africa. They are also consistent with the findings of other research demonstrating the impact of inaccessible physical environments on students with disabilities (Kendall, 2016; Karellou, 2019; Moriña and Perera, 2020; García-González et al., 2021; Odame et al, 2021; Braun and Naami, 2021). For example, in Kendall's study (2016), students with disabilities in UK universities reported that they encountered different architectural barriers that prevented them from accessing rooms, libraries, residence halls and different services on campus, which affected their educational achievement and overall university experience. Additionally, students with disabilities in Spanish universities reported environmental challenges, including outdated buildings and absence of lifts that prevent them from accessing university classrooms resulting in missed sessions (Moriña and Perera, 2020; García-González et al., 2021). Students with disabilities in other studies have also reported the problem of stairs and steps, which prevent them from accessing different buildings such as offices, classrooms, and libraries, and make university stressful for them (Mutasa, Gorongaand Tafangombe, 2013; Spassiani et al, 2017).

Difficulty to move from one building to another due to long distance between university buildings and lack of signposting, and the implications of this for students with disabilities like tiredness, fatigue, missing classes, or arriving late to the class was another environmental challenge reported by students with disabilities in the present study. This finding is congruent with findings of previous studies from different contexts, where students expressed frustration due to the lack of signposting, the distance between buildings and the short time allocated to change classes (Tudzi,

Bugri and Danso, 2020; Moriña and Morgado, 2018; Yusof et al, 2020; Tudzi, Bugri and Danso, 2020). For example, Moriña and Morgado (2018) reported lack of signposting to be an obstacle for students with disabilities studying in the University of Seville, Spain. Similarly, in Ghanaian universities, long distance between different lecture halls and university buildings has been reported as a prevalent issue for students with mobility constraints which has a detrimental impact on their learning (due to missed classes) and wellbeing (due to fatigue and anxiety over being late) (Tudzi, Bugri and Danso, 2020).

As has been noted in the findings chapter, university dormitories also create challenges for students with disabilities in this institution. Although the findings revealed the willingness of accommodation staff to provide ground floor rooms for students with physical disabilities, inaccessible features in these rooms and in common spaces, such as steps leading to toilets and study areas, restrict the access of students with disabilities. Inaccessible residential halls seem to be a challenging aspect of other African universities as well, as reported in the findings of Moswela and Mukhopadhyia (2011), Zoreli (2019), Wilke et al (2019) and Tudzi, Bugri and Danso (2020). For example, Moswela and Mukhopadhyia (2011) reported that students with disabilities in Botswana are struggling with physical accessibility, including residence halls that lack ramps and accessible toilets. Drawing on interviews with students with disabilities in the US, Wilke et al (2019) also point out that inaccessible university dorms can have a detrimental impact on the university experience of students with disabilities and can lead some of them to withdraw from their studies.

The students in the present study reported that inaccessibility or partial accessibility makes them feel dependent on their non-disabled peers to help them access classrooms. This finding is consistent with findings from other studies reporting that

inaccessible infrastructure makes students with disabilities dependent on others to help them (Tudzi, Bugri and Danso, 2020; Braun and Naami, 2021; Arib, 2021; Herrick et al, 2022). Previous research has also found that inaccessibility of the physical environment can have a negative impact on students with disabilities, as it may inhibit them from pursuing their university studies, and may be among the primary reasons for lack of participation of students with disabilities in higher education (Matonya, 2016; Osborne, 2019). This is something that was highlighted by the disability support staff who participated in the present study. These officers revealed that inaccessibility of university infrastructure is a strong reason that pushes some students with disabilities to drop out of their studies, as it is too difficult for them to navigate the university environment.

The findings about the environmental barriers experienced by the students with disabilities who participated in the present study echo findings from the very few existing studies that have considered the physical environment of Algerian universities (Nabti 2018; Zoreli, 2019) and reveal that accessibility remains a significant problem for university students with disabilities in Algeria. In addition, these findings resonate with those of Lane (2017), who synthesised findings from 41 studies from different countries reporting the experience of students with disabilities in higher education. Lane (2017) concluded that despite efforts to enhance the physical environment in universities, there is still much to be done to remove infrastructural barriers and improve physical accessibility in higher education. These findings suggest that the medical model of disability, which puts the onus on the individual to adapt to an ableist environment or be marginalised (Finkelstein, 1993, 1996, 2001; Oliver, 1990, 1999, 2013) is still embedded in higher education in many parts of the world. These limitations impose a disability identity on these students, framing them as disabled,

marking them as different, and setting them apart from their peers(Finkelstein, 1993, 1996, 2001; Oliver, 1990, 1999, 2013). Much more effort is needed to move away from this mentality and ensure that the university microsystem is accessible to all students.

5.2.1.2 Academic support and constraints

In addition to environmental factors that affect the experiences of students with disabilities in the university microsystem, the present study identified structural factors, including academic support and constraints. The disability support staff reported that they are doing everything in their power to enhance the academic experiences of students with disabilities. This includes uploading lectures and lecture notes on the university's e-learning platform, and providing Dictaphones, audiobooks, and enlarged print for those with visual impairments. Accommodations and adjustments related to assessment were also reported by both students and staff in the current study. These include extra time during exams, extra time to submit homework, provision of scribes and readers, and rescheduling exams in response to specific needs. This is consistent with findings from other studies, where both students and staff highlighted accommodations in their institutions that facilitate the learning and academic inclusion of students with disabilities (Moriña and Orozco, 2021; Cotán et al, 2021). Cotán et al (2021), who studied the strategies academics use to accommodate the learning requirements of students with disabilities in Spanish universities, reported that academic support is instrumental to the inclusion of these students.

However, it appears that the academic adjustments reported in the present study are insufficient and do not meet fully the requirements of students with disability. Consequently, the level of academic inclusion for students with disabilities in this university appears to be unsatisfactory, a finding that concurs with the conclusions drawn in the very few studies from the Algerian context (Bouaicha, 2017; Nabti, 2018;

Zoreli, 2019; Arib, 2021) and in many international studies (Okiki and Okonji, 2019; Mustaffa et al, 2019; McKinney and Swartz, 2022; Abrahams et al, 2023; Al-A'dra, 2016; Yusof et al, 2020; Beyene, Mekonnen and Giannoumis, 2023; Cihan, 2021). As pointed out in the study of the university experiences of disabled students in South Africa (McKinney and Swartz, 2022) and in line with the medical model of disability (Rieser, 2017), barriers that limit academic inclusion can make students with disabilities feel excluded as they put the onus on them to seek out alternative solutions and accessible resources to support their learning. Such barriers construct them as 'disabled students' rather than 'students', reinforcing a disability identity that has been created by oppressive power relations in HE and society which marginalise these students and render them unable to participate fully in and out of the university (Shpigelman et al., 2022).

Despite the efforts the disability support officers said they put to support the academic experiences of students with disabilities, the study's findings revealed that both disability support staff and students with disabilities are still not satisfied with the quality of learning accommodations provided to students. It would appear that the academic support needs of students with disabilities are still unfulfilled as the university does not seem to have a strategy for implementing academic adjustments and accommodations. This exclusive pedagogical and assessment environment leads to an unsatisfactory academic experience for students with disabilities in this university. This shows that not much has changed since the study by Bouaicha (2017) which reported that university students with disabilities in Algeria are facing barriers to learning due to lack of accessible resources and technological means that can facilitate their learning. Literature on the experiences of students with disabilities emphasizes the need to invest in technological and assistive tools that meet diverse

learning requirements and promote the active involvement of students with disabilities in higher education (Majoko, 2018; Okiki and Okonji, 2019; García-González et al, 2021, Pacheco, Yoong, and Lips, 2021).

Furthermore, findings from the present study revealed inconsistencies in the provision of accommodations such as extra time during exams, rescheduling exams, arranging exams in different venues, or extending book loans. This has also been reported in previous studies in Algeria (Bouaicha, 2017; Nabti, 2018; Arib, 2021). Bouaicha (2017) highlighted that many students with disabilities feel that the university does not consider their requirements, for example, they have to sit for exams in unsuitable exam rooms or they are grouped with students with disabilities from different departments in a single room, making it difficult for them to concentrate due to the crowded conditions. In addition, the findings of the present study further reinforce the conclusions drawn in Nabti's study (2018) regarding the lack of accessible learning and assessment materials in the Algerian university where her research took place. Both the present study and Nabti's study (2018) highlight that barriers to participation and inclusion at university extend beyond physical inaccessibility and encompass lack of academic accommodations. Nabti's study (2018) reported scarcity of accessible pedagogical materials, unadapted teaching methods, and limited learning resources and technological devices. The present study found similar limitations indicating that not much has changed in the intervening years. These findings also echo findings from Arib's study (2021), where academics expressed concerns about the exclusive and unfair assessment system for university students with disabilities. These findings are also in line with findings from international literature, which demonstrates limitations in the provision of academic adjustments and accommodations for university students with disabilities (Moriña, 2017; Hewett et.al, 2017; Martins, Borges, and Gonçalves,

2018; Osborne, 2019; Lopez-Gavira, Moriña and Morgado, 2021; Yusof et al, 2020; Fabri et al, 2022).

Additionally, the findings of the present study revealed that the limited academic and pedagogical support that is available is not offered to all students with disabilities in a consistent manner. This might signify that the existing equipment are not proportional to the number of students with disabilities in this university. This seems to reinforce the conclusions drawn by Nabti (2018), who highlighted the need of further investment in accessible learning materials and enabling equipment so that all students with disabilities can participate fully in their studies. The efficacy of educational provisions, e.g., assessment accommodations, was also questioned by some of the students with disabilities who participated in the present study. The findings suggest that assessment accommodations are provided mainly for students with visual impairments and hearing impairments (large print materials, scribes/readers, recorders, and braille tools). However, as demonstrated by Aguirre, Carballo and Lopez-Gavira (2021) in a study of seven Spanish universities, adjustments provided for students with visual impairments may not be suitable for students with other additional support needs and may not work for everyone. Additionally, some students with disabilities in the present study stated that the 30 minutes of extra time allocated during exams is not always sufficient or helpful. This was also reported in a study of the experiences of students with disabilities in a university in the US (Yssel, Pak and Beilke, 2016), which highlighted that extending the time of exams is not an effective adjustment for all students with disabilities. The authors suggested that staff should discuss with students with disabilities their specific requirements in order to identify the most suitable assessment accommodations for them (Yssel, Pak and Beilke, 2016).

Students with disabilities in the present study further stated that bureaucracy is another challenge they face in the university microsystem. Students revealed that they have to go through tiresome processes and steps in order to get information and support. This is consistent with the findings of studies in various universities around the world, which have reported the bureaucratic challenges students with disabilities experience at their universities. Students in different countries have described their university services as slow and inefficient due to the lengthy and often daunting processes they must go through in order to receive information and resources or advocate for support (Strnadová, Hájková, and Květoňová, 2015; Al-A'dra, 2016; Lane, 2017; Moriña, 2017, Moriña, and Orozco, 2021).

5.2.1.3 Emotional support

Participants in this study also referred to emotional support, which they consider as an important aspect of their experience of higher education. Barriers to learning and limitations in the inclusion of students with disabilities in the university microsystem can have a negative impact on their wellbeing (Tinklin, Riddell and Wilson, 2006; Gilson and Dymon, 2012; OECD, 2019). Disability support officers in the present study mentioned that the office has a counselling service that provides psychological support for students with disabilities. University-based counselling services have been found to be helpful to students with disabilities (Al-A'dra, 2016; Bartz, 2020; Khazaleh et al, 2022). For example, in their study about the relevance of psychological support and counselling for university students with disabilities in Jordan, Khazaleh et al (2022) reported that students found these services beneficial and recommended that they should be offered to all university students with disabilities. However, despite the availability of the counselling service, the students who participated in the present study reported lack of emotional support and highlighted the need for it. This finding

suggests that students are not aware of the counselling service or consider it to be ineffective. Arib's (2021) study of inclusive education in another Algerian university reported that staff seem to underestimate the emotional support needs of students with disabilities. The responses of the students in the present study suggest that this may also be the case in their university. Lack of emotional support for students with disabilities has also been documented internationally as a challenge that affects the university experiences of students with disabilities (eg). The provision of counselling services for students with disabilities can be an important step towards improving the experiences of these students in higher education.

5.2.1.4 Sense of belonging

Amongst the positive aspects of the university microsystem highlighted by the participants in the present study was peer support. Both disability support staff and students with disabilities reported positive attitudes and practical help from non-disabled peers. Students described their relationships and interactions with peers as helpful and supportive, inside and outside the class. They remarked that this makes them feel included and has a positive impact on their academic experiences. These findings are in line with those of Odame et al (2021) who reported positive relationships between university students with visual impairment and peers without disabilities. They are also consistent with the findings of Bouaicha (2017), where students with disabilities acknowledged the academic support they received from their peers. Additionally, in the UK context, Hewett et al (2017) found that the interaction of students with visual impairment with peers in the university microsystem is a crucial component of their inclusion within higher education, as it makes students with disabilities feel welcome and included.

Other research has also reported positive relationships between university students with disabilities and their peers, and highlighted the potential positive impact of these relationships on the academic achievement, well-being, and inclusion of students with disabilities (Babic and Dowling, 2015; Bell, Carl and Swart, 2016; Moraña, Sandoval and Carnerero, 2020; Fabri et al., 2022). However, contrasting findings also exist, indicating lack of peer support and negative attitudes from classmates (Al-A'dra, 2016). In their study of challenges facing students with disabilities at the University of Jordan, Al-A'dra (2016) found that some non-disabled peers had negative attitudes towards students with disabilities. The authors attributed this to lack of disability awareness and understanding of how to interact with students with disabilities. Such findings reflect prevailing misconceptions in society regarding disabilities and highlight the influence these misconceptions have on students with disabilities (Al-A'dra, 2016; Khazalah et al, 2022). They also point to the oppressive power relations in society that frame disability identity as a deficit and mark people with disabilities as inferior (Parekh and Brown, 2020).

In addition to positive interactions with peers that make them feel that they belong to the learning community, students with disabilities in the current study also spoke of positive interactions with academic staff who show that they value these students and make an effort to accommodate their needs. However, unhelpful interactions with academic staff were also shared during the interviews with the students. Students spoke of academic staff who show unwillingness to help them, ignore them, pity them, or doubt their capabilities. This is consistent with findings from Mutanga's (2017) synthesis of the literature on the experiences of students with disabilities in South African higher education, which revealed that some students with disabilities have had negative experiences in their interactions with academic staff. Mutanga (2017)

attributed this to a range of factors including lack of staff awareness of the needs of students with disabilities, negative attitudes, but also absence of inclusive higher education policy, which can set expectations and protocols for staff to follow. Similar findings have also been reported in other studies (Morina and Perera, 2020; Strnadová, Hájková, and Květoňová, 2015; Karellou, 2019). When academic staff act in ways that convey lack of understanding of the needs of students with disabilities and disregard for their capabilities, students' sense of belonging is undermined, and they feel marginalised. This can have a negative impact on their academic progress and their overall university experience (Opini, 2012; Lane, 2017; Morina and Perera, 2020).

The responses of the students who participated in the present study indicate that their interactions with disability support officers are mostly positive. Students spoke of the friendliness of disability support staff and their efforts to negotiate accommodations with administration and academics. According to the students, such positive interactions boost their self-confidence and make them feel that they belong to the university. However, some students mentioned that they have to remind disability support officers of their requirements each year, which is an additional burden for them. This concurs with findings from previous studies also reporting that having to ask for support repeatedly can be a burdensome task for students with disabilities and can make them feel marginalised (Avellone and Scott, 2017; Rath, 2022). Some of the students in the current study suggested that disability support staff lack training and experience in dealing with students with disabilities and accommodating their additional support needs. This is consistent with previous research findings which suggest that insufficient support can stem from lack of awareness and insufficient training in the area of inclusion and disability (Hewett et al., 2017; Vlachou and

Papananou, 2018; Carballo, Morgado and Cortés-Vega, 2021). The disability staff who participated in the present study reported that they have not received official training in relation to inclusive practices and accommodations for students with disabilities, and pointed out that this affects their ability to provide consistently effective support for these students. In addition, they reported that lack of collaboration between academics, the administrative team, and disability support staff is another barrier that hinders the realization of full inclusion for students with disabilities in this university. Findings from other research have highlighted collaboration as instrumental for enhancing the experiences of students with disabilities in educational settings (Behling and Linder, 2017; Garcia-Melgar et al, 2022). For example, Behling and Linder (2017) have concluded that collaborative work between academic staff, the Disability Support Office and other stakeholders allows for sharing of efforts, strategies and expertise, which can improve the academic outcomes of students with disabilities and strengthen their sense of belonging. Other researchers have also stressed the need for collaboration and described it as a powerful tool towards promoting equity and meeting the needs of all students (Nel et al, 2014; Ainscow, 2016).

The members of the Disability Support Office in the present study also mentioned their efforts to organize events to make students with disabilities feel that they are part of the university. This aligns with the findings of other studies that documented the efforts of disability support services to engage students with disabilities in the social life of the university (Mutanga, 2017; Fossey et al, 2017). However, students who participated in the present study reported that they are not invited to participate in university social events, which makes them feel marginalised and unwanted. As discussed in the previous chapter, this highlights the need for better communication to ensure that students are aware of such events and are encouraged to participate. A number of

studies have found that engagement with the university community can foster a sense of belonging in students with disabilities (Jacklin, 2011; Ekelman, Bazyk and Bazyk, 2013; Bialka et al, 2017; Zaussinger and Terzieva, 2018; Goegan et al, 2019; Moraña and Biagiotti, 2022; Fox et al, 2022; Rath, 2022). In contrast, lack of sense of belonging and engagement at university has been found to be one of the reasons why students are reluctant to declare their disabilities (Jacklin, 2011; Zaussinger and Terzieva, 2018). The findings of these studies indicate that being part of university events, clubs and students' organizations can make students with disabilities feel a sense of belonging and connection with the university community. In contrast, lack of participation in such events can lead to feelings of marginalisation and exclusion, which can have a detrimental effect on the students' overall university experience.

5.2.1.5 Disclosure

All of the above-mentioned factors (lack of collaboration, lack of awareness and understanding, and lack of training) can create distance between staff and students with disabilities. As a result, students may refrain from disclosing their disabilities for fear of being stigmatised (Svendby, 2020). In a study of how students with disabilities perceive university disability support services, Shpigelman et al (2022) reported that the students who participated in their study were torn between disclosing their disability in order to obtain support and not disclosing it out of concern that they will be stigmatised. Decision not to disclose could be interpreted as rejection of the socially constructed disability identity and desire to be identified as a student rather than as a disabled student.

However, lack of disclosure affects the ability of disability support staff to plan and provide appropriate support. According to disability support staff in the present study, the reluctance of students to disclose their disabilities makes it hard for the disability

support officers to negotiate possible solutions, and to secure necessary accommodations for these students. This echoes findings from previous studies (eg Cunnah, 2015; Lindsay et al, 2018), which highlighted the importance of disability disclosure, and reported that, when disability is not disclosed, the support and accommodations needed are not adequately discussed and provided.

Disability disclosure can be seen as the result of an interplay between different factors within the university microsystem that influence the decision of students to declare their disabilities. In a study of disability disclosure amongst students in higher education in Austria, Zaussinger and Terzieva (2018) revealed that reluctance to disclose disability and seek support might be related to fear of being stigmatised. While this fear may stem from various factors beyond the university microsystem, which will be discussed later, factors within the university microsystem can also influence students' decision to disclose. Findings from the present study suggest that inaccessible infrastructure, academic constraints, and inability or unwillingness of staff to support them can lead students to believe that there is no point in disclosing their disability because nothing will change or because they will be marginalised even further. As already noted, this response is tied to the disability identity created by oppressive societal structures which separate and devalue people with disabilities (Parekh and Brown, 2020; Shpigelman et al, 2022). This would suggest that if the university microsystem was more supportive, students might find it easier to disclose their disabilities, which, in turn, would enable disability support staff to arrange appropriate support for them.

5.2.1.6 Self-determination

Students who participated in the current study commented on how the challenges they face in university have helped them to understand themselves and their abilities better.

Accordingly, they stated that they have developed different skills that help them overcome some of the hurdles they encounter at university. These skills include the ability to mobilise their strengths to find solutions and alternative ways to support themselves academically. Other students with disabilities in different studies have also mentioned that they have become more aware of their capabilities and have used them to overcome challenges in the university environment (Vaccaro et al, 2019; McKinney and Swartz, 2022; Abrahams et al, 2023). For example, in Abrahams et al's (2023) study in the Ghanaian context, the participating students with disabilities emphasized the significance of adopting a self-determination approach and assuming responsibility over their lives, as a means of taking control of their situation at university. This was also reported by some students with disabilities in the present study, who mentioned their readiness and openness towards advocating for support, and communicating requirements related to their disabilities. Fabri et al (2022) has explained this openness as a key feature of self-advocacy, and noted that it is associated with students attributing the barriers they experience to limitations in the environment and lack of support, rather than to their disability. This could be interpreted as recognition of the oppressive power structures that impose on them a disability identity that marks them as dependent, and as rejection of this identity adoption of a self constructed positive identity (Shakespeare, 1996). A positive disability identity, self-advocacy and self-determination have been found to be instrumental to retention and academic achievement for university students with disabilities (McKinney and Swartz; 2022; Fabri et al, 2022; Herrick et al, 2022).

5.2.2 Mesosystem

According to Bronfenbrenner (1979, 1989), the mesosystem is the system where the different microsystems to which individuals belong interact with each other. This

includes interactions between the systems that exist in the immediate environment of students with disabilities (e.g., university and home), and affect their experiences positively or negatively. For students who participated in the present study, this involved challenges associated with transportation from one microsystem to the other and dependence on family support that obliged them to study in a university that is close to their home even if they would prefer to study in a different university. The influence of interactions between microsystems was also evident in the students' accounts of challenges they have experienced during the transition from high school to university, which suggest that, while these two microsystems are interconnected, the transition of students with disabilities from one microsystem to the other is not given the consideration that it needs.

Besides the university microsystem, students in the present study spoke of another important microsystem they inhabit: home. Most students referred to their home as a facilitator and a source of support during their time at university. They mentioned their families and other important people around them such as their friends who help them to access the university and to engage with their studies. It would appear that this support serves as a link between the two microsystems i.e., university and home. The practical and emotional support that students with disabilities receive from their families and friends, such as encouragement to pursue higher education, transportation to the university, transcription of lessons, help with exam revision, and financial support, has enabled the students with disabilities to navigate the university system. Some of the students stated that the reason why they chose their university was because it was close to their home as they would not be able to study without the support of their family and local friends. This was also highlighted in the study of Lindsay et al (2018), which focused on the transition to post-secondary education for

young people with physical disabilities in Canada. Lindsay et al (2018) reported the importance of family support and stated that it is an influential factor in the transition of young people with disabilities to higher education. Participants with disabilities in the present study revealed that their families acted as a source of encouragement and motivation, which helped them to have a positive transition experience. Findings from the study of Akoto et al (2022), which focused on the support available to university students with disabilities in Ghana, also emphasized the significance of family support in the experience of students with disabilities. The emotional and financial support that students with disabilities in Akoto et al's (2022) study received from their families facilitated their university experience.

Among other aspects that link the university and home microsystems and affect the experiences of students with disabilities in the present study but also in the study by Lindsay et al (2018) in the Canadian context, is transportation to and from the university. An accessible transportation service is a means via which other services, including education, can be accessed. Therefore, inaccessible transportation excludes individuals with disabilities from accessing different environments and restricts their participation in society (WHO, 2011; Agarwal and Steele, 2016). The present study revealed inaccessible public and university transportation that prevents students with physical disabilities from using it. Students mentioned the difficulties they face trying to use the available buses, and the negative impact this has on them as it makes them feel dependent on others to help them get on the bus. This aligns with the findings from Lindsay et al's (2018) study, where inaccessible transportation was described as a frustrating barrier by the participants. The authors concluded that accessible transportation is instrumental in connecting the university and home microsystems and in enabling students with disabilities to participate in higher education (Lindsay et al.,

2018). This conclusion is reinforced by findings from other similar studies that have reported the difficulties students with disabilities experience with inaccessible transportation, especially those with mobility constraints and visual impairment (Garrison-Wade, 2012; Lindsay et al, 2018; Nabti, 2018; Moriña and Morgado, 2018; Tudzi, Bugri and Danso, 2020). These findings highlight the importance of accessible transportation as an essential factor in facilitating the participation of students with disabilities in higher education.

Lack of preparation for the academic demands in higher education was another mesosystemic factor that appears to affect the university experiences of students with disabilities. Students with disabilities in the present research spoke of a heavy study load and its impact on their emotional and mental health. Especially those who are in their first year revealed that they found the academic demands challenging and that they felt stressed, anxious and sometimes unable to make progress. Biggeri, Masi, and Bellacicco (2019), in their study of the experiences of students with disabilities in two Italian universities, also highlighted the effects of high academic demands on the psychological state and mental health of students with disabilities. Previous research has attributed this to lack of policies and support to prepare students with disabilities for the transition from high school to university (Wessel et al, 2015; Moriña, 2017; Bartz, 2020; Khazaleh et al, 2022; Pacheco, Yoong and Lips, 2021; Lintang Sari et al, 2021). In the Algerian context, Nabti (2018) reported that lack of preparation of students with disabilities, especially those with visual impairments, in using learning equipment, such as Braille, computers, and printers, can make it hard for them to use these equipment independently when they are at university. This is not restricted to the Algerian context, but it extends to other contexts where transition policies for students with disabilities are not available (OECD, 2011; Lindsay et al, 2018). In the

New Zealand context, the study of Pacheco, Yoong and Lips (2021) highlighted that the challenges that await students with disabilities in higher education, particularly in relation to academic workload, are a prominent transition concern for these students. This underscores the importance of preparing students with disabilities for their transition from high school to university (Gil, 2007; Lindsay et al, 2018).

5.2.3 Exosystem

Factors within the university microsystem appear to have a significant impact on the experiences of students with disabilities; however, some of these factors seem to be influenced by forces that operate in the exosystem. The exosystem encompasses contexts and structures that have an indirect impact on the university microsystem and, by extension, on students with disabilities. While some of the students with disabilities who participated in the present study suggested that the barriers they experience, including inaccessible infrastructure and academic accommodations could stem from reluctance of academics and disability support staff to provide support, disability support staff revealed that the responsibility for removing these barriers could not be put entirely on them, as they are a self-funded, voluntary group with limited training, capabilities and connections. Lack of training and limited funds has also been reported in previous studies focusing on the inclusion of students with disabilities in Algerian universities (Bouaicha, 2017; Arib, 2021). These studies identified a gap in the provision of training, professional development, and funding for staff, which prevents them from providing the necessary accommodations for students with disabilities. According to the disability support officers who participated in the present study, this limitation is due to the negligence of the Algerian higher authorities (the Ministry of Higher Education) to make the Disability Support Office an official entity, and to provide adequate training and financial support for disability support staff.

They also noted that the lack of an inclusion policy for higher education makes it difficult for them to establish effective, consistent and adequately resourced approaches to meet the needs of all students with disabilities in the university. As suggested earlier, these limitations reflect oppressive power structures in society which push individuals with disabilities to the margins by disregarding their needs and their human rights (Shakespeare, 1996)

These structural barriers (lack of funding, reluctance to make the Disability Support Office official, lack of training, lack of inclusive policy) are created by forces that are not immediately experienced by students with disabilities, but still affect their experiences at the microsystem (Bronfenbrenner, 1989). For example, while the lack of funding for infrastructural facilities is determined by decisions taken by Government departments at the exosystem, it results in lack of lifts, electric stairs, and ramps for those using wheelchairs, and this affects the experience of students in the university microsystem. Similarly, the lack of inclusion policy in higher education and lack of financial support for the Disability Support Office, which can be traced back to Government decisions in the exosystem, limit significantly the capacity of the disability support staff to organise and enforce university-wide support mechanisms for students with disabilities, and appropriate training for staff. Arguably, these exosystemic factors and the impact they have on the university microsystem could also be responsible for students' reluctance to disclose their disabilities. Some students in the present study highlighted that if there was an inclusive policy to preserve their rights at university, they would be more likely to disclose their disability and request accommodations. A similar conclusion was drawn by Meeks, Herzer and Jain (2018), who argue that the absence of inclusive policies could discourage students from disclosing their disabilities and seeking accommodations, until they begin to struggle in their

programme. These findings reiterate how oppressive powers construct disability identity as a stigmatising label that marks students as different and limits their opportunities (Parekh and Brown, 2020).

Decisions at the exosystem also affect interactions at the mesosystem. The lack of funding to make transportation accessible to all is the result of financial decisions taken at the exosystem, but its impact is felt by students with disabilities in the mesosystem, through the challenges they experience as a result of inaccessible transportation from the home microsystem to the university microsystem. Similarly, the lack of systems and guidance to support the transition of students with disabilities from high school to university can be traced back to the exosystem but affects the students in the mesosystem when they move from one education microsystem to the other.

Another factor at the exosystem that influences the experiences of students with disabilities at the university macrosystem is limited financial support for them. The Algerian government provides a monthly stipend for individuals with disabilities (Moktari and Zerguine, 2021), however, according to the students who participated in the present study, this is not enough to cover their expenses while they study at university. This is congruent with findings from the Ghanaian context (Odame et al, 2021), where students with visual impairments revealed that the governmental financial assistance is insufficient to cover the cost of their education as well as their basic personal support needs. Students with disabilities in the present study also mentioned that they are not entitled to student funding, as they already benefit from disability funding. They consider this to be unfair, as they stated that the monthly disability stipend is not enough, therefore, they feel compelled to work in order to support themselves. They referred to this as an extra burden which puts more pressure on them and affects their progress and university experience. Previous

studies have highlighted consistently the issue of financial hardship for students with disabilities, and have described it as one of the burdens that affect the experiences of students with disabilities at university (Yssel, Pak and Beilke, 2016; Martins, Borges, and Gonçalves, 2018; Tudzi, Bugri and Danso, 2020; Hector, 2020; Pacheco et al, 2021; Abrahams et al, 2023). Financial hardship has been found to affect the retention of students with disabilities as inability to cover the extra costs or to fit the demands of work alongside their studies can lead to withdrawal from university (Mitra et al, 2017; Fox et al, 2022; Abrahams et al, 2023).

Lack of centralised policies, financial support, and training opportunities have been identified as an obstacle to inclusive higher education in many countries (Lane, 2017; Osborne, 2019; Morina and Orozco, 2021; Bartz, 2020; Yusof et al, 2020; Ismail et al, 2021; Aguirre, Carballo and Lopez-Gavira, 2021). While efforts within the university microsystem can go some way towards accommodating students with disabilities, lack of centralised support and resources from the exosystem can limit significantly the effectiveness of these efforts and can have a detrimental impact on the university experiences of the students.

5.2.4 Macrosystem

The university experience of students with disabilities can be affected by multiple external and distal factors outside the university microsystem, including societal attitudes, stigma, and discrimination. These factors exist within the macrosystem, which refers to the societal and cultural forces such as beliefs, values, customs and norms that influence indirectly the microsystems the individual inhabits and, ultimately, the experiences of this individual (Bronfenbrenner, 1989). These forces operate within the oppressive power structures which create and reinforce disability identity as a marker of deficit and as a mechanism for marginalisation (Shakespeare, 1996).

In the current study, students reported different discriminatory acts as well as negative attitudes that have affected their university experience. Despite the fact that admission to higher education in Algeria is based solely on Baccaalaureate test scores (Bouchikhi and Zine, 2017; Guersas and Oudah, 2018), some of the students with disabilities who participated in the current study reported that they were denied the opportunity to study the course of their choice because of stereotypes related to their disability. The students mentioned that they were forced to enrol in courses they were not interested in, which disappointed and frustrated them, but also pushed them to work hard to prove themselves and dispel disability related stereotypes. The findings of the present study concur with findings from international studies which have shown that the main reasons why students with disabilities are prevented from enrolling in the course of their choice are stereotyping and bias towards individuals with disabilities (Hadley, 2011; Redpath et al, 2013; Lindsay et al, 2018; Meehan and Howell, 2019; McKinney and Swartz, 2022). Students with disabilities in the current study indicated that admission teams focused on their disabilities instead of their abilities and qualifications. This demonstrates a disregard for the human rights model of disability, which defends human dignity and argues that disability is part of society's diversity and does not define an individual (Graham et al, 2020).

Students in the current study also reported negative attitudes, stereotyping and discrimination from academic staff who underestimated their abilities, were suspicious of their successes (e.g. suggesting that doing well in a test must be due to cheating) or pitied them. This aligns with the findings of Abrahams et al (2023) in the Ghanaian context, where the participating students with disabilities mentioned that they have experienced negative attitudes which make them feel discriminated and disconnected from classroom activities.

Negative attitudes that see disability as a deficit signify that the medical view towards disability is still prevalent in the Algerian context. This reinforces findings from the study of Arib (2021), who reported that among the challenges university students with disabilities face is negative attitudes towards them. Algeria ratified the CRPD in 2014. The CRPD prohibits the discrimination and stigmatization of persons with disabilities, promotes their rights and dignity, and encourages state parties to respect the freedoms and choices of people with disabilities. However, it seems that people with disabilities in Algeria are still subjected to discrimination and marginalisation (Rohwerder, 2018). Arguably, the perpetuation of negative attitudes could be linked to the lack of implementation of the existing laws that aim to protect the rights and dignity of individuals with disabilities in Algeria. This was addressed by Degener's UN review of the rights of persons with disabilities in Algeria (2018), which stated that there is a wide gap between disability and inclusion legislation and practice in the Algerian context, and that attempts to align the legislation with the CRPD had not been successful up to the point of the review. The experience of negative attitudes coupled with the realisation that disability and inclusion legislation is not enforced can go some way towards explaining the reluctance of some of the students in the present study to disclose their disabilities and register with the Disability Support Office.

Furthermore, students with disabilities in the current study expressed concerns about implementation of the laws at the macrosystem in relation to work after graduation. Arguably, enrolling in higher education is a step towards building a professional career. Joining the workforce after getting a university degree is perceived as a step towards financial independence (Valchou and Papananou, 2018). Joining the workforce is also essential for social connection, as it fosters a sense of belonging and inclusion in society (Cunnah, 2015). Students with disabilities in the current study commented on

their upcoming transition to adulthood and the job market. They seemed to view successful completion of higher education and transitioning to the workforce as a way to become financially independent but also as a necessary step towards proving themselves and their capabilities, and as a means to confront negative attitudes and stereotypes about people with disabilities. However, they shared concerns about lack of employment opportunities for individuals with disabilities in the Algerian context. In addition, as they have already experienced marginalisation and exclusion, they expressed anxiety and fears towards barriers that they may encounter in the workplace, including inaccessibility and negative attitudes. These concerns are shared by students with disabilities in different studies (Valchou and Papananou, 2018; Hector, 2020; Abrahams, et. al, 2023).

The right of people with disabilities to work was included in the UDHR which was established in 1948, and has been reinforced in many treaties and conventions, including Article 27 of the CRPD, which has been ratified and embraced by the Algerian government. However, from the perspective of the students with disabilities who participated in the present study, Algerian society does not seem to acknowledge the right of individuals with disabilities to work. Algerian law stipulates that 1% of the workforce should be individuals with disabilities (Presidential decree N 47, article 3, 2014; Rohwerder, 2018; Muktari and Zerguine, 2021). However, one of the participating students remarked that despite the 1% government quota, only few individuals with disabilities are hired. This reinforces the findings of Rohwerder (2018), who revealed that despite the fact that the Algerian law requires employers to set aside 1% of job positions for individuals with disabilities or face penalties, many companies have not complied with this requirement and the government has not enforced the payment of fines for noncompliance. This also resonates with the findings of Muktari

and Zerguine (2021), which highlight that the job opportunities available in Algeria for people with disabilities are not enough to enable them to attain economic independence and self-sufficiency. Although the Algerian law prohibits discrimination, and mandates the provision of physical accessibility at work (Degener, 2018), participating students with disabilities revealed that access difficulties in the workplace and negative perceptions from colleagues and others at work are still of a great concern to them. This echoes findings of earlier international studies which reported similar concerns about accessibility to buildings and work sites, and about discrimination and marginalisation in the workplace (Georgiou et al, 2012; Erickson et al, 2015; Kim and Williams, 2012; Lindsay et al, 2018). These findings illustrate how societal beliefs, values, customs and norms at the macrosystem shape attitudes and behaviours towards individuals with disabilities affecting their experiences and prospects.

5.2.5 Chronosystem

Ecological systems theory (Bronfenbrenner, 1989) highlights the impact of changes over time. These changes occur at the chronosystem and affect the other systems and, ultimately, the individual (Bronfenbrenner, 1989). Findings from the interviews with students with disabilities and disability support staff who participated in the current study shed light on the development of inclusive education in Algeria over time.

Students with disabilities discussed their experiences in primary, middle, and secondary schools, while staff talked about their experiences as university staff. These experiences indicated that inclusive education has not developed much over time. Both staff and students reflected on past and present experiences and concluded that inclusive education is not yet well-implemented in Algeria. Students with disabilities spoke of obstacles they faced in primary, middle, and secondary schools, and reported

that they continue to encounter the same barriers even at university, over a decade later. For example, physical accessibility remains a problem for students with disabilities in Algeria, as students revealed that they missed experimental classes in middle school due to inaccessible classrooms and are presently missing some university classes due to inaccessible buildings. Disability support staff also commented that the progress of inclusive education in Algeria seems to be limited. This aligns with the conclusion of Pather (2019) that the development of inclusive education in Africa has been very slow suggesting that the oppressive power structures that marginalise individuals with disabilities and disregard their human rights are deeply rooted and difficult to dismantle (Shakespeare, 1996).

5.3 Chapter summary

This chapter considered the findings from the interviews with students with disabilities and disability support staff (which were presented in the previous chapter) through the lens of the ecological systems theory (Bronfenbrenner, 1989) and in relation to international literature focusing on the experiences of university students with disabilities. Several of the factors that influence the experiences of the students and the disability support staff who participated in this study have been located in the university microsystem. Key amongst these factors is physical and academic accessibility, which, similar to many international studies, has been found to be inadequate. Equally important is how accepted and welcomed students with disabilities feel in the university environment. Echoing the findings of previous research, the findings of the present study are mixed in this respect. While positive relationships within the university microsystem foster a sense of belonging in students with disabilities, experiences of indifference, avoidance, pity or neglect make them feel marginalised and excluded. These experiences go some way towards explaining why

they are reluctant to disclose their disabilities. Another salient factor is students' reliance on their own skills and capabilities to help them overcome some of the challenges they experience. This is aligned with findings from the international literature which highlight the role of self-determination in enabling students to navigate the university environment. With regards to mesosystemic influences, similar to previous studies, supportive families were found to create a helpful bridge between the home microsystem and the university microsystem, while inaccessible transportation between home and university, and unsupported transition from secondary school to university were identified as barriers. The exosystem was found to exert indirect influence on students with disabilities and disability support staff, through lack of systemic support from government departments, including lack of funding. Several of the challenges experienced by students with disabilities in the university microsystem were traced to influences emanating from the macrosystem, where medical model mentality, stereotypes and negative attitudes towards people seem to prevail. Finally, with regards to the chronosystem, the findings of the present study indicate that inclusive education continues to be under-developed in Algeria. Recommendations that could lead to some improvements in this area will be offered in the next chapter.

Chapter 6: Conclusions, implications and recommendations

6.1 Introduction

The purpose of this study was to explore the lived experiences of students with disabilities and the processes used by disability support staff to facilitate their inclusion in one Algerian university. The study also considered the effectiveness of existing support services and accommodations provided to students with disabilities in this university, and identified areas for improvement to better meet the needs these students. In this chapter, I present the conclusions that I have drawn from my findings, discuss implications and make recommendations for practice and future research. I reiterate the contributions of my study and revisit its limitations. I conclude the chapter with a reflection on my PhD journey.

6.2 Conclusions

The study set out to address two research questions. The first question was:

What are the lived experiences of students with disabilities in Algerian Higher Education?

This study identified that students' university experiences are influenced by a range of factors. Some of these factors facilitate their inclusion while other factors act as barriers hindering their access and participation. These factors can be organized under three main categories: environmental, structural, and attitudinal.

Environmental factors refer to aspects of the infrastructure that facilitate or restrict the access and participation of students with disabilities in learning and social activities.

When students with disabilities are able to access classes and exam rooms independently, they feel included and empowered. However, the students who participated in this study spoke of inconsistencies in timetabling classes and exams

on the ground floor, and in adapting the physical environment to facilitate their access and inclusion. They also spoke of poor quality adaptations, such as unsafe ramps and corridors, that make it difficult for them to move around the university and access all areas in the same way as their peers without disabilities. These barriers have a negative impact on the experiences of students with disabilities and make them feel marginalised and excluded.

Structural factors refer to organizational processes and procedures but also to interactions with peers and staff. Structural factors emerge as a consequence of the organisation and operation of educational settings. The way an educational setting is organized can create obstacles or facilitators for certain groups of students (students with disabilities in this study). For instance, structural obstacles can be caused by practices, rules, norms, traditions, routines, and other organizational patterns that may not take into consideration the diverse needs of students with disabilities (Allan, 2008, 2013; McAuliffe, 2018).

According to the students who participated in the study, positive structural factors include academic support, assessment accommodations, peer support, and family support. The academic and assessment support they receive from academic and disability support staff enables students to participate in their studies and to experience a sense of achievement. Peer support has practical but also psychological benefits. Peers enable the students with disabilities to access spaces that are inaccessible to them, such as classrooms on upper floors. They also make them feel accepted and part of the university community, fostering in them a sense of belonging. Family support seems to be instrumental for these students' academic engagement. This is because of the practical support families offer, such as financial assistance and transportation, but also because of the encouragement and motivation they provide.

These structural facilitators are instrumental in enabling students with disabilities to engage with their studies. In contrast, structural barriers constrain their opportunities and undermine their capacity to participate in university in the same way as their peers without disabilities. Structural barriers include inconsistencies and limitations in the academic and assessment support available, and the financial challenges students with disabilities experience due to the insufficient financial assistance they receive from the state.

Attitudinal factors are rooted in societal beliefs and values concerning ability, diversity, and difference. For example, when individuals hold negative views about the abilities, backgrounds, or other characteristics of individuals or groups, this can result in exclusionary practices that can have a detrimental impact on the individual's development, and can limit their achievements (Allan, 2008, 2013; McAuliffe, 2018). While students with disabilities reported positive and supportive interactions with peers and some university staff, they also spoke of experiencing negative attitudes, stereotyping and stigmatization. These experiences reflect attitudinal barriers to inclusion which are informed by societal values and beliefs. In addition to the toll they take on students' wellbeing, negative attitudes, stereotyping and stigmatization can make them reluctant to disclose their disabilities, which means that they miss out on available support. Despite this, through self-determination these students seem to have developed skills and strategies that enable them to navigate the university environment and to make progress in their studies. However, as suggested below, these issues need to be addressed as not doing so places a constant burden on students with disabilities to use their own resources to find solutions for problems that are created by organizational and systemic failures. This situation perpetuates inequality and compromises the right of students with disabilities to experience

university education in the same way as their peers without disabilities. It reflects medical model mentality (Hasroumi and Haffad, 2021) and the 'hegemony of ableism' (McLean, 2008, p. 614) which expects people with disabilities to fit into a physical and social environment that has been built from an ableist perspective. While a culture change in the macrosystem is needed to reverse this, as will be seen later in this chapter, actions at the university microsystem are also needed as they can make a difference at the local level while also contributing to wider improvements.

The second question was:

How do disability support staff facilitate the inclusion of students with disabilities in Algerian higher education?

The findings indicate that the disability support staff are committed to facilitate the inclusion of students with disabilities in this university and strive to fulfil this commitment by mobilising the limited resources that are available to them. They have instigated changes in the physical environment to remove some of the barriers that prevent students with disabilities from accessing buildings and spaces independently. They arrange teaching and exams on the ground floor for groups that include students with disabilities. They provide accessible learning materials such as large print and braille. They have organized a counselling service which operates from the disability support office and offers psychological support to students with disabilities. They invite students with disabilities to social events and include them in decision making. Considering that the Disability Support Office is not an official entity and that the disability support staff are volunteers, their efforts demonstrate remarkable dedication. However, as the findings indicate, these efforts are undermined by structural limitations.

The disability support staff seem to be aware of some of the environmental barriers that affect the experiences of students with disabilities and expressed frustration at the lack of funding that prevents them from making the university infrastructure fully accessible. However, the disability support staff did not seem to be aware of the extent of environmental barriers experienced by students with disabilities. For example, they spoke positively about some accessibility features the Disability Support Office has been able to put in place but seem to be unaware of the poor functionality of some of these features, as reported by the students. This indicates the need for better communication channels to ensure that disability support staff are aware of all accessibility issues so that they can work on possible solutions.

The absence of an inclusive higher education policy and the reluctance of the state to make the Disability Support Office an official entity and to allocate funding to them emerged as significant structural barriers that limit the capacity of the disability support staff to provide an effective service and cause them frustration. The absence of an inclusive higher education policy results in gaps and inconsistencies in the support provided to students. While a policy by itself cannot resolve the issues and achieve inclusion, it can help this and other universities to establish guidelines and procedures to ensure that the needs of students with disabilities are met effectively. The lack of official status for the Disability Support Office undermines the efforts of the disability support staff to collaborate with academic and administrative staff to implement necessary accommodations and adjustments. Becoming an official entity can give the Disability Support Office more authority to proceed with the changes needed to make the university accessible and inclusive. In addition, official status can help the Disability Support Office secure funding to invest in resources, equipment, technology and staff training that can facilitate the inclusion and success of students with disabilities. State

recognition of the Disability Support Office and allocation of funding to it can strengthen the Office's efforts to raise awareness and remove barriers that hinder the inclusion of students with disabilities in the university.

While disability support staff recognize the impact of negative attitudes on students with disabilities, and appreciate why they may be reluctant to disclose their disabilities, they expressed concerns about the consequences of non disclosure. When students do not disclose their disabilities, disability support staff are not aware of their needs and cannot provide the support they need. While addressing the societal values and beliefs that underpin negative attitudes towards disability can take many years of awareness raising at all education levels and community contexts, disability support staff can focus on what can be done within the university to combat negative attitudes towards students with disabilities. For example, they can partner with disability groups and associations to organize awareness raising campaigns. In addition, they should enlist the help of students with disabilities to review the processes that are in place for disability disclosure and support. Making these processes more sensitive and discreet could be one way to encourage more students to disclose their disabilities and benefit from available support.

6.3 Implications

The aim of this study was to explore factors that shape the experiences of students with disabilities and affect the capacity of disability support staff to provide appropriate support. The analysis of the collected data indicated that the experiences of students with disabilities and the capacity of disability support officers to support them are influenced by internal and external forces. The use of Bronfenbrenner's (1989) ecological systems theory has been useful in identifying the contexts from where these forces emanate. This enabled a deeper understanding of the effects of the context and

its surrounding systems on the experiences of the participants. The findings highlight the impact of different factors and interactions within the university microsystem but also in outer systems in which the participants are not involved directly. Facilitators identified at the microsystem level include environmental factors, such as timetabling classes and exams on the ground floor, as well as structural factors such as support from peers, staff, and family. Barriers included inaccessible buildings and facilities, limited assistive resources and equipment, insufficient emotional and academic support, difficulties in enrolling in desired courses, and negative attitudes towards disability. While the disability support staff seem to be aware of some of the challenges affecting the university experience of students with disabilities, they do not seem to appreciate the extent of these challenges and the impact they have on the students. This highlights the need for the university to listen to the students' concerns and to work with them to ensure their equitable access to education.

Numerous barriers were uncovered at the level of the meso, exo and macro systems. The lack of accessible transportation makes the interaction between the home microsystem and the university microsystem difficult and puts the onus on the student to find a way to get to the university. Similarly, lack of preparation for higher education makes the transition from the secondary school microsystem to the university microsystem difficult. Financial constraints, absence of inclusion policies, and limited employment opportunities are forces operating in the exosystem but their influence reaches the microsystem and ultimately the students. These barriers highlight the pressing need for systemic changes to address the challenges faced by students with disabilities.

Bronfenbrenner's (1989) ecological systems theory reveals the interconnectedness of various factors influencing the experiences of students with disabilities and affecting

the capacity of disability support staff to facilitate their inclusion. At the microsystem level, differences were identified between staff perceptions and the experiences of students with disabilities, with staff highlighting progress in terms of support provision, while students spoke of many challenges. At the level of the mesosystem, the study highlighted the positive influence of family support, and the negative impact of inaccessible transportation and lack of preparation for higher education. Students with disabilities reported that family support, including emotional, academic, and financial assistance, plays a crucial role in enabling them to attend university. However, inaccessible transportation poses challenges for students with disabilities, hindering travel between home and university. Additionally, some students with disabilities encountered challenges when transitioning to higher education because they felt overwhelmed by the academic workload and ill equipped to meet the demands of university life.

A number of external factors situated at the exosystem level influence the experiences of students with disabilities in an indirect way. These include the absence of an inclusion policy and the reluctance of the Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research to make the Disability Support Office an official entity and allocate funding to it. These exosystemic barriers affect the university microsystem and ultimately the students as they limit the capacity of disability support staff to implement changes that can improve the student experience. Absence of an inclusion policy and lack of official endorsement of the Disability Support Office make it difficult for disability support staff to take initiatives and play a more active role in guiding other staff in the development of inclusive practices.

Forces operating in the macrosystem include negative attitudes towards people with disabilities leading to stereotyping, stigma and discrimination. These attitudes are

associated with the medical model, which sees disability as dysfunction and people with disabilities as flawed. This model seems to be prevalent in Algerian society and permeates all systems (Hasroumi and Haffad, 2021). Medical model mentality and negative attitudes towards people with disabilities could explain the limitations in the enforcement of the national disability legislation and policy that are in place in the exosystem. In addition, it could be argued that an ableist culture at the macrosystem is responsible for inaccessible transportation and transition challenges in the mesosystem, and for inadequate support at the university microsystem.

Despite the numerous barriers reported by students with disabilities in this study, these participants revealed that, over time, they have developed a strong sense of self-determination. This has enabled them to navigate the university microsystem and overcome barriers by finding alternative solutions to support themselves. The participants referred to themselves as warriors who refused to surrender to the barriers imposed by the university environment. Their determination and perseverance enabled them to pursue their academic goals despite the challenges they face. However, they should not need to make heroic efforts to pursue their university studies. This is their right and they should be able to exercise it without first needing to remove obstacles blocking their access.

By highlighting different systemic factors that affect the experiences of students with disabilities and the capacity of disability support staff to facilitate their inclusion, the findings of this study underscore the need for comprehensive changes at various levels to create an inclusive and supportive educational environment for students with disabilities. By identifying the barriers that operate within immediate and more distant contexts and by taking action to address them, this university can improve the support

provided for students with disabilities, facilitate their inclusion, and ensure their participation.

6.4 Recommendations

With the increasing number of students with disabilities enrolling in higher education institutions in Algeria (Arroudj, 2019), universities have responsibility to ensure accessibility and support for these students, in order to provide a fair and equitable educational experience for them.

Findings of the present study revealed the willingness and good intentions of disability support officers to facilitate the inclusion of students with disabilities and to provide the support they need to engage with their studies. However, due to a range of structural barriers that undermine the efforts of the disability support staff, the support students receive is not always consistent and sufficient. This puts pressure on students with disabilities to remind staff of the accommodations they need and to seek alternative solutions to overcome the challenges they face. To address this, the university should develop a strategy for inclusive disability support to ensure that every student receives the accommodations they need in an efficient and timely manner.

It was apparent from the findings that the university environment is not welcoming for students with disabilities, given the multiple environmental, structural and attitudinal barriers that they encounter. In addition, it was apparent that structural barriers prevent disability support staff from providing effective and comprehensive support for these students. In these circumstances, it is not surprising that some students do not feel comfortable to disclose their disabilities for fear of being stigmatised and marginalised. Raising awareness about inclusion and disability issues can lead to a shift in attitudes

and perceptions towards disability, which is much needed in the Algerian context(Hasroumi and Haffad, 2021).

This section presents a set of recommendations that have been derived from the findings of this study. These recommendations are provided with the intention of addressing the challenges that have been identified. If implemented, they could help enhance existing practices in order to improve the experiences of students with disabilities at this university. They could also contribute to a much needed culture change that establishes inclusion as a core value and aligns all processes and practices to it. This section will outline these specific recommendations, highlighting their impact on the area of inclusion and disability, and underscoring the significance of their implementation for ensuring a good experience for students with disabilities at university. Emerging from the findings of the present study, these recommendations can be useful to the university where the study was conducted. However, given that the existing (albeit very limited) literature on the experiences of university students in Algeria indicates that the findings of the current study are not unique to this university, these recommendations can be of use and value to the wider higher education community as well.

6.4.1 Recommendations related to the microsystem

The university microsystem has a direct impact on the experience of students with disabilities. Therefore, it is important to ensure that it is a supportive environment, which enables students with disabilities to pursue their academic goals and have positive outcomes. The following points are suggestions and recommendations that could optimize the experiences of students with disabilities at the university microsystem.

Address accessibility challenges

It is crucial that the university takes action to address the accessibility challenges that students with disabilities face. As suggested in several previous studies considering the environmental barriers experienced by university students with disabilities (Morina and Morgado's, 2018; Vlachou and Papananou, 2018; Karellou, 2019; Fathi-Ahmed, 2020; Khayatzadeh-Mahani *et al.*, 2020; Madhesh, 2023), this could be achieved through conducting accessibility audits and evaluations to identify all infrastructural obstacles and plan the necessary refurbishments. These plans should include specific actions that will enable students with disabilities to move independently within and between buildings (Vlachou and Papananou, 2018). Such actions include the provision of quality ramps and elevators, renovation of old buildings, and widening corridors to ensure that they fit wheelchairs. The university should invest in accessible infrastructure to ensure access and inclusion for students with disabilities. University buildings, classrooms, libraries, and dormitories should be fully accessible and equipped with all necessary features to ensure that students with disabilities feel welcome and empowered to learn without worrying about how they will manage to reach the various learning spaces (Fathi-Ahmed, 2020).

Ensure that the educational content is accessible

In line with the conclusions of many previous studies (Black, Weinberg and Brodwin, 2015; Yusof *et al.*, 2019; Bartz, 2020; Biggeri, Masi and Bellaciccao, 2020), the current study highlights the importance of inclusive teaching practices that cater for the diverse needs and preferences of students with disabilities. By incorporating a variety of inclusive approaches in their teaching, academic staff can create an inclusive learning environment that will allow students] with disabilities to fully participate and thrive academically (Yusof *et al.*, 2019). The learning environment can become more

inclusive when academic staff make instructional materials accessible by providing them in alternative formats such as large print, PDFs, and audio, and by uploading them to the e-learning platform (Beyene, Mekonnen and Giannoumis, 2023). The use of visual aids and technological tools can also enhance the learning experience for students with disabilities by providing multiple modalities for accessing information (Nabti, 2018; Pacheco, Yoong and Lips, 2021). This is in line with the principles of Universal Design of Learning (UDL): content should be presented in various formats; there should be variety and choice in how to engage with the learning; students should be given the opportunity to demonstrate what they have learnt in ways that are optimal for them (Black, Weinberg and Brodwin, 2015; Cumming & Rose, 2022; Dalton *et al*, 2019). By embracing and applying these principles, academic staff can ensure that students with disabilities have access to the educational content, which will enable them to participate effectively in learning, contribute to class discussions and activities, and experience success in their assessments (Black, Weinberg and Brodwin, 2015; Fornauf & Erickson, 2020; Cumming & Rose, 2022; Dalton *et al*, 2019).

Enhance academic support

To enhance academic support, the university should invest in assistive technologies and resources (Khumalo, 2019; Olatokunbo, and Patrick, 2019; García-González *et al.*, 2021; Lourens and Swartz, 2020; Pacheco, Yoong and Lips, 2021). Additionally, a shift away from a one-size-fits-all approach is necessary, and a move towards providing individualized learning support tailored to the specific additional support needs of each student (Khumalo, 2019). This should include adapting learning and teaching materials to accommodate diverse learning needs and preferences. Moreover, the assessment system should be inclusive for all students with disabilities.

This can be achieved through the provision of accommodations during exams that are tailored to meet the specific requirements of each student. However, it should be noted that the demand for individualized support is likely to decrease when teaching, learning and assessment are reformed in line with the principles of UDL (Black, Weinberg and Brodwin, 2015; Fornauf & Erickson, 2020; Cumming & Rose, 2022; Dalton *et al*, 2019). This is because UDL encourages flexibility, choice and multimodality in the presentation of content, in students' engagement with the learning, and in assessment (Black, Weinberg and Brodwin, 2015; Fornauf & Erickson, 2020; Cumming & Rose, 2022; Dalton *et al*, 2019). When curriculum and assessment are informed by these principles, they can be accessed by students with diverse needs and preferences. Taking a proactive approach to accessibility through UDL can ensure that the learning environment is inclusive from the outset, however, additional support should also be available for more complex accessibility needs (Black, Weinberg and Brodwin, 2015; Fornauf & Erickson, 2020; Cumming & Rose, 2022; Dalton *et al*, 2019).

Engage students in extracurricular activities

While the disability support staff mentioned that they organize events and activities for students with disabilities, students revealed that they have not been invited to participate. This suggests the need for improvements in the way such opportunities are communicated to students. It also suggests that it would be helpful to involve students with disabilities in the organization of extracurricular activities and events to ensure that these are accessible to all. As noted in the literature, encouraging students with disabilities to lead initiatives and actively involving them in planning social events and activities can make them feel included and valued (Tuomi, Lehtomäki, and Matonya, 2015; Bailey *et al*, 2019; Morina and Biagiotti, 2022). Furthermore, while students with disabilities may appreciate activities and events that have been

organized exclusively for them, it is important to ensure that they have access to all university extracurricular activities and events, and that they feel welcome in them (Abrahams et al, 2023). Universities should ensure that event locations and venues are accessible for all and should provide accommodations such as sign language and assistive technology. By creating an inclusive environment for all students, the university can foster a sense of belonging and can ensure that all students are able to participate fully and engage in all aspects of campus life (Tuomi, Lehtomäki, and Matonya, 2015; Bailey *et al*, 2019; Morina and Biagiotti, 2022). Involving students with disabilities into various university activities and decision-making processes is essential for fostering an inclusive and dynamic campus environment.

Strengthen emotional and counselling services

Findings from the interviews with the students suggest that it is essential to review the processes whereby emotional and psychological support is offered to students with disabilities. While disability support officers mentioned the existence of a counseling service, the students' comments in the interviews suggest that this service does not reach all students with disabilities. This would suggest that it may be helpful to review this service. Involving students with disabilities in the review process can ensure that changes will be effective. A review could lead to the identification of other mechanisms that could be put in place to provide emotional support to students with disabilities. One idea could be that the university should hire additional counselors and mental health professionals who specialize in supporting students with disabilities (Akoto, *et al*, 2022). Moreover, the university should actively raise awareness about the availability of emotional and psychological support services, both through the Disability Support Office and within the broader university community (Khazaleh et al, 2022).

Finally, it may be useful to consider the development of peer support programmes where appropriately trained and effectively supervised peers can provide emotional support to students with disabilities.

Facilitate collaboration between disability support staff and students with disabilities

Collaboration between disability support staff and students with disabilities is vital to ensure that students are effectively supported and included within the university settings (Behling and Linder, 2017; Garcia-Melgar et al, 2022). Disability support staff should actively engage students with disabilities by providing them with information and support to help them understand their rights and available accommodations. The processes whereby students register with the Disability Support Office should be reviewed to ensure that they are efficient and student-centered. Workshops and peer mentoring programs could be helpful in reducing the concerns students with disabilities may have about disclosure. Ongoing communication between disability support staff and students with disabilities can facilitate the identification and resolution of barriers to access, and the development of individualized support plans (Carballo et al, 2022). Moreover, it is crucial to consider the perspectives and input of students with disabilities when making decisions about accommodations, learning facilities, social spaces, and physical activities (Garrison-Wade, 2012). By actively involving students with disabilities in these discussions, the university can ensure that their additional support requirements and preferences are taken into account, ultimately leading to a more inclusive and accommodating environment. This collaborative approach can ensure that students with disabilities receive the support they need to thrive academically, and can enhance their overall university experience.

Encourage advocacy and disclosure

To foster a culture of openness and support, it is important for the university to encourage students to disclose their disabilities (Cunnah, 2015; Bell, Car and Swart, 2016). This can be achieved through various means, such as awareness campaigns, and orientation sessions. The university should provide clear information on the steps involved in disclosing disabilities and on the available support systems to alleviate any concerns or fears that students may have. It should be emphasized that disclosure is voluntary, and that confidentiality is maintained throughout the process. By creating a welcoming environment and highlighting the benefits of disclosure, such as access to appropriate accommodations and support services, the university can demonstrate its commitment to inclusivity and can encourage students with disabilities to advocate for their rights (Cole and Cawthon, 2015).

It is also important to provide multiple avenues for disclosure and support advocacy (Cunnah, 2015; Bell, Car and Swart, 2016). The university should establish various channels for this purpose. This could include the development of an online portal where students can confidentially disclose their disabilities and specify their accommodation requirements. Additionally, offering options like email or in-person meetings with disability support staff can create opportunities for personalized communication and can ensure that students with disabilities feel comfortable and empowered to advocate for their rights. Providing multiple channels for disclosure not only enhances the accessibility of the accommodation process but also acknowledges the diverse preferences and circumstances of students with disabilities (Cole and Cawthon, 2015). By offering these flexible avenues, the university can engage effectively with students with disabilities, facilitate timely accommodation arrangements, and promote a supportive and inclusive educational environment.

Provide financial support for students with disabilities

To ensure equal access to educational opportunities for students with disabilities in Algeria, it is crucial to address their specific financial challenges. As noted earlier, while university students receive a stipend, students with disabilities are excluded from this because they receive a disability stipend. However, the students who participated in this study pointed out that this stipend is not sufficient to cover their costs while at university. To ensure equitable access to educational opportunities for students with disabilities, it is crucial to provide them with additional financial support tailored to their individual needs (Odame et al., 2021; Hector, 2020; Abrahams et al., 2023). This financial support should go beyond any existing financial aid programs based on disability. It should be designed to specifically address the costs associated with necessary accommodations and assistive technology that students with disabilities require to fully participate in university (Odame et al., 2016; Hewett et al., 2017; Abrahams et al., 2023). This may include funding for specialized software, adaptive devices, or other assistive aids. Moreover, the financial support should also consider the additional expenses related to their disabilities, such as medical costs or therapy sessions. This could involve covering expenses for healthcare services, rehabilitation programs, or ongoing treatments that are essential for the well-being and success of students with disabilities. While the issue of financial support for university students with disabilities should be addressed at the exosystem, through a review of the stipend paid to people with disabilities and consideration of the additional costs they may incur while studying at university, the university should also consider how they may support students with disabilities financially. It could be argued that, if the university is not able to fund the work required to make the physical environment accessible and to provide accessible learning resources, offering financial support to students with disabilities

may lie outside the sphere of possibility. However, a review of the university's use of its financial resources may help identify funds that could be used to support students with disabilities. Such a review would require the involvement of students with disabilities and disability support staff whose understanding of the issue could be instrumental for the development of effective solutions. Such solutions could ensure that students with disabilities are not hindered by financial constraints and can fully engage in their academic pursuits without extra financial stress (Odame et al., 2021; Fox et al., 2022; Hector, 2020; Abrahams et al., 2023). Providing financial support that caters to the specific needs of students with disabilities, the university can help alleviate the financial burden they may experience and ensure they have access to educational resources and opportunities.

Provide financial support for the Disability Support Office

The study revealed that the Disability Support Office does not have official status and does not receive financial assistance from the state. In line with findings from previous studies (Behling and Linder, 2017; Fossey et al., 2017; Polo Sánchez, Fernández-Jiménez, and Cabezas, 2018; Khumalo, 2019; Lopez-Gavira, Moriña and Morgado, 2021), the findings indicate that the Disability Support Office can play an important role in facilitating inclusion for university students with disabilities. For this reason, officials within the Ministry of Higher Education should recognise the contribution such an office can make in universities across the country and should ensure that an official disability support service is established in every university. Until this happens, it is recommended that the Disability Support Office at this university is allocated funding from the university budget, to enable its members to purchase necessary equipment and arrange accommodations for students with disabilities. The financial support could also help to provide training for staff in the office, allowing them to better understand

the additional support needs of students with disabilities and how to provide effective support. Furthermore, it can facilitate the recruitment of specialized staff who can provide specialist support to students, including disability advisors, sign language interpreters, note-takers, and stakeholders. Ultimately, providing financial support to the Disability Support Office could help to ensure that students with disabilities have the resources and accommodations necessary to succeed in higher education, which could lead to increased opportunities and more positive outcomes for these students (Behling and Linder, 2017; Fossey et al., 2017; Lopez-Gavira, Moraña and Morgado, 2021).

Provide training for the Disability Support Office and academics

The study revealed that disability support officers received training in the early 2010s, and there has been a lack of professional development opportunities for them since then. In line with the conclusions of previous research (Hewett et al., 2017; Vlachou and Papananou, 2018; Carballo, Morgado and Cortés-Vega, 2021), it is recommended that the university should invest in comprehensive training programmes to provide inclusion related training not only for disability support staff but also for academics and administrative staff so that they can assist students with disabilities effectively. This should include disability awareness training, training on assistive technology and adaptive equipment, but also training on how to tailor accommodations and support to specific needs rather than offer a one size fits all type of support (Hewett et al., 2017; Vlachou and Papananou, 2018; Carballo, Morgado and Cortés-Vega, 2021). Furthermore, the training should be ongoing and should incorporate opportunities for continuous learning and professional growth. As understanding and best practices in disability support evolve, regular updates should be provided to ensure that disability support staff and academics stay informed and equipped with the latest knowledge

and skills on inclusion and how to accommodate students with disabilities(Kendal, 2016, 2018; Carballo, Morgado and Cortés-Vega, 2021; Hector, 2020).

Facilitate collaboration between staff across the university

The study revealed limited opportunities for collaboration and cooperative work between university staff. Therefore, in line with the conclusions of previous studies (Young & Schaefer, 2019; de la Torre, Calleja & Erro-Garcés, 2023)it is recommended that the university should consider how to encourage and facilitate collaboration between different staff, departments and entities. A climate of collaboration can promote efficiency and can lead to improvements in the support provided to students with disabilities(Carballo, Morgado and Cortés-Vega, 2021). Collaboration could include students with disabilities, the disability support officers, academics, administration team, residency team, and student union. To facilitate collaboration, regular meetings should be organized and efficient communication channels should be established to discuss issues related to disability support services and accommodations, to negotiate solutions and to ensure that support is provided consistently across all departments. Collaboration will create opportunities to share practices, solutions and suggestions that can be beneficial to students with disabilities. For example, the Disability Support Office can share insights on effective accommodation strategies, academics can discuss inclusive teaching methods, and the student union can bring the concerns and issues of students with disabilities to the attention of the university authorities. Through the exchange of knowledge, expertise and information, the different parties can gain insights from one another and this can lead to improvements in their collective capacity to provide effective support for students with disabilities(Young & Schaefer, 2019; Carballo, Morgado and Cortés-Vega, 2021; de la Torre, Calleja & Erro-Garcés, 2023).

6.2.2 Recommendations related to the mesosystem

The mesosystem is the space where microsystems interact. Microsystems are interconnected and exert influence on each other. The university microsystem is connected with the students' home microsystem, but also with other educational settings such as the high school students attended before they started university(Lindsay et al., 2018; Akoto et al., 2022). The mesosystem is also the space where the university microsystem interacts with community microsystems, such as local disability groups and associations. Finally, in the mesosystem universities interact with each other. Through sharing practices and resources, they can influence the experiences of their students. Echoing findings of previous research(Lindsay et al., 2018; Kimball & Thoma, 2019; Kitchen et al., 2019; Akoto et al., 2022), the findings of the current study suggest that positive interactions of the various microsystems in the mesosystem can strengthen the capacity of the university microsystem to include students with disabilities and support them effectively. The following recommendations focus on this.

Provide transition support

Concurring with findings in previous research (Gil, 2007; Lindsay et al., 2018; Meehan and Howell, 2019; Pacheco, Yoong and Lips, 2021), students with disabilities in this study reported that they were unprepared for university life, as they have found it really challenging to adapt to the academic demands and responsibilities, particularly during their first year at university. This underscores the importance of preparing students with disabilities for university life. To effectively prepare students with disabilities for the transition to higher education, high schools should offer transition programs which should be developed in collaboration with universities (Eckes and Ochoa, 2005; Pacheco, Yoong and Lips, 2021). These programs should anticipate the challenges

that students with disabilities may encounter at university and should equip them with information and skills that will enable them to overcome these challenges. Furthermore, universities should establish dedicated transition support services to offer students with disabilities guidance on course selection, academic life, and available support services(Gil, 2007). Peer mentoring programs can also be implemented to connect new university students with disabilities with continuing students with disabilities who have already navigated the transition to higher education(Morina, 2017).

Provide accessible transportation

Similar to previous research (Moriña and Morgado, 2018; Yusof *et al.*, 2019;Fathi-Ahmed, 2020), the current study identified inaccessible transportation as a significant challenge for students with disabilities as it prevents them from being able to travel to the university independently. While, like the financial support discussed above, the reform of the transportation infrastructure is a matter that should be addressed at the exosystemic level, there may be actions that can be taken at a more local level. Joining forces with disability organisations and the local community, the university could identify ways to make travel to the university more accessible for students with disabilities (Yusof *et al.*, 2019).

Facilitate collaboration between educational microsystems

Another recommendation arising from this study is that there should be collaboration between different universities and between universities and educational establishments in other sectors(primary, middle and high schools). As noted in the literature (Bartz, 2020; Hector, 2020; Pacheco, Yoong and Lips, 2021),this is important as it can facilitate the sharing of expertise, knowledge, resources, and practices about inclusion and support for students with disabilities. It could be done through

conferences and workshops that can provide opportunities to staff from different educational establishments to work together in order to develop more welcoming and more supportive educational institutions across the different sectors(Pacheco, Yoong and Lips, 2021).

Facilitate collaboration between the university and local disability groups

Collaboration between the university and local disability advocacy groups can also be useful. By fostering partnerships and encouraging the sharing of resources, knowledge and best practices, the university can enhance its capacity to meet the diverse needs of students with disabilities(Chiang, 2020; Garberoglio, 2020). By engaging with local disability and advocacy groups and organizations, the university can access and benefit from the specific expertise and specialized knowledge that these external organizations and advocacy groups have(Garberoglio, 2020). This collaboration can facilitate the exchange of information, resources, and training opportunities, enabling the university to enhance its support services. Ultimately, fostering collaboration between the university microsystem and local disability and advocacy groups can lead to improved outcomes, increased opportunities, and a more inclusive higher education environment for students with disabilities(Chiang, 2020; Garberoglio, 2020).

6.4.3 Recommendations related to the exosystem

Although outside of the students' direct circle of influence, the exosystem seems to play a significant role in shaping the experiences of students with disabilities at this university. Echoing findings from previous research(Bouaicha, 2017; Meeks, Herzer and Jain, 2018; Arib, 2021), findings from the interviews with the students with disabilities and the disability support staff revealed that due to structural barriers caused by external factors, students face various challenges. The following

recommendations are aimed at the exosystem on the basis that, improvements in the exosystem will exert a positive influence on the inner circles (mesosystem and microsystem) and, ultimately, will lead to improvements in the experiences of students with disabilities.

Create a university inclusion policy

The study identified the absence of a university inclusion policy as a structural barrier that contributes to the marginalisation of students with disabilities. The students with disabilities who participated in the study stated that they were not aware of the existence of a policy that promotes inclusion at university, but such policy does not exist in the first place, as confirmed by the disability support staff. The disability support staff stated that policies that support and promote the inclusion of individuals with disabilities are in place for primary, middle, and high schools and in the health service. This is confirmed by existing literature (Boutebal and Yahi, 2018; Fekih, 2018). A need to create inclusive higher education policies has been highlighted in the present study but also in earlier studies (Kendall, 2016; Tudzi, Bugri and Danso, 2017; Yusof et al, 2020; Lindsay et al, 2018). While, as noted earlier, by itself, a policy cannot guarantee the meaningful inclusion of university students with disabilities, it can provide a framework and benchmarks that universities can use to develop inclusive practices. An inclusion policy can promote accountability across university services and can give students with disabilities more confidence to advocate for their rights.

In line with existing literature (Evans et al., 2017; Hitch, Macfarlane and Nihill, 2015), it is recommended that policymakers, in collaboration with disability organisations, university staff and students work towards developing a policy that can promote the inclusion of students with disabilities in higher education institutions in the Algerian context. Such a policy must adhere to both international standards and conventions,

as well as Algerian national legislation for people with disabilities. The policy should specify precisely the entitlements, support services, and accommodations that should be available for students with disabilities and the responsibilities of the university in offering support. Following this, a system should be implemented to evaluate the effectiveness of policy implementation. This can include regular evaluations of the accessibility of the physical and learning infrastructure, tracking the provision of accommodations and support services, collecting feedback from students with disabilities, and conducting observations and reviews to address any gaps or emerging issues (Hitch, Macfarlane and Nihill, 2015).

Make the disability support office official

Given how significant the contribution of disability support services is, as noted in the literature (Moriña, López-Gavira and Morgado 2017) and in the findings of the present study, another recommendation for policy makers operating in the exosystem is to give the Disability Support Office official status within the university structure. This would recognise the importance of disability support services and provide them with the resources needed to facilitate the inclusion of students with disabilities. Making the Disability Support Office official involves securing an accessible physical space for it, hiring trained staff members who specialize in disability support services, and allocating a budget to it. Making the Disability Support Office official in this university and initiating the creation of Disability Support Offices in universities across the country could serve as an indication of the Algerian state's commitment to provide equitable opportunities and support for students with disabilities. This would facilitate access to accommodations and services, and would enable students with disabilities to identify the office as one of the main support mechanisms at university and to engage with it in a more structured and efficient manner.

Improve employment opportunities for people with disabilities

The findings of this study revealed a concerning issue that is related to the low quota (1%) of individuals with disabilities employers are obliged to hire in Algeria. Not only that but, as noted earlier, this policy is not enforced by the state, which results in many employers ignoring it (Rohwerder, 2018). Consequently, there is significant under-representation of individuals with disabilities in the Algerian society, which explains the concerns expressed by the students who participated in the study regarding their employment opportunities. Barriers faced by students with disabilities transitioning to workplace have also been reported in previous studies (Vlachou and Papananou, 2018; Hector, 2020). These studies recommended that governments should establish a system that provides continuous support for individuals with disabilities to ensure a seamless transition from educational settings to the workplace. Therefore, state officials with responsibility for employment matters in Algeria should work with disability organizations to develop strategies that can improve employment rates for people with disabilities. It is also important to ensure that workplace settings are accessible and inclusive.

6.4.4 Recommendations related to the macrosystem

Aligned with findings from previous research (Lindsay et al., 2018; Kimball and Thoma, 2019), the findings of the present study indicate that the macrosystem has a profound impact on the experiences of students with disabilities. Acknowledging the importance of outside influences that stem from the macrosystem, including societal attitudes towards disability, it would be useful to consider what actions can contribute to a cultural shift away from the medical model of disability and towards recognition of the role of the environment in shaping the experiences and outcomes of people with disabilities (Edna, 2016; Polo Sánchez, Fernández-Jiménez, and Cabezas, 2018;).

Enforce disability legislation

To ensure that individuals with disabilities can enjoy their rights at all levels, and to eliminate discrimination, disability rights legislation must be enforced and effectively implemented (Morina and Perera, 2020). Enacting legislation that protects the rights of individuals with disabilities is a way to preserve their rights. However, it is important to recognize that legislation alone is not sufficient to address all the barriers faced by individuals with disabilities. In order to promote inclusion, it is necessary to complement such legislation with effective practice, and any failure to comply with it should be penalized (Morina and Morgado, 2018). Practice that focuses on removing environmental barriers and promoting accessibility can facilitate the inclusion and effective participation of people with disabilities across societal contexts and sectors. This can help dispel stereotypes that see disability as a deficit and personal tragedy, can improve attitudes toward people with disabilities, and can reduce discrimination.

Promote disability awareness

Echoing findings of previous research (Martins, Morges, and Gonçalves, 2018; Polo Sánchez, Fernández-Jiménez, and Cabezas, 2018), the findings of this study highlighted the detrimental impact of negative attitudes towards students with disabilities. This highlights the importance of raising disability awareness across education sectors and community contexts (Yusof *et al*, 2019). This can be done through projects, events and campaigns that promote disability awareness and inclusion. Such initiatives can help develop a better understanding of disability, and can contribute to the decrease of discrimination, stereotyping and marginalization of individuals with disabilities (Yusof *et al*, 2019). One way to make such initiatives effective is to incorporate them in the education curriculum across sectors, primary, middle, secondary and university. Learning about disability and seeing disability in a

positive light through disability awareness talks, activities, books, videos and other resources can help students develop more positive attitudes towards people with disabilities. Through the students' interactions in their microsystem, these positive attitudes can influence the attitudes of the local community, and, ultimately, penetrate the outer systems leading to a more inclusive culture in Algerian society.

6.5 Study contributions

My aim in conducting this study was to explore an important topic that is under researched in my home country, Algeria. As noted in chapter 1, studies on the experiences of students with disabilities in Algerian universities are scarce. My extensive search identified one study in English (Arib, 2020), two in Arabic (Bouaicha, 2017; Djedidi and Djedidi, 2018), and two in French (Zoreli, 2018 and Nabti, 2018, which is a master's dissertation). My findings echo and extend the findings of these studies. By giving students with disabilities and disability support staff in one Algerian university the opportunity to share their experiences and perspectives, my study makes a significant contribution to the limited knowledge about the inclusion of students with disabilities in Algerian higher education. In addition, the study makes a contribution to the growing body of international research on the experiences of university students with disabilities by providing insights from an untapped context: Algeria.

To my knowledge, this is the first study to use IPA to research an education topic in Algeria and Bronfenbrenner's (1989) ecological systems theory to contextualise the findings. The study makes a significant contribution to Algerian educational research by demonstrating the value of IPA in illuminating educational phenomena. Furthermore, the study makes a contribution to the limited body of international

research using IPA to examine the lived experiences of university students with disabilities.

The use of Bronfenbrenner's (1989) ecological systems theory enabled me to situate barriers and facilitators to the inclusion of students with disabilities within the students' immediate and broader contexts. As a result, the study makes a contribution to policy and practice by highlighting areas that could be improved and by making specific recommendations which, if implemented, can enhance the experiences of students with disabilities in higher education. While some of these recommendations require action at the exosystem and macrosystem, which are beyond the influence of students and staff, others can be applied in the university microsystem and can lead to concrete improvements for the students with disabilities not only in this university but in other universities as well.

6.6 Limitations

While the study produced rich findings leading to a series of recommendations, it has a number of limitations:

- While the methodology used provided data rich in depth and detail, the findings cannot be generalised to other contexts due to the small sample size of nine students and four disability support officers. In addition, the participants were recruited through the Disability Support Office or, in the case of seven of the students, through friend referral. Because of this, it should be acknowledged that the findings may be unique to this group and those who received the invitation to participate in the study but chose not to do so may have different experiences and perspectives.

- Another limitation is that the data were collected via online interviews through platforms such as Zoom. Face-to-face interviews and spending more time with the participants could have revealed information that has not been captured in this study.
- Yet another limitation is my positionality. Being Algerian and able-bodied is likely to have influenced my interactions with the participants and ultimately their responses. For example, participants may have omitted details they assumed I would know because I am from Algeria. Similarly, information might have been left out by students with disabilities on the assumption that I would not understand because I do not have a disability.
- Finally, while the focus of the study was on university students with disabilities, I recognise that disability is only one aspect of an individual's identity. Other characteristics such as age and gender intersect with disability to create experiences that are unique to each individual. It is inevitable that the intersectionality of disability, age, gender and other characteristics will have an impact on the experiences of university students with disabilities and it is likely that tapping into this could have provided additional insights. While I acknowledge this, it should be noted that none of the students made any reference to their gender, age or other characteristic during the interviews. Had they done so, I would have followed up on it

6.7 Recommendations for future research

This study investigated the lived experiences of students with disabilities and the processes used by disability support staff to facilitate their inclusion in one Algerian university. Using IPA as a qualitative design, the study elicited firsthand experiences

from the participants. Data were gathered from students with disabilities and disability support staff through semi-structured interviews. This design facilitated a deep understanding of the experiences of students with disabilities and the perspectives of disability support staff. The study offers valuable insights into the factors that affect the university experience of the students and the capacity of the disability support staff to remove barriers to their access and participation. However, it is recognized that more research is needed to complement and extend the findings of the current study.

- Future research can adopt a transformative paradigm (Mertens, 2008). The transformative paradigm is informed by social justice principles and used by researchers who wish to contribute to the elimination of inequalities. In a transformative study, students with disabilities can be invited to become co-researchers. The study can take the form of an action research project offering opportunities to implement improvements and evaluate their impact.
- Future research can recruit participants from other Algerian universities to provide a broader picture of the experiences of students with disabilities at Algerian universities and the support offered to them. Researching this topic in multiple universities could provide a more diverse range of perspectives and more holistic understanding of what improvements are needed.
- Future research may consider using other data collections tools e.g. focus groups and diaries. The use of focus groups can facilitate the emergence of collective experiences and can provide the participants with the chance to interact and exchange ideas, perceptions and thoughts on different aspects of their university experience, which might not be possible to capture through individual interviews. Moreover, the use of diaries will allow the researcher to gain access to thoughts, opinions, and ideas as they occur to the participants,

rather than relying on their accounts of experiences that happened in the past. This will enable participants to keep track of important changes, and to describe how they are experiencing the phenomenon as it evolves and as it develops over a given period of time.

- Future research may consider focusing on only one type of disability. This can provide valuable insights and in-depth understanding of the experiences of students with this particular disability, and the type of accommodations and support they need.
- Future research can include the voices of other stakeholders, such as academic and administrative staff, and peers without disabilities. Their perspectives can provide important insights into the university microsystem illuminating aspects that were not captured in the current study.
- Future research could employ a mixed methods approach to investigate the topic. Combining both qualitative and quantitative methods will allow the researcher to capture both depth and breadth. Using qualitative methods will allow for nuanced perceptions, and in-depth understanding of the topic. On the other hand, using quantitative methods such as questionnaires to collect numerical data will provide triangulation and generalizability of the study's findings and conclusions.
- Further research could explore the experiences of individuals with disabilities after graduation, as they join the job market. This can provide valuable insights about employability skills that universities may need to build into their programmes to support students with disabilities in their transition to the workplace.

- Future research can investigate the transition of students with disabilities from high school to higher education, to understand the transition pathways, experiences and needs of students with disabilities making this transition.
- Future research may consider analyzing national inclusive policy and legislation documents. By understanding how inclusive policies and legislation are developed and implemented, researchers can contribute to the development of more effective and equitable policies in the future. Additionally, such research could shed light on the barriers that hinder the implementation of inclusive policies and provide insights into how these barriers can be overcome.

6.8 Reflections on my PhD journey

I started my PhD journey in November 2019. Having established the dearth of previous studies of relevance to my topic that were conducted in Algeria, I delved into the international literature. My reading indicated that university students with disabilities experience challenges everywhere, not only in countries where inclusion and equality may be under-developed and universities may be under-resourced. I found this surprising as I had thought that, in countries with well established inclusive education systems and equality legislation, university students with disabilities will not face barriers. However, as I progressed with my reading, a pattern of environmental, structural and attitudinal barriers emerged from across the international literature.

While I was conducting my literature review, the COVID 19 pandemic occurred. The closing of the university and the general lockdown unsettled me but I continued with my literature review as it gave me purpose. Once I compiled a draft literature review, I started working on my methodology. While I was working on the literature review, I kept thinking about my topic and considering what methodology would be a good fit

for it. Listening to insider voices emerged as particularly important from the literature and is very well aligned with my own worldview. This led me to explore qualitative methodologies. I eventually chose IPA because it considers cases individually as well as well as holistically. This resonated with my belief that individuals can experience the same phenomenon differently and because of this it is important to consider individual perspectives. The double hermeneutics also resonated with me because it acknowledges that, ultimately, the researcher interprets the participants' interpretations of their experiences. Once I decided to use IPA, I immersed myself in the IPA literature, both methodological texts but also educational research that has used IPA methodology. I attended a masterclass offered by Jonathan Smith, the founder of IPA, and became a member of the online IPA group he co-leads with his colleague Michael Larkin. Looking back, I feel a sense of pride at the depth of understanding of IPA I have developed. I have come a long way from the apprehension I felt when I started reading up on it.

I approached the first interview with trepidation but I felt at ease as soon as the participant started talking. I had prepared prompts but they were not necessary as this and the other participants had a lot to say and there were no silences that I needed to fill. During the interviews I tried to maintain a neutral stance and to make my presence as non-obtrusive as possible. I could sense strong emotions in the participants' accounts. In the students' accounts I could detect passion for their studies, pride for their achievements but also anger at what they perceived as injustices, anxiety due to the impact of environmental barriers on their progress, sadness at being stereotyped, misunderstood and marginalised. In the disability support officers' accounts I could detect passion for the work they do for the Disability Support Office, pride for the improvements they have been able to instigate, but also disappointment at some of

their academic and administration colleagues' lack of interest to make their practices more inclusive, and frustration at the lack of recognition of the work of the Disability Support Office by the state. These emotions lingered well after the interviews. To process them, I wrote my thoughts in my diary and discussed them with my supervisor.

When I contacted the university to ask permission to recruit participants for my research, I had no idea that the Disability Support Office is not an official entity and that the disability support officers are volunteers. I was very surprised to hear this during the first interview with disability support staff. I was saddened by some of the experiences the students shared with me, especially those that involved negative attitudes and discrimination from academic staff. While I could not offer any practical support to these students, I sensed that they appreciated the opportunity to share their experiences. I will disseminate my findings to the university, to the Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research, and to other authorities who may be able to take some action to improve the experiences of students with disabilities in this university and in Algerian higher education more broadly.

Analysing the data was a lengthy, challenging, but also rewarding process. Doing the analysis manually with post-it notes, highlighters, pen and paper helped me develop deep understanding of each case and of all the cases holistically. Moving from the parts to the whole and back again allowed the themes to emerge organically. Seeing how the themes fitted in the theoretical framework felt like puzzle pieces coming together to create a picture. Bringing all the elements together to create this thesis was a laborious and often overwhelming task but I experienced a great sense of achievement when I reached the end.

Looking back at my PhD journey, I feel that I have grown and matured considerably. I have developed confidence and competence as a researcher, and have completed a study that I consider to be worthwhile, not only because of the contribution to knowledge that it makes, but also because of the potential the findings and recommendations have to lead to improvements. I am returning to Algeria determined to bring the findings to the attention of everyone who can put them to good use. I am also determined to use the findings to inform my own practice and to work with colleagues develop inclusive academic environments where all students feel welcome, appreciated and supported to achieve their goals.

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Appendix 1: Permission from the disability support office

République Algérienne Démocratique et Populaire
Ministère de l'Enseignement Supérieur et de la Recherche Scientifique

Mme Fatma Bouabida PhD

Personal details withheld.

Autorisation de récolter des informations et données, produites par [redacted] relatives à l'accompagnement des étudiants en situation de handicap

Par cette présente autorisation, nous donnons notre accord à Mme Bouabida Fatma, PhD Université de West of Scotland (UWS), qui mène une étude intitulée : 'Support Provision for Students with Disabilities in Algerian Higher Education', *de récolter les données relatives à l'accompagnement des étudiants avec handicaps*, au sein de l'université

L'autorisation est délivrée conformément à l'autorisation de l'université à effectuer la recherche doctorale à l'université 'A'

Cette étude va s'intéresser aux Dispositifs d'accompagnement des étudiants en situation de handicap dans l'enseignement supérieur algérien : opportunités, défis et perspectives d'avenir ; cas de l'université

Cette autorisation fait foi de consentement à mener l'étude intitulée : 'Support Provision for Students with Disabilities in Algerian Higher Education'

Le 07/03/2022

Appendix 2: Ethical approval from the University of the West of Scotland

07/06/2021

Dear Fatma Bouabida,

Your application 16412: Support Provision for Students with Disabilities in Algerian Higher Education: Opportunities, Challenges and Future prospects, submission 13700, has been approved by the Education and Social Sciences SEC. You may now proceed with your study. If you wish to make any significant changes to the study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Title

What is the expected duration of participation in the study for each participant?

Comment

the questions scheduled are extensive - it is likely that they will take longer than the allocated time to discuss and participants should be aware of this. Please discuss with your supervisor and consider revising either the length of the interview or the detail in the questions in order to clarify expectations for participants.

Good luck with your research.

Dr Iain McPhee

Appendix 3: Correspondence to the gatekeeper

08-04-2021

Personal details withheld.

Fatma Bouabida

PhD Researcher

REQUEST FOR PERMISSION TO CONDUCT RESEARCH

To whom it may concern,

My name is Fatma Bouabida and I am a PhD student in the University of the West of Scotland (UWS). The title of my PhD is:

Voices on inclusion: an IPA study of the lived experiences of students with disabilities and the perspectives of disability support staff in one Algerian university.

As part of my PhD I will undertake a study which will aim to answer the following question:

1. What are the lived experiences of students with disabilities in Algerian higher education?
2. How do disability support staff facilitate the inclusion of students with disabilities in Algerian higher education?

The purpose of my study is to:

- To explore and understand the lived experiences of students with disabilities in Algerian higher education, including factors that facilitate and hinder their participation and achievement.
- To identify the needs of students with disabilities in Algerian higher education and convey their recommendations for improving their overall experience and academic success.

- To understand the processes used by disability support staff to facilitate the inclusion of students with disabilities in Algerian higher education, and the factors that affect their efforts.
- To investigate the effectiveness of existing support services and accommodations provided by Algerian higher education institutions and identify areas for improvement to better meet the additional support needs of students with disabilities.

I intend to collect data through interviews with students with disabilities and disability officers supporting students with disabilities. Any information provided during the interviews that could lead to the identification of the participants or the university will be removed or pseudonymised. The invitation for potential participants, and the questions I intend to ask during the interviews are provided at the end of this letter for information. It is hoped that the findings of this study will provide valuable insights into the academic experiences of students with disabilities in this university and of the staff working with them. These insights can highlight effective practices that could be of interest and use to other universities. The findings could also lead to recommendations that can be used to enhance the quality of support provided to students with disabilities in Higher Education.

The research will have possible benefits, as it will provide participants with the opportunity to share their experiences, highlight effective practice, and make suggestions for any improvements that they might consider beneficial. Resulting conclusions may be of value to your university and to other Higher Education Institutions in Algeria and more widely. A report of the findings of the study will be sent to all participants.

This study has already been approved by the UWS Ethics committee. I would be grateful if you give me permission to conduct the study in your University. If you agree to this, my intention would be to approach the University's Disability Office and ask that the information about the study is sent to students who are registered with the Disability Office, academic staff who teach students with disabilities, and disability officers who support students with disabilities. If you give permission for my study to be conducted at your University, I would be grateful if you or someone might email me at B00376402@studentmail.uws.ac.uk, detailing the necessary steps I should take to proceed with this study.

My supervisor is Dr Lisa McAuliffe, a senior lecturer at the University of the West of Scotland. Her email address is: lisa.mcauliffe@uws.ac.uk. You can contact her or myself at any stage of the research should you have questions.

Thank you very much for taking the time to consider my request.

Yours sincerely,

Fatma Bouabida

University of the West of Scotland,

High Street,

Paisley,

PA1 2BE

UK

[REDACTED]

Personal details withheld.

Appendix 4: Participant information sheet for students with disabilities

Participant Information sheet for students with disabilities

Study title

Voices on inclusion: an IPA study of the lived experiences of students with disabilities and the perspectives of disability support staff in one Algerian university.

My name is Fatma Bouabida and I am a PhD student in the University of the West of Scotland (UWS). As part of my PhD I will conduct a research study and I am inviting you to take part in it. Before you decide, it is important for you to understand why the research is being done and what it will involve. Please take time to read the following information carefully and discuss it with others if you wish. Please ask me if there is anything that is not clear or if you would like more information. Take time to decide whether or not you wish to take part.

What is the purpose of this study?

The purpose of this study is to:

- To explore and understand the lived experiences of students with disabilities in Algerian higher education, including factors that facilitate and hinder their participation and achievement.
- To identify the needs of students with disabilities in Algerian higher education and convey their recommendations for improving their overall experience and academic success.
- To understand the processes used by disability support staff to facilitate the inclusion of students with disabilities in Algerian higher education, and the factors that affect their efforts.
- To investigate the effectiveness of existing support services and accommodations provided by Algerian higher education institutions and identify areas for improvement to better meet the needs of students with disabilities.

Why have I been chosen?

You have been chosen to take part in this study because you are a student in an Algerian University and have registered with the Disability Office.

Do I have to take part?

It is up to you to decide whether or not to take part. If you do decide to take part you will be asked to sign a consent form. If you decide to take part you are still free to withdraw without giving a reason at any time until April 2022 when the analysis of the data will commence.

What will I do if I take part?

Your participation in the study will involve an interview with me at a date and time that is convenient to you. The interview will last between 30-45 minutes and will take place face-to-face in a mutually agreed quiet place in or near the university, eg in one of the library study rooms, or online via Zoom or Stream-Yard application. With your agreement, I will record the interview so that I can have an accurate version of your responses. A list of the questions I would like to ask you can be found below. You can skip any questions that you do not wish to answer and provide any additional information that you consider to be relevant to the purpose of my study. If you think this would be helpful, you can have a companion of your choice with you during the interview.

What are the possible disadvantages and risks of taking part?

There are no possible disadvantages or risks associated with taking part in this study.

What are the possible benefits of taking part?

The research will have possible benefits, as it will provide you with the opportunity to share your experiences, highlight effective practice, and make suggestions for any improvements that you might consider beneficial. Resulting conclusions may be of value to your university and to other Higher Education Institutions in Algeria and more widely. A report of the findings of the study will be sent to all participants.

Data Protection Privacy Notice

The data controller for this project will be University of the West of Scotland (UWS). The UWS Data Protection Office provides oversight of UWS activities involving the processing of personal data and can be contacted at dataprotection@uws.ac.uk. UWS's Data Protection Officer is Emma Cockrow and can be contacted at dataprotection@uws.ac.uk.

Any personal data you provide will be pseudonymised. This means that I will replace with pseudonyms your name, the name of the University and any other details that could lead to your identification. This will ensure that you will not be identified in the PhD thesis and in publications and presentations arising from the study.

If you are concerned about how your personal data is being processed, please contact UWS in the first instance at dataprotection@uws.ac.uk. If you remain unsatisfied, you may wish to contact the Information Commissioner's Office (ICO). Contact details, and details of data subject rights, are available on the ICO website at: <https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/data-protection-reform/overview-of-the-gdpr/individuals-rights/>

What will happen to the results of the research study?

The results of this study will be disseminated through the PhD thesis, presentations and publications such as journal articles.

Who has reviewed the study?

ESS Ethics Committee

Contact for further information

If you require any further information please contact:

Researcher:

Fatma Bouabida

University of the West of Scotland,

High Street,

Paisley,

PA1 2BE

UK

Telephone: .xxxxxxxxxxxxxx

E-mail address: [REDACTED]

Research Supervisor:

Dr Lisa McAuliffe

University of the West of Scotland,

High Street,

Paisley,

PA1 2BE

UK

Telephone: .

E-mail address: [REDACTED]

Personal details withheld.

Thank you for considering my invitation to take part in my research.

Appendix 5: Participants information sheet for disability support staff

Participant Information sheet for disability support staff

Study title

Voices on inclusion: an IPA study of the lived experiences of students with disabilities and the perspectives of disability support staff in one Algerian university.

My name is Fatma Bouabida and I am a PhD student in the University of the West of Scotland (UWS). As part of my PhD I will conduct a research study and I am inviting you to take part in it. Before you decide, it is important for you to understand why the research is being done and what it will involve. Please take time to read the following information carefully and discuss it with others if you wish. Please ask me if there is anything that is not clear or if you would like more information. Take time to decide whether or not you wish to take part.

What is the purpose of this study?

The purpose of this study is to:

- To explore and understand the lived experiences of students with disabilities in Algerian higher education, including factors that facilitate and hinder their participation and achievement.
- To identify the needs of students with disabilities in Algerian higher education and convey their recommendations for improving their overall experience and academic success.
- To understand the processes used by disability support staff to facilitate the inclusion of students with disabilities in Algerian higher education, and the factors that affect their efforts.
- To investigate the effectiveness of existing support services and accommodations provided by Algerian higher education institutions and identify areas for improvement to better meet the needs of students with disabilities.

Why have I been chosen?

You have been chosen to take part in this study because you are disability officer in an Algerian University and have been supporting students with disabilities.

Do I have to take part?

It is up to you to decide whether or not to take part. If you do decide to take part you will be asked to sign a consent form. If you decide to take part you are still free to withdraw without giving a reason at any time until April 2022 when the analysis of the data will commence.

What will I do if I take part?

Your participation in the study will involve an interview with me at a date and time that is convenient to you. The interview will last between 30-45 minutes and will take place face-to-face in a mutually agreed quiet place in or near the university, eg in one of the library study rooms, or online via Zoom or Stream-Yard application. With your agreement, I will record the interview so that I can have an accurate version of your responses. A list of the questions I would like to ask you can be found below. You can skip any questions that you do not wish to answer and provide any additional information that you consider to be relevant to the purpose of my study.

What are the possible disadvantages and risks of taking part?

There are no possible disadvantages or risks associated with taking part in this study.

What are the possible benefits of taking part?

The research will have possible benefits, as it will provide you with the opportunity to share your experiences, highlight effective practice, and make suggestions for any improvements that you might consider beneficial. Resulting conclusions may be of value to your university and to other Higher Education Institutions in Algeria and more widely. A report of the findings of the study will be sent to all participants.

Data Protection Privacy Notice

The data controller for this project will be University of the West of Scotland (UWS). The UWS Data Protection Office provides oversight of UWS activities involving the processing of personal data and can be contacted at dataprotection@uws.ac.uk. UWS's Data Protection Officer is Emma Cockrow and can be contacted at dataprotection@uws.ac.uk.

Any personal data you provide will be pseudonymised. This means that I will replace with pseudonyms your name, the name of the University and any other details that could lead to your identification. This will ensure that you will not be identified in the PhD thesis and in publications and presentations arising from the study.

If you are concerned about how your personal data is being processed, please contact UWS in the first instance at dataprotection@uws.ac.uk. If you remain unsatisfied, you may wish to contact the Information Commissioner's Office (ICO). Contact details, and details of data subject rights, are available on the ICO website at: <https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/data-protection-reform/overview-of-the-gdpr/individuals-rights/>

What will happen to the results of the research study?

The results of this study will be disseminated through the PhD thesis, presentations and publications such as journal articles.

Who has reviewed the study?

ESS Ethics Committee

Contact for further information

If you require any further information please contact:

Researcher:

Fatma Bouabida

University of the West of Scotland,

High Street,

Paisley,

PA1 2BE

UK

Telephone: .xxxxxxxxxxxxxx

E-mail address: [REDACTED]

Personal details withheld.

Research Supervisor:

Dr Lisa McAuliffe

University of the West of Scotland,

High Street,

Paisley,

PA1 2BE

UK

Telephone: .

E-mail address: [REDACTED]

Personal details withheld.

Thank you for considering my invitation to take part in my research.

Appendix 6: The interview schedule for students with disabilities

Interview questions for students with disability

General questions

- 1- Could you tell me a bit about yourself?
- 2- What do you study? In which year are you?
- 3- Why did you choose to study in this university?
- 4- What did you take into account when deciding to study in this university or this department?

University experiences

Accessibility of the physical environment

1. Can you please tell me about the accessibility of buildings and campus facilities including classrooms, libraries, toilets, prayer rooms, rest rooms, university offices, Disability support office, students' lounge or cafeteria, and any other places in the campus?
2. How does the level of accessibility of these spaces influence your experiences in the university?
3. Which features of the physical environment have you found particularly effective/helpful?
4. What, if any, recommendations do you have about changes that can improve the accessibility of the physical environment?

Academic experiences

1. Can you please tell me about your academic experience including accessibility of the academic content in your programmes of study, individual and group activities, assessment and feedback, learning resources and materials, and available accommodations that enable you to engage fully with the academic content, activities and resources?
2. How does the level of accessibility of the above influence your experiences in the university?
3. In your opinion and experience, which accommodations in academic content and activities, learning resources and materials, assessment and feedback are particularly effective/helpful for Students with disabilities?
4. What, if any, recommendations do you have about changes that can improve the accessibility of the academic content and activities, learning resources and materials, assessment and feedback for Students with disabilities?

Social experiences

1. Can you please tell me about your interactions and experiences with the academic staff teaching in your programme of study, the disability support office, and your classmates and other students in the university?
2. Can you please tell me about the opportunities that you have had to take part in social events organised by the university, or join social clubs and associations?
3. How does the level of accessibility of the above influence your experiences in the university?
4. Which aspects of your social experiences in the university have you found particularly enjoyable/beneficial?

5. What, if any, recommendations do you have about changes that can improve your social experiences in the university?

Policy awareness

1. Are you aware of the rights that Students with disabilities have? Do you have knowledge about the international and national inclusive policies aiming to promote the rights of Students with disabilities and accommodate their needs?
 - If yes, how do you judge the incorporation and application of these policies in your university?
2. To what extent do you think that your rights are preserved by the university policies, and that you are receiving the support that you deserve?
3. How inclusive do you consider the university to be?

Conclusion

1. Are there any instances of particularly effective practice regarding the support for Students with disabilities in this university that you would like to highlight?
2. Do you have any general recommendations and suggestions that could help improve the quality of support provided for students with disabilities?
3. Is there anything else of relevance to this topic that you wish to add to your responses to the above questions?

Appendix 7: The interview schedule for disability support staff

Interview questions for disability support staff

General questions

1. Could you tell me a bit about yourself?
2. Could you tell me about the disability support office, and how it works?
3. How did you join the disability support office, when and why?
4. What is your position in the disability support office?
5. Could you tell me about your position, what are the tasks you deliver, what are you responsible of, and what do you like about your current position?
6. Have you received any training before/since joining the disability support office? If, yes, can you tell me about the training, eg what aspects you found particularly useful and any aspects that, in your opinion, could be improved? If you have not received any training, what type of training would be beneficial to you?
7. Does the disability support office organize any training for academic staff in order to prepare them for teaching Students with disabilities effectively? If yes, can you please tell me about this training? If not, what type of training would be beneficial to academic staff, in your opinion?
8. How do you register Students with disabilities?
9. Do you think that there are Students with disabilities who do not want to disclose their disabilities? If so, what, in your opinion, are the reasons for this? Is there anything that is being done or can be done to support these students?
10. What reasonable accommodations do you provide for Students with disabilities, and what are the steps you follow to support them?
11. How do you evaluate the support provided for Students with disabilities?

University experiences

Accessibility of the physical environment

1. Can you please tell me about the accessibility of buildings and campus facilities including classrooms, libraries, toilets, prayer rooms, rest rooms, university offices,
2. Disability support office, students' lounge or cafeteria, and any other places in the campus?
3. In your opinion and experience, which features of the physical environment are particularly effective/helpful for Students with disabilities?
4. What, if any, recommendations do you have about changes that can improve the accessibility of the physical environment for Students with disabilities?

Academic experiences

5. Can you please tell me about the accessibility of the academic content, individual and group activities, learning resources and materials, assessments and feedback in the programmes of study in the university?
6. What accommodations are available to enable Students with disabilities to engage fully with the academic content, individual and group activities, learning resources and materials, assessments and feedback in the programmes of study in the university? Who provides these accommodations?

7. In your opinion and experience, which accommodations in academic content and activities, learning resources and materials, assessment and feedback are particularly effective/helpful for Students with disabilities?
8. What, if any, recommendations do you have about changes that can improve the accessibility of the academic content and activities, learning resources and materials, assessment and feedback for Students with disabilities?

Social experiences

1. Based on your interactions and observations, how effective do you consider the social experiences of Students with disabilities to be while at university?
2. Can you please tell me about the opportunities that Students with disabilities have to take part in social events organised by the university, or join social clubs and associations?
3. Does the disability support office organise social activities for Students with disabilities to help them socialize and feel included? If so, can you tell me about them?
4. Based on your interactions and observations, which aspects of the social experiences of Students with disabilities in the university do you consider particularly enjoyable/beneficial?
5. What, if any, recommendations do you have about changes that can improve the social experiences of Students with disabilities in the university?

Policy awareness

- 1- Are you aware of international and national policy focusing on the rights of Students with disabilities and the accommodations required to realise their right to education? Does the university have an inclusive policies in relation to Students with disabilities?
- 2- How inclusive do you consider the university to be?

Conclusion

1. Are there any instances of particularly effective practice regarding the support for Students with disabilities in this university that you would like to highlight?
2. Do you have any general recommendations and suggestions that could help improve the quality of support provided for students with disabilities?
3. Is there anything else of relevance to this topic that you wish to add to your responses to the above questions?

Appendix 8: Consent form for interviewees

RESEARCH INFORMED CONSENT FORM

Title of Project: Voices on inclusion: an IPA study of the lived experiences of students with disabilities and the perspectives of disability support staff in one Algerian university.

Ethics Approval Number: 16412

Investigator's name: Fatma Bouabida

Researcher Email: [REDACTED] Personal details withheld.

You have been invited to take part in a study whose purpose is:

- To explore and understand the lived experiences of students with disabilities in Algerian higher education, including factors that facilitate and hinder their participation and achievement.
- To identify the needs of students with disabilities in Algerian higher education and convey their recommendations for improving their overall experience and academic success.
- To understand the processes used by disability support staff to facilitate the inclusion of students with disabilities in Algerian higher education, and the factors that affect their efforts.
- To investigate the effectiveness of existing support services and accommodations provided by Algerian higher education institutions and identify areas for improvement to better meet the needs of students with disabilities.

By completing this form you agree that you have read and understood the participant information sheet and what is being asked of you in this study.

Please read the following statements and, if you agree, initial the corresponding box to confirm your agreement:

	Initial below:
I confirm that I have read and understand the participant information sheet for the study. I have had the opportunity to consider the information, ask questions and have had these answered satisfactorily.	
I understand that my participation is voluntary and I need not answer any questions I prefer not to answer. I understand that I am free to withdraw at any time up until April 2022 when the analysis of the data will commence.	
I understand that the information I give is confidential and any publication or presentation resulting from this work will not identify me or my institution.	
I consent to the processing of personal information I may provide (<i>age, sex, and contact details</i>) for the purposes explained to me. I	

understand that such information will be handled in accordance with all applicable data protection legislation.	
I agree to have my voice/likeness digitally recorded.	
I freely agree to participate in this study.	

Signatures:

Name of participant (block capitals):
(block capitals):

Name of researcher

Date:

Date: Fatma Bouabida

Signature:

Signature:

Appendix 9: Initial noting and coding process

The image displays 12 pages of handwritten notes, each corresponding to a page of a scanned document. The notes are organized into sections and lists, often with arrows pointing to specific text in the scanned document. The pages are numbered 1 through 12.

- Page 1:** Notes on 'Pare affluence', 'Reverend', 'No positive', 'No negative', 'Adequate', 'Stress', 'Positive', 'Not', 'Alot', 'positive', 'Above', 'Notes', 'Reverend'. Includes a list: '1- how many are there in the class?' and '2- how many are there in the class?'. A note at the bottom says 'Notion of WAR CASAM'.
- Page 2:** Notes on 'No positive', 'No negative', 'Adequate', 'Stress', 'Positive', 'Not', 'Alot', 'positive', 'Above', 'Notes', 'Reverend'. Includes a list: '1- how many are there in the class?' and '2- how many are there in the class?'. A note at the bottom says 'Notion of WAR CASAM'.
- Page 3:** Notes on 'No positive', 'No negative', 'Adequate', 'Stress', 'Positive', 'Not', 'Alot', 'positive', 'Above', 'Notes', 'Reverend'. Includes a list: '1- how many are there in the class?' and '2- how many are there in the class?'. A note at the bottom says 'Notion of WAR CASAM'.
- Page 4:** Notes on 'No positive', 'No negative', 'Adequate', 'Stress', 'Positive', 'Not', 'Alot', 'positive', 'Above', 'Notes', 'Reverend'. Includes a list: '1- how many are there in the class?' and '2- how many are there in the class?'. A note at the bottom says 'Notion of WAR CASAM'.
- Page 5:** Notes on 'No positive', 'No negative', 'Adequate', 'Stress', 'Positive', 'Not', 'Alot', 'positive', 'Above', 'Notes', 'Reverend'. Includes a list: '1- how many are there in the class?' and '2- how many are there in the class?'. A note at the bottom says 'Notion of WAR CASAM'.
- Page 6:** Notes on 'No positive', 'No negative', 'Adequate', 'Stress', 'Positive', 'Not', 'Alot', 'positive', 'Above', 'Notes', 'Reverend'. Includes a list: '1- how many are there in the class?' and '2- how many are there in the class?'. A note at the bottom says 'Notion of WAR CASAM'.
- Page 7:** Notes on 'No positive', 'No negative', 'Adequate', 'Stress', 'Positive', 'Not', 'Alot', 'positive', 'Above', 'Notes', 'Reverend'. Includes a list: '1- how many are there in the class?' and '2- how many are there in the class?'. A note at the bottom says 'Notion of WAR CASAM'.
- Page 8:** Notes on 'No positive', 'No negative', 'Adequate', 'Stress', 'Positive', 'Not', 'Alot', 'positive', 'Above', 'Notes', 'Reverend'. Includes a list: '1- how many are there in the class?' and '2- how many are there in the class?'. A note at the bottom says 'Notion of WAR CASAM'.
- Page 9:** Notes on 'No positive', 'No negative', 'Adequate', 'Stress', 'Positive', 'Not', 'Alot', 'positive', 'Above', 'Notes', 'Reverend'. Includes a list: '1- how many are there in the class?' and '2- how many are there in the class?'. A note at the bottom says 'Notion of WAR CASAM'.
- Page 10:** Notes on 'No positive', 'No negative', 'Adequate', 'Stress', 'Positive', 'Not', 'Alot', 'positive', 'Above', 'Notes', 'Reverend'. Includes a list: '1- how many are there in the class?' and '2- how many are there in the class?'. A note at the bottom says 'Notion of WAR CASAM'.
- Page 11:** Notes on 'No positive', 'No negative', 'Adequate', 'Stress', 'Positive', 'Not', 'Alot', 'positive', 'Above', 'Notes', 'Reverend'. Includes a list: '1- how many are there in the class?' and '2- how many are there in the class?'. A note at the bottom says 'Notion of WAR CASAM'.
- Page 12:** Notes on 'No positive', 'No negative', 'Adequate', 'Stress', 'Positive', 'Not', 'Alot', 'positive', 'Above', 'Notes', 'Reverend'. Includes a list: '1- how many are there in the class?' and '2- how many are there in the class?'. A note at the bottom says 'Notion of WAR CASAM'.

(examples from Student E initial notes from the original transcript)

Right things from the course

- Physical Accessibility
- Social experiences
- Financial support

Physical Accessibility:

- There is some flexibility
- They do not have a fixed time
- There is some flexibility
- They do not have a fixed time
- There is some flexibility
- They do not have a fixed time

Academic Accessibility:

- There is some flexibility
- They do not have a fixed time
- There is some flexibility
- They do not have a fixed time
- There is some flexibility
- They do not have a fixed time

Social Experiences:

- There is some flexibility
- They do not have a fixed time
- There is some flexibility
- They do not have a fixed time
- There is some flexibility
- They do not have a fixed time

Financial Support:

- There is some flexibility
- They do not have a fixed time
- There is some flexibility
- They do not have a fixed time
- There is some flexibility
- They do not have a fixed time

Physical Accessibility:

- There is some flexibility
- They do not have a fixed time
- There is some flexibility
- They do not have a fixed time
- There is some flexibility
- They do not have a fixed time

Academic Accessibility:

- There is some flexibility
- They do not have a fixed time
- There is some flexibility
- They do not have a fixed time
- There is some flexibility
- They do not have a fixed time

Social Experiences:

- There is some flexibility
- They do not have a fixed time
- There is some flexibility
- They do not have a fixed time
- There is some flexibility
- They do not have a fixed time

Financial Support:

- There is some flexibility
- They do not have a fixed time
- There is some flexibility
- They do not have a fixed time
- There is some flexibility
- They do not have a fixed time

Physical Accessibility:

- There is some flexibility
- They do not have a fixed time
- There is some flexibility
- They do not have a fixed time
- There is some flexibility
- They do not have a fixed time

Academic Accessibility:

- There is some flexibility
- They do not have a fixed time
- There is some flexibility
- They do not have a fixed time
- There is some flexibility
- They do not have a fixed time

Social Experiences:

- There is some flexibility
- They do not have a fixed time
- There is some flexibility
- They do not have a fixed time
- There is some flexibility
- They do not have a fixed time

Financial Support:

- There is some flexibility
- They do not have a fixed time
- There is some flexibility
- They do not have a fixed time
- There is some flexibility
- They do not have a fixed time

(developing codes and emergent themes manually Student E)

Appendix 10: Sample analysis individual cases (exploratory comments and developing emergent themes)

Sample analysis for Student E (developing emergent themes and exploratory comments)

Exploratory comments code: Black= descriptive comments, Red= linguistic comments, and black underlined= conceptual comments

Emergent themes	Extracts	Exploratory comments
Challenges with accessing ramps Negative effects of lack of accessibility	<p>" [...] I had no idea about how horrible these facilities were... I study in a building that has a passage for Students with disabilities, a passage that allows you to use your electric wheel chair to make it upstairs, but it was not built well at all. When I used my wheelchair to get upstairs, I was not aware of the terrible quality of the passage; it seemed as if I am climbing a mountain. I tried to get up until I saw my wheel chair falling backwards. I screamed, and thank god there were two guys there that rushed to my aid and got a hold of my chair, had they not come in that instance, I would've fell... from that moment I never used that passage on my own again, I have to be accompanied with another person, who can help me climb that mountain." ///</p>	<p>The student here is describing and narrating her experience using the ramp, which seems to be not constructed well.</p> <p>Terrible, climbing a mountain. The use of language to express the difficulty trying to navigate university buildings.</p> <p>Accessibility challenges mainly unadapt ramps</p> <p>Supportive father</p> <p>The use of the conditional phrases "If it is... built well" shows language use to express the desire for independent access.</p>
Challenges with the quality of accessibility to university environment	<p>"Sometimes I make it late to class because of the inability to find someone that can help me get to classrooms. The other times I am forced to wait in the winter where it can get very cold, and when</p>	

<p>Lack of accessibility support</p>	<p>I enter class, I have to get into the class mood and follow along with the teacher, but it can be very difficult. Sometimes we are tasked to write and I wouldn't be able to, because I would be very exhausted and feeling cold from all the waiting"</p>	<p>Describing what consequences these difficulties have on the learning process, as this can affect their learning and participation.</p>
<p>Desire for independent access</p>	<p>//////////////////// What I am trying to say from all of this is that if actual facilities that could help me access classrooms and other places existed, I would not need the help of others... I have an electric chair that my father bought me an electric chair from his own pocket, so that I can depend on myself and do not ask others to help pushing my chair. The only thing that bothers me is the access to these environmental buildings and places in college, because if it was organized and built well, it would have been much easier.</p>	<p>The use of the conditional "if.... existed"" if it was organised" shows language use to express the desire for independent access.</p>

<p>Questioning the effectiveness of the office</p>	<p>In actuality, I had no idea that such an office exists until this year, I coincidentally met up with a college professor, and after he saw me, he told me about an office that offers support and told me to sign up for it, but I honestly do not think that they will do /change much. ///</p>	<p>Unawareness of the existence of DISABILITY SUPPORT OFFICE</p> <p>Skepticism about the effectiveness of the DISABILITY SUPPORT OFFICE</p>
<p>Unresponsiveness of DISABILITY SUPPORT OFFICE members Unfriendly transportation</p>	<p>“[...] I told him about a lot of stuff including the bus transportation that is not adequate to my disability, which means I always need the help of the driver or my friends to get on the bus.” ///</p>	<p>I do not think they will do/change much, it seems that there is a doubt towards the office’s ability to bring any changes. <u>Why is that? and why is the student ignorant of the existence of the office?</u> Unfriendly buses and transportation, which made her dependent on others. Use of the adverb always shows recurring need of assistance.</p>
<p>Inaccessible residency halls Adaptation and coping as self-support strategies.</p>	<p>I do not live there; I go to college and return home on a daily basis [...] I don’t live there because the conditions there are very poor for someone with a disability, I went once and it was terrible, I was given a room in a place that wasn’t comfortable and inappropriate at all. This includes the room and the bathrooms. They were at least aware of my disability [...]. I’m not talking about the room because I can get used to it, but the bathrooms had stairs leading up to it, which meant I couldn’t get there on my own [...] ///</p>	<p>Poor conditions in residency hall Use of strong adjectives and language was not comfortable, inappropriate, poor conditions to reflect on the living condition on campus. <u>I can get used to it. This might signify a level of adaptation, determination or resilience?.</u></p>

<p>Negative effects of inaccessible residency hall</p>	<p>Using university transport of course, I get up at 5 A.M in the morning and I return home at 6 P.M in the evening, and I return extremely tired. ///</p>	<p>fatigue and exhaustion Describing the tiresome process and the effect of non-disability friendly residency halls on the participant.</p>
<p>Inaccessibility of library self-reliance in obtaining resources. Development of study skills to support themselves</p>	<p>As for the library, I don't go there to be honest, because I can't make it there, besides, everything is available on the internet, which means if I wanted anything or any book I'd simply look for it on the internet. ///</p>	<p>Lack of motivation to go to the library, citing difficulties in reaching it. This suggests physical barriers that discourage library usage. <u>Developing determination and reliance on oneself as a strategy to obtain learning materials, because of inability to benefit from the library.</u></p>
<p>Supportive classroom environment</p>	<p>"I got used to it, but it affects me a little bit, let's say 30/40%, and in the outside world, life is very hard, but in class, everything is easier and better, my teachers and my colleagues are very understanding and they even offer me help whenever it's needed." ///</p>	<p><u>Again, I got used to it. This might signify a level of resilience and coping.</u> Use of positive adjectives to describe the support she receives from teachers and peers.</p>
<p>negative effects of inaccessibility of the physical environment</p>	<p>Sometimes I make it late to class because of the inability to find someone that can help me, and sometimes I'm forced to wait in the winter where it can get very cold, and when I enter class, I have to get into the class mood and follow along with the teacher/professor, but it can be very difficult. Sometimes we are tasked to write and I wouldn't be able to, because I would be very exhausted and cold from all the waiting. ///</p>	<p>The negative effects of inaccessibility of the physical environment <u>Reliance on others for assistance What are the effects of this on participants?</u> The quote also describes the negative effects of inaccessibility and poor quality facilities on the educational experience of this participant.</p>
<p>Accessibility issues and Challenges with the quality of accessibility to university environment</p>	<p>[...]allocating classes in the ground floor, this might be a solution, but it doesn't always work, because I am always in need of someone to help me reach lecture halls. I don't know if that's possible or not, but providing someone who's capable of helping me instead of my friends, as someone whose job is to help</p>	<p>Recommendations for enhancing accessibility <u>Feeling always in need of others. Time for addressing accessibility issues and raising awareness towards independent access and the</u></p>

	<p>people like me. I wish they can provide that in a professional manner so that you won't feel that you're always in need of others."</p>	<p><u>creation of inclusive environment.</u></p>
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<p>Supportive classroom environment</p>	<p>/// To be quite frank, I don't remember facing an issue at all regarding that. The professors are very understanding and I do my tasks and my homework regularly and, I saw friends of mine who were incapable of writing but the college provided individual for them that can help them and write for them. As for group activities and individual activities, everything is normal. ///</p>	<p>Supportive teachers and peers Describing the positive support received from teachers towards students with disabilities.</p>
<p>Lack of engagement in extracurricular activities</p>	<p>/// However, when it comes to participating in clubs and meetings, I'd rather not do such a thing because I am a shy person and also an introvert, and I don't think I'd have anything interesting to add there or do. I even get invited to places that aren't related to college, but I don't go there. ///</p>	<p><u>Not feeling comfortable to participate in events/meeting/clubs... feeling excluded/not welcomed?</u> Lack of engagement in university social and academic activities</p>
<p>social events as a chance for recognition</p>	<p>/// I don't think it affects my experience that much, of course these social opportunities give you a chance to show yourself and stand out in front of others, and it can be a chance for others to hear your voice and know you and see your situation, which further helps raising your concerns and issues. I see these social activities as a chance for people to see and pay attention to those with handicaps that exist in college, and It can be a chance to meet others so that I can get rid of my shyness.</p>	<p>Describing the benefits of social events and participation in extracurricular activities. <u>Social activities as a way to voice concerns and challenges</u></p>

<p>lack of awareness of inclusive policy</p>	<p>///</p> <p>I only hear about them, but I've never seen them applied throughout the years I spent in college, and haven't seen any application of these policies that preserve our rights at university.</p> <p>///</p>	<p><u>Lack of policies could be the reason behind the barriers mentioned by this student.</u></p>
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<p>Inexistence of university policy lack of policy implementation</p>	<p>There is no support or application of any policy that safeguards the rights of students with special needs, I'd our university's inclusiveness by 4.5/10 or even a 5/10 and that is solely because of the teachers and not because of the university itself and its environment, because students and teachers treat me very respectfully and very nicely. /// Another thing I want to talk about is my academic experience with the teachers and the environment in high school and middle school, which was good, but I always suffered when it came to physical environment and I got tired a lot. ///</p>	<p><u>What might be other potential consequences of absence of policy implementation on these students' experiences?</u></p>
<p>Lack of progress in the area inclusive education</p>	<p>/// "There should be a lot more of thorough research and studies about the support that is given to students with special needs, so that these conditions and the support could be improved, there should be interviews and surveys conducted with the students so that they could assess the situation and provide solutions and extra care and support depending on the results of these surveys, so that the main concern wouldn't only be studying and the ability to learn but also the concern of those with special needs and the things that affects them, sometimes I wish for a day where I won't bother or need anyone to help me get to classes. And I wish for the only concern to</p>	<p><u>Referring to past experiences with inaccessible physical environment. This might suggest that barriers in the physical environment persist and little progress has been made in achieving inclusive education in Algeria.</u></p> <p><u>Persisting physical accessibility barriers, this raises questions anoutevolution of inclusive education in Algeria</u></p>
<p>Desire for autonomy and independence</p>	<p>be my studies rather than the difficulties I face getting there."</p>	<p>The call for a more accessible environment Sometimes I wish for a day where I won't bother or need anyone to help me get to classes. This describes the strong desire of the student for independent and autonomous accessibility.</p>

Sample analysis for Staff B (developing emergent themes and exploratory comments)

Exploratory comments code: Black= descriptive comments, Red= **linguistic comments**, and black underlined= conceptual comments

Emergent themes	Extracts	Exploratory comments
<p>DISABILITY SUPPORT OFFICE as a voluntary initiative</p> <p>Physical accessibility improvement</p> <p>Provision of academic</p>	<p>“So,DISABILITY SUPPORT OFFICE in the university is still active though it has no really official entity, that is the main problem, so we are working as volunteers. So, I see myself as an educator, as an editor, as a teacher, and as a facilitator, these help as a person working on her filed of interest to work with this category of people. Of course when dealing with inclusive education we do not think only about people ...handicapped people. It means our aim is to reach an inclusive society, so that’s the main aim behind our work. Haven’t talked a lot about my self but I related my experience to my role to in the DISABILITY SUPPORT OFFICE. ///</p> <p>I am happy to tell you that the office contributed a lot in changing some aspects of accessibility. In the past, we had no access to restrooms, and everything was based on stairs. Stairs everywhere, even for ground floor buildings there are steps [...] DISABILITY SUPPORT OFFICEoffice now is accessible to everyone at the uni [sic], and it is at the main entrance of the university, in the ground floor with ramps.” ///</p>	<p>Describing her role within the DISABILITY SUPPORT OFFICE.</p> <p><u>DISABILITY SUPPORT OFFICE as a voluntary office and not as an official entity. What effects could this have on inclusivity and support for Students with disabilities?</u> <u>The use of terminology “students with special needs” does it reflect lack of awareness on inclusion and inclusive terminology.</u></p> <p>Expressing gratitude and acknowledging the positive impact of DISABILITY SUPPORT OFFICE on physical accessibility.</p> <p><u>Are these improvements enough?</u> <u>Questioning the mpact of DISABILITY SUPPORT OFFICE on improving accessibility at this university?</u></p> <p>Provision of learning materials. The participant is describing the learning materials and accommodations they provide for Students with disabilities in class and during exams.</p>

<p>and learning facilities and Assessment support</p>	<p>we do offer some academic facilities and resources in order to help Students with disabilities, as extra time during exams, access to exams with a companion (reader or scribe)...etc. we also offer Dictaphones, large print font materials, and we ask teachers to upload lectures on the E-learning platform.” ///</p> <p>“[...] for example, I have a student who suffers from psychological problems. I always try to negotiate possible support solutions with the department, other teachers, and my other colleagues at DISABILITY SUPPORT OFFICE. Especially when it comes to extra time to submit work or dissertation...etc ////</p>	<p><u>There seems to be positive intentions to support Students with disabilities. However, are the provided resources enough and tailored to cater the additional support needs of all students?</u></p> <p><u>The use of terminology “suffer” lack of awareness on inclusion and inclusive terminology/ the use of medical model terms.</u></p> <p>The participant is describing her active involvement in negotiating support and consideration towards her students with disabilities.</p> <p><u>Try? Isn't it no always possible to do that? This might signify that it is not always possible to accommodate the requirements of these students, and may also reflect the absence of individualised support plans and proactive support approach in this university.</u></p>
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<p>Counselling service and provision of well-being support</p>	<p>[...] the academic facilities offered by our university to allow students with special needs to engage in the learning process as their peers are diverse, including counselling service that provides psychological support for handicapped students... we have a full time psychologist who schedule meetings with students and organize counselling sessions with them [...].” ////</p>	<p><u>Only one full time psychologist? Does he has enough time to manage to assist all students?</u></p> <p><u>The use of the terminology handicapped, mark unawareness of this participant on inclusive language, and inclusive terminology.</u></p>
<p>Unfriendly buses and transportation</p>	<p>buses are not accessible for handicapped students. I think we also need to allocate buses that can help students to move between university buildings, because as I told you our uni [sic] is so big and it sometimes takes lot of time to reach some buildings especially between sessions [...] it would have been easier if there are shortcuts, or buses inside university...etc ///</p>	<p>The participant is expressing her concerns towards inaccessible transportation system, and at the same time are offering solutions to enhance accessibility and movement between buildings.</p> <p><u>This reflects insufficient materials available at this university, which highlights another institutional barrier to the learning experience of Students with disabilities.</u> <u>Why is this shortage of materials and resources?</u> <u>Why this limitation in budget ?</u></p>
<p>Lack of learning materials and assistive tools</p> <p>lack of budget for DISABILITY SUPPORT OFFICE</p>	<p>we do not have enough and appropriate materials to help disabled students we do not have enough budget to afford new technological material ///</p>	<p>The participant here is addressing the financial constraints faced by DISABILITY SUPPORT OFFICE to afford necessary support for Students with disabilities.</p>

<p>Need for training discrediting students testimonies.</p>	<p>we need experts [...] in inclusive education, in order be updated with the techniques and methodologies we should use. We need to have training about the tools and instruments that each category of disabled learners need [...] we need to be trained in order to know how to help. It happened to me once, I had a student with vision problems [...] she could not read what teachers write on the board easily, and even when writing during the exams she had difficulties, so she needs somebody to help her.</p> <p>///</p>	<p>Lack of training in the area of inclusion and the way staff should deal with and provide support for these students.</p>
<p>inability to support and understand the needs of Students with disabilities</p>	<p>The problem we encounter with such category of students is sometimes they take disability as a profit to gain compassion from others [...] we need to be trained to be able to differentiate between the real need of students or the vicious part of the student because they need a good mark.</p> <p>///</p>	<p>Thinking that students are faking their disabilities to benefit from support/discrediting students testimonies.</p>
<p>Need for inclusive training</p>	<p>we need to be trained to be able to differentiate between the real need of students or the vicious part of the student because they need a good mark.</p> <p>///</p>	<p>Lack of training in the area of inclusion and the way staff should deal with and provide support for these students.</p>
<p>Lack of collaboration between university systems</p>	<p>I think we are far away from having an inclusive university. We are trying at least to raise awareness [...] there is no collaboration as well [...] administration is here to collaborate, but</p>	<p>Use of language "far away" to express the existing gap in this university in relation to inclusion.</p> <p>This extract showcases the importance of collaboration. What are the potential benefits</p>

<p>Reluctance of disclosure</p>	<p>teachers do not collaborate with us, they take what the department says, sometimes they apply it and sometimes not. There is no teamwork, teamwork is in the DISABILITY SUPPORT OFFICE only, apart from that, there is no collaboration. ///</p> <p>Of course there are students who don't want to reveal their handicap or illness, because they feel they don't need to, or think that nobody can do much for them, so they do not advocate support. However, others register with the office, because they need help and support, and without support, they will feel lost. Registering with the office helps us know which type of support students need.</p>	<p><u>of collaboration on the experience of Students with disabilities?</u></p> <p>The participant here is describing the importance of disclosing disability to the DISABILITY SUPPORT OFFICE, and recognizing the need for advocating for support and seeking help. <u>How could reluctance of disclosure affect the office work to support Students with disabilities?</u> <u>What might be other factors that affect students' disclosure?</u></p>
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<p>Significance of collaboration and Lack of awareness towards Students with disabilities' needs</p>	<p>we are trying to invite other teachers to join our office, but not all of them are interested in that, maybe they do not have time to volunteer, or they have other commitments ///</p>	<p>What are the actual reasons behind lack of collaboration of other teachers with DISABILITY SUPPORT OFFICE members? This statement sheds light on lack of collaboration and awareness towards accommodating the needs of Students with disabilities.</p>
<p>Persisting accessibility barriers in primary school</p>	<p>I joined this office because my little niece has a disability,[...] she is in primary school and there is no support provided to her [...] I always write papers and present in conferences to raise awareness about this category of students. ///</p>	<p><u>This quote may signify the lack of support in other educational systems and not only at university.</u> The need towards raising awareness.</p>
<p>Lack of engagement of Students with disabilities</p>	<p>I have a student with disability in my class, and I noticed that she is isolated. [...] when I asked her about the reason behind having no friends, she said that she cannot trust anyone at this university, because she got disappointed, as she always discovers that she is not accepted by her friends, especially when they refuse to work with her or be friends with her.</p>	<p>Isolated, disappointed, cannot trust. Use of language to reflect feelings and experiences of the student in relation to her interactions at university. <u>Could this be interpreted as Lack of engagement/ lack on interaction/ exclusion?</u></p>

Appendix 11: Across-case analysis

Looking for patterns, and creating group sub-ordinate themes and superordinate themes across cases

Appendix12: Sample master table of themes for students with disabilities

Superordinate theme 1: Facilitators of inclusion		
Subordinate themes	Emergent Themes	sample of quotes
<p>Structural facilitators</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Academic support - Emotional support - Family support 	<p>Recognition of students additional support needs from teachers</p> <p>Provision of learning materials</p> <p>Extra time during exams</p> <p>Deadline extensions</p> <p>Assessment accommodations</p> <p>Family involvement</p> <p>Supportive classroom environment</p> <p>Supportive peers</p> <p>Supportive lecturers</p>	<p>“ in class, everything is easier and better, my teachers are very understanding and they even offer me help whenever it’s needed [...], some teachers dictate slowly for me, others offer to write for me, while some teachers allow me to enter class no matter how late I am.” (Student E)</p> <p>“[...] I do not know about others, but my teachers always inform observer teachers about my case, so I always receive extra 30 minutes during exams.” (Student C)</p> <p>“[...] my XX teacher for example, always offer us additional time to submit homework and assignments, in case we failed to submit on time.” (Student G)</p> <p>“some teachers are nice, and try to support you with everything they can, they even encourage you and do not care about your disability at all [...].” (Student H)</p>

		<p>“[...] regarding my peers, I don't know what to say, but without them, I would have been lost. They helped me many times, they afforded a Dictaphone for me, and even when it was damaged, they bought me another one. They helped me a lot and I will never forget that” (Student D)</p> <p>“[...] I usually get summaries and lessons from my friends. We also used to gather at the library in order to revise together and to explain for me the lectures I missed [...]”(Student A)</p> <p>“My family are very supportive [...] especially my father. Above all He supported me to go to university, as he believes in my abilities, and this matters a lot [...]” (Student F)</p> <p>“I am grateful for my big sister, without her I would have never entered school, she was the one who encouraged me to go to school, and she always accompanied me wherever I go, and without her support I would have never reached university level [...]” (Student B)</p>
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<p>Self-determination</p>	<p>Self-reliance to obtain learning resources and materials</p> <p>Acceptance of disability</p> <p>Self-determination</p> <p>Coping with existing barriers</p> <p>Seeing disability as an ability</p> <p>depending on one-self</p> <p>self-confidence</p> <p>self-support strategies</p>	<p>" [...] everything is available on internet; I do not wait for teachers to upload lectures or provide me with notes. If I wanted anything I would simply get it from google scholar or other databases." (Student A)</p> <p>"[...] everything is available on the internet, which means if I wanted anything or any book I'd simply look for it on the internet." (Student E)</p> <p>"At university, you should attract the attention of teachers and fellow students by different means. I mean your level determines who you are after all. Studying hard, and doing your best to succeed, is your only weapon at university." (Student A)</p> <p>"[...] despite all the barriers I am facing, I am proud of myself, and I am now more confident, you just have to accept yourself that is how you overcome your fears and all other barriers [...]" (Student D)</p>
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Superordinate theme 2: Barriers to inclusion		
Subordinate themes	Emergent Themes	sample of quotes
<p>Environmental Barriers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Inaccessible university buildings - Inaccessible transportation 	<p>Inaccessible libraries</p> <p>existence of stairs</p> <p>absence of lifts in university buildings</p> <p>outdated building</p> <p>catastrophic accessibility</p> <p>superficial accessibility measures and hidden reality of accessibility</p> <p>Inaccessible residency halls</p> <p>Long distance between buildings</p> <p>poor quality ramps</p> <p>Need for help to access buildings</p> <p>Desire of independent accessibility</p> <p>Risky pathways</p> <p>unfriendly transportation</p>	<p>“I am in my final year, and I have never went to the library, it is so far and not accessible at all.” Student also stated: “[...] I cannot make it to the library alone, it is inaccessible”. (Student C)</p> <p>“ [...] I study in a building that has a ramp. When I used my electric wheelchair to get to the building, I was not aware of the terrible quality of the passage; it seemed as if I am climbing a mountain.” (Student E)</p> <p>“ [...] I remember once on a rainy day, a sewage pipe was let open , I didn't pay attention, and I fell into it [...] thank God I was not alone, and people hurried to help me [...]” (Student F)</p> <p>“[...]there is a huge distance between them (buildings and classrooms) [...]imagine yourself studying in a class for 1 hour and a half, and then moving to another class in a different building, which is situated in a very far place, and vice versa. [Pause] long, very long distance. This makes me obliged to miss or skip classes, because it is very tiring to get there. Especially when it is raining, it is even more difficult.” (Student C)</p> <p>“university is full of stairs; there are no lifts, I am always obliged to get upstairs with the help of my friends, when I have classes in the upper floors” (Student B).</p> <p>“ [...] I don't live there because the conditions there are very poor for someone with a disability, I went once and it was terrible, I was given a room in a place that wasn't comfortable and inappropriate at all. This includes the</p>

		<p>room and the bathrooms. They were at least aware of my disability [...]. I'm not talking about the room because I can get used to it, but the bathrooms had stairs leading up to it, which meant I couldn't get there on my own [...]" (Student E)</p> <p>"[...]although they have managed to numerate classrooms after I raised my concerns, I still get lost if teachers changed classes, I always need someone to guide me to get to classes and rooms, [...] in order to avoid being late, I always come earlier to fetch for classrooms [...]" (Student F)</p> <p>"[...] university buses are not equipped at all, imagine a bus with steps, this makes you always feel helpless, and wait for others to get you on the bus." (Student B).</p>
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<p>Structural Barriers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The challenge of transition - lack of institutional support - Lack of academic support - lack of emotional support - lack of financial support - Limited employment opportunities - Lack of sense of belonging - Absence of inclusive policy 	<p>scepticism about the effectiveness of DISABILITY SUPPORT OFFICE</p>	<p>“Well, I really do not think that such an office exists. If it does exist, I would definitely register with it.” (Student B)</p>
	<p>Unawareness of existence of DISABILITY SUPPORT OFFICE</p>	<p>“In actuality, I had no idea that such an office exists until this year, I coincidentally met up with a college professor, and after he saw me, he told me about an office that offers support and told me to register with it. I registered but I honestly do not think that they will change much, as I have spoken to them many times about many problems, but nothing happened so far.”(Student F)</p>
	<p>Lack of assistive technology</p>	
	<p>unadapt teaching methods</p>	
	<p>inaccessible learning materials</p>	<p>“ [...] they registered me and wrote my issue, but I have never been contacted by any of them. I think this office is only ink on paper.” (Student C)</p>
	<p>Lack of learning materials and resources</p>	
	<p>lack of sense of belonging</p>	<p>“[...] I have always tried to raise the problem related to bus accessibility to the office, but in vain [...]” (Student B)</p>
	<p>Social activities as a way to voice concerns</p>	<p>“I use a Dictaphone to record lectures, because most of lectures are PPT based [...]” (Student D)</p>
<p>social events as a chance for recognition</p>	<p>“None of my teachers provide lectures or notes before the session,</p>	
<p>lack of engagement in extracurricular activities</p>		

	<p>Work load</p> <p>High academic demands</p> <p>lack of emotional support</p> <p>Bureaucracy</p> <p>lack of financial support</p> <p>inability to work and study at the same time</p> <p>entering job market</p> <p>limited job opportunities</p> <p>unawareness of policy</p> <p>lack of implementation of policies</p>	<p>so if I was absent, I have to contact my friends to provide me with lectures [...]” (Student C)</p> <p>“[...] I find it difficult to follow the pace of some teachers, it is difficult for me to absorb what they say; I mean listening and trying to jot down some notes [...]” (Student F)</p> <p>“ [...] there are no audio resources, no magnifiers, no zoom tools and no assistive tools to make it there [...]” (Student D)</p> <p>“[...] you know 30 minutes of extra time is not always enough for me [...]” (Student C)</p> <p>“I find it difficult to find someone who would write for me during exams, [...]” (Student D)</p> <p>“[...] there should be a dedicated number or email that Students with disabilities can use to ask for support [...] also to avoid moving from one office to another in vein.” (Student A)</p> <p>“[...] even with my condition, they made me sign on papers from several offices, and each office is very far from the other. They sent me to several places to sign a document [...]” (Student C)</p> <p>“[...] at least, university should make it easier for Students with disabilities so that they do not feel discouraged and undetermined [...] I suggest they provide us with mental health support, in order to boost our determination and not the opposite.”(Student E)</p>
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	<p>“Student grant is insufficient; I hope they take this into consideration [...] those who do not understand our struggle, have never been in our shoes.” (Student G)</p> <p>“[...] not much individuals with disabilities are recruited in workforce, government should consider this, where are the disabled in workplace?” (Student C)</p> <p>“I do not participate in social events, and I would do not do that, actually I was never invited to participate.” (Student C)</p> <p>“[...] these social events are a chance that enables us to stand in front of others and show ourselves. Moreover, it is a chance for others as well to see your situation and hear about the problems you are facing [...].” (Student D)</p> <p>“I don’t see any application of any of the policies that preserve the rights of individuals with disabilities in Algeria. And I have no idea about the international level.” (Student E)</p> <p>“I don’t think that such policies exist. Even if you do a search on governmental websites, you will find nothing [...].”(Student C)</p>
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<p>Attitudinal barriers :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Negative attitudes inside the university context - Negative attitudes outside the university context 	<p>underestimating the abilities of students with disabilities.</p> <p>Unprofessional comments and treatment from some lecturers</p> <p>Misconceptions and stereotypes about disability</p> <p>Labelling disability</p> <p>Medical model view of disability</p> <p>Dealing with people with disabilities as charitable cases.</p>	<p>“ [...] my XX teacher did not believe I took the best mark, once she saw who I am , she was surprised and thought I cheated to pass her module with an excellent grade, and this is all because of my disability [...]” Student A</p> <p>“ [...] some teachers [...] do not bother to communicate with you [...] some of them provoke you, try to belittle you or underestimate you through their looks and offensive comment [...] I remember once a teacher stood in the class and said to me in front of all my peers: do you think you can manage to teach like that? I do not know how I felt exactly, but I was so down, I said I am sure I can, but I was so hurt.” (Student C)</p> <p>“[...] at university or outside university, people do not know me well, so they make different scenarios in their heads about me. [...] some of them think that my parents provide me with financial support, but this is wrong and it annoys me a lot. They think that a person with a disability cannot do things on his own [...] they call me handicapped, but I just want to tell them, I do have a brain and I built myself up.” (Student A)</p> <p>“[...] you know if someone, for instance, breaks something, they’ll say he has temper or anger issues, but if someone with a mental disability did, they’ll say that he is crazy [...]” (Student G)</p>
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Appendix 13: Extracts from my reflective journal

As my research focuses on the experiences of students with disabilities at university. I was a bit hesitant about how insights from students with disabilities about family support relate to their university experience, when I noticed this theme (family support) emerging from students with disabilities data, as I had not specifically asked any questions about their relationship with their families. However, I soon realized that this was an important aspect for students with disabilities, and it was crucial for understanding their experiences and the external factors that may influence their university life.

While analysing data, I was astonished by the number of challenges that exist within this university. It was surprising to know that despite the several infrastructural hindrances that face these students, they managed to adapt to the physical environment and therefore were able to navigate their educational journeys at this university. I was also interested by the suggestions participating students in this study provided to enhance the quality of accessibility to the university infrastructure, and I will even use them when developing recommendations in my concluding chapter.

It is disheartening and concerning to hear stories about the negative attitudes that some academics hold towards students with disabilities. While hearing participants sharing their experiences, it appeared that such attitudes have left a strong emotional impact on them, and demotivated them. Discriminatory attitudes towards students with disabilities are unacceptable and must be addressed. Therefore, this university, and us as individuals must work towards spreading awareness and promoting inclusion in the Algerian community, so that to create a society that is truly inclusive for everyone.

Lack of funds seems to be a critical challenge in the provision of both physical accessibility and academic support for students with disabilities at this university. Since the disability support office is not official and underfunded, proposing such costly renovations and services that often require significant finances is challenging for the staff. Therefore, to address these challenges, the ministry of higher education should take steps towards making the office an official entity. This will further acknowledge its role and importance, and make it benefit from funds to carry out necessary renovations and adaptations, to ensure the provision of significant accommodations and materials that support and promote the inclusion of students with disabilities in this university.

When I first started my analysis, I had the idea that university services may not be fulfilling their responsibilities to support students with disabilities. This assumption led me to consider that students may be hesitant to declare their disabilities before enrolment due to a lack of trust in the university's ability to provide adequate support, or thoughts from students that even if they declared their disabilities, this would change nothing. However, I made sure not to let my positionality and pre-experience studying in Algerian universities affect and distract my objective to gain an in-depth and comprehensive understanding regarding the issue of disclosure that was brought by disability support officers. Because without conducting research it would remain unclear if the concerns, I had in mind are related to practical issues only or other aspects. It appears that there are attitudinal factors mainly negative stereotypes and stigma that affect students' disclosure.

Therefore, aside from structural and attitudinal reasons that these findings reveal, I think is important also to question whether the current methods of identifying and registering students with disabilities are effective in capturing students' needs, particularly those with hidden disabilities. This suggests the importance of creating a confidential platform for students with disabilities to register themselves and raise their concerns, which can inform the development of adequate support strategies for these students, and empower them to actively engage in the process of support advocacy before transitioning to Higher education.